

The health and environmental impact of dental amalgam and alternative restorative materials: a systematic review

Final Report

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Addendum notice

This report is accompanied by an addendum which sets out the implications of a study report identified after completion of the systematic review. The addendum explains how this additional evidence affects interpretation of findings relating to environmental impact. The overall conclusions of the systematic review remain unchanged.

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Data-sharing statement

Requests for access to data should be addressed to the corresponding author.

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This work is part of an ongoing programme of work funded by the NIHR Policy Research Programme. Throughout the review, stakeholders from the Department of Health and Social Care were consulted to understand the context of the issue under study, collaborated on the development of the research question(s) and protocol and presentation of findings from the narrative synthesis.

Guarantor of the review

Professor Jo Thompson Coon

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Guidance on the type of review and how to read this report

This is a technical report structured to highlight the findings of the narrative evidence synthesis. Thus, the report is divided into the following sections:

1. **Executive summary:** An executive summary providing an overview of the methods, key findings and implications for future research and clinical practice.
2. **Part 1 report: background, brief methods, findings and discussion.** Provides background to the systematic review and brief methods. The results section details descriptive characteristics of included studies, gives an overview of findings from studies evaluating the health impact of different restorative materials and presents the full findings from the narrative synthesis evaluating environmental outcomes associated with different restorative materials. The discussion summarises the main findings of the review in the context of existing research, identifying potential implications for future policy, research and practice.
3. **Part 2 report: detailed methods.** This section provides full details of the processes followed regarding study identification, data extraction and quality appraisal, narrative synthesis and stakeholder involvement.
4. **Part 3 report: full narrative synthesis** of studies evaluating health outcomes.
5. **Appendices:** These provide the information necessary to support comprehension of the conduct and findings of the review.
6. **Supplementary Materials:** These provide additional information regarding detailed methodology, population and study characteristics, intervention structure and outcomes associated with the individual studies included within the review.
 - **Supplementary Materials A:** Tables summarising key characteristics of the 134 studies evaluating health impacts which were included in the review, but were not prioritised for full data extraction, quality appraisal and narrative synthesis.
 - **Supplementary Materials B:** Table describing key population characteristics for the 61 studies evaluating health impacts that were included in the narrative synthesis.
 - **Supplementary Materials C:** Table summarising detail regarding intervention/exposure of interest and comparator for the 61 studies prioritised for synthesis evaluating health impacts.
 - **Supplementary Materials D:** Table summarizing the data collection and analysis methods used in the 61 studies evaluating health impact prioritised for narrative synthesis.

- **Supplementary Materials E:** Tables providing detail regarding the findings associated with the specific health impacts evaluated by each of the studies prioritised for narrative synthesis.

Executive summary

What do we want to know?

Dental restorations are among the most common medical procedures performed globally and can be indirect where restorations are custom-made outside of the mouth, or direct where filling materials are applied directly to the tooth.^{1, 2} Dental caries (also known as tooth decay) are one of the major reasons for needing direct dental restoration.^{2, 3} A 2018 survey of adults in England (n=14,270) showed that 90.2% had fillings, with an average of 7.2 filled teeth each.⁴ Historically, dental amalgam—a combination of liquid mercury and a powdered alloy of silver, tin, and copper—has been widely used for these fillings.⁵ However, there is concern over mercury's toxicity and its potential risks to human health⁶ and the environment.⁷ Concerns apply not only to mercury exposure throughout the life cycle in patients after receiving amalgam restorations but also during the process of placement or removal.⁸ Other direct restorative materials, such as resin composites and glass ionomers, are now more frequently used, but their health and environmental impacts are not yet fully understood.^{9, 10}

The Minamata Convention on Mercury is a UN global treaty adopted by 147 parties, including the UK in 2013, to protect human health and the environment from mercury's adverse effects. This has led to significant reduction in the use of amalgam across countries in Europe, Canada and the USA.¹² At the time of commissioning this report, the UK was phasing down dental amalgam with plans for Northern Ireland to phase out dental amalgam by 2035 (following a change in EU regulations and specific arrangements for Northern Ireland).^{13, 14} Following the 2023 Conference of the Parties (COP-5), which reviewed a proposal from Botswana and Burkina Faso to phase out dental amalgam by 2030, the University of Exeter Policy Research Programme Evidence Review Facility was independently commissioned to undertake a review to provide comprehensive understanding of the current evidence regarding dental amalgam and alternatives to amalgam, considering both health and environmental impacts. This review aims to support and inform decisions on the future use of dental amalgam within the UK. Findings from this review may complement decisions made at the sixth Meeting of the Conference of the Parties to the Minamata Convention on Mercury (COP-6), where a 2034 phase out of dental amalgam was agreed.¹⁵

Review aims and research questions:

To compare the adverse health and environmental impacts of dental amalgam versus other dental restorative materials.

- 1) What is the health impact of direct dental restorations made of amalgam compared to other direct restorative materials?

- 2) What is the environmental impact of direct dental restorations made of dental amalgam compared to other direct restorative materials?

What we did

We prospectively registered our review on PROSPERO (CRD42024608563) prior to running searches.¹⁶ The methods used to conduct and report the findings of this review were consistent with the best practice approach for the conduct of systematic reviews and reporting of quantitative evidence synthesis.¹⁷

We searched a selection of bibliographic databases with coverage of both health care and environmental science journals, with a date limit of 2007 and English language limit applied. These searches were supplemented with backward and forward citation searches of studies which met the inclusion criteria, searches of Google Search (www.google.com), and checking the included studies of topically similar systematic reviews. In addition, we inspected the Healthcare LCA database for relevant studies.

We quality appraised and synthesised data from studies evaluating health and environmental impacts separately. We narratively synthesised health impacts by grouping studies according to the type of restorative material evaluated. Within these groups, we divided studies into categories based on the broad health impact being evaluated. Studies evaluating environmental impacts were synthesized in a similar way.

What did we find?

In total, 215 studies (266 articles) met the inclusion criteria for this review; 195 studies (246 articles) evaluated health impacts associated with different restorative materials, and 21 studies (21 articles) evaluated environmental impacts. We prioritised 61 studies (87 articles) evaluating health impacts and 21 studies evaluating environmental impact for narrative synthesis.

134 studies (159 articles) were less relevant to the aims of this review and were not included in the narrative synthesis. The main reasons for study de-prioritisation were:

- Exposure outcomes not directly related to health impact (n=69, 84 articles),¹⁸⁻¹⁰¹
- Link between dental restorative material and health impact not the primary focus of study (n=31, 33 articles),¹⁰²⁻¹³⁴ and
- Study design was cross-sectional with/without comparison group (n=35, 42 articles).¹³⁵⁻¹⁷⁶

Health impacts

We separated the 61 studies (87 articles) prioritised for narrative synthesis into four categories according to the type of restorative material evaluated:¹

- 1) Amalgam versus composite: health impact of the two restorative materials statistically compared (n=6 studies, 17 articles),¹⁷⁷⁻¹⁹³
- 2) Amalgam only (n=52 studies, 66 articles),^{178, 182, 187, 190, 192, 194-254}
- 3) Composite resin only (n=16 studies, 20 articles),^{187, 190, 192, 195, 207, 209, 213, 218, 230, 233, 239, 242, 255-262}
and
- 4) Glass ionomer versus composite (n=3 studies).^{185, 255, 263}

Of the 60 studies appraised by the Effective Public Health Practice Project (EPHPP) tool,² 16 studies (34 articles) received an overall global study quality rating of ‘strong’,^{177-182, 184-188, 191-193, 196, 204-206, 209, 213, 216, 217, 221, 224, 230, 233, 235, 236, 244, 245, 252, 258, 259, 262} 18 studies (22 articles) received a ‘moderate’ quality rating,^{183, 189, 190, 198-200, 208, 210, 214, 218, 231, 240-243, 246-249, 253, 256, 263} and the remaining 26 studies (30 articles) were given a ‘weak’ rating.^{194, 195, 197, 201-203, 207, 211, 212, 215, 219, 220, 222, 223, 225-229, 232, 234, 237-239, 250, 251, 255, 257, 260, 261}

The quantity of evidence directly comparing health impacts of amalgam with those of composite resin was limited, relying heavily on articles reporting the New England Children’s Amalgam Trial (NECAT) and Casa Pia trials,^{179, 181} with health impacts following occupational or maternal exposure not represented by the evidence base. Similarly, the quantity of evidence evaluating the health impacts of composite resin restorations was much smaller than the quantity of evidence evaluating amalgam, reducing opportunities to compare the impact of these different types of materials for individual health outcomes across the two groups of evidence.

We identified 25 broad health impact categories, 18 of which were supported by evidence from more than one category of restorative material. The broad health impacts supported by the highest number of studies included:

- Allergy (n=13),^{179, 195, 210, 212, 213, 218, 223, 229, 231, 238, 239, 242, 249}
- General physical health (n=14),^{179, 191, 199-201, 208, 210-212, 219, 220, 222, 228, 232, 240, 241, 250, 251, 253}
- Musculoskeletal (n=10),^{179, 201, 210, 212, 220, 222, 228, 240, 241, 251, 253}
- Neurological (n=13),^{179, 181, 184, 205, 208, 212, 214, 219-222, 244, 245, 253}

¹ Total > 61 as findings from non-comparative studies evaluating more than one type of restorative material were included across multiple categories.

² One modelling study was not quality appraised by the EPHPP tool.²⁵⁴

- Neuropsychological (n=15),^{178, 179, 181, 196, 201, 206, 208-210, 219, 220, 222, 228, 233, 235, 241, 246-248, 251, 253, 258, 259}
- Oral health (n=18).^{183, 190, 191, 195, 207, 212, 222, 223, 229-231, 234, 238, 239, 242, 251, 257, 263}
- Psychosocial (n=13).^{179, 180, 200, 201, 208-210, 212, 219, 220, 222, 228, 232, 237, 240, 250, 251, 253, 258}

Amalgam vs composite resin

Six studies (17 articles) provided direct comparative evidence regarding the health impacts of amalgam versus composite resin restorations, with most evidence comparing health impacts associated with amalgam vs composite resin restorations stemming from NECAT and the Casa Pia trial, both appraised as strong quality.^{179, 181}

The quantity of evidence pertaining to amalgam was much larger than that relevant to composite resin restorations, which limited comparisons that could be made between these two bodies of evidence for different health impacts.

Broad health impacts with the highest quantity of data statistically comparing amalgam with composite resin restorations included immune function, neuropsychological, oral health and psychosocial symptoms, although confidence in reported findings is limited due to moderate-weak evidence quality, heterogeneity of health impacts within specific categories and/or small number of studies.

Whilst few significant differences between treatment groups were observed across the broad impact categories, the limited quantity of comparative evidence means we cannot be confident that there is no significant difference in health impact between amalgam and composite restorative materials. Whilst some differences between the health impact of amalgam versus composite resin were found for neuropsychological and psychosocial symptoms, one type of restorative material was not consistently better than the other.

Amalgam only (non-comparative)

The majority of evidence evaluated health impacts of patients exposed to amalgam via restorations in situ or via removal and/or replacement of existing restorations (n=36),^{178, 187, 190, 192, 195-197, 199-205, 207, 209-213, 215, 216, 221, 223, 225, 228-234, 237-242, 244, 245, 249-254, 259} Ten studies (13 articles) explored the impact of maternal exposure to amalgam prior to or during pregnancy and child health impacts,^{194, 198, 206, 217, 222, 224, 226, 227, 235, 236, 246-248} and seven studies focused on the health impacts experienced by dental professionals occupationally exposed to amalgam and/or mercury.^{208, 214, 218-220, 222, 243} Findings for different population groups are as follows:

Dental professionals: very few consistent significant associations between dental professional exposure to mercury and health impacts were found.

Maternal exposure: Findings are grouped into the following impact categories:

- *ADHD/Autism* (n=2): Insufficient and weak quality evidence prevents conclusions pertaining to autism/ADHD in children following maternal exposure to amalgam.^{194, 226}
- *Neuropsychological* (n=3): some evidence suggests maternal amalgam exposure may impact on tests of overall cognitive ability with some sex differences, but heterogeneity in terms of populations, types of amalgam exposure metrics used, neuropsychological symptoms investigated, and measures used, age of child at testing, limits conclusions that can be drawn.^{206, 235, 246-248}
- *Pregnancy impacts* (n=7): Three studies pertain to pregnancy impacts for dental professionals exposed to amalgam/mercury during their occupational practice. Evidence suggests that there is no association between maternal amalgam exposure and childhood death for non-occupationally exposed mothers, although further research is required into the risk of miscarriage for individuals with higher amalgam exposure. Birth impacts for dental professionals were mixed, and further research is required. There is tentative evidence to suggest no association between maternal exposure via occupational and non-occupational exposure to amalgam/mercury and birth malformations, but again the limited number of studies and their low-quality limit confidence in this finding.^{198, 206, 217, 222, 224, 227, 236}

Patients: Overall, the heterogeneity in how amalgam exposure and health impacts were measured and dominance of weak quality evidence within each broad outcome category prevented firm conclusions from being drawn regarding the impact of amalgam restorations on patient health. However, there appears to be tentative evidence that amalgam restorations on permanent teeth may have a detrimental influence on some blood chemistry markers of immune function, musculoskeletal symptoms, oral lichenoid lesions/reaction symptoms, but is not associated with oral lichen planus or psychosocial difficulties and no evidence to indicate a link between amalgam restorations and neuropsychological test performance. Further high-quality research is needed to increase confidence in these findings.

Composite resin only (non-comparative)

The quantity of evidence evaluating health impacts associated with composite resin restorations was much smaller than the quantity of evidence evaluating the health impact of amalgam. The limited number of studies and heterogeneity of study populations and outcome measures limited the confidence in the few associations between composite resin restorations and health impacts identified. The strongest, most consistent evidence stemmed from three articles associated with the NECAT which supported the neuropsychological and/or psychosocial impact categories.^{187, 259} Only a few associations were found between composite resin restorations and performance on psychological tests and greater exposure to BisGMA-composite was linked to poorer psychosocial health at follow-

up. The potential impact of composite restorations on patient health needs further appraisal by high quality randomized controlled trials.

Glass ionomer vs composite resin/compomer

Three studies compared the health impact of glass ionomer restorations with composite/compomer resins. Study designs, outcomes of interest and findings were heterogeneous, precluding identification of any clear conclusions regarding which restorative material was least detrimental to health.^{185, 255, 263}

Environmental impacts

We identified 21 studies which report findings relating to environmental impacts.^{254, 264-283} Of these, five studies include a comparison between different types of restorative material, including between amalgam, composites and glass-ionomer materials.^{264, 266, 270, 277, 278} The remaining studies only assessed one type of relevant restorative material,^{254, 267-269, 271-276, 279-283} or included multiple types of restorative materials collectively without comparing them.²⁶⁵

We assessed the quality of studies using the Centre for Environmental Evidence Critical Appraisal Tool (CEECAT) which rates the studies as high, medium or low risk of bias.²⁸⁴ None of the studies were rated as low risk of bias. Ten studies were rated medium risk, and 11 studies were rated high risk of bias, thus indicating that there were weaknesses in the methods across all the studies which limited the trustworthiness of the findings.

Within these studies, a variety of different environmental impacts or potential impacts were reported. Potential impacts were classified as findings which directly relate to environmental impact but do not measure this, e.g. studies which report toxicity levels associated with restoration material, but do not assess whether this exceeds recommended levels or the effects on the environment. These studies were included in view of the limited evidence relating to actual environmental impacts. Types of environmental impact (or potential impact) were grouped into 10 broad impact categories. Most of these categories relate to the type of toxicity associated with either amalgam or non-amalgam (mainly composites and glass-ionomer) restorative materials – specifically, *mercury* for amalgam restorations, and *monomers* for non-amalgam-based restorations. The broad impact categories are listed below (n=number of studies):

- Environmental impacts relating to mercury:
 - Mercury levels in wastewater (n=5)^{264, 274, 275, 277, 279}
 - Mercury levels in solid waste (n=3)^{269, 271, 274}
 - Mercury levels in emissions (n=3)^{254, 268, 280}
 - Mercury levels in vapour (n=3)^{267, 282, 283}
 - Mercury levels in particulate matter (n=2)^{267, 278}
- Environmental impacts relating to monomers:

- Monomer levels in wastewater (n=2)^{273, 276}
- Monomer levels in particulate matter (n=1)²⁸¹
- Monomer levels in emissions (n=1)²⁷²
- Environmental impacts relating to multiple restoration materials:
 - Carbon footprint of restorative materials (n=1)²⁶⁶
 - Animal toxicity of restorative materials (n=2)^{265, 270}

Studies were sometimes duplicated across these categories, e.g. one study could report data relating to both mercury levels in wastewater and solid waste.

Overall, the studies were highly heterogeneous in their aims, methods, settings, and in the specific impacts which were reported within each broad category. This meant it was difficult to draw meaningful comparisons between different studies, even within the same broad impact categories; and the degree to which studies could be pooled together to establish an overall understanding of what the evidence-base shows in relation to the research question was very limited.

In particular, as noted above, most studies did not compare different restorative materials, i.e. included only one type of material, or included multiple materials without comparison. Additionally, even in studies where impacts relating to the environment were compared between two or more restorative materials, the studies did not always measure more than one type of toxicity (e.g. did not measure both mercury and monomers in studies which included amalgam and non-amalgam materials). Thus, comparative studies sometimes missed the opportunity to make comparisons between different types of environmental toxicity associated with different materials.

Furthermore, less than half of the studies measured an actual environmental impact, either in terms of animal toxicity, carbon footprint, or compliance with recommended levels of toxic waste in guidance. The remainder only reported the *potential* for environmental impact, such as a measure of toxicity associated with restorative materials without indicating the degree to which this was likely to cause harm.

There was some indication that composites are less environmentally harmful than amalgam with respect to animal toxicity, and that glass-ionomer is the least environmentally harmful of all direct restoration materials, but this was drawn only from one study.²⁷⁰ The only study to compare carbon footprint of different restorative materials crucially did not include any data relating to the materials themselves, only factors such as the time and energy required to undertake restorations.²⁶⁶

What are the implications?

This systematic review was requested by the Department of Health and Social Care (DHSC) to inform and support decision making around the future use of dental amalgam.

Health impacts

The current evidence base does not present a clear picture as to the health impacts associated with individual restorative materials, or which material may have fewer health implications when compared to another. Hence, further high-quality research is required to more fully understand the health impacts associated with different types of material both individually and compared to one another. There are comparatively fewer studies evaluating the health impacts of composite resin and glass ionomer restorative materials across all population groups which should be addressed, particularly given current UK public health policy directing the phasing down of amalgam use. Specific health impacts associated with composite resin restorations where further high-quality trials would be particularly useful to support comparative analysis within the existing evidence base include adverse events, cardiovascular disease, dermatological, gastrointestinal, general physical health, musculoskeletal, neurological, respiratory and visual ocular symptoms. Similarly, the health impacts associated with occupational and maternal exposure to glass ionomer or composite resin restorations need to be evaluated.

This systematic review and narrative synthesis provide some evidence regarding association between individual restorative materials and certain health impacts, which dental professionals may wish to consider when choosing the dental material for a restoration. Choice of dental restorative material may be influenced by a variety of factors including type and position of cavity, cost, longevity, clinical performance and availability of restorative material within certain geographical areas or funding for use within the NHS. Our engagement with the PERSPEX PPI group for this project indicates that patients would like to be kept informed as to the potential health implications of different types of restorative material, particularly where they may disproportionately impact certain patient groups (e.g. respiratory/allergy outcomes for people living with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease) and involved in the decision-making process. There may be tension between the clinical performance of each restorative material, their availability to patients receiving care via the National Health Service (NHS) and the lack of certainty regarding potential health impacts for both dental professionals and patients, highlighting the need for clear information to support decision making for all those involved.

Environment impacts

The most important finding of the review of environmental studies is that more research is needed which clearly addresses the question about which restorative materials have the most harmful environmental impact. Future studies should include a meaningful comparison between the toxicity associated with amalgam and non-amalgam-based materials, specifically, mercury and monomers respectively. This requires either using established guidance to assess whether levels of toxicity are compliant with guidance or comparing the effects of toxicity from different restorative materials on

the environment, ideally in a controlled setting. More studies which measure carbon emissions are also needed.

Furthermore, the lack of any studies classified as low risk of bias points to the need for future research to use more rigorous methods which are in line with recommended guidance.

Addendum notice

An addendum accompanies this report, setting out the implications of additional evidence identified after completion of the systematic review; the overall conclusions of the review remain unchanged.

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Glossary

Amalgam	Dental filling material composed primarily of a mixture of mercury, silver, tin, and copper
Anthropomorphic	Body characteristics such as mass and height
Composite resin	Tooth-colored filling material composed of a resin matrix (usually a synthetic resin) and a filler (usually glass or ceramic particles)
Glass ionomer	Dental material primarily used for fillings, sealants, and cementing crowns and bridges
Inlays	An indirect restoration fabricated outside the mouth and then bonded to the tooth. It's used to repair cavities or fracture that are too extensive for a simple filling but don't require a full crown
Onlays	A custom-made filling, larger than an inlay, that is bonded to the tooth to repair damage or decay

Abbreviations

ACGIH	American Conference of Governmental Industrial Hygienists
Bis-GMA	Bisphenol A-glycidyl methacrylate
BPA	Bisphenol A
CAD/CAM	Computer-Aided Design/Computer-Aided Manufacturing
CEECAT	Centre for Environmental Evidence Critical Appraisal Tool
DCDS	Dental chair drainage system
DHSC	Department of Health and Social Care
EC	Effective concentration
EDGMA	Ethylene Glycol Dimethacrylate
ENT	Ear, Nose and Throat
EPA	Environment Protection Agency
HEMA	2-Hydroxyethyl Methacrylate
ISO	International Organisation for Standardization
LC	Lethal concentration
NHS	National Health Service
NHSE-I	NHS England and NHS Improvement
OSHA	Occupational Safety and Health Administration
PM	Particulate matter
PPIE	Patient and Public Involvement and Engagement
PRISMA	Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses
PRP	Policy Research Programme
TEGDMA	Triethylene Glycol Dimethacrylate
UDMA	Urethane Dimethacrylate
UN	United Nations
UK	United Kingdom
USA	United States of America

Part 1: Background, brief methods, findings and discussion

Background

Dental restorations are among the most common medical procedures performed globally and can be indirect where restorations are custom-made outside of the mouth, or direct where filling materials are applied directly to the tooth.^{1,2} Dental caries (also known as tooth decay) are one of the major reasons for needing direct dental restoration.^{2,3} A 2018 England survey of adults (n=14,270) showed that 90.2% had fillings, with an average of 7.2 filled teeth each.⁴ Historically, dental amalgam—a combination of liquid mercury and a powdered alloy of silver, tin, and copper—has been widely used for these fillings.⁵ However, due to concerns over mercury's toxicity and its potential risks to human health⁶ and the environment,⁷ the use of amalgam has continued to decline in the last 10 years.^{3, 285} These concerns apply not only to mercury exposure throughout the life cycle in patients after receiving amalgam restorations but also during the process of placement or removal.⁸ Other direct restorative materials, such as resin composites and glass ionomers, are now more frequently used, but their health and environmental impacts are not yet fully understood.^{9,10} Figure 1 below outlines some of the properties of the most commonly used dental restorative materials.

Figure 1: Properties of dental amalgam, glass ionomer and resin composite

Currently, the most recent systematic reviews which compare the health and environmental effects of dental amalgam to other direct restorative materials have produced inconclusive findings.²⁸⁶⁻²⁸⁸ Two trials, NECAT and the Casa Pia children's dental amalgam clinical trial, reported in nine publications, form the basis of two systematic reviews on the health and safety impacts of amalgam versus resin

for dental restorations.²⁸⁶⁻²⁸⁸ A 2014 Cochrane review found resin restorations had a higher risk of secondary caries (RR 2.14; 95% CI 1.67 to 2.74, $P < 0.001$) compared to amalgam.²⁸⁹ A 2015 systematic review reported significantly higher urinary mercury levels in children with amalgam compared to composite resin, though not at toxic levels, and noted these levels decrease over time.²⁸⁷ Differences in outcomes like post-operative pain and renal effects were observed, but no consistent or clinically significant patterns of benefit or harm were found between the materials.²⁸⁷ Worthington's 2021 systematic review suggested composite resin restorations might have nearly double the failure rate of amalgam, with a higher risk of secondary caries. However, very low-certainty evidence indicates no significant differences in safety profiles regarding neurological and renal effects between the two materials.²⁸⁶

Gallusi's 2021 systematic review, included mostly studies in children but also reported on one study in adults who received composite resin, compomer resin, glass ionomer cement, or amalgam restorations. The study observed that all the restorative materials caused changes in gingival crevicular fluid cytokine levels.²⁸⁸ However, other systematic reviews comparing glass ionomers and compomers to amalgam and resin composites have mainly focused on clinical performance and efficacy.^{290, 291} One review reported an 85-90% survival rate for resin composite restorations after 10 years, while glass ionomer cement (GIC) had an 80% survival rate after six years.²⁹⁰ A meta-analysis found lower caries rates in patients with conventional GIC (CGIC) restorations compared to amalgam (RR=0.57, 95% CI:0.43–0.76, $p = 0.0001$) and resin-modified GIC (RMGIC) restorations (RR=0.70, 95% CI:0.56–0.87, $p = 0.002$) but no significant difference compared to composite resin in primary dentition (RR=0.73, 95% CI:0.51–1.04, $p = 0.08$). RMGIC showed no significant difference in caries incidence compared to composite resin in either dentition.⁹ Another meta-analysis found GIC had better retention than composite resin (risk difference 0.07, 95% CI: 0.02-0.12, $p = 0.003$) but similar rates of secondary caries (risk difference -0.00, 95% CI:-0.01-0.01, $p = 0.87$).²⁹² A key thing to note is that these reviews only include randomized controlled trials, excluding observational studies. Observational studies often provide longer follow-up periods, which are crucial for capturing potential long-term adverse effects of amalgam and other restorative materials.

While the health impacts of direct dental restorative materials are relatively more studied, research on their environmental effects remains limited. A review attempted to make a detailed comparison of the environmental effects of amalgam and resin composite materials but found it was not possible due to a lack of focused studies.²⁸⁷ The environmental impact of amalgam continues to receive attention due to the presence of mercury.²⁹³ However, less is known about other direct filling materials including the quantities of Bisphenol A (BPA), monomers, and other materials released

during their manufacture, use, and disposal. Some of these substances can persist in the environment,²⁹⁴ bioaccumulate in animals,²⁹⁵ disrupt their endocrine function,²⁸⁷ and can affect growth and reproduction in plant and animal cells.²⁹⁵

Figure 2: A conceptual model of complexities in health and environmental impact of dental restorative materials

As shown in Figure 2, linking restorative materials, including amalgams and non-amalgams, to adverse human health and environmental impacts is inherently complex. This reflects in how existing evidence capture only a small portion of the entire pathway. For example, while studies suggest that dental procedures may lead to increased concentrations of harmful substances like mercury or BPA in patients having restorations, focusing on level of concentration, rather than the associated health impact, limits our ability to draw conclusions about their overall safety and environmental impact.²⁹⁶ Additionally, the production, use, and end-of-life stages of these materials contribute to environmental contamination and health risks. However, isolating the specific impacts of restorative materials from other industrial sources remains a significant challenge.

The Minamata Convention on Mercury is a UN global treaty adopted by 147 parties, including the UK in 2013, to protect human health and the environment from mercury's adverse effects. This has led to significant reduction in the use of amalgam across countries in Europe, Canada and the USA.¹² At

the time of commissioning this report, the UK was phasing down dental amalgam with plans for Northern Ireland to phase out dental amalgam by 2035 (following a change in EU regulations and specific arrangements for Northern Ireland).^{13, 14} Following the 2023 Conference of the Parties (COP-5), which reviewed a proposal from Botswana and Burkina Faso to phase out dental amalgam by 2030, the University of Exeter Policy Research Programme Evidence Review Facility was independently commissioned to undertake a review to provide comprehensive understanding of the current evidence regarding dental amalgam and alternatives to amalgam, considering both health and environmental impacts. This review aims to support and inform decisions on the future use of dental amalgam within the UK. Findings from this review may complement decisions made at the sixth Meeting of the Conference of the Parties to the Minamata Convention on Mercury (COP-6), where a 2034 phase out of dental amalgam was agreed.¹⁵

Aim

To compare the adverse health and environmental impacts of dental amalgam versus other dental restorative materials.

Research questions

1. What is the health impact of direct dental restorations made of amalgam compared to other direct restorative materials?
2. What is the environmental impact of direct dental restorations made of dental amalgam compared to other direct restorative materials?

Brief Methods

We prospectively registered our review on PROSPERO (CRD42024608563) prior to running searches.¹⁶ The methods used to conduct and report the findings of this review were consistent with the best practice approach for the conduct of systematic reviews and reporting of quantitative evidence synthesis.¹⁷ Below, we provide a brief overview of how we identified, quality appraised, data extracted and synthesised the findings from the primary quantitative studies included within this review. For full methodological detail, please see [Part 2: Full description of methods](#).

Search strategy

We searched a selection of bibliographic databases on 6th November 2024 with coverage of both health care and environmental science journals, with a date limit of 2007 and English language limit applied. These searches were supplemented with backward and forward citation searches of studies which met the inclusion criteria, searches of Google Search (www.google.com), and checking the included studies of topically similar systematic reviews. In addition, we inspected the Healthcare LCA database (<https://healthcarelca.com/>) for relevant studies. We intended to search for grey literature via other relevant websites but, in consultation with topic experts, did not identify any relevant sources to search. See [Appendix A: Search report](#) for our full search strategy.

Study identification

Once finalised, the inclusion and exclusion criteria listed in *Table 1* below were independently applied to the title and abstracts of studies identified via our search strategy by two reviewers. Disagreements were resolved through discussion or referral to a third reviewer as required. Full-texts were screened in the same manner.

Table 1: Inclusion and exclusion criteria

PICO criterion	Inclusion criteria
Population	<p>Include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Any patient having direct filling/restoration (including children and adults)• Professionals with a direct link to dentistry (including dentists, dental nurse, dental hygienist and therapist, dental technicians) <p>In addition, for environmental impact studies <u>only</u>, relevant Settings can be substituted for population groups, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Dental clinics• Crematoriums• Natural world (including animal studies)• Lab-based settings (including in vitro studies) <p>Exclude:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Professionals without a direct link to dentistry• Patients with indirect dental fillings/restoration• Professionals that primarily perform indirect restorations (e.g., orthodontists, orthodontic therapists)

	<p>In addition, for health <u>only</u>:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Animals • In vitro studies
Intervention	<p>Include: Direct dental restoration made from:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dental amalgam • Resin composites • Conventional glass ionomers • Resin modified glass ionomers cement including (compomers or polyacid-modified resin-based composites and giomers) <p>Exclude:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All other direct restorations not using amalgam, resin composites or glass ionomers • Indirect dental restorations using: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Metal alloys (e.g., High Noble Alloys, Gold alloys, Titanium and Titanium Alloys, Noble Alloys, Predominantly Base Alloys) ○ Ceramics (e.g., Silicate glasses, porcelains, glass-ceramics, and polycrystalline, ceramics) ○ Porcelain-fused-to-metal or metal-ceramic prostheses ○ Resin composite, glass ionomers • Inlays, onlays and overlays • Crowns, bridges, dental implants, veneers <p>However, for environment <u>only</u>:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Studies which included non-relevant materials were included if they also included relevant materials, even if the findings relating to relevant materials could not be disaggregated from the irrelevant materials.
Comparator	<p>Include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct dental restorations using: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Resin composites ○ Conventional glass ionomers ○ Resin modified glass ionomers cement (including compomers, polyacid-modified resin-based composites and giomers) • No comparator <p>Exclude:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Indirect restorations using <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Metal alloys (e.g., High Noble Alloys, Gold alloys, Titanium and Titanium Alloys, Noble Alloys, Predominantly Base Alloys) ○ Ceramics (e.g., Silicate glasses, porcelains, glass-ceramics, and polycrystalline, ceramics) ○ Porcelain-fused-to-metal or metal-ceramic prostheses ○ Resin composite, glass ionomers • Inlays, onlays and overlays • Crowns, bridges, dental implants, veneers <p>However, for environment <u>only</u>:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Studies which included non-relevant materials were included if they also included relevant materials, even if the findings relating to relevant materials could not be disaggregated from the irrelevant materials.
Outcomes	<p>Include: EITHER: Health studies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All adverse health outcomes of dental restorations made using amalgam, resin composite, glass ionomer cements and resin modified glass ionomers cement including (but not limited to):

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Mercury, BPA, monomers concentration ○ Secondary caries ○ Psychological impact, Neurological disease, Postoperative sensitivity ○ Renal function ○ Allergies ○ Changes in health markers such as cytokine levels, white blood cell counts, and lymphocyte counts ○ Subjective health measured by patients with filling <p>OR:</p> <p>Environmental studies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● All environmental outcomes of direct dental restorations made using amalgam, resin composite, glass ionomer cements and resin modified glass ionomers cement including (but not limited to): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Mercury, BPA, monomers concentration (where this is not explicitly linked to health outcome) ○ Global warming potential, carbon-emission data, ozone depletion, ozone formation ○ Water toxicity, ecotoxicity, human non/carcinogenic toxicity ○ Acidification, eutrophication, fossil resource scarcity, mineral resource depletion, land use, water consumption ○ Smog, respiratory or fine particulate matter <p>Exclude:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Clinical suitability and performance of dental amalgam and other restorative materials (composites/ionomers)– e.g., survival of restoration, number of failures and fractures. ● Subjective health self-reported by parent or carer of patient with filling
Design	<p>Include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Prospective and retrospective cohort studies ● Cross-sectional studies ● Before and after studies ● Interrupted time series ● Life cycle assessments ● Randomised controlled trials ● Controlled trials <p>Exclude:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Systematic, scoping or narrative reviews ● Case studies, Case series ● Qualitative studies ● Conference abstracts, protocols ● Letters, editorials, discussion pieces
Other	2007 date limit, English language only, high income countries according to World Bank List. ²⁹⁸

BPA=Bisphenol A

Protocol deviations

Health impacts

Due to the high number of included studies evaluating health impacts identified by our search strategy, we made a pragmatic decision during title and abstract screening to exclude studies that focused on pain, sensitivity, and secondary caries. This was because, following consultation with stakeholders, these health impacts were identified as being closely related to the clinical performance of the restorative material used, which are currently being evaluated by another systematic review (personal correspondence).

Following full-text screening and preliminary data extraction, we used a prioritisation process to identify studies which focussed on evaluating health impacts which had the highest quantity of data relevant to our research questions for full data extraction, quality appraisal and synthesis. This process prioritised studies where the primary focus was evaluating the link between dental material and health/environmental impact and where study design was not cross-sectional or cross-sectional with comparison group. Studies which evaluated exposure outcomes, e.g. mercury concentration in hair, which were not linked to an explicit health impact were deprioritised.

During full-text screening and preliminary data extraction, we excluded studies where the link between dental material and health impact was not clear. However, to ensure that dental professionals were more adequately represented within the included studies, we included studies where the link between allergen and dental material was not always clear and acknowledged this within the synthesis where applicable.

Two of the studies included in the review published multiple papers associated with findings from RCTs with follow-up over multiple years.^{179, 181} The primary papers for both these studies were published in 2006, prior to the 2007 date limit for this review. Because other papers from these studies met the inclusion criteria for this review, we included the primary papers published in 2006 within this review to support completeness of data.

Environmental impacts

In contrast, we identified relatively few studies relating to environmental impacts. Thus, we made the following decisions to increase the number of studies which were eligible for inclusion:

- 1) We included lab-based studies, including studies with no human participants, i.e. in vitro studies.
- 2) We also made the decision to include animal studies, including both in real world and lab-based settings. (This was again made in view of the limited evidence-base, although the inclusion of animal studies is also appropriate from the point of view of wanting to assess the

environmental impact – unlike health impacts, including animal studies did not compromise the relevance of the findings for the environmental part of the review).

- 3) Studies which included non-relevant materials were included if they also included relevant materials, even if the findings relating to relevant materials could not be disaggregated from the irrelevant materials.
- 4) Studies were included if they showed *potential* as well as *actual* environmental impact, e.g. if a study only reported the level of toxic chemicals in waste relating to dental restoration activity, without linking this to measurable environmental impact (e.g. animal toxicity, or compliance with guidance) studies were still included as showing potential environmental impact.

Data extraction and quality appraisal

One reviewer applied the full data extraction form shown in

[Appendix B: Data extraction items for included studies](#) to prioritised studies evaluating health or environmental impact (LS, HML, SB, NO, CMP), which was then checked by a second reviewer (LS, HML, SB, NO, CMP). The data extraction form was designed to capture baseline and outcome data from included studies which related to population characteristics associated with social determinants of health, with reference to the PROGRESS+ framework.²⁹⁹ Disagreements were settled by a third reviewer if necessary.

We undertook quality appraisal at the same time as data extraction in the same way, using separate tools for the appraisal of health and environmental studies. We used the Effective Public Health Practice Project (EPHPP) Quality Assessment Tool for Quantitative Studies to assess the quality of studies focused on health outcomes.³⁰⁰ For environmental studies, we used the Collaboration for Environmental Evidence Critical Appraisal Tool (CEECAAT) Version 0.3 (prototype).²⁸⁴ Where a study was reported across multiple papers, we selected the key index paper for quality appraisal. For full details regarding the data extraction and quality appraisal processes, please see [Part 2: Full description of methods](#).

Synthesis of the evidence

We synthesised data from studies evaluating health and environmental impacts separately. For prioritised studies evaluating health impacts, we tabulated data regarding study population, setting, intervention, methodological and quality characteristics of the included studies. Within these groups, we divided studies according to categories based on the population group and broad health impact/s, evaluated. We summarised key characteristics of deprioritised studies which only measured exposure outcomes in tables and summarised these narratively.

We synthesised studies evaluating environmental impacts in a similar way. We grouped studies according to the type of restoration material evaluated, within which we had separate groups for studies which included multiple restorative materials, and studies which only included one type of restorative material.

Across both health and environmental studies, the narrative synthesis sought to identify and explain, where possible, patterns in the data regarding the health and environmental impact of the restorative materials. Impact was assessed in terms of the degree to which exposure to dental restorative materials was associated with health or environmental harms. Health harms included diagnosis with particular health conditions or health ill-effects as measured by biological tests (e.g. blood-tests, patch tests). For environmental harms, this included both harm to the natural environment, and human exposure to harmful levels of toxic substances in the immediate environment of activity relating to restorative materials which was not otherwise related to health conditions. We also included studies

which showed *potential* environmental impact, e.g. studies which only reported the level of toxic chemicals in waste relating to dental restoration activity, without linking this to actual (e.g. measurable) environmental impact (e.g. animal toxicity, or compliance with guidance).

For full details regarding data synthesis, see [Part 2: Full description of methods](#)

Stakeholder involvement

We consulted with and worked closely alongside several stakeholder groups throughout the review. Stakeholders included those requesting the review from the Department of Health and Social Care (DHSC), people with expertise in dental restoration, the Cochrane Oral Health team and members of PERSPEX patient and public involvement group. This stakeholder involvement informed each stage of this review, including identification of the research question, refinement and application of inclusion criteria, creating the synthesis structure and supporting the write-up and dissemination of findings. Full detail of methods for involvement and respective impact on the review process, of each of these stakeholder groups on the review process and outputs is summarised in [Part 2: Full description of methods](#)

Results

This results section is structured as follows:

1. **Descriptive results:** presents key features of the studies included in our review, including characteristics of the participants/health systems, interventions, environmental setting, methods and study quality.
2. **Narrative synthesis:** Summarises key findings from the synthesis of the prioritised studies evaluating health impacts and presents the full synthesis of studies evaluating environmental impacts.
3. **Full narrative synthesis of studies evaluating health outcomes:** presented in Part 3 of this report.

Descriptive results

Search and study identification

The bibliographic database searches identified 13,708 records in total on 6th November 2025. This reduced to 9,150 following de-duplication. All 9,150 records were screened at title and abstract. Of these, 378 full-texts were sought for full-text screening of which 376 were successfully retrieved. One hundred fifty-one full-texts were excluded for the reasons stated in the PRISMA flow diagram in Figure 3. This resulted in 225 full-text includes (i.e. articles) from bibliographic database searches. In addition, supplementary searches identified 1,278 records of which 77 full-texts were sought for full-text screening, following title and abstract screening. All 77 full-texts were successfully retrieved. Thirty-six were excluded for the reasons stated in the PRISMA follow chart in Figure 3. The reasons for exclusion are also reported in full for both bibliographic databases and supplementary searches for each individual full-text in [Appendix C](#). Overall, 266 full-text articles were included in the review, including 245 in the health impacts review^{18-253, 255-263} and 21 in the environmental impacts review.^{254, 264-283} This process is depicted in the PRISMA flow diagram in Figure 3. Furthermore, the 245 health related articles represented 195 individual studies. The 21 environmental articles were all individual studies.

Figure 3. PRISMA flow diagram

Key characteristics of prioritised health impact studies

We identified 61 health impact studies (87 articles) for prioritisation.¹⁷⁸⁻²⁶³ This included one study which reported both health and environmental impacts and therefore is reported under both the health and environmental impacts studies sections.²⁵⁴ This section presents a narrative summary of the key characteristics of the prioritised health impact studies. Data for the key characteristics of prioritised health impact studies are presented in full across the study overview table ([Appendix D](#)) the population characteristics table (Supplementary Materials B), and the intervention/outcome table (Supplementary Materials C).

Publication characteristics

All prioritised health impact studies were published as journal articles. There were 5 studies (6 articles) published in the year of the historical date limit (2007),^{103, 178, 196, 215, 222, 224} albeit two included studies (two articles) preceded this date limit owing to being sibling papers of relevant trials in the review (both published in 2006).^{179, 181} The most recent articles were published in 2024 (2 studies, 2 articles),^{210, 213} with just over half of the studies published before 2015 (33 studies, 57 articles).^{177-182, 184, 186-188, 191-197, 206, 208, 209, 211, 212, 214-217, 219, 220, 222-224, 228, 231, 232, 234-241, 243, 246-253, 257-259, 261, 262} The year with the most published studies was 2012 (11 studies, 13 articles),^{188, 197, 208, 209, 214, 223, 234, 235, 239, 246, 249, 252, 259} followed by 2014 (seven studies, eight articles),^{187, 195, 231, 236, 253, 257, 258, 261} 2011 (seven studies, seven articles),^{182, 211, 217, 219, 240, 243, 247} 2008 (five studies, 10 articles),^{177, 180, 184, 186, 191-194, 232, 238} and 2020 (four studies, five articles).^{200, 205, 225, 244, 245} Details on date of publication for all studies are reported in [Appendix C](#): List of studies excluded at full-text from both bibliographic database and supplementary searches.

Study design

All prioritised studies used a quantitative design, details of which are reported in Appendix C and summarised in *Figure 4* below. **Seven studies (24 articles) were randomised control trials (RCTs).**^{177-181, 184, 186-188, 191-193, 196, 209, 232, 250, 251, 255, 257-259, 261-263} This included eight articles (across three different studies) carrying out retrospective secondary analyses of RCTs,^{182, 188, 191, 192, 196, 216, 250, 251} with two of these articles carrying out prospective cohort studies with data from the parent RCT study. Most articles with a RCT component stemmed from either the Casa Pia study (eight articles),^{181, 182, 184, 186, 191, 193, 216, 262} or the NECAT study (eleven articles).^{177-180, 187, 188, 192, 196, 209, 258, 259} Of the articles with an RCT element, samples sizes ranged from eight patients with 24 oral sites being randomised²⁵⁷ to 534 patients.^{179, 188, 259}

Twenty-four studies (31 articles) were longitudinal or cohort studies.^{183, 185, 189, 190, 197-201, 206, 208, 210, 211, 214, 217, 221, 225-227, 229, 231, 235, 236, 240, 241, 243, 246-249, 253} Of these, 13 studies (14 articles) were retrospective,^{183,}

185, 189, 190, 208, 214, 217, 221, 229, 231, 235, 236, 243, 253 and 11 studies (17 articles) were prospective.^{197-201, 206, 210, 211, 225-227, 240, 241, 246-249} Of the 24 studies, three included both longitudinal and cross-sectional analyses,^{214, 240, 241} and four (six articles) included a before and after component.^{197, 200, 201, 211, 229, 231}

Ten studies used a cross-sectional study design with a control group,^{202, 203, 207, 219, 220, 222, 224, 239, 256, 260} and six were before and after studies.^{215, 223, 228, 234, 237, 238} Eleven studies (11 articles) were case-control studies,^{194, 195, 204, 205, 218, 230, 233, 242, 244, 245, 252} and two studies were retrospective reviews of records.^{212, 213} One study was a modelling study.²⁵⁴

Figure 4: Study design of all prioritised health outcome studies.

Country

All studies were from high-income countries. 19 countries were represented across the studies, with most studies being conducted within the USA (Nine studies, 20 articles),^{177-180, 182, 187, 188, 190, 192, 194-196, 208, 209, 214, 216, 249, 257-259} followed by Taiwan (ten studies),^{185, 189, 204, 205, 221, 230, 233, 244, 245, 256} and Norway (9 studies, 13 articles).^{197-201, 210, 211, 217, 219, 220, 226-228} Two studies were conducted across three different countries (Germany, Switzerland, Austria).^{213, 218}

Other represented countries include: Sweden (seven studies, eight articles),^{195, 215, 231, 235-237, 240, 241} Canada (three studies),^{225, 253, 254} Germany (three studies, four articles),^{207, 232, 250, 251} Spain (three studies),^{202, 203, 223} Italy (two studies),^{234, 260} Chile (n=1),²³⁹ Croatia (three studies),^{238, 255, 261} Finland (two studies),^{103, 224} Greece (one study),²⁶³ Ireland (one study),²²⁹ Israel (one study),¹⁸³ New Zealand (one study),²²² Portugal (one study, 6 articles),^{181, 184, 186, 191, 193, 262} Republic of Seychelles (one study, three articles),²⁴⁶⁻²⁴⁸ and the UK (four studies).^{206, 212, 242, 252} All countries are reported in [Appendix C: List of studies excluded at full-text from both bibliographic database and supplementary searches.](#)

For detail on the specific settings where studies were carried out, refer to Supplementary Materials B.

Population

Forty-four studies (67 articles) investigated the effects of dental restorative materials on patients,^{177-193, 195-197, 199-205, 207, 209-213, 215, 216, 221, 223, 225, 228-234, 237-242, 244, 245, 249-253, 255-263} 10 studies (13 articles) focused on the effects of these materials during maternal exposure,^{194, 198, 206, 217, 222, 224, 226, 227, 235, 236, 246-248} and seven studies explore the effects of occupational exposures to dental restorative materials amongst dental professionals (see Figure 5).^{208, 214, 218-220, 222, 243} Three studies (four articles) focusing on maternal exposure effects also included women who worked as dental professionals.^{217, 224, 235, 236} One study was a modelling study and did not include a population group.²⁵⁴ Where reported, the breakdown of children and/or adults included within each study are summarised in Figure 6 below.

Figure 5: Study population

Of the studies including a population group, 55 studies (83 articles) reported age-related data. In the patient studies, adults (≥ 18 years of age) were the most frequently included age group: 31 studies (37 articles) included solely adults,^{183, 195, 197, 199-201, 204, 205, 207, 210-213, 215, 221, 223, 225, 228-234, 237, 239-242, 244, 245, 249-251, 257, 260, 261} 6 studies (23 articles) included solely children,^{177-182, 184, 186-188, 191-193, 196, 209, 216, 252, 255, 256, 258, 259, 262, 263} and two studies included both adults and children/adolescents.^{185, 189} Five studies did not clearly specify the population age range.^{190, 202, 203, 238, 253}

Figure 6: Population breakdown by age (patient studies)

Fifty-eight studies (83 articles) included details on the gender/sex of participants. Most patient studies included data relating to both male and female participants (40 studies, 62 articles). Two studies reported data relating solely to female participants,^{202, 225} and no studies included only male participants. Of the studies which focused on dental professionals,^{208, 214, 218-220, 222, 243} four reported data relating to both male and female participants,^{214, 218, 219, 243} two reported data solely on female participants,^{220, 222} and one reported data solely on male participants.²⁰⁸ Of the nine studies (12 articles) focusing on maternal exposure, eight studies (11 articles) reported the children's gender, with seven studies (9 articles) reporting both males and females,^{194, 198, 206, 217, 226, 227, 246-248} and two studies (two articles) reporting data only on males.^{235, 236}

PROGRESS-PLUS

With regards to other PROGRESS-PLUS characteristics,²⁹⁹ 15 prioritised studies (20 articles) reported details on the occupation of participants,^{189, 197, 200, 201, 208, 211, 214, 217-220, 224, 232, 235, 236, 240, 241, 243, 250, 251} six studies (23 articles) reported details on the race/ethnicity of participants,^{177-182, 184, 186-188, 191-193, 196, 209, 216, 225, 242, 249, 258-260, 262} 13 (24 articles) reported on the socioeconomic status of participants,^{177-180, 185, 188, 189, 192, 196, 200, 202-205, 209, 225, 233, 244-248, 258, 259} 15 studies (26 articles) reported detail on the education of participants,^{65, 177-180, 188, 192, 196, 198, 200, 201, 206, 210, 211, 217, 220, 225-227, 232, 235, 236, 240, 241, 250, 251} and 12 studies (19 articles) provided detail on place of residence.^{179, 181, 185, 187-189, 192, 194, 203-205, 209, 230, 233, 244, 245, 256, 258, 259} Five studies (6 articles) provided detail on the PLUS category, including one study reporting details on features of relationships,²³² one study including details on time-dependent relationships,²³³ and 3 studies (4 articles) which referred to disability (see Figure 7).^{201, 211, 215, 228} Only one study did not include any PROGRESS+ related data.²⁵⁷ Three studies (8 articles) also reported additional information outside the PROGRESS+ framework e.g. assessment of children's home environment or sources of drinking water.^{188, 209, 224, 246-248, 258, 259} Full detail regarding study populations within the prioritised studies can be found in Supplementary Materials B.

Figure 7: PROGRESS-PLUS data across all prioritised health outcome studies which include a population group

Detail regarding the dental material being evaluated is provided below in [Summary of narrative synthesis: Health impacts](#) and summarised in Supplementary Materials C. Full details regarding methods of data collection and analysis are provided in Supplementary Materials D.

Key characteristics of environmental impact studies

This section presents an overview of the environmental impact studies. Data for the key characteristics of environmental impact studies are presented in full in the key characteristics and overview of environmental studies tables in [Appendix E: Descriptive tables – environmental studies](#).

Publication characteristics

All 21 of the included environmental impact studies were published as journal articles.^{254, 264-283} (Each journal article represents an individual study, although one journal article, Majstorovic et al., included two separate study designs within the same overall study).²⁷⁰ Date of publication ranged from 2007 (n=1)²⁶⁷ to 2024 (n=1).²⁷⁰ The year with the most studies published was 2008 (n=3).^{264, 269, 271}

Study design

Environmental impact studies included one before and after study,²⁶⁷ five controlled trials,^{270, 273, 276, 281, 283} eight cross-sectional studies (including one, Majstorovic et al,²⁷⁰ which also included a controlled trial component),^{264, 265, 268-272, 278} three modelling/simulation studies,^{254, 275, 280} four prospective longitudinal studies^{274, 277, 279, 282} (including two with control groups^{279, 282} and one with a comparator)²⁷⁷ and one secondary analysis of a dataset (see Figure 8).²⁶⁶ Because Majstorovic et al. included both a controlled trial and cross-sectional study within the same journal article the total number of studies within the 21 articles is 22.²⁷⁰

Figure 8: Study design of included environmental outcome studies*

Country

All studies were from high-income countries. Studies were conducted across 14 countries, with most being conducted within the USA (n=3),^{267, 274, 279} Greece (n=3)^{269, 271, 273} and Canada (n=3).^{254, 282, 283} Two studies were conducted withing Germany,^{272, 276} and all other represented countries included one study each: United Arab Emirates,²⁶⁴ Ireland,²⁶⁵ UK,²⁶⁶ South Korea,²⁶⁸ Saudi Arabia,²⁷⁷ Romania,²⁷⁸ Croatia,²⁷⁰ Belgium,²⁸¹ Trinidad and Tobago,²⁷⁵ and Japan.²⁸⁰

Setting

Eleven studies included a component which took place in a clinic setting,^{264-266, 268, 269, 271, 272, 274, 277, 278, 282} and three studies took place solely in a lab setting.^{275, 276, 283} A further five studies included both clinic and lab settings.^{267, 270, 273, 279, 281} Two studies took place in a crematorium setting (see Figure 9).^{254, 280}

Figure 9: Setting of included environmental studies

Restorative material

Sixteen studies included amalgam restorative material (see Figure 10).^{254, 264, 266-271, 274, 275, 277-280, 282, 283} Ten studies included composite resin material,^{264-266, 270, 272, 273, 276, 277, 281} and six studies included glass-ionomer restorative material.^{264-266, 270, 277, 278} Of these, seven studies included multiple types of restorative material,^{264-266, 270, 277, 278} with six studies including a comparison between different types of restorative material.^{264, 266, 270, 273, 277, 278} Studies also included data relating to alkasite (n=1)²⁷⁰ and polymer infiltrated ceramic CAD/CAM restorative materials, the latter of which is not relevant to this review but was included within a comparison with composite material (n=1).²⁷³ Additionally, studies included materials relating to other dental activities such as bridges, crowns, scaling and polishing, which do not meet the inclusion criteria for this systematic review, but for which the data could not be disaggregated from the data relating to restorative materials.^{264, 273, 277, 278, 281}

Figure 10: Breakdown of restorative materials evaluated in environmental studies

Treatment/activity

With respect to treatment activity, ten studies reported data relating to restorations,^{264, 266, 267, 271, 272, 274, 276-278, 281} eight studies reported data relating to removals,^{264, 267, 271, 273, 275, 277, 282, 283} three studies reported data relating to incineration of extracted teeth,^{254, 268, 280} and four studies did not report the specific dental activity.^{265, 269, 270, 279} Five of these studies included activities which are not relevant but for which the data could not be disaggregated from the restoration material data, including bridges, crowns, scaling and polishing, amongst other activities (see Figure 11).^{264, 273, 277, 278, 281}

Figure 11: Breakdown of treatment/activities carried out in environmental studies

Quality appraisal

Health impact studies

Quality ratings are displayed in [Appendix F: Quality appraisal](#). There were six included studies which had two or more publications and from each study, an index paper (the first publication in date order) was used for the quality appraisal.^{179, 181, 200, 211, 232, 235} For the Casa Pia Trial and NECAT, three publications published prior to the 2007 exclusion criteria were used as they contained further detail of the design of these trials.^{179, 181}

Sixteen studies (34 articles) received an overall global study quality rating of ‘strong’,^{177-182, 184-188, 191-193, 196, 204-206, 209, 213, 216, 217, 221, 224, 230, 233, 235, 236, 244, 245, 252, 258, 259, 262} 17 studies (22 articles) received a ‘moderate’ quality rating,^{183, 189, 190, 198-200, 208, 210, 214, 218, 231, 240-243, 246-249, 253, 256, 263} and the remaining 26 studies (30 articles) were given a ‘weak’ rating.^{194, 195, 197, 201-203, 207, 211, 212, 215, 219, 220, 222, 223, 225-229, 232, 234, 237-239, 250, 251, 255, 257, 260, 261}

Two RCT studies (19 articles) were rated as strong quality,^{179, 181} one as moderate quality,²⁶³ and four as weak quality.^{232, 255, 257, 261} All RCTs were rated as ‘strong’ for study design. Four RCTs received a ‘weak’ rating because of selection bias,^{232, 257, 261} confounders,^{255, 257, 261} blinding,^{232, 255, 257, 261} and withdrawals and dropouts.²⁶¹ Five longitudinal or cohort studies (six articles) received a ‘strong’ rating,^{185, 206, 217, 221, 235, 236} 14 studies (18 articles) received a ‘moderate’ rating,^{183, 189, 190, 198-200, 208, 210, 214, 231, 240, 241, 243, 246-249, 253} and six studies (eight articles) received a ‘weak’ rating.^{197, 201, 211, 225-229} One cross-sectional study with a control group was rated as ‘strong’,²²⁴ and the remaining were rated as ‘weak’.^{202, 203, 207, 219, 220, 222, 239, 260} All before and after studies received a quality appraised as weak.^{215, 223, 228, 234, 237, 238} Seven case control studies were rated as strong quality,^{204, 205, 230, 233, 244, 245, 252} three as moderate quality,^{218, 242, 256} and two as weak quality.^{194, 195} One retrospective review of records received a strong rating,²¹³ and one received a weak rating.²¹²

The component with the highest ratings of ‘strong’ was ‘data collection methods’ (45 studies; 68 articles),^{177-193, 195, 196, 198-200, 202-210, 212-218, 221, 222, 225, 229-231, 233-239, 242-249, 252, 256, 258-263} indicating that in these studies the reliability and validity of the data collection methods were clearly described. Only two studies were graded as ‘weak’,^{219, 220} and the remaining 14 studies (20 articles) were graded as ‘moderate’.^{194, 197, 199-201, 210, 211, 223, 224, 226-228, 232, 240, 241, 250, 251, 253, 255, 257}

Seven studies (26 articles) were rated as ‘strong’ for ‘study design’, all of which were RCTs.^{177-182, 184, 186-188, 191-193, 196, 209, 216, 232, 250, 251, 255, 257-259, 261-263} Four studies received a ‘weak’ rating,^{183, 207, 212, 214} and 50 studies (56 articles) received a ‘moderate’ rating.^{185, 189, 190, 194, 195, 197-206, 208, 210, 211, 213, 215, 217-231, 233-249, 252, 253, 256, 260}

Seven studies (26 articles) were rated as ‘strong’ for ‘study design’, all of which were RCTs.^{177-182, 184, 186-188, 191-193, 196, 209, 216, 232, 250, 251, 255, 257-259, 261-263} Four studies received a ‘weak’ rating,^{183, 207, 212, 214} and 49 studies (56 articles) received a ‘moderate’ rating.^{185, 189, 190, 194, 195, 197-206, 208, 210, 211, 213, 215, 217-231, 233-249, 252, 253, 256, 260}

The component with the highest ratings of ‘weak’ was ‘confounders’ (30 studies; 30 articles) suggesting that there was a likelihood of possible confounding of results.^{105, 189, 190, 202, 203, 207, 208, 212, 215, 218-220, 222, 223, 228, 229, 234, 237-243, 253, 255, 257, 260, 261, 263} However, 23 studies (45 articles) were rated as ‘strong’,^{177-182, 184-188, 191-193, 196, 198-200, 204-206, 209, 210, 216, 217, 221, 224-227, 230-233, 235, 236, 244, 245, 249-252, 258, 259, 262} and five (seven articles) as moderate.^{183, 194, 197, 201, 211, 214, 219} Two studies (four articles), one retrospective records review and one prospective cohort, were given ‘not applicable’ for this component.^{213, 246-248} Twenty-four studies (30 articles) were rated as ‘weak’ in relation to blinding of assessors and participants,^{195, 197, 199-203, 207, 210, 211, 215, 219, 220, 222, 225-228, 231, 232, 237-239, 249-251, 255, 257, 260, 261} including four RCTs [Gavic 2019; Leybovich 2014; Melchart 2008; Tadin 2014]. No studies were rated as being ‘strong’ for this item and six studies (23 articles) were rated as ‘moderate’.^{177-182, 184, 186-188, 191-194, 196, 209, 216, 224, 252, 258, 259, 262, 263} However, 30 studies (33 articles) were given ‘not applicable’.^{183, 185, 189, 190, 198, 204-206, 208, 212-214, 217, 218, 221, 223, 229, 230, 233-236, 240-248, 253, 256}

Twenty-one studies (32 articles) were rated as ‘moderate’ for ‘selection bias’,^{181-184, 186, 190, 191, 193, 195, 199, 200, 207, 208, 210, 212-214, 216, 223, 231, 239-242, 246-249, 252, 255, 262, 263} indicating that the selected individuals in most studies were ‘somewhat likely’ to be representative of the target population. There were also 21 studies (25 articles) with a ‘weak’ rating,^{194, 197, 198, 201-203, 211, 215, 219, 220, 222, 225-229, 232, 234, 237, 238, 250, 251, 257, 260, 261} and 18 (29 articles) with a ‘strong’ rating on this item.^{177-180, 185, 188, 189, 192, 196, 204-206, 209, 217, 218, 221, 233, 235, 236, 243-245, 253, 256, 259}

Fourteen studies (28 articles) received a ‘strong’ rating for their reporting of rates and reasons for ‘withdrawals and dropouts’.^{177-180, 187, 188, 192, 196, 197, 201, 209, 211, 215, 225, 228, 229, 231, 232, 234, 238, 239, 250-252, 255, 257-259} The majority were non-RCT studies with only three RCTs.^{179, 232, 257} Five studies (14 articles) were moderate,^{181, 182, 184, 186, 191, 193, 198-200, 206, 210, 216, 262, 263} and six studies (nine articles) were weak on this item.^{194, 195, 223, 237, 246-249, 261} However, the majority of studies (34; 35 articles) received a ‘not applicable’ rating on this component.^{183, 185, 189, 190, 202-205, 207, 208, 212-214, 217-222, 224, 226, 227, 230, 233, 235, 236, 240-245, 253, 256, 260}

Environmental impact studies

Quality ratings are displayed in *Appendix F: Quality appraisal*. One study comprising two parts, one of which was cross-sectional design in a clinic setting and the other, a clinical trial in a laboratory setting, was appraised in two parts.²⁷⁰ There are 17 observational studies^{254, 264-272, 275, 277-280, 282, 283} and five experimental studies.^{270, 273, 276, 281, 283} In accordance with the CEECAT tool, two risk-of-bias criteria

(criterion 3 and criterion 4) were only applicable to one type of study (one for observational studies only and one for experimental studies only).²⁸⁴

Eleven studies (including Majstorovic et al. 2024 part 1)^{254, 264-268, 270, 271, 275, 277, 279} had a 'high' risk of bias and 11 studies (including Majstorovic et al. 2024 part 2) had a 'medium' risk of bias.^{269, 270, 272-274, 276, 278, 280-283} No studies were classified as 'low' risk of bias. Five cross-sectional studies had a 'high' risk of bias^{264, 265, 268, 270, 271} and three had a 'medium' risk of bias.^{269, 272, 278} Three longitudinal or cohort studies had a 'medium' risk of bias^{274, 277, 281} and one a 'high' risk of bias.²⁷⁹ All of the controlled trial studies had a 'medium' risk of bias^{270, 273, 276, 281, 283} and two modelling studies had a 'high' risk of bias.^{254, 275} and one medium risk of bias.²⁸⁰ One before and after study²⁶⁷ and one secondary analysis of dataset study²⁶⁶ both had a 'high' risk of bias.

Confounding bias (criterion 1) contributed to a 'high' risk of bias in nine studies^{264-268, 270, 271, 277, 279} and was present in 12 studies as a 'low' risk of bias.^{254, 269, 270, 272, 274-276, 278, 280-283} Selection bias (criterion 2) was present in 15 studies as a 'medium' risk of bias^{254, 264-270, 273, 278, 280-283} and outcome assessment bias (criterion 7) in 16 studies.^{264, 265, 268-270, 272-274, 276-283} Detection bias (criterion 5) was present in 18 studies as a 'low' risk of bias,^{264, 265, 268, 270-277, 279-282} as was outcome reporting bias (criterion 6).^{264-267, 270, 271, 275, 277-280, 282, 283}

Summary of narrative synthesis: Health impacts

Sixty-one studies (87 articles) prioritised for synthesis evaluated the health impact of different dental materials. For the narrative synthesis, these studies were divided into four categories based on the restorative material/s evaluated:

- 1) Amalgam versus composite: health impact of the two restorative materials statistically compared (n=6 studies, 17 articles),¹⁷⁷⁻¹⁹³
- 2) Amalgam only (n=52 studies, 67 articles),^{178, 182, 187, 190, 192, 194-254}
- 3) Composite resin only (n=16 studies, 20 articles),^{187, 190, 192, 195, 207, 209, 213, 218, 230, 233, 239, 242, 255-262} and
- 4) Glass ionomer versus composite (n=3 studies).^{185, 255, 263}

Findings from studies which evaluated the health impact of both amalgam and composite/methacrylates, but didn't statistically compare the health impact of the two materials were assigned to the amalgam only and composite resin only categories according to which material the reported finding related to (n=7).^{190, 207, 213, 218, 230, 233, 239} Results which only pertained to one restorative material within comparative studies were split in a similar way. Hence, a study evaluating several restorative materials could contribute to more than one of the four categories listed above.

The majority of studies evaluated health impacts associated with amalgam restorations in patients or general population (n=36),^{178, 187, 190, 192, 195-197, 199-205, 207, 209-213, 215, 216, 221, 223, 225, 228-234, 237-242, 244, 245, 249-254, 259} in children following maternal amalgam exposure (n=10),^{194, 198, 206, 217, 222, 224, 226, 227, 235, 236, 246-248} or dental professionals (n=7).^{208, 214, 218-220, 222, 243} The quantity of evidence evaluating the health impact of composite resin restorations alone (n=16), or in comparison with glass ionomer restorations (n=3), was much smaller and limited to only patient outcomes. Similarly, the quantity of evidence comparing health impacts of amalgam with those of composite resin restorations was also limited, relying heavily on articles reporting the NECAT and Casa Pia trial,^{179, 181} with health impacts following occupational or maternal exposure not represented by the evidence base. However, evidence supporting this category was of better quality than the evidence supporting the other three categories, generally appraised as strong overall.

We identified 25 broad health impact groups, 18 of which were supported by evidence from more than one category of restorative material: ADHD/autism, adverse events allergy, anthropomorphic, cardiovascular disease, dermatological, female health, gastrointestinal, general physical health, genotoxicity, immune function, musculoskeletal, neurological, neuropsychological, oral health, psychosocial, renal and respiratory. Only two broad health impact groups were supported by evidence

from studies evaluating all four categories of restorative material: ADHD/Autism (n=5),^{185, 194, 226, 252, 256} and oral health (n=18).^{183, 190, 191, 195, 207, 212, 222, 223, 229-231, 234, 238, 239, 242, 251, 257, 263} The broad health impact groups supported by the highest number of studies were: allergy (n=13),^{179, 195, 210, 212, 213, 218, 223, 229, 231, 238, 239, 242, 249} general physical health (n=14),^{179, 191, 199-201, 208, 210-212, 219, 220, 222, 228, 232, 240, 241, 250, 251, 253} musculoskeletal (n=10),^{179, 201, 210, 212, 220, 222, 228, 240, 241, 251, 253} neurological (n=13),^{179, 181, 184, 205, 208, 212, 214, 219-222, 244, 245, 253} neuropsychological (n=15),^{178, 179, 181, 196, 201, 206, 208-210, 219, 220, 222, 228, 233, 235, 241, 246-248, 251, 253, 258, 259} oral health (n=18).^{183, 190, 191, 195, 207, 212, 222, 223, 229-231, 234, 238, 239, 242, 251, 257, 263} and psychosocial (n=13).^{179, 180, 200, 201, 208-210, 212, 219, 220, 222, 228, 232, 237, 240, 250, 251, 253, 258}

However, as stated above, the majority of this was non-comparative evidence evaluating amalgam restorations.

Table 2 below provides an overview of the quantity and quality of evidence supporting the broad health outcomes evaluated within each category, alongside a summary of findings.

Summaries of the main findings pertaining to the health outcomes for each of the four categories of restoration material are provided below. For full details, please see the full synthesis in [Part 3: Full synthesis – health outcomes](#).

Table 2: Overview of quantity, quality and main findings of evidence appraising health outcomes

Broad health impact group	Restoration material category					
	Amalgam (n=52)			Amalgam vs Composite Resin	Composite Resin	Glass ionomer vs composite resin/composer
	Dental professional (n=7)*	Pregnant women: child outcomes (n=10)	Patient (n=36)*	Patient (n=6)	Patient (n=15), Dental professional (n=1)*	Patient (n=3)
ADHD/Autism		● N=2: NA ^{194, 226}	● N=1: NA ²⁵²	● N=1: NA ¹⁸⁵	● N=1: SA increase exposure=adverse effect ²⁵⁶	● N=1: NA ¹⁸⁵
Adverse events			● ● N=3: AE ^{199, 201, 211, 232}	● N=2: NA ^{179, 181}		
Allergy	● N=1: *218		● N=11: MF ^{195, 210, 212, 213, 223, 229, 231, 238, 239, 242, 249}	Patient: ● N=1: NA ¹⁷⁹	Patient: ● N=4: MF ^{195, 213, 239, 242} Dental professionals: ● N=1: *218	
Anthropomorphic			● N=1: NA ²¹⁰	● N=1: NA ¹⁸⁸	● N=1: NA ¹⁸⁷	
Cancer	● N=1: NA ²²²					
Cardiovascular disease	● N=1: AE ²⁰⁸		● ● N=6: MF ^{210, 212, 228, 240, 241, 251}	● N=1: NA ¹⁷⁹		
Dermatological	● N=1: AE ²²²		● ● N=5: MF ^{210, 228, 240, 241, 251}	● N=1: NA ¹⁷⁹		
Ear, nose and throat			● ● N=5: MF ^{210, 228, 240, 241, 253}			
Endocrine	● N=1: NA ²²²					

Broad health impact group	Restoration material category					
	Amalgam (n=52)			Amalgam vs Composite Resin	Composite Resin	Glass ionomer vs composite resin/composer
	Dental professional (n=7)*	Pregnant women: child outcomes (n=10)	Patient (n=36)*	Patient (n=6)	Patient (n=15), Dental professional (n=1)*	Patient (n=3)
Female health	● N=1: AE ²²²		● N=2: NA ^{210, 225}	● N=1: SA favours amalgam ¹⁸⁸	● N=1: NA ²⁵⁸	
Gastrointestinal			● ● N=7: MF ^{201, 210, 228, 240, 241, 251, 253}	● N=1: NA ¹⁷⁹		
General physical health	● N=4: MF ^{208, 219, 220, 222}		● ● N=9: MF ^{199-201, 210-212, 228, 232, 237, 240, 241, 250, 251, 253}	● N=2: NA ^{179, 191}		
Genotoxicity					● N=3: MF ^{255, 260, 261}	● N=1: MF ²⁵⁵
Immune function			● N=7: MF ^{187, 192, 197, 204, 212, 215, 237, 238}	● ● N=2: MF favours amalgam ^{187, 189, 192}	● N=1: MF Some outcomes: increase exposure=adverse effect ^{187, 192}	
Musculoskeletal	● N=2: MF ^{220, 222}		● ● N=9: SA adverse effect 201, 210, 212, 228, 237, 240, 241, 251, 253	● N=1: NA ¹⁷⁹		
Neurological	● ● N=5: MF ^{208, 214, 219, 220, 222}		● ● N=6: MF ^{205, 212, 221, 244, 245, 253}	● N=2: NA ^{179, 181, 184}		

Broad health impact group	Restoration material category					
	Amalgam (n=52)			Amalgam vs Composite Resin	Composite Resin	Glass ionomer vs composite resin/composer
	Dental professional (n=7)*	Pregnant women: child outcomes (n=10)	Patient (n=36)*	Patient (n=6)	Patient (n=15), Dental professional (n=1)*	Patient (n=3)
Neuropsychological	●● N=5 ^{247, 248} : MF ^{208, 214, 219, 220, 222}	●● N=3: MF ^{206, 235, 246-248}	● N=8: NA ^{178, 196, 201, 210, 228, 233, 241, 251, 253, 259}	● N=2: MF favours amalgam ^{178, 179, 181}	● N=2: MF some outcomes: increase exposure =adverse effect ^{233, 258, 259}	
Oral health	● N=1: AE ²²²		● N=13: MF ^{190, 195, 207, 212, 223, 229-231, 234, 238, 239, 242, 251}	● N=3: MF ^{183, 190, 191}	● N=5: NA ^{190, 195, 207, 230, 257}	● N=1: SA favoured GI ²⁶³
Orofacial			●● N=4: MF ^{201, 210, 211, 228, 237}			
Pregnancy outcomes		●● N=7: MF ^{198, 206, 217, 222, 224, 227, 236}				
Psychosocial	●● N=4: NA (2/4, Euroquest mood), otherwise: MF ^{208, 219, 220, 222}		● N=9: NA ^{200, 201, 209, 210, 212, 228, 232, 237, 240, 241, 250, 251, 253}	● N=1: MF favours amalgam ^{179, 180}	● N=1: MF ^{209, 258}	
Renal	●● N=2: NA ^{220, 243}		● N=1: MF ²¹⁶	● N=2: MF ^{177, 181, 186, 193}		
Respiratory	●● N=2: NA ^{220, 243}		● N=3: MF ^{210, 240, 241}	● N=1: NA ¹⁷⁹		
Urinary			● N=2: NA ^{240, 241}			

Broad health impact group	Restoration material category					
	Amalgam (n=52)			Amalgam vs Composite Resin	Composite Resin	Glass ionomer vs composite resin/composer
	Dental professional (n=7)*	Pregnant women: child outcomes (n=10)	Patient (n=36)*	Patient (n=6)	Patient (n=15), Dental professional (n=1)*	Patient (n=3)
Visual/Ocular			●● N=4: MF ^{210, 240, 241 228}			
Other			N=4: NP ^{202, 203, 237, 254}	● N=2: MF ^{179, 182}	● N=1: NA ²⁶²	

*non-comparative studies evaluating the health impact of both amalgam and composite materials included in multiple restoration material categories. Evidence Quality: ●=Weak, ●=Moderate, ●=Strong, ●●=Mixed Weak/Moderate, ●●=Mixed Moderate/Strong, ●=Variable. *Only reports rates of sensitisation. **AE=Adverse Effect, MF=Mixed Findings, NA=No Association, SA=Significant Association, NP=Not Pooled.** ADHD=Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder, ENT=Ear, Nose & Throat, N=Number of studies

Health impacts: Amalgam vs composite resin-patient only

The quantity of direct comparative evidence was extremely limited, with the majority of evidence comparing health impacts associated with amalgam vs composite resin restorations stemming from the strong quality New England Children's Amalgam (NECAT) and Casa Pia randomised controlled trials.^{179, 181} Six studies (16 articles) provided direct comparative evidence regarding the health impacts of amalgam versus composite resin restorations.^{177-181, 183-193} The 18 broad impact categories supported by direct comparative evidence are: ADHD (n=1),¹⁸⁵ adverse events (n=2),^{179, 181} allergy (n=1),¹⁷⁹ anthropomorphic (n=1),¹⁸⁸ cardiovascular disease (n=1),¹⁷⁹ dermatological (n=1),¹⁷⁹ female health (n=1),¹⁸⁸ gastrointestinal (n=1),¹⁷⁹ general physical health (n=2),^{179, 191} immune function (n=2),^{187, 189, 192} musculoskeletal (n=1),¹⁷⁹ neurological (n=2),^{179, 181, 184} neuropsychological (n=2),^{178, 179, 181} oral health (n=3),^{183, 190, 191} psychosocial (n=1),^{179, 180} renal (n=2),^{177, 181, 186, 193} respiratory (n=1),¹⁷⁹ and other (n=2).^{179, 182}

All studies directly comparing the health impact of amalgam with composite resin were conducted with patients (see Table 2 above). This direct comparative evidence could be supplemented by studies evaluating the patient health impacts associated with amalgam and/or composite separately. Eight of these categories are supported by evidence from these two groups: ADHD/Autism, allergy, anthropomorphic, female health, immune function, neuropsychological, oral health and psychosocial.

The quantity of evidence pertaining to amalgam was much larger than that relevant to composite resin restorations, which limited comparisons which could be made between these two bodies of evidence for different health impacts. Ten health impact categories supported by direct comparative evidence were supplemented by studies evaluating only the health impact of amalgam: adverse events, cardiovascular disease, dermatological, female health, gastrointestinal, general physical health, musculoskeletal, neurological, renal and respiratory.

Broad health impact categories with the highest quantity of data evaluating both amalgam and composite resin restorations available to support a comparative synthesis included immune function, neuropsychological, oral health and psychosocial symptoms, although confidence in reported findings is limited due to moderate-weak quality of evidence, heterogeneity of specific outcome measures within broad impact categories and/or small number of studies.

Summaries of the findings from all impact categories are presented below, with full details provided in [Part 3: Full synthesis – health outcomes](#). See Supplementary Materials, Tables 1-8 for details on study findings.

ADHD and/or Autism

The number of studies evaluating the link between different restorative materials and ADHD/autism was limited (n=3),^{185, 252, 256} with only one study directly comparing different restorative materials.¹⁸⁵ This strong quality study reported no significant difference in ADHD prevalence between groups receiving amalgam, composite or glass ionomer restorations. Incidence of autism and ADHD diagnosis, linked to amalgam and composite resin restorations respectively, were appraised by one study each, with a significant association between composite resin restorations and ADHD risk identified by one moderate quality study.²⁵⁶

Adverse events

Two of the five studies within this category provided direct comparative evidence.^{179, 181} Adverse events linked to composite resin restorations alone were not evaluated by any study. Three weak quality studies (four articles) evaluated the relationship between amalgam removal/replacement and adverse events reported that patients experienced an aggravation of general health complaints following amalgam removal/replacement.^{199, 201, 211, 232} Overall, direct statistical comparisons, both between and within groups, was minimal, limiting the usefulness of reported data.

Allergy

Only one of the sixteen studies supporting this health impact directly compared between individuals receiving amalgam vs composite resin restorations.¹⁷⁹ This study was appraised as strong quality and reported no significant differences between treatment groups. Findings from evidence evaluating the link between amalgam (n=11),^{195, 210, 212, 213, 223, 229, 231, 238, 239, 242, 249} composite resin restorations (n=3),^{195, 213, 242} or methacrylates/acrylates (n=3) and allergy varied considerably, reflecting heterogeneity in population groups and outcomes measured used.^{213, 239, 242} Whilst more limited in quantity, the quality of evidence evaluating composite resin restorations was higher than that evaluating amalgam, although findings were similarly conflicting.

Of note is one moderate quality study which reported sensitization rates to amalgam and/or methacrylates/acrylates among dental professionals, finding that allergies to methacrylates/acrylates were the most frequently reported, with allergy to dental metals being less frequent.²¹⁸

Anthropomorphic

No significant associations were found between type of restorative material and anthropomorphic health impact. However, only two studies evaluated this health impact, one strong quality from the NECAT study and one weak, and the specific outcomes measured/reported varied considerably.^{187, 188,}

Cardiovascular disease

One article reporting on the strong quality NECAT reported no significant differences between treatment groups regarding cardiovascular symptoms.¹⁷⁹ There was no evidence evaluating cardiovascular symptoms relating to composite resin restorations, and findings from the six studies of variable quality relating to amalgam were inconsistent.^{210, 212, 228, 240, 241, 251}

Dermatological

The quantity of evidence supporting this health impact is extremely limited with only article from the NECAT, appraised as strong quality, providing direct comparative evidence.¹⁷⁹ This study found no significant difference between treatment groups and number of children reporting skin disorders. No consistent findings were reported in the five weak-moderate quality studies evaluating association between amalgam and dermatological symptoms.^{210, 228, 240, 241, 251} No studies evaluating composite resin restorations were represented.

Female health

Overall the quantity of evidence supporting this impact category was limited, with one strong quality study providing direct comparative evidence,¹⁸⁸ two weak-moderate quality studies evaluating amalgam,^{210, 225} and one strong quality article associated with the NECAT appraised flowable composite/preventative resin restorations.²⁵⁸ Together, there is tentative evidence to suggest that there is no link between type of restorative material and menstrual symptoms in children/young adults. Findings relating to other female health symptoms in pregnant women were only supported by one other weak quality study.²²⁵

Gastrointestinal

No significant differences in gastrointestinal disorders between treatment groups were reported in a single article, appraised as strong quality, associated with the NECAT.¹⁷⁹ Findings from seven studies of predominantly weak-moderate quality evaluating amalgam were inconsistent, with studies evaluating composite resin restorations unrepresented.^{201, 210, 228, 240, 241, 251, 253}

General physical health

No significant differences in general physical health complaints between treatment groups were reported in two strong quality articles associated with the Casa Pia and NECAT randomized controlled trials.^{179, 191} Findings from nine studies of variable quality evaluating amalgam were inconsistent,^{199-201, 210-212, 228, 232, 237, 240, 241, 250, 251, 253} with studies evaluating composite resin restorations not represented.

Immune function

Two studies (one strong, one moderate quality) contributed direct comparative evidence to this health impact,^{187, 189, 192} seven studies of variable quality examined the relationship between amalgam restorations and immune function,^{187, 192, 197, 204, 212, 215, 237, 238} and two articles appraised as strong quality from the NECAT contributed findings relevant to composite resin.^{187, 192} Overall, there appears to be some evidence indicating that both amalgam and composite resin restorations can impact on immune function, although more research is needed to fully understand which specific health outcomes are impacted, the duration for which these effects can be observed and the comparative impact of different types of restoration material.

Musculoskeletal

Only one strong quality article associated with the NECAT trial provided direct comparative evidence to support this category, indicating no significant difference between treatment groups.¹⁷⁹ Findings from nine studies indicate some evidence suggesting amalgam is associated with musculoskeletal symptoms, although evidence is predominantly based on self-report symptoms and appraised as weak quality.^{201, 210, 212, 228, 237, 240, 241, 251, 253} The absence of studies evaluating composite resin restorations precludes comparison between findings from separate groups of studies evaluating different types of restorative material.

Neurological

Findings from two studies appraised as strong quality representing the Casa Pia and NECAT randomised controlled trials found no reliable significant differences in neurological symptoms between treatment groups.^{179, 181, 184} Six moderate-strong quality studies evaluated amalgam,^{205, 212, 221, 244, 245, 253} with heterogeneity of specific health impact measures and findings preventing identification of firm conclusions regarding the potential link between restorative material and neurological impact. We did not identify any evidence evaluating the impact of composite resin restorations on neurological functioning, hence no comparison between separate groups of studies evaluating association between amalgam or composite resin restorations and this health impact was possible.

Neuropsychological

Two strong quality studies representing the NECAT and Casa Pia randomized controlled trials found no statistically significant differences between the treatment groups on most neuropsychological tests administered.^{178, 179, 181} Where group differences on specific subtests were observed, children in the amalgam group tended to perform better than those who received composite resin restorations. Due to the bias inherent in self-report measures used in the five variable quality studies evaluating the relationship between amalgam restorations in situ and neuropsychological test performance,^{178, 196, 233,}

^{241, 251, 259} and the moderate-weak quality of the five studies evaluating the impact of amalgam removal/replacement on neuropsychological symptoms,^{201, 210, 228, 241, 253} there is currently no evidence to indicate a link between amalgam restorations and neuropsychological test performance. One retrospective observational study appraised as strong quality found no significant association between number of amalgam or composite fillings and risk of developing dementia. This finding contrasts with two strong quality articles based on the NECAT which found a few significant associations between resin composite/compomer exposure and neuropsychological outcomes,^{233, 258, 259} however, the heterogeneity in population characteristics and health impacts and limited number of studies prevents firm conclusions.

Oral Health

Three studies of variable quality provided direct comparative elements to support this category.^{183, 190, 191} These studies presented mixed findings with respect to which dental restorative material was associated with fewer oral health symptoms. Evidence from six studies indicates amalgam removal (n=6) may support resolution of oral lichenoid lesions or reactions where amalgam is in close contact with lesions and individuals have a positive mercury patch test.^{223, 229, 231, 234, 238, 242} A limited quantity of evidence available from two studies also suggests that amalgam restorations may not be associated with oral lichen planus.^{207, 231} This latter finding aligns with the finding from one strong quality study which found no significant association between composite resin restorations and oral lichen planus, apart from individuals receiving 3-4 composite fillings/year.²³⁰ No association was found between composite resin restorations and oral lichenoid lesions in one study appraised as weak quality.¹⁹⁵ Otherwise, the two groups of studies largely evaluated different symptoms. Where comparable, the limited evidence base favours composite resin restorations.

Psychosocial

Two articles appraised as strong quality from the NECAT study provided direct comparative evidence to support this outcome.^{179, 180} There was no significant difference between treatment groups for most specific impacts evaluated. Where significant differences were found, improved scores were found in children receiving amalgam restorations. Overall, the current evidence does not indicate an association between amalgam restorations and patient psychosocial outcomes (n=9),^{200, 201, 209, 210, 212, 228, 232, 237, 240, 241, 250, 251, 253} although the low to moderate quality of studies evaluating the impact of amalgam removal/replacement means this finding should be interpreted with caution. The quantity of evidence evaluating the association between composite resin/compomer restorations and psychosocial functioning was more limited, evaluated by only the NECAT study.^{209, 258} Eleven significant associations were identified of the 53 outcomes measured, The majority of these concerned use of BisGMA-based

composite on permanent teeth. Change scores indicated greater exposure to BisGMA-composite was linked to poorer psychosocial performance at follow-up. Further studies are needed to evaluate the reliability of these findings. Overall, the evidence base for this outcome favours amalgam, although the limited evidence available evaluating composite resin restorations limits confidence in this conclusion.

Renal

Two studies (four articles) appraised as strong quality from the NECAT and Casa Pia trials found no significant differences between treatment groups for the majority of specific symptoms or measures within this category.^{177, 181, 186, 193} The exception to this was urinary albumin, where findings between studies were inconsistent.¹⁷⁷ Findings relating to amalgam exposure and renal function were mixed within one strong quality article representing findings from the Casa Pia trial.²¹⁶ No evidence was available from studies evaluating composite resin restorations alone. Whilst findings indicate there is no significant impact of restorative material on renal functioning, this needs to be replicated in further high-quality studies.

Respiratory

The evidence available to support this category was extremely limited, with only one study from the NECAT providing direct comparative evidence.¹⁷⁹ There is no evidence to suggest difference in risk of respiratory symptoms between treatment groups. Comparison between separate groups of studies evaluating association between amalgam or composite resin restorations and this health outcome was not possible, as we identified no studies evaluating the impact of composite resin on respiratory symptoms. Findings relating to exposure to amalgam were mixed in three moderate quality studies.^{210,}

240, 241

Overall, few significant differences between restorative materials were observed across different health impact groups (see *Table 2*). The limited quantity of studies which directly compared different restorative materials and the limited number of comparisons which could be made between studies evaluating amalgam or composite resin separately within the same health impact group, means we cannot be confident that there is no significant health impact for many of the above groups. Where differences did exist between amalgam and composite resin, the direction of effect varied according to the health impact being evaluated.

Health impacts: Amalgam

Fifty-two studies (67 articles) evaluated the health impact of amalgam and/or mercury. The majority of these evaluated health outcomes of patients exposed to amalgam via restorations in situ or via removal and/or replacement of existing restorations (n=36).^{178, 187, 190, 192, 195-197, 199-205, 207, 209-213, 215, 216, 221, 223, 225, 228-234, 237-242, 244, 245, 249-254, 259} Ten studies (13 articles) explored the impact of maternal exposure to amalgam prior to or during pregnancy and child health outcomes,^{194, 198, 206, 217, 222, 224, 226, 227, 235, 236, 246-248} and seven studies focused on the health outcomes experienced by dental professionals occupationally exposed to amalgam and/or mercury.^{208, 214, 218-220, 222, 243}

Studies were appraised as weak (n=22),^{194, 195, 197, 201-203, 207, 211, 212, 215, 219, 220, 222, 223, 225-229, 232, 234, 237-239, 250, 251} moderate (n=14),^{190, 198-200, 208, 210, 214, 218, 231, 240-243, 246-249, 253} or strong (n=15) quality.^{178, 187, 192, 196, 204-206, 209, 213, 216, 217, 221, 224, 230, 233, 235, 236, 244, 245, 252, 259}

Dental professionals

Seven studies examined the relationship between dental professional exposure to amalgam or mercury and different health impacts, with three studies appraised by reviewers as weak quality,^{219, 220, 222} and four as moderate.^{208, 214, 218, 243} Outcomes evaluated included allergy (n=1),²¹⁸ general physical health (n=4),^{208, 219, 220, 222} musculoskeletal (n=2),^{220, 222} neurological (n=5),^{208, 214, 219, 220, 243} neuropsychological (n=4),^{208, 219, 220, 222} psychological (n=4),^{208, 219, 220, 222} renal (n=2),^{220, 243} respiratory (n=2),^{208, 220} and other (n=4).^{208, 218, 222, 243} Specific outcome measures were heterogenous, often precluding meaningful comparisons across studies within the same broad outcome category. Regarding specific outcomes, no consistent significant associations between dental professional exposure to mercury and health outcomes were found.

Maternal exposure

Ten studies (13 articles) examined the relationship between maternal exposure to amalgam and child health outcomes. Four studies were appraised as weak quality,^{194, 222, 226, 227} two as moderate quality,^{198, 247-249} and four as strong quality.^{206, 217, 224, 235, 236} Findings are grouped into the following outcome categories: ADHD/Autism (n=2),^{194, 226} neuropsychological (n=3),^{206, 235, 246-248} and pregnancy outcomes (n=7).^{198, 206, 217, 222, 224, 227, 236} Three studies pertain to pregnancy outcomes for dental professionals exposed to amalgam/mercury during their occupational practice.^{217, 222, 236}

Insufficient and weak quality evidence prevents conclusions pertaining to autism/ADHD outcomes in children following maternal exposure to amalgam. The quantity of evidence relating to child neuropsychological outcomes is of better quality (moderate-strong), but whilst some evidence suggests maternal amalgam exposure may impact on tests of overall cognitive ability with some sex

differences, heterogeneity in terms of populations, types of amalgam exposure metrics used, neuropsychological outcomes investigated and measures used, age of child at testing limits conclusions that can be drawn. The quality of evidence evaluating pregnancy outcomes was variable, but the majority were appraised as strong quality (n=4 of seven studies). Evidence suggests that there is no association between maternal amalgam exposure and childhood death outcomes for non-occupationally exposed mothers, although further research is required into the risk of miscarriage for individuals with higher amalgam exposure. Birth outcomes for dental professional were mixed, and further research is required. There is tentative evidence to suggest no association between maternal exposure via occupational and non-occupational exposure to amalgam/mercury and birth malformations, but again the limited number of studies and their low-quality limit confidence in this finding.

Patients

Thirty-six studies (46 articles) evaluated the health impact of amalgam restorations and/or mercury exposure on the health of adults or children. Thirty-three of these were appraised using the EPHPP tool, with quality appraisal scores being: weak (n=16),^{195, 197, 201-203, 207, 211, 212, 215, 223, 225, 228, 229, 232, 234, 237-239, 250, 251} moderate (n=9),^{190, 199, 200, 210, 231, 233, 240-242, 249, 253} and strong (n=10).^{178, 187, 188, 192, 196, 204, 205, 209, 213, 216, 221, 230, 244, 245, 252} The other study was primarily focused on calculating environmental impacts, of which one was related to human health outcomes and was thus appraised using the CEECAT as high risk of bias.²⁵⁴

These studies were synthesised within the following broad outcome categories: adverse events (n=3),^{199, 201, 211, 232} allergy (n=11),^{195, 210, 212, 213, 223, 229, 231, 238, 239, 242, 249} anthropomorphic (n=1),²¹⁰ cardiovascular disease (n=6),^{210, 212, 228, 240, 241, 251} dermatological (n=5),^{210, 228, 240, 241, 251} ear, nose and throat (ENT)(n=5),^{210, 228, 240, 241, 253} female health (n=2),^{210, 225} gastrointestinal (n=7),^{201, 210, 228, 240, 241, 251, 253} general physical health (n=9),^{199-201, 210-212, 228, 232, 237, 240, 241, 250, 251, 253} immune function (n=7),^{187, 192, 197, 204, 212, 215, 237, 238} musculoskeletal (n=9),^{201, 210, 212, 228, 237, 240, 241, 251, 253} neurological (n=6),^{205, 212, 221, 244, 245, 253} neuropsychological (n=8),^{178, 196, 201, 210, 228, 233, 241, 251, 253, 259} oral health (n=13),^{190, 195, 207, 212, 223, 229-231, 234, 238, 239, 242, 251} orofacial (n=4),^{201, 210, 211, 228, 237} psychosocial (n=9),^{200, 201, 209, 210, 212, 228, 232, 237, 240, 241, 250, 251, 253} respiratory, urinary and visual ocular (n=4),^{210, 228, 240, 241} and other (n=6).^{202, 203, 216, 237, 252, 254}

Overall, the heterogeneity in how amalgam exposure and health outcomes were measured and dominance of weak quality evidence within each broad outcome category prevented firm conclusions from being drawn regarding the impact of amalgam restorations on patient health. However, there appears to be tentative evidence that amalgam restorations on permanent teeth may have a detrimental influence on some blood chemistry markers of immune function, musculoskeletal

symptoms and oral lichenoid lesion/reaction symptoms, but is not associated with oral lichen planus symptoms, psychosocial difficulties and no evidence to indicate a link between amalgam restorations and neuropsychological test performance. Further high-quality randomized controlled trials are needed to increase confidence in these findings. Below, abbreviated summaries of the association of amalgam restorations with broad health outcome categories supported by more than one study are provided, with full detail in [Part 3: Full synthesis – health outcomes](#).

Adverse events

The limited number (n=3) and weak-moderate quality of studies, lack of statistical comparison and generally low quality of the studies prevents firm conclusions being drawn.^{199, 201, 211, 232}

Allergy

Findings from eleven studies of variable quality evaluated the association between allergy to amalgam/mercury and oral health symptoms were mixed, with rates of allergy to mercury and/or amalgam varying widely between studies conducted with individuals with oral lichenoid lesion/reaction and oral lichen planus symptoms. This possibly reflects the heterogeneity in symptom aetiology, populations and methods used alongside the majority weak quality of evidence within this category.^{195, 210, 212, 213, 223, 229, 231, 238, 239, 242, 249}

Cardiovascular disease

Whilst three studies of weak to moderate quality using self-report measures of cardiovascular symptoms reported variable findings regarding in individuals who attributed health complaints to amalgam versus those who attributed health complaints to another cause or healthy controls,^{240, 241, 251} studies using more objective measures of exposure reported cardiovascular symptoms were not associated with urinary or blood mercury levels,²¹² and inconsistent findings relating to improvement of cardiovascular symptoms following amalgam removal/replacement.^{210, 228} Overall, the variability in quality of the evidence and findings pertaining to relationship between cardiovascular outcomes and amalgam exposure prevents identification of firm conclusions.

Dermatological

Within five studies evaluating the association between amalgam restorations and dermatological symptoms, findings were mixed.^{210, 228, 240, 241, 251} The heterogeneity of findings and weak-moderate quality of the studies overall prevents firm conclusions being drawn.

ENT

The five studies (four moderate, one weak quality) supporting this category indicate that there is no consistent evidence to support a significant association between amalgam removal and reduction in auditory or other ENT symptoms.^{210, 228, 240, 241, 253}

Female health

Two weak quality studies evaluated the impact of amalgam removal and/or replacement on different aspects of female and maternal health.^{210, 225} Heterogeneity of specific measures used prevented further synthesis.

Gastrointestinal

The seven studies contributing to the evidence base in this category were mostly of mixed moderate to weak quality.^{201, 210, 228, 240, 241, 251, 253} There appears to be some weak evidence to support the association between amalgam restorations and the occurrence and resolution of gastrointestinal symptoms, although findings vary according to specific outcome of interest and may be outweighed by findings from a moderate quality study which indicates patients may experience both improvement and worsening of stomach symptoms.²⁵³

General physical health

Findings of four studies of variable quality reported inconsistent findings regarding the relationship between self-reported general health symptoms and amalgam exposure, with the latter measured by number/presence of amalgams or mercury levels in blood or urine.^{212, 240, 241, 251} Similarly, findings from six studies appraised as mainly weak quality which evaluated the impact of amalgam removal on general physical health symptoms varied, possibly influenced by heterogenous outcome measures, control groups and follow-up time periods.^{199-201, 210, 211, 228, 232, 237, 250, 253}

Immune function

Evidence from three studies (two strong, one weak quality) indicated no statistically significant association between amalgam exposure, as measured by number of **amalgams in situ**, and various indicators of immune function which included diagnosis of primary Sjögren's syndrome, and an array of blood chemistry variables in children with amalgams on primary teeth.^{187, 192, 204, 212} However, one study found a significant association between number of amalgams on permanent teeth and lymphocyte function.¹⁸⁷ Four controlled before and after studies examined the relationship between **amalgam removal/replacement** and immune function outcomes: one appraised as Moderate quality,¹⁹⁷ and three appraised as weak quality.^{215, 237, 238} Generally, studies demonstrated a significant improvement in immune function markers in individuals who had their amalgam removed in

comparison to control groups where baseline measures were not statistically different between groups,^{215, 238} although one weak quality study indicated that self-reported susceptibility to infection was higher in patients who had amalgams removed versus those who did not.²³⁷ Overall, there appears to be tentative evidence that amalgam restorations on permanent teeth may have a detrimental influence on some blood chemistry markers of immune function, but further high quality trials are needed to increase confidence in this finding.

Musculoskeletal

Overall, the findings suggest an association of higher number of musculoskeletal symptoms with increased amalgam exposure and suggest a reduction in symptoms after removal. Self-reported musculoskeletal symptoms were higher in individuals attributing health complaints to amalgam restorations compared to control groups in three out of four studies of variable quality which examined the relationship between amalgam/mercury exposure (n=1),²¹² or amalgam exposure (n=3),^{240, 241} and musculoskeletal symptoms. However one weak quality study found a lower number of symptoms within the patient group compared to a control group who attributed their symptoms to environmental causes.²⁵¹ Another weak quality study found no significant difference in blood or urinary mercury levels between those experiencing musculoskeletal complaints and those that did not.²¹² Four of five studies reported significant reductions on different measures of musculoskeletal symptoms in the treatment group following amalgam removal compared to non-removal group,^{201, 210, 228, 253} however, three of the four studies were appraised as weak quality, so confidence in the finding is limited.

Neurological

Findings in six studies, the majority of which were appraised as strong quality, varied across specific outcomes measured, preventing identification of firm conclusions regarding any potential association between amalgam restorations in situ and patient neurological outcomes.^{205, 212, 221, 244, 245, 253}

Neuropsychological

None of the four variable quality studies (five articles) evaluating the relationship between amalgam restorations in situ and neuropsychological test performance found any significant association between the two variables,^{178, 196, 233, 241, 251, 259} aside from one strong quality study where increased amalgam exposure was associated with higher scores on memory and letter fluency tasks.¹⁹⁶ Due to the bias inherent in self-report measures and moderate-weak quality of the five studies evaluating impact of amalgam removal/replacement on neuropsychological symptoms, there is currently no evidence to indicate a link between amalgam restorations and neuropsychological test performance.

Oral health

Seven studies of variable quality evaluated the association between amalgam exposure,^{190, 195, 207, 230, 239, 251} or blood mercury level and oral disease or symptoms.²¹² Whilst the variable quality of evidence limits confidence in the findings (n=4), the evidence indicates that amalgam removal may support resolution of oral lichenoid lesions/reaction symptoms where amalgam is in close contact with lesions and individuals have a positive mercury patch test.^{223, 229, 231, 234} A limited quantity of evidence available from two studies also suggests that amalgam restorations may not be associated with oral lichen planus.^{230, 242}

Orofacial

Four studies (three weak, one moderate quality) contributing to this category presented mixed findings with respect to the following specific symptoms: burning sensation, pain/tenderness, stiffness/paraesthesia, temporomandibular joint pain, facial skin problems, taste disturbance, dry mouth and salivation.^{201, 210, 211, 228, 237}

Psychosocial

Four studies of variable quality examined the relationship between **amalgam restorations in situ** and psychological outcomes.^{209, 212, 240, 241, 251} Six studies, four of which were appraised as weak quality, examined the association between psychosocial outcomes and amalgam removal/replacement.^{200, 201, 210, 228, 232, 237, 250, 253} Overall, the current evidence does not indicate an association between amalgam restorations and patient psychosocial outcomes, although the predominantly low-quality of studies evaluating the impact of amalgam removal/replacement means this finding should be interpreted with caution.

Respiratory, urinary and visual/ocular

Findings from three moderate quality studies examining the association between amalgam restorations and respiratory symptoms were mixed.^{210, 240, 241} Two of these studies reported individuals with health symptoms attributed to amalgam did not have a significantly higher number of urinary symptoms than those who did not attribute health complaints to amalgam.^{240, 241} Four studies studied the association between removal/replacement of amalgam restorations and visual/ocular outcomes.^{210, 240, 241, 228} The two moderate quality studies by the same author found a significantly higher number of visual problems in individuals with health complaints attributed to amalgam.^{240, 241} The other weak-moderate quality studies reporting mixed findings, with two studies reporting no significant change in eye infection, visual disorder and intensity of visual disturbances from

pretreatment to one- or three-year follow-up, but a significant reduction in visual disturbances on a different outcome questionnaire at one- but not five-year follow-up.^{210, 228}

Health impacts: Composite resin and/or methacrylates

Fifteen studies (19 articles) evaluated the health impact of patient exposure to composite resin or methacrylate compounds on the health of adults or children. Quality appraisal scores were as follows: weak (n=7),^{195, 207, 239, 255, 257, 260, 261} moderate (n=3),^{190, 242, 256} and strong (n=5).^{192, 209, 213, 230, 233, 258, 262} Studies were synthesised within the following broad impact categories: allergy (n=5),^{195, 213, 229, 239, 242} genotoxicity (n=3),^{255, 260, 261} immune function (n=1),^{187, 192} neuropsychological (n=2),^{233, 258, 259} oral health (n=5),^{190, 195, 207, 230, 257} psychosocial (n=1),^{209, 258} and other (n=3).^{187, 256, 258, 262} One moderate quality study evaluated the rate of sensitisation to methacrylates/acrylates in dental health professionals.²¹⁸

The quantity of evidence evaluating health outcomes associated with composite resin restorations was much smaller than the quantity of evidence evaluating the health impact of amalgam, although similarly the limited number of studies and heterogeneity of study populations and outcome measures limited the confidence in the few associations between composite resin restorations and health outcomes which were identified. The strongest, most consistent evidence was found for neuropsychological health outcomes which found few associations between composite resin restorations and performance on psychological tests, where greater exposure to BisGMA-composite was linked to poorer psychosocial health at follow-up. However, both these broad health impact categories were only supported by two articles from the NECAT study.^{209, 258, 259} Overall, the health impact of composite resin restorations needs further appraisal by high quality randomized controlled trials. Below, abbreviated summaries of the association of composite resin restorations with each broad health impact group are provided, with full detail in [Part 3: Full synthesis – health outcomes](#).

Allergy

No clear association was found between patient allergy to composite materials and symptom characteristics in three studies of variable quality,^{195, 213, 242} although differences between population characteristics made comparison across different studies difficult. Similarly rates of allergy to methacrylates and/or acrylates between patients with oral health conditions and control populations varied across three studies, according to type methacrylate/acrylate exposure, with the strongest/most consistent evidence available for ethyl methacrylate and diurethane dimethacrylate, where two studies found no significant difference in sensitization rate between population groups.^{213, 239} Findings relating to other types of methacrylates/acrylates were mixed and/or extremely limited. Only one study reported allergy rates to methacrylates/acrylates in dental health professionals.²¹⁸

Genotoxicity

Population groups and/or specific outcome measures tended to be non-comparable across three studies, all appraised as weak quality.^{255, 260, 261} Where outcomes measured were the same across studies, findings were inconsistent, potentially reflecting differences in restorative material being evaluated and low-quality of the evidence contributing this outcome.

Immune function

Two strong quality articles from the NECAT randomised controlled trial contributed to this category.^{187, 192} No consistent associations were shown between type of restorative material, immune function outcome and time of follow up (six months, one- and five-years), although increased numbers of surfaces treated with non-flowable compomer restorations positively associated with one out of two measures of monocyte function.¹⁸⁷ The same article indicated higher numbers of tooth surfaces treated on permanent teeth treated with Bis-GMA based non-flowable composite fillings were associated with increased B-cell activation, higher numbers of flowable composites used in preventative treatment were associated with increased total white blood cell count, although findings pertaining to neutrophil function varied.¹⁸⁷ The other article reported no significant differences in measures of immune function at different points of follow-up for children who received composite restorations.¹⁹² The limited number of studies and use of different outcome measures makes it difficult to draw firm conclusions regarding the relationship between composite resin restorations in children and immune function outcomes.

Neuropsychological

Two articles appraised as strong quality from the NECAT study found few significant associations between exposure to resin composite/compomers or flowable sealant/preventative resin restorations (PRR) in situ and neuropsychological outcomes.^{258, 259} One strong quality retrospective observational study found no link between number of composite resin restorations and risk of developing dementia.²³³ The limited number of studies supporting this category prevents firm conclusions based on these findings.

Oral health

Five studies of variable quality examined the association between composite resin restorations in situ and patient oral health outcomes.^{190, 195, 207, 230, 257} Populations and specific outcomes of interest across these studies were heterogenous and non-comparable, but broadly indicated no significant association between composite resin restorations exposure and oral health symptoms, although adjusted odds

ratio for oral lichen planus was significantly increased for individuals receiving 3-4 composite fillings per year in one strong quality study.²³⁰

Psychosocial

Two articles from the NECAT study appraised as strong quality found eleven significant associations between child exposure to resin composite/comonomers or flowable sealant/preventative resin restorations (PRR) in situ on primary or posterior teeth and psychosocial health outcomes out of the 53 symptoms measured.^{209, 258} Most of these concerned use of BisGMA-based composite on permanent teeth, with specific measures focusing on clinical maladjustment, personal adjustment, and emotional symptoms index, interpersonal relations, anxiety, depression, clinical maladjustment, interpersonal relation and the emotional symptoms index. Results indicate greater exposure to BisGMA-composite was linked to poorer psychosocial performance at follow-up. Further studies are needed to evaluate the reliability of these findings.

Health impacts: Glass ionomer vs composite resin/compomer

Three studies compared the health impact of glass ionomer restorations with composite/compomer resins (see Supplementary Materials E, Table 59).

One retrospective cohort study appraised as strong quality, reported no significant differences between groups receiving glass ionomer, amalgam or composite resin restorations with ADHD incidence or 10-year hazard probability.¹⁸⁵

One RCT appraised as moderate quality compared gingival health glass ionomer Vitremer with composite resin material Z250, with findings significantly favouring Vitremer at 12- and 24-months.²⁶³

Another RCT appraised as weak quality compared genotoxicity outcomes, including: micro nucleated/binucleated cells, cells with nucleoplasmic bridges, nuclear buds, pyknosis, condensed chromatin, karyorrhexis, among individuals who received one of two different types of glass ionomer restoration (Ketac Molar and Ionofil Molar) or a compomer restoration.²⁵⁵ Within-group comparisons for GIC materials showed no significant changes over time, aside for micronuclei and binucleated cell frequency for Ketac Molar and Ionofil Molar respectively.²⁵⁵ No significant difference were observed for any outcome between different types of restorative material, aside for number of binucleated cells at seven-day follow up for individuals receiving 'Twinkly Star' compomer and Ketac Molar, with age significantly impacting occurrence of binuclear cells.²⁵⁵

Full narrative synthesis: Environmental impacts

In this section we present the findings of studies which reported data relating to environmental impacts, and whether these related to actual environment impacts or potential environmental impacts (see [Synthesis: Environmental impacts](#) in Part 2 for how we distinguish between actual and potential environmental impact). Studies which included a comparison between different types of restorative material are presented first, followed by non-comparative studies, i.e. studies which only included one type of restorative material (either amalgam or composite) or multiple types with no comparison between materials. Within each section for comparative and non-comparative studies, the studies are grouped within broad impact categories. These are listed below per category of study, in the order in which they are narratively synthesised:

- Studies which compared different types of restorative material (n=5):
 - Mercury levels in wastewater (n=2)^{264, 277}
 - Mercury levels in particulate matter (PM) (n=1)²⁷⁸
 - Animal toxicity (n=1)²⁷⁰
 - Carbon footprint (n=1)²⁶⁶
- Studies which included multiple restorative materials with no comparison (n=2)
 - Animal toxicity (n=2)^{265, 270}
- Studies which only included amalgam restorative material (n=11):
 - Mercury levels in wastewater (n=3)^{274, 275, 279}
 - Mercury levels in solid waste (n=3)^{269, 271, 274}
 - Mercury levels in emissions (n=3)^{254, 268, 280}
 - Mercury levels in vapour (n=3)^{267, 282, 283}
 - Mercury levels in PM (n=1)²⁶⁷
- Studies which only included composite restorative materials (n=4):
 - Monomer levels in wastewater (n=2)^{273, 276}
 - Monomer levels in PM (n=1)²⁸¹
 - Monomer levels in emissions (n=1)²⁷²

Finally in this section, we draw together the findings from studies where environmental impact was measured (i.e. actual environmental impact) versus studies where there was only potential environmental impact.

Environmental impact: multiple restorative materials with comparison (n=5)

Five studies included a comparison between different restoration materials.^{264, 266, 270, 277, 278} These studies were categorised within four broad impact categories: mercury levels in wastewater (n=2);^{264,}

²⁷⁷ mercury levels in particulate matter (n=1);²⁷⁸ animal toxicity (n=1);²⁷⁰ and carbon footprint (n=1).²⁶⁶ All of these studies included amalgam in the comparison with other materials.

Mercury levels in wastewater in studies which compare restorative materials (n=2)

Al Kawas et al.²⁶⁴ and Shraim et al.²⁷⁷ compared mercury levels in wastewater for different restorative materials, both including amalgam (see *Table 3*). Both were in clinic settings and classified as high risk of bias.

Clinic setting (n=2]

Al-Kawas et al. assessed mercury levels in wastewater from two clinics which used only amalgam restorative material, and one clinic which used multiple materials, including composite and glass-ionomer, which provided wastewater samples with no amalgam for comparison.²⁶⁴ The study had a specific focus on restorations, although samples contained wastewater relating to other activities including removals (see *Table 3*). Mercury levels were highest in samples from clinics where only amalgam restorations were performed, but was still present in samples when no amalgam was used due to sedimentation of amalgam particles from previous treatments inside wastewater tubes.²⁶⁴ No statistical testing was undertaken to assess the significance of the results, nor assessment of compliance with wastewater guidance.

Shraim et al. also assessed mercury levels in wastewater from dental chairs at three clinics.²⁷⁷ Similarly to Al Kawas et al., mercury levels were highest in the clinic where the most amalgam restorations were carried out, but still present where no amalgam restorations were performed (see *Table 3*).²⁶⁴ The authors suggest the latter finding is likely due to amalgam removals taking place in this clinic.²⁷⁷ The study reports that hazardous levels of amalgam were found in most samples, according to the Technical Regulations for Discharge of Raw Wastewater of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA) Ministry of Municipal and Rural Affairs, 2002; also hazardous levels of Mg, Mn, Cu, Zn, Sn and Ba, some of which are amalgam constituents.²⁷⁷ Negligible levels of metal concentration were found in the inlet water. Statistical significance of findings was not assessed.

Table 3. Mercury levels in wastewater in studies which compare restorative materials (n=2)

Study (Date) [Study design]	Restorative material (activity)	Exposure (control/comparator)	Specific outcomes measured, units	Outcome details
Clinic setting (n=2)				
Al-Kawas (2008) [Cross-sectional with comparator] ²⁶⁴	Amalgam, composite, glass ionomer (restorations, removals)*	Wastewater from dental chairs at three dental clinics (comparator: different restorative materials used per wastewater sample)	Hg concentration in wastewater samples, mean SD (range), mg/L	<p>Amalgam only samples: 0.039 mg/L (SD: 0.037; range: 0.004–0.142)</p> <p>Amalgam + composite + glass ionomer samples: 0.024 mg/L (SD: 0.024; range: 0–0.077)</p> <p>Composite + glass ionomer samples: 0.018 mg/L (SD: 0.016; range: 0–0.033)</p> <p style="text-align: right;">Guidance compliant: ●</p>
Shraim (2011) [Prospective longitudinal with comparator] ²⁷⁷	Amalgam, composite, glass ionomer (restorations, removals) [†]	Wastewater discharged from three dental clinics (1, 2 and 3A, 3B and 3C) (comparator: all clinics use amalgam except only composite at 3C clinic)	<p>Hg mass in samples, average mg per sample, coefficient of variation (CV), range</p> <p>Comparison of Hg across clinics, mg</p> <p>Hg and other metal concentrations in inlet water, mg</p>	<p>Hg mass in samples: Overall average mass per sample: 5.3 mg; CV: 0.0021; range of values of Hg in all samples: 0.009–59.3 mg L⁻¹. Most samples contained hazardous levels of metals, including Mg, Mn, Cu, Zn, Sn, Ba, and Hg, many of which are amalgam constituents.</p> <p>Clinic comparison: Clinics 1 and 2, where the most amalgam-based operations are carried out, produced the most Hg (114.2 and 207.1 mg respectively. Clinics 3A and 3B, which treat mostly children and use less amalgam restorations, produced only 9.6 and 12.8 mg Hg respectively. Clinic 3C produced higher Hg content (94.0 mg) than 3A and 3B despite not undertaking amalgam restorations. However, this clinic treats adults who mostly replace Hg amalgam restorations with non-mercury composites and denture operations on amalgam-treated tooth.</p> <p>Inlet water Hg and other metals concentration: Very low metal concentrations, except for Mg (7 mg/L) and Sr (0.1 mg/L). Contribution of inlet water to the metals content of the clinics' wastewater is negligible, except for Mg, which is relatively high.</p> <p style="text-align: right;">Guidance compliant: ●</p>

Abbreviations: CV=coefficient of variation; Hg=mercury; SD=standard deviation.

Key: Guidance compliant: Yes=● No=● NR=●

* Also root canal, tooth extraction, cavity preparation and temporary restoration, pulpotomy, scaling and polishing, and other.

†Also gingivectomy, crown, bridge, endodontic treatment, pulpectomy, cementation and other.

Mercury levels in particulate matter in studies which compare restorative materials (n=1)

One study compared mercury levels in particulate matter for different restorative materials in a clinic setting, including amalgam (see *Table 4*).²⁷⁸ This was rated medium risk of bias.

Clinic setting (n=1)

Simu et al. reported levels of mercury in particulate matter in a dental clinic setting, and reported that silver amalgam restorations contained more toxic compounds than other types of restoration material, including composites and glass-ionomers (see *Table 4*).²⁷⁸ However, the study does not report the relative degree to which amalgam and non-amalgam restorative materials contain toxic particles and whether these are at harmful levels.²⁷⁸ Compliance with guidelines was also not reported.

Table 4. Mercury levels in particulate matter in studies which compare restorative materials (n=1)

Study (Year) [Study design]	Restorative material (activity)	Exposure (control/comparator)	Specific outcomes measured, units	Outcome details
Clinic setting (n=1)				
Simu (2014) [Cross-sectional] ²⁷⁸	Amalgam, composite, glass ionomer (restorations, removals)*	Exposure to particulate matter in dental clinic setting (comparator: different restorative materials described in analysis)	Size and nature of dental aerosol particles.	Silver amalgam restorations contained the largest number of compounds compared to other types of restoration material, including composite and glass ionomer. Elements of compounds identified during amalgam removals had moderate to high toxicity: Ce, Cs, Gd, Hg, La, Lu, Os, Tl.

Guidance compliant: ●

Key: Guidance compliant: Yes=● No=● NR=●

*Also, ultrasound scaling, root canal preparation, cavity preparation, teeth preparation for prosthetic purpose, orthodontic controls and other.

Animal toxicity in studies which compare restorative materials (n=1)

One study compared the animal toxicity of mercury and monomer levels in wastewater associated with amalgam and composite restorative materials respectively (see *Table 5*).²⁷⁰ This study was conducted in a lab setting and rated medium risk of bias.

Lab setting (n=1)

Majstorovic et al. assessed toxicity of mercury and monomers released into water through leaching of amalgam and composite restorative materials for zebrafish.²⁷⁰ Testing took place after both 48 hours and 7 days incubation of water samples. The highest toxicity to zebrafish was caused by experimental composite, followed by amalgam, commercial composite, glass-ionomer and alkasite (see *Table 5*). Toxicity reduced after 7 days. Developmental abnormalities were statistically significant for amalgam and experimental composite, including at LC₃₀ values for both incubation periods. Developmental abnormalities were not statistically significant for other restorative materials.

Table 5. Animal toxicity in studies which compare restorative materials (n=1)

Study (Year) [Study design]	Restorative material (activity)	Exposure (control/comparator)	Specific outcomes measured, units	Outcome details
Lab setting (n=1)				
Majstorovic (2024) [Part 2: Controlled trial] ²⁷⁰	Alkasite: Cention Forte Amalgam Commercial composite: Tetric EvoCeram Experimental composite: Bis-GMA/TEGDMA Glass ionomer cement: Equia Forte HT Fil (Leaching)	Hg/monomer concentration leached from dental materials in aqueous solution (comparator: amalgam vs non-amalgam materials [i.e. composite vs glass ionomer vs alkasite]; control: E3 medium)	Hg concentration (amalgam samples) after 48h and 7d incubation, µg/L BPA, TEGDMA and UDMA concentration (non-amalgam samples) after 48h and 7d incubation, mg/mL Toxicity to zebrafish: 48-hour and 7-day lethal concentrations (LC ₅₀ and LC ₃₀ , g/L)	Hg concentration (amalgam samples): 50.5 µg/L (48h); 4.48 µg/L (7d) Monomer concentration (non-amalgam samples): TEGDMA was detected only in experimental composite and alkasite, both after 48h and 7d. UDMA was detected only in commercial composite after both 48h and 7d. No residual monomers detected from glass ionomer cement. Where detected, concentrations reduced between 48h and 7d. Toxicity to zebrafish 48h: The highest toxicity to zebrafish was observed in experimental composite (i.e. TEGDMA) (LC ₅₀ =0.70 g/L), followed by amalgam (i.e. Hg) (LC ₅₀ =8.27 g/L), commercial composite (i.e. UDMA) (LC ₅₀ =10.94 g/L), glass ionomer (monomer n.d.) (LC ₅₀ =24.84 g/L) and alkasite (i.e. BPA and TEGDMA) (LC ₅₀ =32.22 g/L). Control: ND 7d: LC ₅₀ values of commercial and experimental composite suspensions were 22.49% and 38.57% higher, respectively, when incubated for 48 h than when incubated for 7d. Samples of glass ionomer and Alkasite incubated for 7d showed no adverse outcomes. Amalgam 314.75% higher toxicity after 48 h of incubation than after 7d. Control: ND At 96 hpf both experimental composite and amalgam induced dose-dependent developmental abnormalities, including pericardial edema and scoliosis. This was statistically significant at concentrations corresponding to LC ₃₀ values for both incubation periods compared control group (p < 0.05). Exposure to commercial composite (both incubation periods) did not result in a statistically significant incidence of developmental alterations (p>0.05), as was the case with glass ionomer and alkasite materials. Guidance compliant: ●

Abbreviations: BPA=Bisphenol A; Hg=mercury; hpf=hours post fertilization; LC=lethal concentration; ND=not detected; TEGDMA= Triethylene Glycol Dimethacrylate; UDMA=Urethane Dimethacrylate
Key: Guidance compliant: Yes=● No=● NR=●

Carbon footprint in studies which compare different restorative materials (n=1)

One study compared the carbon footprint of different restoration materials, including amalgam (see *Table 6*).²⁶⁶ This related to clinic settings, i.e. measuring carbon footprint associated with dental activities in NHS primary care dental clinics in England, and rated high risk of bias.

Clinic setting (n=1)

Duane et al. reported that the total carbon footprint for amalgam and composite restorative materials was similar, with amalgam slightly higher (see *Table 6*).²⁶⁶ Total carbon footprint for glass-ionomer restorative materials was lowest of three materials, but also accounted for the smallest proportion of dental services (1.5%) compared to amalgam (9.79%) or composite (9.52%) restorative treatment.²⁶⁶ Per procedure, glass-ionomer restorations had just over half the carbon footprint of amalgam or composite (8.58 vs 14.76 vs 14.75 kgCO₂e respectively).²⁶⁶ However, Duane et al. also note that most of the data for calculating carbon footprint of procedures is based on time and energy use, and that there were no data available relating to the materials.²⁶⁶ Examinations had a higher overall carbon footprint than restoration procedures, but this only related to volume of examinations versus procedures: individually, the carbon footprint of examinations is lower than restoration procedures (5.50 kgCO₂e).²⁶⁶ Patient and staff travel was the highest contributor to carbon footprint in NHS dental services in England, but it was not clear whether travel to dental services was incorporated into the carbon footprint of each procedure.

Table 6. Carbon footprint in studies which compare restorative materials (n=1)

Study (Year) [Study design]	Restorative material	Total carbon footprint, TCO ₂ e	Proportion of dental services, %	Carbon footprint per procedure, kgCO ₂ e
Duane (2017) [Secondary analysis of dataset] ²⁶⁶	Amalgam	65,560	9.79%	14.76
	Composite	63,799	9.52%	14.75
	Glass ionomer	10,041	1.5%	8.58
				Guidance compliant: ●

Abbreviations: kgCO₂e=kilograms of carbon dioxide equivalent; NA=not applicable; TCO₂e=tonnes of carbon dioxide equivalent.
Key: Guidance compliant: Yes=● No=● NR=●

Environmental impact: multiple restorative materials with no comparison (n=2)

Two studies included multiple restorative materials with no comparison between materials (see *Table 7*).^{265, 270} Both studies assessed animal toxicity relating to wastewater in clinic settings. One study included non-amalgam materials,²⁶⁵ and one study did not report the materials which were included.²⁷⁰

Animal toxicity in studies which include multiple materials (with no comparison) (n=2)

Majstorovic et al. investigated the toxicity of dental wastewater for zebrafish.²⁷⁰ They did not report which materials were used, but there was no indication that this was limited to one type of material.²⁷⁰ Binner et al. investigated the toxicity of composites and glass-ionomer on *Daphnia magna*.²⁶⁵ Both studies were rated as high risk of bias.

Clinic setting (n=2)

Majstorovic et al. identified mercury in the dental wastewater from three dental chair drainage systems in one clinic, and found that the toxicity was statistically significant for zebrafish exposed to samples from the clinic with the highest mercury concentration ($p < 0.001$) (see *Table 7*).²⁷⁰ Although no zebrafish mortality occurred, developmental abnormalities were observed, and no hatching was recorded in embryos exposed to samples from the clinic with the highest mercury concentrations (see *Table 7*). No monomers were detected in the wastewater, but the fact that testing was undertaken for monomers suggests that composites or glass-ionomers may have been used in the clinic.

In Binner et al., 48-hour EC₅₀ values for *Daphnia magna* exposed to wastewater samples from non-amalgam restorative materials – including composites and glass-ionomers – ranged from 0.2 to 32.9 mL/L (see *Table 7*).²⁶⁵ The variation was attributed to differing levels of disinfectants in the wastewater.²⁶⁵ Binner et al. interpreted their finding as showing environmental impact associated with non-amalgam materials despite the preference for using these instead of amalgam due to the absence of mercury.²⁶⁵

Table 7. Animal toxicity in studies which include multiple materials (with no comparison) (n=2)

Study (Year) [Study design]	Restorative material (activity)	Exposure (control/comparator)	Specific outcomes measured, units	Outcome details
Clinic setting (n=2)				
Binner (2022) [Cross-sectional] ²⁶⁵	Resin composite, glass ionomer, resin-modified glass ionomer cements (NR)	Dental wastewater samples collected from three dental facilities (NA)	48-hour EC ₅₀ for <i>Daphnia magna</i> , mL/L	Overall, the EC ₅₀ ranged from 0.2 to 32.9 mL dental wastewater/L in the three dental practices. Variation in toxicity was attributed to high concentrations of disinfection products in the analysed dental wastewater. These volumes will become diluted as the dental wastewater is released to the sewerage system. Guidance compliant: ●
Majstorovic (2024) [Part 1: Cross-sectional] ²⁷⁰	NR* (NR)	Wastewater from dental chair drainage systems (DCDS) for three chairs in one dental clinic (control: E3 medium in lab setting)	Hg/monomer concentration in wastewater samples taken from DCDS with different incubation periods (48h and 7d), µg/L Toxicity for zebrafish, narrative summary	Hg concentration: DCDS 1: 1.86 µg/L (7d); DCDS 2: 0.08 µg/L (48h); DCDS 3: 0.39 µg/L (7d) Monomer concentration: n.d. Toxicity for zebrafish: Exposure of zebrafish to DCDS samples resulted in decreased larval body length and increased occurrences of oedema and blood accumulation. Greatest reduction in body length was for DCDS1 (2.912 µm; p < 0.001), compared to the control group (3.774 µm). Yolk sac oedemas and blood accumulation were recorded on DCDS1 and DCDS3 samples, showing 67.50 % and 45.00 % abnormalities, respectively. Diluting these samples to 50 % reduced toxicity, and no abnormalities were detected at 25 % dilution. No developmental abnormalities were observed in the DCDS2 sample. None of the specimens exposed to DCDS1 hatched at 96 hpf. DCDS2–3 did not impact hatching rates. Control=100% hatching success. Guidance compliant: ●

Abbreviations: DCDS=dental chair drainage system; EC=effective concentration; Hg=mercury; NA=not applicable

Key: Guidance compliant: Yes=● No=● NR=●

*Dental materials used in clinics not reported, but testing was undertaken for both mercury and monomers. Only mercury was detected in the wastewater, most likely relating to amalgam restorative material, but it is not clear that only amalgam was used in the clinics.

Environmental impact: amalgam only (n=11)

Eleven studies included amalgam restoration material only.^{254, 267-269, 271, 274, 275, 279, 280, 282, 283} These studies were categorised within five broad impacts: mercury levels in dental wastewater (n=3),^{274, 275, 279} mercury levels in solid waste (n=3),^{269, 271, 274} mercury levels in emissions (n=3),^{254, 268, 280} mercury levels in vapour (n=3),^{267, 282, 283} and mercury levels in PM (n=1).²⁶⁷

Mercury levels in wastewater in studies which include amalgam only (n=3)

Three studies reported data relating to mercury levels in dental wastewater, including one study in a clinic setting,²⁷⁴ one in a lab setting,²⁷⁵ and one undertook analysis of findings from a clinic and lab setting combined (see *Table 8*).²⁷⁹

Clinic setting (n=1)

Olivera et al. assessed mercury levels in wastewater from chairside amalgam separators (CAS) (n=6) in a military dental clinic setting as part of dental amalgam separators ISO 11143:200820 testing (see *Table 8*).²⁷⁴ Overall, the CAS units assessed in the study were found to perform better than the US Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) standard with respect to mercury levels in wastewater; albeit, this related to overall performance of the CAS rather than specifically focusing on mercury levels.²⁷⁴ No statistical analysis of the significance of findings was undertaken. The study was rated medium risk of bias.

Lab setting (n=1)

Paryag et al. used water collected from a lab-based simulation study of amalgam restorations to calculate an estimate of the daily and monthly amount of mercury discharge in wastewater generated by dentists in Trinidad and Tobago.²⁷⁵ They included both liquid and solid portions of mercury filtrate in the lab-based simulation to estimate the total amount of mercury discharge. No statistical analysis or comparison with guidance was reported. However, they compared the estimate with previous estimations of daily mercury waste from Canadian dentists, which was found to be much lower despite no amalgam separators used in Trinidad and Tobago.²⁷⁵ The study was rated high risk of bias.

Clinic/lab settings combined (n=1)

Stone et al. compared the degree to which chlorine and chloramine mobilise mercury from dental amalgam, including both lab prepared amalgam and samples obtained from dental wastewater.²⁷⁹ This was done to assess the relative mercury levels following switch to chloramine in many water treatment facilities in the USA. The study found that chloramine mobilises mercury to a lesser degree than chlorine ($p < 0.001$) (see *Table 8*). The study was rated high risk of bias.

Table 8. Mercury levels in wastewater in studies which include amalgam only (n=3)

Study (Date) [Study design]	Restorative material (activity)	Exposure (control/comparator)	Specific outcomes measured, units	Outcome details
Clinic setting (n=1)				
Olivera (2020) [Prospective longitudinal]* ²⁷⁴	Amalgam (restorations)	Effluent from chairside amalgam separators (CAS) (n=6) at end of service life in military dental centre (NA)	Hg concentrations in effluent of CAS, mg/L (mean and range)	Mean CAS effluent Hg concentration: 0.95 +/- 0.89 mg/L to 4.15 +/- 2.51 mg/L. Minimum and maximum Hg concentrations measured in CAS effluent grab samples: 0.05 mg/L and 11.93 mg/L. respectively, and mean concentration was 1.99 +/- 2.09 mg/L Guidance compliant: ●
Lab setting (n=1)				
Paryag (2010) [Modelling study] ²⁷⁵	Amalgam (removals)	Concentration of Hg in filtrate from wastewater and solid sample in lab setting (NA)	Hg discharge from amalgam restoration removal in Trinidad and Tobago, mean mg per month and mg per day	All Dentists in Trinidad and Tobago for 1 month: 22,285,350 mg/month Per Dentist per month: 94,820 mg/month Per Dentist per day: 3,400 mg/day Guidance compliant: ●
Clinic/lab setting combined (n=1)				
Stone (2009) [Prospective longitudinal with control] ²⁷⁹	Amalgam (NR)	Clinic: Chairside wastewater from dental chairs fitted with air/water separator (n=5) Lab: lab-prepared samples (Control: de-ionized water)	Hg level from wastewater exposed to chlorine vs monochloramine (1 mg/L and 10 mg/L) T-test of mean natural log-transformed mercury concentration, ln(Hg), µg/L ANCOVA	Hg concentration: 10 mg/L chlorine: 0.59 Hg mg/L (mean) (n= 25, SD= 1.06). 1 mg/L chloramine: 0.023 Hg mg/L (mean) (n= 25, SD = 0.010). 10 mg/L chloramine: 0.024 Hg mg/L (mean) (n= 25, SD = 0.011). Control: 0.013 Hg mg/L (mean) (n=19, SD=0.006) T-tests: Statistically significant difference in the natural log-transformed mercury (Hg) concentrations between 10 mg/L chlorine and both 1 mg/L and 10 mg/L monochloramine treatments. E.g. the mean ln(Hg) for 10 mg/L chlorine was -1.52 (SD: 1.34), compared to -3.87 (SD: 0.56) for 10 mg/L monochloramine. This difference was statistically significant (p < 0.001), indicating that significantly higher levels of mercury were observed following treatment with 10 mg/L chlorine compared to 10 mg/L monochloramine. ANCOVA results: Each one of the independent variables was significantly related to the Hg concentration: treatment, sample (laboratory-generated vs. clinical amalgam), time and pH all significant (p<0.001). Results demonstrate that chloramine does not mobilize Hg to the same degree as chlorine. Guidance compliant: ●

Abbreviations: ANCOVA=analysis of covariance; CAS=chairside amalgam separator; Hg=mercury; NA=not applicable; NR=not reported

Key: Guidance compliant: Yes=● No=● NR=●

*Unlike other studies assessing guidance compliance, which focus on assessments in relation to Hg levels, Olivera et al. assess guidance compliance in relation to CAS performance.

Mercury levels in solid filtrate/solid waste in studies which include amalgam only (n=3)

Three studies reported data relating to mercury in solid filtrate or solid waste.^{269, 271, 274} All three were in clinic settings.

Table 9. Mercury levels in solid filtrate/solid waste in studies which include amalgam only (n=3)*

Study (Year) [Study design]	Restorative material (activity)	Exposure (control/comparator)	Specific outcomes measured, units	Outcome details
Clinic setting (n=3)				
Kontogianni (2007) [Cross-sectional survey] ²⁶⁹	Amalgam (NR)	Disposal of solid amalgam waste in Thessaloniki, Greece (comparison: % total amalgam waste vs [other] metal-bearing and non-metal bearing waste)	Total amalgam waste per year (vs metal-bearing vs non-metal bearing), % and g Mean daily disposal of solid amalgam waste per clinic, g	% of total waste per year: 0.1% (amalgam) vs 15.12% (metal bearing) vs 84.78% (non-metal bearing) Daily disposal per clinic: 5g Guidance compliant: ●
Mandalidis (2018) [Cross-sectional] ²⁷¹	Amalgam (removals, restorations)	Disposal of solid amalgam waste in Xanthi, Greece (NA)	Overall waste production, % Daily waste production per practice, g	Overall waste production: Excess amalgam: 0.01% Plastic amalgam capsules: 0.03% Daily waste production per practice: Excess amalgam: 0.02g ± 0.01 Plastic amalgam capsules: 0.1g ± 0.04 Guidance compliant: ●
Olivera (2020) [Prospective longitudinal] ¹²⁷⁴	Amalgam (restorations)	Solid filtrate from chairside amalgam separators (CAS) (n=6) at end of service life in military dental centre (NA)	Material in filtrate, % and g Hg in solid filtrate of CAS, %	Material in filtrate: 57% non-amalgam materials (145.422 g); 43% amalgam (109.511 g). Hg in filtrate: Hg (20.9%) was the major metal of the recovered solids, with silver (11.7%), tin (6.1%), and copper (4.3%) making up the remaining amalgam constituent. Guidance compliant: ●

Abbreviations: CAS=Chairside amalgam separator; Hg=mercury; NA=not applicable; NR=not reported; %w/w=weight/weight percentage.

Key: Guidance compliant: Yes=● No=● NR=●

*Includes solid waste without measuring mercury concentration; included here because it is implied that this waste is related to environmental impact from mercury levels in waste.

†Unlike other studies assessing guidance compliance, which focus on assessments in relation to Hg levels, Olivera et al. assess guidance compliance in relation to CAS performance.

Clinic settings (n=3)

Olivera et al. reported the mean total solids accumulated in each CAS (n=6) at the end of service life (see *Table 9*).²⁷⁴ Overall, the CAS units assessed in the study were found to perform better than the USA EPA standard; albeit, this related to overall performance of the CAS rather than specifically focusing on mercury levels.²⁷⁴ The study was rated medium risk of bias.

Kontogianni et al.²⁶⁹ and Mandalidis et al.²⁷¹ reported amalgam waste generated by dental clinics in two different regions of Greece, with a seven-year gap between data collection periods (2006-2013 respectively). Kontogianni et al. was rated medium risk of bias²⁶⁹ and Mandalidis et al. rated high risk of bias.²⁷¹ The proportion of total waste comprised of amalgam was lower in the more recent study, potentially reflecting the declining use of amalgam restorative materials over time (see *Table 9*).²⁷¹ Although both studies linked amalgam waste with mercury, neither assessed mercury concentrations in the waste nor evaluated waste levels against waste management guidelines.

Mercury levels in emissions in studies which include amalgam only (n=3)

Three studies reported data relating to mercury levels in emissions (see *Table 10*).^{254, 268, 280} One study was conducted in a clinic setting,²⁶⁸ and two studies were in a crematorium setting.^{254, 280} All studies reported environmental outcomes relating to amalgam restorative material, although the focus on amalgam relates mainly to this being the main source of mercury rather than the only restorative material in the teeth in the samples.

Table 10. Mercury levels in emissions in studies which include amalgam only (n=3)

Study (Year) [Study design]	Restorative material (activity)	Exposure (control/comparator)	Specific outcomes measured, units	Outcome details
Clinic setting (n=1)				
Kim (2018) [Cross-sectional with modelling] ²⁶⁸	Amalgam (incineration of extracted teeth)	Emissions from general dental clinics (n=2) and private dental clinics (n=5) (NA)	Hg levels in emissions per year (total and adjusted estimate for dental institution weights in Korean dentistry units), kg	Total emissions: 48.86 kg (95% confidence interval [CI] 41.53–58.63 kg) of Hg incinerated with extracted teeth. Adjusted estimate for dental institution weights: 42.53 kg (95% CI 34.11–52.17 kg). Guidance compliant: ●
Crematorium setting (n=2)				
Piagno (2020) [Modelling study] ²⁵⁴	Amalgam (incineration of extracted teeth)	Emissions from crematoriums in BC, Canada (NA)	Estimated annual Hg emissions from cremations, kg/year Overall Hg contribution to emissions in BC, %	Estimated annual emissions: 35.8 kg/year Overall %: >7% of overall emissions of Hg to the atmosphere in BC. Guidance compliant: ●
Takaoka (2010) [Modelling study] ²⁸⁰	Amalgam (incineration of extracted teeth)	Emissions from crematoriums in Japan (NA)	Estimated annual Hg emissions from cremations, kg/year Overall Hg contribution to emissions in Japan, %	Estimated annual emissions: 35.1 kg/year Overall %: <0.01% of the total amount of Hg released into the atmosphere in Japan. Guidance compliant: ●

Abbreviations: BC=British Columbia; NA=not applicable; NR=not reported; OSHA= Occupational Safety and Health Administration
SE=standard error

Key: Guidance compliant: Yes=● No=● NR=●

Clinic settings (n=1)

Kim et al. reported total mercury emissions from incineration of extracted teeth at Korean dentistry units (see Table 10).²⁶⁸ The study was rated high risk of bias. They do not report whether this meets recommended guidance, but they do report that Korean guidelines do not (at time of writing) require separating amalgam from non-amalgam restorations before incinerating as required in the USA, and they recommend that this practice is introduced.²⁶⁸ They also cite a trend for reduction in amalgam restorations in Korea in the last decade (4.1 million in 2012 to 3.54 million in 2013 and 3.09 million in 2014).²⁶⁸

Crematorium settings (n=2)

Two studies measured mercury concentrations in crematorium emissions, one was rated high risk of bias²⁵⁴ and the other medium risk.²⁸⁰ Both studies used modelling approaches to estimate the average annual mercury emissions from the incineration of extracted teeth during cremation: one in British Columbia, Canada,²⁵⁴ and the other in Japan.²⁸⁰ Although the estimated total annual mercury emissions were similar (approximately 35 kg/year), and both studies assumed c. 50% mercury content per filling, the estimated mercury released per cremation varied dramatically: Takaoka et al. estimated

31.2 mg per cremation,²⁸⁰ while Piagno et al. estimated 2.1 g per cremation, i.e. a 6,400% increase.²⁵⁴ This discrepancy likely reflects differences in model assumptions, such as amalgam prevalence, pre-cremation tooth removal, and population dental history. The difference in the overall percentage of national mercury emissions attributed to crematoriums (>7% in BC vs <0.01% in Japan) may be due to industrial and demographic factors, including Japan's much larger industrial economy.³⁰¹

Mercury levels in vapour in studies which include amalgam only (n=3)

Three studies reported data relating to mercury levels in vapour, including one which reported data from a clinic setting,²⁸² one from a lab setting,²⁸³ and one from both a clinic and lab setting (see *Table 11*).²⁶⁷

Table 11. Mercury levels in vapour in studies which include amalgam only (n=3)

Study (Year) [Study design]	Restorative material (activity)	Exposure (control/comparator)	Specific outcomes measured, units	Outcome details
Clinic setting (n=2)				
Gioda (2007) [Before and after study] ^{*267}	Amalgam (restorations, removals)	Vapour from students undertaking dental exam in clinic setting (comparator: student vs professors observing exam, stationary measurements inside vs outside building)	Hg levels in vapour per student and professors, $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (mean and SE) Hg levels in vapour in room and outside building (baseline reference), $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (mean and SE)	People in room: Students: 50.6 (mean) $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (+/- 9.7 SE); Professors: 39.7 (mean) $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (+/-6.4 SE). Stationary samplers in/outside room: Indoor stationary sampler: 24.2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (+/- 3.1 SE); Outdoor indoor stationary sampler: 10.9 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ Guidance compliant: ● [†]
Warwick (2019) [Prospective longitudinal with control] ²⁸²	Amalgam (removals)	Concentration of Hg vapour after exposure to particulate matter during restoration removal (control: no amalgam removal)	Peak Hg Vapour, $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ 15 min average Hg vapour, $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ 30 min average Hg vapour, $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ 60 min average Hg vapour, $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$	Peak Hg vapour: 195 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (mean) (241 SD), Median: 80 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ 15 min average Hg vapour: 152 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (mean) (217 SD), Median: 46 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ 30 min average Hg vapour: Mean 135 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (196 SD), Median: 43 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ 60 min average Hg vapour: Mean: 109 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (163 SD), Median: 26 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ Control: <detectable μg of Hg mass Guidance compliant: ●
Lab setting (n=2)				
Gioda (2007) [Before and after study] ^{*267}	Amalgam (restorations, removals)	Vapour from students undertaking dental exam in lab setting (NA)	Hg levels per student, mg/m^3 (median and range)	2.2 mg/m^3 (median) (range: 1.1-3.3) Guidance compliant: ●
Warwick (2013) [Controlled trial] ²⁸³	Amalgam (removals)	Vapour from removals with simultaneous use of water spray and suction vs with suction only (control: with neither suction nor water spray)	Hg levels in vapour, mean and SD ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$); median and range ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$); statistical significance	With water spray and suction: 8.0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (mean) \pm 3.7 (SD); 8.0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (median) (range: 4.0–19.0) Guidance compliant: ● With suction only: 142.0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (mean) \pm 234.6 (SD); 68.0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (median) (range: 14.0–999.0); exposure greater than suction & water statistically significant ($p < 0.001$) Guidance compliant: ● With no water spray or suction: 214 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (mean) \pm 226.4 (SD); 117.0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (median) (range: 34.0–796.0); exposure greater than suction and water statistically significant ($p = 0.031$)

Abbreviations: ACGIH=American Conference of Governmental Industrial Hygienists; Hg=mercury; OSHA=Occupational Safety and Health Administration; NA=not applicable; SD=standard deviation; SE=standard error

Key: Guidance compliant: Yes=● No=● NR=●

*Does not include pre-post mercury level comparison for vapour levels (this is limited to the particulate matter component of the study, see table below).

†Compliant with US Occupational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA) permissible exposure limit (100 µg/m³) but slightly above the advisory American Conference of Governmental Industrial Hygienists (ACGIH) time-weighted average (TWA) 8h day/40h week recommendation (i.e. 50 µg/m³), although students are only exposed for 4.2 hours on one day.

Clinic settings (n=2)

The two studies in clinic settings (including one which included a clinic component alongside a separate lab component) both assessed findings with reference to the USA Occupational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA) permissible exposure limit ($100 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$).^{267, 282} Gioda et al.²⁶⁷ was rated high risk of bias and Warwick et al. (2019) medium risk of bias.²⁸²

Gioda et al. reported mercury concentrations in vapour released from amalgam restorations and removals during a third-year dental student examination, using personal vapour samplers worn by students ($n = 23$).²⁶⁷ The mean mercury exposure level was $50.6 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (± 9.7 SE), which is below the OSHA permissible exposure limit but slightly above the advisory time-weighted average (TWA) recommended by the American Conference of Governmental Industrial Hygienists (ACGIH) for an 8-hour day/40-hour week ($50 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$). However, students were only exposed for approximately 4.2 hours on a single day.²⁶⁷ No mercury vapour was detected in the room prior to the examination (see *Table 11*).

Warwick et al. (2019) reported mercury vapour concentrations during amalgam extractions for 21 patients across two clinics, alongside two control patients.²⁸² Mercury levels were recorded as peak values as well as 15-, 30-, and 60-minute averages for each procedure (see *Table 11*). In contrast to Gioda et al.,²⁶⁷ Warwick et al. observed mean peak concentrations exceeding the OSHA permissible exposure limit ($195 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, $\text{SD} = 241$).²⁸² However, this refers to peak levels, whereas Gioda et al. reported a mean exposure over a 4.2-hour period. Although levels declined over the subsequent hour, the mean 60-minute concentration remained above the OSHA limit at $109 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. Warwick et al. further noted that the 60-minute average was high enough that, even assuming no further exposure for the remaining 7 hours of an 8-hour workday, the time-weighted average would still exceed the ACGIH's recommended limit of $25 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$.²⁸²

Lab settings (n=2)

Gioda et al. reported mercury concentration in vapour from amalgam restorations and removals during a dental student exam in a lab setting using vapour samplers attached to students ($n=5$).²⁶⁷ They report that some students were exposed to mercury concentrations 30 times above the OSHA's recommended level of $100 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (see *Table 11*).²⁶⁷ They noted this was higher than in the clinic setting exam because of the longer sampling period and higher number of amalgam capsules used. Also, the students in the clinic setting were third year students versus second-year students in the lab setting who are less experienced.²⁶⁷

Warwick et al. (2019) reported mercury vapour concentrations during a laboratory simulation of removal of amalgam restorations from teeth under three different conditions (see *Table 11*).²⁸² When

both suction and water spray were used, mercury concentrations remained below the Alberta Occupational Ceiling Limit of 125 µg/m³. In contrast, this limit was exceeded during 8% of the suction-only test duration and 16% of the time in the no-suction/no-spray condition.²⁸² The Alberta Occupational Threshold Limit Value (AOTLV) of 25 µg/m³ (8-hour time-weighted average) was breached in 100% of readings under the no suction or water condition, 84% of readings with suction only, and 0% with water spray and suction.²⁸² The study was rated medium risk of bias.

Mercury levels in particulate matter (n=1)

One study reported mercury levels in particulate matter (see *Table 12*).²⁶⁷ This study included only amalgam restorative material, included both a clinic and lab component, and was rated high risk of bias.²⁶⁷

Clinic setting (n=1)

Gioda et al. reported mercury concentration in PM from amalgam restorations and removals during a one-day dental student exam (n=35 students).²⁶⁷ The average concentration of Hg bound to PM₁₀ was 0.1 µg/m³ (0.01–0.2 µg/m³) (see *Table 12*). They report that there are no recommended PM₁₀ indoor air quality standards, but total dust should not exceed 100 µg/m³.²⁶⁷

Lab setting (n=1)

Gioda et al. undertook the same test in a lab environment, for a different set of students (n=39).²⁶⁷ The average concentration of mercury bound to PM₁₀ was nine times higher at 0.6 µg/m³ (0.1–1.2 µg/m³). The highest mercury concentrations occurred during the day of the exam. They reported that the higher concentrations of mercury were associated with students needing to repeat restorations which were not properly performed, and may be higher than in the dental clinic due to the students being less experienced than the clinic students.²⁶⁷

Table 12. Mercury levels in particulate matter (PM) in studies which include amalgam only (n=1)

Study (Year) [Study design]	Restorative material (activity)	Exposure (control/comparator)	Specific outcomes measured, units	Outcome details
Clinic setting (n=1)				
Gioda (2007) [Before and after study] ²⁶⁷	Amalgam (restorations, removals)	PM ₁₀ from students undertaking dental exam in clinic setting (comparator: particulate matter before exam)	Overall levels of PM ₁₀ ; Hg bound to PM ₁₀ , µg/m ³	Two days before exam: 35.6 (ug/m ³); Hg: 0.02 (ug/m ³) Exam day: 68.2 (ug/m ³); Hg: 0.2 (ug/m ³) Three days after exam: 35.0 (ug/m ³); Hg: 0.01 (ug/m ³) Guidance compliant: ●
Lab setting (n=1)				
Gioda (2007) [Before and after study] ²⁶⁷	Amalgam (restorations, removals)	PM ₁₀ from students undertaking dental exam in lab setting (comparator: particulate matter before exam)	Overall levels of PM ₁₀ ; Hg bound to PM ₁₀ , µg/m ³	Day 1: (no activity): 9.2 µg/m ³ ; ND Day 2: (preparation): 39.8 µg/m ³ ND Day 3: (restorations): 12.2 µg/m ³ ; 0.2 µg/m ³ Day 4: (removing and restorations): 16.2 µg/m ³ ; 0.1 µg/m ³ Day 5: (removing and restorations): 12.4 µg/m ³ ; 1.1 µg/m ³ Day 6: (removing and restorations, cleaning lab): 41.6 µg/m ³ ; 0.9 µg/m ³ Guidance compliant: ●

Abbreviations: ND=not detected; PM=particulate matter

Key: Guidance compliant: Yes=● No=● NR=●

Environmental impacts: composite resin only (n=4)

Four studies included composite resin material only,^{272, 273, 276, 281} albeit one of these studies included a comparison with a restoration material which does not meet the inclusion criteria for this review.²⁷³ These were categorised within three broad impact categories: monomer levels in wastewater (n=2),^{273, 276} monomer levels in particulate matter (n=1),²⁸¹ and monomer levels in emissions (n=1).²⁷²

Monomer levels in wastewater in studies which include composite only (n=2)

Two studies reported monomer levels in wastewater for composite materials only²⁷⁶ (specifically, including one without comparison to a relevant restorative material) (see *Table 13*).²⁷³ Mourouzis et al. included a comparison with an indirect restoration material (polymer infiltrated ceramic material) which does not meet the inclusion criteria. Mourouzis et al. included both a clinic and lab setting, and is rated medium risk of bias.²⁷⁴ Polydorou et al. was in a lab setting and rated medium risk of bias.²⁷⁶

Clinic setting (n=1)

Mourouzis et al. assessed wastewater from clinics which used composites and polymer infiltrated ceramic restorative material.²⁷³ Testing related specifically to removals, albeit this was simulated by aggravating the restoration material in healthy volunteers, and aimed to detect monomers. Levels of monomers reduced over seven-day time period (see *Table 13*). Levels of BPA and Triethylene Glycol

Dimethacrylate (TEGDMA) were statistically significant both during tests immediately after placement and after seven days. In the only comparative finding between composites and polymer infiltrated ceramic material, Urethane Dimethacrylate (UDMA) was detected only for the latter material (7.47 ± 0.62 ng/ μ L).

Lab setting (n=2)

In the lab setting, Mourouzis et al. assessed the same materials as in the clinic setting using an in vitro test to simulate leaching.²⁷³ TEGDMA was the most commonly detected monomer, and was statistically significant ($F(3,36) = 64.119$, $p < 0.001$) (see *Table 13*). In the only comparative finding between composites and polymer infiltrated ceramic material, as in the clinic setting, UDMA was released only from the polymer infiltrated ceramic material (0.66 ± 0.14 ng/ μ L).

Polydorou et al. showed that BPA levels in wastewater collected during grinding procedures with composite resin materials was significantly reduced by using filtration materials, but did not report whether this complied with guidance (see *Table 13*).²⁷⁶

Table 13. Monomer levels in wastewater in studies which included composite only (n=2)

Study (Year) [Study design]	Restorative material (activity)	Exposure (control/comparator)	Specific outcomes measured, units	Outcome details
Clinic setting (n=1)				
Mourouzis (2022) [Controlled trial] ²⁷³	Composites: Clearfil Majesty Posterior PLT; Clearfil Photo Core PLT Polymer infiltrated ceramic CAD/CAM: Vita Enamic® [not relevant] (removals)*	Wastewater from dental unit (control: clean dental unit wastewater; comparator: different composite materials and polymer infiltrated ceramic [not relevant])	BPA, Bis-GMA, TEGDMA and UDMA at two time points: immediately after placement and 7d, ng/μL	Immediately after placement: BPA and TEGDMA monomers showed statistically significant results for the materials tested (F(3,36) = 37.990 and F(3,36) = 54.441, p < 0.001, respectively). The highest levels of TEGDMA were released by Clearfil Majesty Posterior PLT material (1.35 ± 0.52 ng/μL) and this was statistically significant compared to other materials (p < 0.001). UDMA was detected only for Vita Enamic® material (7.47 ± 0.62 ng/μL). Control: ND 7d timepoint: BPA and TEGDMA monomers showed statistically significant results (F(3,36) = 6.760 and F(3,36) = 4.176, p < 0.001, respectively). Pairwise comparisons between different group materials for all the released monomers showed that Clearfil Majesty Posterior PLT material released the highest levels of TEGDMA (1.31 ± 0.58 ng/μL) and this was statistically significant compared to other materials (p < 0.001). UDMA and Bis-GMA were not detected in any material after 7d. Control: ND Guidance compliant: ●
Lab setting (n=2)				
Mourouzis (2022) [Controlled trial] ²⁷³	Composites: Clearfil Majesty Posterior PLT; Clearfil Photo Core PLT Polymer infiltrated ceramic CAD/CAM: Vita Enamic® [not relevant] (removals)†	Wastewater from dental unit collected during in vitro experiment (control: clean dental unit wastewater)	BPA, Bis-GMA, TEGDMA and UDMA, ng/μL	BPA was detected in the wastewater samples only for the high-viscosity core build-up composite material (0.11 ± 0.02 ng/μL). TEGDMA was detected in the wastewater samples of all the materials. TEGDMA monomer yielded statistically significant results (F(3,36) = 64.119, p < 0.001). Pairwise comparisons between Clearfil Majesty Posterior PLT and Clearfil PhotoCore PLT revealed that Clearfil Majesty Posterior PLT material released the highest amount of TEGDMA (1.07 ± 0.19 ng/μL) and the result was statistically significant (p < 0.001). Between the CAD/CAM material Vita Enamic® and the Clearfil Photo Core PLT material, no statistically significant result was identified (p > 0.05) for the amount of TEGDMA. UDMA was released only from the Vita Enamic® CAD/CAM material (0.66 ± 0.14 ng/μL). Control: ND Guidance compliant: ●
Polydorou (2020) [Controlled trial] ²⁷⁶	Ormocer: Ceram X® Nanofilled resin composite: FiltekTM Supreme XTE Dual-cure core build-up material: Core-X® flow	Wastewater from dental unit collected during in vitro experiment (control: clean dental unit wastewater)	BPA before filtration, mg/L BPA after filtration (filtration materials: Zeosorb; Katalox Light; Catalytic Carbon), mg/L	Significant difference in BPA reduction observed for three filtration materials (p < 0.0001). Paired t-test analysis showed significant reduction in BPA amount after filtration for all the materials (p < 0.05). However, filtration with Zeosorb and Katalox Light resulted in only small reduction of BPA, while treatment with Catalytic Carbon resulted in a clinically relevant reduction of BPA by 99.3% (p < 0.05). Guidance compliant: ●

(Dental grinding
procedures)

Abbreviations: Bis-GMA=Bisphenol A-glycidyl methacrylate; BPA=Bisphenol A; CAD/CAM=Computer-Aided Design/Computer-Aided Manufacturing; ND=not detected; TEGDMA= Triethylene Glycol Dimethacrylate; UDMA=Urethane Dimethacrylate

Key: Guidance compliant: Yes=● No=● NR=●

*Samples in healthy volunteers were milled to simulate the clinical operations of polishing resin composite restorations or the grinding and removal of failed composite resin restorations.

†Also, simulation of polishing resin composite restorations.

Monomer levels in particulate matter (n=1)

One study considered monomer levels in particulate matter (see *Table 14*).²⁸¹ This study included both a clinic and lab-based component, and was rated as medium risk of bias.²⁸¹

Clinic settings (n=1)

Van Landuyt et al. assessed particulate matter in the breathing zone of dentists when working with composite restorative materials (see *Table 14*).²⁸¹ Tests showed that particles included small methacrylate resin particles which can be linked to monomers, but there was no further analysis of the toxicity for humans.²⁸¹ The authors noted that a health relevant metric for the quantification of exposure and dose for nanoscale particles is still under discussion.²⁸¹

Lab settings (n=1)

The lab-based in vitro study component of Van Landuyt et al. provided more detail about the size of particles for different types of composite material (see *Table 14*).²⁸¹

Table 14. Monomer levels in particulate matter in studies which include composite only (n=1)

Study (Year) [Study design]	Restorative material (activity)	Exposure (control/comparator)	Specific outcomes measured, units	Outcome details
Clinic setting (n=1)				
Van Landuyt (2014) [Controlled trial] ²⁸¹	Composite (restorations)*	Abrasive procedures relating to composites in clinic setting (NA)	Concentrations of nanoparticles, particle size	Peak moments of high concentrations of nanoparticles in breathing zone of the dentist and patient were associated with abrasive procedures of composites. Reshaping and contouring of composites resulted in peak concentrations between 0.1 and 1 x 10 ⁶ cm ⁻³ in the breathing zone of the dentist. Background measurements remained stable during these peaks between 5000 and 10,000 cm ⁻³ . Guidance compliant: ●
Lab setting (n=1)				
Van Landuyt (2014) [Controlled trial] ²⁸¹	Composite (grinding material to simulate abrasive procedures, including restorations)	Abrasive procedures relating to composites in clinic setting (NA)	Concentrations of nanoparticles, nm	Kruskal–Wallis analysis showed Gradia Direct and Tetric EvoCeram (Ivoclar-Vivadent, Schaan, Liechtenstein) produced statistically larger particles (p < 0.05) than Filtek Supreme XTE (3M ESPE), GrandiO and Z100 (3M ESPE). Nanoparticles released by the latter three composites were not statistically different in size. When measured after 1, 4 or 7 min the mean particle diameter was statistically different for all composites indicating that all composites had an individual agglomeration tendency. Guidance compliant: ●

Abbreviations: NA=not applicable; nm=na

Key: Guidance compliant: Yes=● No=● NR=●

*Also, reshaping and contouring of composites.

Monomer levels in emissions (n=1)

One study assessed monomer levels in emissions (see *Table 15*).²⁷² This study was based in a clinic setting and rated medium level of bias.²⁷²

Table 15. Monomer levels in emissions in studies which include composite only (n=1)

Study (Year) [Study design]	Restorative material (activity)	Exposure (control/comparator)	Specific outcomes measured, units	Outcome details
Clinic setting (n=1)				
Marquardt (2009) [Cross-sectional] ²⁷²	Composite (restorations)	Air sampling during the treatment of patients at four dental practices (NA)	Measurements of methacrylates during composite restoration treatments	Methyl methacrylate (MMA) concentrations (=0.4 mg/m ³) were 10 times higher than HEMA and TEGDMA, and 30 times higher than EGDMA. Levels of MMA were lower than the maximum allowable concentration value and short-term threshold values (reported as 210 mg/m ³ in Germany between 100 and 400 mg/m ³ in other countries). Toxicological risk for dental personnel reported as minor. No maximum allowable concentration values are available for HEMA, EGDMA, or TEGDMA.
Guidance compliant: ●				

Abbreviations: EGDMA=Ethylene Glycol Dimethacrylate; HEMA=2-Hydroxyethyl Methacrylate; MMA=methyl methacrylate; NA=not applicable; TEGDMA=Triethylene Glycol Dimethacrylate

Key: Guidance compliant: Yes=● No=● NR=●

Clinic setting (n=1)

Marquardt et al. assessed methacrylate emission levels during composite restorations (see *Table 15*).²⁷² Levels of MMA were the highest, followed by HEMA, TEGDMA and EGDMA, but all were reported to be within recommended guidance levels.²⁷²

Summary of environmental impacts versus potential environmental impacts

Of the 21 included studies, nine studies reported an actual environmental impact either through (a) assessing compliance with guidance^{267, 272, 274, 277, 282, 283} or (b) using a measurable impact, the latter comprising of (i) animal toxicity and (ii) carbon footprint.^{265, 266, 270} The remaining 12 studies only showed potential environmental impact due to reporting toxicity levels associated with restorative materials without either assessing compliance with guidance or reporting a measurable impact on the environment.^{254, 264, 268, 269, 271, 273, 275, 276, 278-281} In the following sections, we describe the studies which were categorised in according to type of impact, specifically: studies which show environmental impacts with reference to compliance with guidance (n=6);^{267, 272, 274, 277, 282, 283} studies which show environmental impact via animal toxicity (n=2);^{265, 270} studies which show environmental impact via carbon footprint (n=1);²⁶⁶ and studies which show potential environmental impact (n=12).^{254, 264, 268, 269, 271, 273, 275, 276, 278-281} A summary of these studies with respect to whether or not they measured impact is provided in *Table 16*.

Environmental impacts relating to compliance with guidance (n=6)

Compliance with guidance was reported in relation to whether toxic chemical substances in byproducts of restorative materials complied with relevant guidance. Two studies measured compliance with guidance with respect to mercury levels in waste which is disposed of outside of the clinic setting.^{274, 277} Olivera et al. showed that the CASs in a dental military unit complied with USA EPA guidance on wastewater and solid waste disposal, albeit the guidance focused on CAS functioning overall rather than mercury specifically (see Table 8).²⁷⁴ Contrastingly, Shraim et al. measured hazardous levels of mercury in dental wastewater according to local guidance (Technical Regulations for Discharge of Raw Wastewater of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, Ministry of Municipal and Rural Affairs; see Table 3).²⁷⁷ Shraim et al. notes that, at the time of writing, the adoption of measures to reduce mercury concentration in dental wastewater, including amalgam separators, is unregulated in Saudi Arabia.²⁷⁷

Other environmental impacts relating to measures of toxic chemical byproducts of restorative materials were measured in the immediate environment of dental practices – thus primarily affecting dentists and patients. The most frequently documented environmental impact was mercury levels in vapour, which were measured in all three studies included in this category.^{267, 282, 283} In Gioda et al., compliance with OSHA guidance was associated with the level of experience of the dental practitioner during an exam, with less experienced students (year 2) using more amalgam capsules, and requiring more extractions and repeated restorations due to low quality fittings, than more experienced students (year 3).²⁶⁷ Warwick et al. (2019) reported levels of mercury in vapour which breached OSHA guidance in a professional clinic setting.²⁸² This, potentially surprising, contrasting finding may partly relate to different ways of measuring vapour, with Gioda et al. measuring an average over time, and Warwick et al. (2019) measuring vapour at peak levels and at 15 minutes intervals (see Table 11).²⁸²

Warwick et al. (2013) reported that mercury levels in vapour were within guidance recommendations if all interventions were used to reduce mercury, i.e. spray and suction, without which guidance was breached (see Table 11).²⁸³ In the only study to measure monomer levels in relation to guidance, Marquardt et al. reported that monomer levels in emissions were below relevant guidance in Germany (specific guidance not reported; see Table 15).²⁸³

Environmental impact relating to animal toxicity (n=2)

Majstorovic et al. assessed the toxicity of mercury and monomers leached from amalgam and composite restorative materials, respectively, using zebrafish as a model organism.²⁷⁰ Their study highlights statistically significant environmental impacts, including a comparative analysis of the two materials, although the findings are limited by the laboratory setting (see Table 7).²⁷⁰ The same study also measured toxicity in dental wastewater from clinic settings, and found that the toxic levels of

mercury were lower (thus no zebrafish mortality was observed, only developmental abnormalities), and did not identify any monomers.²⁷⁰ Binner et al., contrastingly, shows toxicity of dental wastewater from non-amalgam based restoration activity, likely including monomers, for *Daphnia magna*.²⁶⁵ This showed impact measured using effective concentration levels – as per the clinic based study in Majstorovic et al. no animal mortality was observed.^{265, 270}

Environmental impact relating to carbon footprint (n=1)

Duane et al. reported environmental impact in the form of carbon footprint, which was contextualised within the wider context of carbon footprint NHS primary care dental activity in England (see Table 6).²⁶⁶

Potential environmental impacts (n=12)

The remaining studies only showed potential environmental impacts, relating to levels of toxic chemical substances associated with dental restorative activity. These included potential environmental impact both in the wider environment (including from mercury and monomers in dental wastewater released into the environment,^{264, 273, 279} emissions from the incineration of teeth in crematoriums,^{254, 280} and solid waste disposal,^{269, 271} and with respect to the immediate environment of the dental practice (including monomers in particulate matter).^{273, 281} In these studies, it was not clear that the reported levels of toxic substances breached guidance or had any actual environmental impact.

Table 16. Summary of environmental impact vs potential impact only by study and broad impact category

Study	Impact assessed	Restorative material	Comparative study	Statistically significant finding	Compliance with guidance	Impact measured? (Y/N: summary)
<i>Animal toxicity (n=2)</i>						
Binner (2022) ²⁶⁵	Animal toxicity	Resin composite, glass ionomer, resin-modified glass ionomer cements	N	NR	NR	Y: animal toxicity
Majstorovic (2024) ²⁷⁰	Animal toxicity	Alkaside, amalgam, commercial composite, experimental composite, glass-ionomer (lab); NR (clinic)	Y	Y	NR	Y: animal toxicity; comparison with different materials
<i>Carbon footprint (n=1)</i>						
Duane (2017) ²⁶⁶	Carbon footprint	Amalgam, composite, glass-ionomer	Y	NR	NR	Y: carbon footprint; comparison with different materials
<i>Mercury levels in emissions (n=3)</i>						
Kim (2018) ²⁶⁸	Mercury levels in emissions	Amalgam	N	NR	NR	N: potential impact only
Piagno (2020) ²⁵⁴	Mercury levels in emissions	Amalgam	N	NR	NR	N: potential impact only
Takaoka (2010) ²⁸⁰	Mercury levels in emissions	Amalgam	N	NR	NR	N: potential impact only
<i>Mercury levels in particulate matter (n=2)</i>						
Gioda (2007) ²⁶⁷	Mercury levels in particulate matter	Amalgam	N	NR	NR	N: potential impact only
Simu (2014) ²⁷⁸	Mercury in particulate matter	Amalgam, composite, glass-ionomer	Y	NR	NR	N: potential impact only
<i>Mercury levels in solid waste (n=3)</i>						
Kontogianni (2008) ²⁶⁹	Mercury levels in solid waste	Amalgam	N	NR	NR	N: potential impact only
Mandalidis (2018) ²⁷¹	Mercury levels in solid waste	Amalgam	N	NR	NR	N: potential impact only

Olivera (2020) ²⁷⁴	Mercury levels in solid waste	Amalgam	N	NR	Environmental Protection Agency ●	Y: compliance with guidance
<i>Mercury levels in vapour (n=3)</i>						
Gioda (2007) ²⁶⁷	Mercury levels in vapour	Amalgam	N	NR	Clinic setting: OSHA ●; Lab setting: OSHA ●	Y: compliance with guidance
Warwick (2013) ²⁸³	Mercury levels in vapour	Amalgam	N	Y	Alberta Occupational Ceiling Limit ● ●;* Alberta Occupational Threshold Limit Value ● ●*	Y: compliance with guidance; statistically significant effect
Warwick (2019) ²⁸²	Mercury levels in vapour	Amalgam	N	N	OHSA ●	Y: compliance with guidance
<i>Mercury levels in wastewater (n=5)</i>						
Al-Kawas (2008) ²⁶⁴	Mercury in wastewater	Amalgam, composite, glass-ionomer	Y	NR	NR	N: potential impact only
Olivera (2020) ²⁷⁴	Mercury levels in wastewater	Amalgam	N	N	Environmental Protection Agency ●	Y: compliance with guidance
Paryag (2010) ²⁷⁵	Mercury levels in wastewater	Amalgam	N	N	NR	N: potential impact only
Shraim (2012) ²⁷⁷	Mercury in wastewater	Amalgam, composite, glass-ionomer	Y	NR	Technical Regulations for Discharge of Raw Wastewater of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA) Ministry of Municipal and Rural Affairs (2002) ●	Y: compliance with guidance; comparison with different materials
Stone (2008) ²⁷⁹	Mercury levels in wastewater	Amalgam	N	Y	NR	N: potential impact only
<i>Monomer levels in emissions (n=1)</i>						
Marquardt (2009) ²⁷²	Monomer levels in emissions	Composite	N	N	Guidance in Germany [†] ●	Y: compliance with guidance
<i>Monomer levels in particulate matter (n=1)</i>						
Van Landuyt (2014) ²⁸¹	Monomer levels in particulate matter	Composite	N	Y	NR	N: potential impact only
<i>Monomer levels in wastewater (n=2)</i>						

Mourouzis (2022) ²⁷³	Monomers in wastewater	Composite, polymer infiltrated ceramic CAD/CAM (not relevant)	N	Y	NR	N: potential impact only
Polydorou (2020) ²⁷⁶	Monomers in wastewater	Composite	N	Y	NR	N: potential impact only

Abbreviations: NR=not reported; OSHA=Occupational Safety and Health Administration; USA=United States of America

Key: Compliance with guidance: ●=Yes; ●=No

*Outcome depends on intervention used to reduce vapour emissions exposure.

†Specific guidance not reported.

Key characteristics of deprioritised health outcome studies

Of the 215 studies (266 articles) included in this systematic review, 134 studies (159 articles) evaluating health outcomes associated with different types of restorative material were not prioritised for full data extraction, quality appraisal and inclusion in the narrative synthesis. The main reasons for study de-prioritisation were as follows: exposure outcomes not directly related to health impact (n=69, 84 articles),^{18-66, 68-101, 118} link between dental restorative material and health impact not the primary focus of study (n=31, 33 articles),^{46, 102-106, 108-134} and study design was cross-sectional with/without comparison group (n=35, 42 articles).^{48, 135, 136, 138-176}

Deprioritised studies were conducted in the following countries: USA (n=23),^{36, 41-44, 47, 48, 55, 68-71, 80, 89, 98, 100, 101, 108, 112, 117, 119, 123, 134, 136, 137, 144, 149, 157-161, 173, 176} Canada (n=8),^{34, 37, 65, 66, 77, 86, 110, 127} Germany (n=13),^{23, 24, 50, 62, 63, 72, 96, 113, 120, 124, 141, 162, 164, 172} Norway (n=10),^{18, 25-27, 76, 91, 97, 132, 148, 165, 167} Italy (n=7),^{28, 33, 38, 78, 146, 150, 151} Slovenia (n=7),^{40, 57, 79, 90, 92, 131, 133} Sweden (n=7),^{22, 45, 105, 106, 115, 143, 168, 171} Croatia (n=4),^{49, 56, 61, 129} Czech Republic (n=5),^{58, 59, 88, 94, 99, 135} Korea/Republic of Korea (n=4),^{21, 54, 60, 109} UK (n=5),^{32, 35, 46, 107, 142, 170} South Korea (n=3),^{31, 53, 81} Australia (n=3),^{116, 128, 147} Belgium (n=3),^{83, 84, 95} Bulgaria (n=3),^{64, 138, 139} Finland (n=3),^{102-104, 122, 174} Poland (n=3),^{73-75, 85, 93} Spain (n=3),^{29, 121, 163} Japan (n=2),^{87, 111} Romania (n=2),^{156, 166} Saudi Arabia (n=2),^{19, 20, 118, 152-155} Germany (n=2),^{72, 164} and one each for the following countries: Austria,¹²⁵ France,³⁰ Greece,¹⁷⁵ Ireland,¹⁴⁵ Portugal,¹¹⁴ and Taiwan.¹⁶⁹ Seven studies were conducted across multiple countries (n=6),^{39, 51, 52, 82, 126, 140} and one study did not report this information.(n=1).¹³⁰

Forty deprioritized studies did not use a cross-sectional with/without comparison group design. These included: cross-sectional with control group (n=14),^{25, 38, 64, 81, 93, 108, 111, 115, 116, 121, 122, 124, 128, 134} retrospective observational (n=7),^{18, 23, 24, 37, 86, 92, 97, 103, 104} prospective longitudinal/cohort (n=8),^{21, 32, 106, 107, 112, 119, 125, 131} before and after (n=9),^{26, 55, 60, 66, 68, 71, 76, 95, 130} retrospective cohort (n=2),^{35, 127} RCT (n=5),^{36, 42, 50, 72, 98} and a database review (n=1).¹⁰⁹

The largest population group represented by the deprioritised studies were patients or members of the public (n=89), including both adults and children, with the other main population groups represented including dental professionals (n=22),^{35, 47, 48, 64, 80, 89, 91, 93, 94, 99, 103, 104, 136, 138, 139, 144, 147, 157, 160, 161, 165-167, 174-176} and mothers/pregnant women and/or children at risk of exposure during pregnancy (n=24).^{20, 32, 39, 41, 45, 46, 49, 54, 56, 57, 61, 79, 84, 90, 92, 107, 112, 118, 119, 122, 123, 125, 129, 131, 133, 149, 173}

Amalgam was the dental restorative material evaluated by most deprioritized studies (n=118), with the largest groups of other dental materials evaluated including composite resin/methacrylates/comonomers (n=13),^{25, 26, 31, 55, 60, 64, 66, 68, 70, 71, 76, 95, 102, 139, 143, 166, 174} amalgam and composite (n=8),^{27, 42, 98, 101, 120, 141, 146, 151, 162} or a mix of multiple materials (n=5).^{109, 110, 127, 138, 139, 164}

The largest health impact categories evaluated within the deprioritised studies were the closely related allergy (n=11),^{102-105, 109, 111, 113, 115-117, 130, 135, 138, 139, 143} allergy/oral health (n=4),^{110, 140, 141, 164} and oral health (n=8).^{127, 152, 154, 155, 162, 163, 166, 168, 172} Other health impact categories evaluated included: auditory (n=2),^{112, 142} autism (n=3),^{107, 108, 173} cardiovascular disease (n=3),^{48, 106, 144} genotoxicity (n=4),^{121, 129, 136, 151} immune function (n=6),^{120, 145-147, 149, 150} neurological (n=1),¹⁷⁶ neuropsychological (n=4),^{131, 157, 167, 169} pregnancy outcomes (n=2),^{119, 125} renal (n=2),^{126, 153} respiratory (n=2),^{159, 174} and other health (n=5).^{124, 132, 134, 148} Eight studies evaluated multiple potential health impacts,^{122, 123, 130, 156, 160, 161, 165, 170, 171} and the following health impacts were evaluated by one study each: endocrine,¹³³ musculoskeletal,¹⁵⁸ neurological,¹²⁸ and visual/ocular.¹⁷⁵ Further detail regarding the non-prioritised studies can be found in Supplementary Materials A.

Discussion

This systematic review aimed to identify and narratively synthesise primary quantitative evidence to support the comparison of the health and environmental impacts of different dental restoration materials. Our comprehensive search strategy of health and environmental databases, existing reviews and forward and backward citation searches identified 215 studies which met the inclusion criteria for this review across 266 journal articles; 195 studies (across 246 journal articles) evaluating health outcomes of different types of restorative materials and 21 studies (each an individual journal article) evaluating environmental outcomes. Within these studies, it was possible to identify specific health or environmental impacts in 61 and 9 studies respectively. We included 61 studies (87 articles) which evaluated health impacts in the narrative synthesis following a prioritisation process to identify the studies where a clear link to health impact could be ascertained; and we included all 21 studies which reported actual or potential environmental impact. The difference in treatment between the health and environmental impact studies, in terms of the prioritisation process for health impact studies, owes to the much larger body of evidence found relating to health impacts.

In the following sections we summarise the key findings for health and environmental studies respectively, contextualise the findings in the existing literature, identify the strengths and limitations of the review, and summarise the implications for future research and practice.

Health: summary of key findings

Of the 195 studies (246 articles) included in this review which evaluated health outcomes, we deprioritized 134 studies (159 articles) which were not included in the narrative synthesis. These studies included those where the health outcomes evaluated were not explicitly linked to health impact, where the link between health impact and dental restorative materials was not the sole focus of the study and/or studies which used a cross-sectional design, with or without comparison group. We extracted key descriptive characteristics for these studies, comprising details regarding study design, population, dental material being evaluated and key health outcomes/impacts measured alongside of a summary of each study's main findings. These are tabulated within Supplementary Materials A and summarised narratively within Part 1 of this report.

The 61 studies (87 articles) prioritised for narrative synthesis, were divided into four categories based on the restorative material/s being evaluated: 1) amalgam versus composite (n=6), 2) amalgam only (n=52), 3) composite resin only (n=16), and 4) glass ionomer versus composite (n=3). The majority of evidence available was non-comparative evidence focusing on evaluating the health impact of amalgam restorations, particularly in patients (n=36) most of which was weak to moderate quality. The quantity of non-comparative evidence evaluating health impacts associated with other types of

restorative material was much smaller with 16 studies evaluating outcomes associated with composite resin restorations and three studies comparing outcomes for glass ionomer against composite resin restorations. Only six studies statistically compared health impacts associated with amalgam versus composite resin restorations, although the quality of this evidence was higher, with the majority appraised as strong quality. The potential health impacts via maternal or occupational exposure were only evaluated via non-comparative evidence focusing on amalgam restorations.

We identified 25 broad health impact categories supported by the studies prioritised for synthesis. The most evaluated included allergy (n=13), general physical health (n=14), neurological (n=13), neuropsychological (n=15) and oral health (n=18). Only two broad health categories were supported by evidence from across all four categories: ADHD/Autism (n=5) and oral health.

Overall, the heterogeneity of specific outcomes evaluated within these broad outcome categories and the variety of outcome measures used where the same specific outcomes were measured made it challenging to identify clear/consistent patterns across included studies within the same broad outcome category. This was exacerbated by the variability in study design, population groups and duration of follow-up after initial exposure to the restorative material within individual studies. Below we summarize the findings from the comparative and non-comparative evidence separately with respect to health impact.

Comparative evidence

The quantity of direct comparative evidence was extremely limited. Six studies (17 articles) provided direct comparative evidence regarding the health impacts of amalgam versus composite resin restorations across 18 broad health outcome categories.¹⁷⁷⁻¹⁹³ Most of this evidence stemmed from the New England Children's Amalgam or Casa Pia randomized controlled trials, which had limited follow-up periods and excluded certain at risk groups.^{179, 181} Whilst we supplemented this evidence with non-comparative studies evaluating amalgam or composite separately, the limited evidence pertaining to composite resin restorations restricted comparisons which could be made between these two bodies of evidence within broad health impact categories. Broad health impact categories with the highest quantity of data evaluating both amalgam and composite resin restorations available to support a comparative synthesis included immune function, neuropsychological, oral health and psychosocial symptoms, although confidence in reported findings is limited due to moderate-weak quality of evidence, heterogeneity of specific outcomes within specific categories and/or small number of studies. Overall, few significant differences between treatment groups were observed across broad impact categories but again, the limited number of comparative studies evaluating the same broad health impact means we cannot be certain that such differential health impacts between amalgam

and composite restoration do not exist. Where significant differences in health impact were found, the restorative material with the better outcome varied depending on the health impact evaluated.

The number of studies comparing health impacts associated with glass-ionomer versus composite resin restorations was extremely limited (n=3),^{185, 255, 263} with heterogeneity in outcome measures, mixed findings within studies and variable study quality precluding the identification of clear messages for this group of comparative evidence.

Non-comparative evidence

Amalgam

Insufficient, heterogeneous and weak quality evidence limits the conclusions that can be made regarding the health impacts of occupational (n=7),^{208, 214, 218-220, 222, 243} or maternal exposure to mercury or amalgam (n=10).^{194, 198, 206, 217, 222, 224, 226, 227, 235, 236, 246-248} There is tentative evidence to indicate no association between maternal amalgam exposure and childhood death for non-occupationally exposed mothers,^{217, 222, 224, 236} although further research is required into the risk of miscarriage for individuals with higher amalgam exposure. Birth outcomes for dental professional were mixed,^{217, 222, 236} and further research is required. There is tentative evidence suggesting no association between maternal exposure via occupational and non-occupational exposure to amalgam/mercury and birth malformations,^{206, 217, 222, 227} but again the limited number of studies and their weak-quality limits confidence in this finding.

With the aforementioned caveats, there appears to be some evidence that amalgam restorations on permanent teeth may have a detrimental influence on some blood chemistry markers of immune function,^{187, 197, 215, 237, 238} musculoskeletal symptoms,^{212, 240, 241, 251} oral lichenoid lesion/reaction symptoms,^{223, 229, 231, 234} but is not associated with oral lichen planus or oral lichenoid reactions,^{230, 242} and psychosocial difficulties,^{209, 212, 240, 251} with no evidence to indicate a link between amalgam restorations and neuropsychological test performance.^{178, 196, 233, 241, 251, 259} Further high-quality randomized controlled trials are needed to increase confidence in these findings.

Composite resin and/or methacrylates

The strongest, most consistent evidence was found for neuropsychological health, which found few associations between composite resin restorations and performance on neuropsychological tests, where greater exposure to BisGMA-composite was linked to poorer psychosocial performance at follow-up. Both these broad health impact categories were only supported by two articles from the NECAT study.^{187, 209, 259}

Five studies of variable quality examined the association between composite resin restorations in situ and patient oral health.^{190, 195, 207, 230, 257} Populations and specific outcomes of interest across were non-

comparable but broadly indicated no significant association between composite resin exposure and oral health symptoms, although findings were inconsistent for oral lichen planus. Findings reported in two articles supporting the NECAT studies indicated greater exposure to BisGMA-composite was linked to poorer psychosocial performance at follow-up.^{209, 258} However, as with all potential health impacts, further appraisal by high quality trials is required.

The limited quantity of evidence and/or mixed findings limits the conclusions relating to other broad health outcome categories.

Non-prioritised vs prioritised studies

Across both prioritised and non-prioritised studies, the most common population group represented were patients/members of the public, with amalgam the most common type of restorative material evaluated within this group. Other population groups represented within the non-prioritized studies included dental professionals (n=19),^{18, 35, 47, 48, 64, 80, 89, 91, 93, 94, 99, 136, 137, 144, 157, 160, 161, 165-167, 174, 175} and pregnant mothers/mothers/children exposed during pregnancy (n=25),^{20, 32, 39, 41, 44-46, 49, 54, 56, 57, 61, 79, 84, 90, 92, 97, 107, 112, 118, 119, 122, 123, 125, 129, 131, 133, 149, 173} which mirrors those within the prioritised studies. Of note are four studies which evaluate health impacts associated with composite resin/acrylic monomers/methacrylates within dental professionals,^{102-104, 138, 139, 166, 174} The link between these types of restoration/materials and health impacts within this population is under-represented in the current narrative synthesis. Two studies reported frequency of allergy to different acrylic monomers,¹⁰²⁻¹⁰⁴ or composite resins,^{138, 139} one reported frequency of oral health outcomes,¹⁶⁶ and the other reported that increased exposure to methacrylates significantly increased the risk of various respiratory symptoms, including adult-onset asthma, nasal drip and work-related cough.(Jaakola) The heterogeneity of outcomes measured and lack of statistical comparison between population groups limits the potential contributions of these studies to the narrative synthesis.

All of the non-prioritised studies conducted with pregnant mothers/children concerned exposure to dental amalgam (n=25). Twelve of these evaluated health impacts,^{107, 112, 118, 119, 122, 123, 125, 129, 131, 133, 149, 173} with six deprioritised due to sole focus not being on the link between restorative material and health impact (all six studies also evaluating the impact of fish consumption).^{107, 112, 123, 125, 129, 131} Each of the 12 studies evaluated the link between amalgam restorations and a different health impact, namely: autism (n=2),^{107, 173} auditory (n=1),¹¹² endocrine (n=1),¹³³ genotoxicity (n=1),¹²⁹ immune function(n=1),¹⁴⁹ multiple (n=2),^{122, 123} neuropsychological (n=1),¹³¹ pregnancy outcomes (n=2),^{119, 125} and not specified/other (n=1).¹¹⁸ Whilst these studies may provide some additional data to contribute towards the existing broad health impact categories within the narrative synthesis, the

limited number and heterogeneity of health impacts measured reduces the impact of these individual studies on the overall findings of this review.

Most non-prioritised studies evaluated exposure outcomes, such as concentrations of mercury in hair or urine. The most common health impacts evaluated in non-prioritised studies were allergy and/or oral health (n=24),^{102-105, 109-111, 113-117, 127, 135, 138-141, 143, 152, 154, 155, 162-164, 166, 168, 172} genotoxicity (n=4),^{121, 129, 137, 151} immune function (n=6),^{120, 145-147, 149, 150} and neuropsychological (n=4).^{131, 157, 167, 169} The majority of studies within these impact categories evaluated amalgam restorations. These non-prioritised studies may supplement health impact categories within the synthesis of prioritised studies, particularly for genotoxicity, which was supported by only three studies evaluating the genotoxicity of composite resin and/or glass ionomer.^{255, 260, 261}

Environment: summary of key findings

We identified 10 broad impact categories across 21 studies which measured actual or potential environmental impacts relating to dental restorative materials.^{254, 264-283} These studies were highly heterogeneous in their aims and methods, settings, and in the specific outcomes they reported. They were also limited in terms of the analysis of findings, sometimes only reporting the raw data or descriptive statistical analysis (e.g. averages and standard deviation/error or range of values). Furthermore, none of the studies had a low risk of bias. Due to this heterogeneity and limited analyses, there was limited scope for the narrative synthesis to incorporate a pooled assessment of the evidence. This meant that the narrative synthesis was unable to do much more than sequentially summarise the findings for studies which fall within each impact category, although it was possible to undertake a limited comparison of some studies. In this section, we discuss the findings as these relate to comparative studies and non-comparative studies respectively, and the inclusion of evidence shows potential rather than actual environmental impact.

Studies which compared restorative materials

The five studies which compared relevant restorative material were categorised across four broad impacts (mercury levels in wastewater (n=2),^{264, 277} mercury levels in particulate matter (n=1),²⁷⁸ animal toxicity (n=1)²⁷⁰ and carbon footprint (n=1).²⁶⁶ All five studies included amalgam in the comparison. The two studies which reported mercury levels in wastewater included comparative detail between clinics which used amalgam and those which used non-amalgam restorative materials, reporting the unsurprising finding that levels of mercury in wastewater are generally lower in clinics which do not undertake amalgam restorations.^{264, 277} Although these studies included both amalgam and non-amalgam restorative materials, they show a key limitation in the evidence base, which is a lack of comparative analysis of relevant toxicity associated with the different restorative materials,

e.g. mercury for amalgam, monomers for composites and glass-ionomers. Guidance was only able to show that one of these studies reported hazardous levels of mercury, which is a clear link to environmental impact.²⁷⁷

Majstorovic et al.'s lab-based comparative analysis of mercury and monomers associated with amalgam and non-amalgam restorative materials, respectively, is the only study to compare both types of toxicity, and furthermore uses animal toxicity as the outcome to create a meaningful comparison of environmental impact.²⁷⁰ The experimental composite which had the highest toxicity may not be typically used in clinic settings, thereafter the relative toxicity of amalgam compared to commercial composite, followed by glass ionomer, is the clearest finding with respect to the relative environmental impact of the toxicity of these restorative materials.²⁷⁰ Thus, on the basis of this one study it appears that glass-ionomer restorative material may be less environmentally harmful than either amalgam or composite restorative materials, and that amalgam may be more harmful than composite used in real-world clinic settings.²⁷⁰ However, this finding needs to be investigated further with additional studies, in particular, the finding is situated in a lab setting which may not reflect real-world toxicity. The clinic arm of Majstorovic et al. detected lower levels of toxicity and no monomers in wastewater, suggesting that toxic levels in dental wastewater are indeed lower outside of the lab setting.²⁷⁰

Duane et al.'s comparison of the carbon footprint of amalgam, composite and glass ionomer showed differences in overall carbon footprint and carbon footprint per procedure, but crucially did not include any data relating to the materials themselves, only factors such as the time and energy required to undertake restorations.²⁶⁶

Studies with no comparison of restorative materials

Most identified studies did not include a comparison between different restorative materials. These studies typically reported the level of toxicity associated with just one or multiple restorative materials, with no comparative aspect. Within the broad impact categories for these studies, there was limited scope for pooling evidence. Two studies provided further evidence of animal toxicity relating to amalgam and non-amalgam restorative materials respectively, which complement the findings of the lab-based component of Majstorovic et al. by providing further evidence of toxicity for both amalgam and non-amalgam restorative materials.^{265, 270} In contrast to the lab-based component of Majstorovic et al., the clinic arm, and the clinic setting of Binner et al., did not observe any animal mortality, suggesting lab-based simulation had a higher level of toxicity than observed in real-world settings.^{265, 270}

The toxicity observed across the other studies similarly contributed to an overall picture in which mercury and monomers are clearly present in dental restoration activities, in a variety of forms (including wastewater, particulate matter, vapour and emissions), including in some studies levels which are considered harmful for humans and the natural environment. However, the heterogeneity of settings and specific outcomes (and the associated aims and methods) makes meaningful comparison of the findings difficult or impossible. For example, studies which assessed mercury levels in dental wastewater relating to amalgam included findings of ISO testing of chairside amalgam separators,²⁷⁴ wastewater generated by dentists in Trinidad and Tobago,²⁷⁵ and the degree to which chlorine vs chloramine mobilise mercury in wastewater²⁷⁹ – none of which can be meaningfully compared. Other broad impact categories included studies which are more similar but for which comparison is still limited, e.g. calculations of emissions from incineration of extracted teeth contain some similarities; but the model assumptions, and the many structural and demographic variables between different countries and regions, make meaningful comparison between findings challenging.^{254, 280}

Actual versus potential environmental impact

Across both comparative and non-comparative studies, although studies measured levels of toxic material which have the potential to cause harm to the environment (e.g. emissions, vapour, particulate matter, wastewater, solid waste), just under half measured this effect in real terms (e.g. as in the animal toxicity studies, or studies which show compliance with guidance).^{265, 267, 270, 274, 277, 283} Building on the analysis of comparative versus non-comparative studies, comparison of studies which measure *actual* environmental impact showed animal toxicity was associated with both amalgam and non-amalgam restorative materials in both lab and clinic settings; and that whether levels of toxicity comply with recommended levels depends on variables such as the appropriate use of amalgam separators and other measures such as spray and suction devices, and differences in how measurements are undertaken also affects compliance with guidance.

Relation of findings to existing literature:

Health impacts

Our findings from this review are consistent with those from previously published systematic reviews of randomized controlled trial which state that very few, if any, differences can be observed between individuals with amalgam versus composite resin restorations on specific health impact measures.²⁸⁶⁻²⁸⁸ Where some differences on specific health outcome measures were identified, these reviews highlight the uncertainty regarding direction of effect,²⁸⁷ and limited number of studies.²⁸⁶ This similarity in findings reflects that, like this review, previous reviews have relied on the Casa Pia and NECAT trials for direct comparative evidence to evaluate the health outcomes associated with

amalgam or composite resin restorations.^{179, 181} One of the previous review highlights the risk of ‘false-positives’ given the high number of outcome measures evaluated in these trials,(Worthington) which we agree should also apply to the interpretation of findings from our review.²⁸⁶

The broad health outcomes identified by this review reflect those in previously published systematic reviews, although there are more of them, likely reflecting the higher quantity of literature included in this review due to our inclusion of non-randomized trials and observational studies. However, most evidence contributing to these health impact categories evaluates only a single type of restorative material, with the number of studies comparing health impacts of two different restorative materials against each other being more limited. One of our impact categories Allergy, and the closely related Oral Health address a specific gap in the literature identified by Khangura et al.²⁸⁷ Other existing reviews also considered the performance of different restorative materials in relation to each other, which was outside of the remit of this review. However, this work is currently being undertaken by the Cochrane Oral Health Group (personal correspondence).

Our findings underscore that which has already been highlighted by previous reviews; the paucity of research directly comparing health impacts associated with amalgam to those associated with other types of restorative material. In addition, our work highlights that the health impacts potentially associated with amalgam have not been consistently demonstrated and the health impacts associated with composite resin restorations are understudied.

Environmental impacts

To the best of our knowledge, the most recent systematic review on the environmental impact of amalgam versus non-amalgam restoration materials (specifically, focusing on composite resin) is the review conducted as part of the CADTH report by Khangura et al.²⁸⁷ Alongside clinical and cost effectiveness, Khangura et al. includes a review of the environmental effects associated with the use of dental amalgam versus composite resin restorations.²⁸⁷ The environmental effects review was date limited to 2006 to focus on studies which are more relevant to contemporary dental practices (i.e. one year earlier than the present review), and the search strategy identified studies published up until February 2018 (i.e. 6.5 years earlier than the present review).²⁸⁷ (See note on different date limit used in Khangura et al. in Part 2: Full description of methods).²⁸⁷ The review also focused on studies from countries which could facilitate relevant comparison with Canada, including USA, Australia, UK, New Zealand and the European Union, but (unlike the present review which focused on World Bank High Income countries) did not specify criteria for how relevant countries were selected.²⁸⁷ As per the present review, both comparative and non-comparative studies were included.²⁸⁷

The searches for Khangura et al. identified 19 studies relevant to environmental effects of amalgam and/or composite restoration materials. The included studies were not listed in full, making it difficult to ascertain what these studies are: the narrative synthesis of this part of the review includes 22 references, albeit seven of these were published prior to the 2006 date limit, making it possible that some studies which were included are not cited in the narrative synthesis. Only one of the studies overlaps with a study which was identified for the present systematic review, which in the present review was categorised differently as health impact.⁵⁵ The remaining studies cited in Khangura et al.'s environmental review would not meet the inclusion criteria for the present systematic review, as they are either published pre-2007, or are literature reviews,³⁰² or commentaries,^{303, 304} or reports which use a mix of case studies, literature reviews and expert opinion,^{305, 306} or provide wider context on toxic materials, particularly in Canada, but with limited data on dentistry.³⁰⁷ Khangura et al. concludes that while there is concern in the literature about the environmental effects of both amalgam and composite restorative materials, there is insufficient evidence to determine their relative impact.²⁸⁷ It particularly notes that the environmental effects of composite materials are less well understood than those of amalgam, and that while dental amalgam contributes to environmental mercury, its impact is relatively minor compared to other sources.²⁸⁷

The present systematic review has identified studies relevant to environmental outcomes which were either excluded or missed by Khangura et al., or not reported in the narrative synthesis.²⁸⁷ Nonetheless, the overall conclusion is broadly the same, i.e. that more evidence is needed to understand the relative environmental impact of amalgam and non-amalgam restoration materials.

Strengths and limitations

This systematic review presents an update evaluation of what is known regarding the health and environmental impacts of a variety of dental restorative materials. The review is based on a systematic search strategy and rigorous screening process, with reference to broad inclusion criteria which were set out in a prospectively registered protocol. With respect to health impacts, whilst direct comparative evidence was limited, the narrative synthesis is structured to support readers to identify and compare the health impacts associated with different types of restorative material. However, heterogeneity of study design, quality, population characteristics and outcome measures limits both the number of and confidence in the comparisons which could be made within and between different types of restorative material. This was also the case for environmental studies, within which data on the impact of restorative materials on the environment was very limited. The prioritisation process undertaken during and after screening for health studies means that evidence regarding pain/sensitivity and exposure outcomes, the latter as measured by concentration of various chemical substances associated with restorative materials in urine, blood or hair, were not included in the

narrative synthesis. Instead, we provide an overview of the key characteristics of these studies in Supplementary Materials A. Prioritising the evidence included in the narrative synthesis helped ensure our findings are based on the most relevant and reliable evidence necessary to address the research aims and that the review remained deliverable within the timeframe available. As discussed in the [Health: summary of key findings](#) above, there are groups of non-prioritised studies which may provide additional information relevant to the broad health impact categories identified.

Implications for research, practice, and policy

This systematic review was commissioned by DHSC to support decision making around the future use of dental amalgam in the UK. Overall, the current evidence base does not present a clear picture as to the health or environmental impacts associated with individual restorative materials, or which material may have fewer health or environmental implications when compared to another. Hence, further high-quality studies are required to more fully understand the health and environmental impacts associated with different types of material both individually and compared to one another. There are comparatively fewer studies evaluating the health or environmental impacts of composite resin and glass ionomer restorative materials across all population groups and environmental settings which should be addressed. This is particularly important given that, at the time this report was commissioned, the UK was committed to phasing down the use of dental amalgam, however the UK has now agreed to the 2034 phase out of dental amalgam following the sixth meeting of the Conference of Parties (COP-6) to the Minamata Convention on Mercury^{13,15} In this final decision, the COP-6 added dental amalgam to Annex A of the Minamata Convention, indicating the manufacture, import, or export of dental amalgam will not be allowed after the 2034 phase out date, although exceptions for the use of amalgams in patients is still allowed when considered necessary by the dental practitioner based on the needs of the patient.

Within the non-comparative evidence base, several health impacts were not represented in studies evaluating the health impact of composite resin. Further high-quality research evaluating the health impacts of composite resin may be particularly useful to facilitate comparative analysis with other materials, particularly for the following health impact categories: adverse events, cardiovascular disease, dermatological, gastrointestinal, general physical health, musculoskeletal, neurological, respiratory and visual ocular symptoms. Similarly, the health impacts associated with occupational and maternal exposure to non-amalgam restorations need to be evaluated more extensively. This could be complemented by qualitative studies exploring the views and experiences of patients and dental professionals regarding the potential health benefits and risks associated with different types of restorative material.

With respect to environmental impacts, future research should include meaningful comparisons of the different types of toxicity which are associated with different dental restorative materials, e.g. mercury for amalgam, and monomers for composites and glass-ionomers. To achieve a meaningful comparison between different restorative materials, it is important to consider either the degree to which levels of toxicity comply with established guidance, or measure toxicity using an approach which can be compared between different materials, e.g. animal toxicity, the latter as used in two of the studies in the review^{265, 270} (albeit only one of these studies included comparison of restorative materials).²⁷⁰ If studies only show that dental procedures may lead to increased concentrations of harmful substances like mercury or monomers without further analysis, this limits the ability to draw conclusions about their individual or relative environmental impact. There is also a specific need for more data relating to the carbon footprint of different restorative materials.²⁶⁶ Furthermore, the lack of any studies classified as low risk of bias points to the need for future research to use more rigorous methods which are in line with recommended guidance.

Choice of dental material may be influenced by a variety of factors including type and position of cavity, cost, longevity, clinical performance and availability of restorative material within certain geographical areas or on the NHS. Any changes to the use of restorative materials should be backed by the evidence available and health and service structure necessary to support change.

Our engagement with the PERSPEX PPI group for this project indicates that patients would like to be kept informed as to the potential health implications of different types of restorative material, particularly where they may disproportionately impact certain patient groups (e.g. respiratory/allergy outcomes for people living with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease) and involved in the decision-making process. There may be tension between the clinical performance of each restorative material, availability and the lack of certainty regarding potential health outcomes for both dental professionals and patients, highlighting the need for clear information to support decision making for all those involved. PERSPEX members generally prioritised safe and effective materials above the wider environmental impact. Their views are broadly consistent with findings from a survey-based study where participants indicated that whilst they were broadly supportive of initiatives to promote sustainable dentistry and a willingness to compromise on the convenience and durability of their dental treatment.³⁰⁸ However, this willingness to compromise did not extend to their health or aesthetics of their teeth.³⁰⁸ Whilst the group indicated they would still like to know about potential environmental impacts and this information may inform their decision making, they did not have experience of being given a choice regarding the restorative material they received. Hence, knowledge regarding potential environmental concerns might not affect the choice of restorative material from the patient standpoint.

Conclusions

This report represents the most up to date and comprehensive systematic review of comparative and non-comparative evidence which aimed to understand the potential health and environmental impacts of amalgam versus non-amalgam restorative materials. Whilst the evidence included in this review indicates that both amalgam and non-amalgam materials may be associated with both health and environmental impacts, confidence in these findings are limited due to the heterogeneity of specific measures used and findings within similar impact categories. It is also difficult to determine to what extent there are differences in the health and environmental impact of different restorative materials relative to one another. This is due to the lack of directly comparative evidence evaluating health and environmental impacts.

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Part 2: Full description of methods

We prospectively registered our review on PROSPERO (CRD42024608563) prior to running searches.¹⁶ The methods used to conduct and report the findings of this review were consistent with the best practice approach for the conduct of systematic reviews and reporting of quantitative evidence synthesis.¹⁷ Below, we provide full methodological details of how we identified, quality appraised, data extracted and synthesised the findings from the primary quantitative studies included within this review.

Search strategy

Our overall approach combined searches of bibliographic databases with backward and forward citation searches of studies which met the inclusion criteria, searches of Google Search (www.google.com), and checking the included studies of topically similar systematic reviews. In addition, we inspected the Healthcare LCA database (<https://healthcarelca.com/>) for relevant studies.

Bibliographic databases

We searched six bibliographic databases on the 6th November 2024 with coverage of both health care and environmental science journals, including the health care databases MEDLINE, CAB Abstracts (both via Ovid) and CINAHL (via EBSCO), the environmental science databases Environment Complete and GREENFile (via EBSCO) and the multidisciplinary Science Citation Index database (via Web of Science, Clarivate Analytics). The MEDLINE search strategy for the Ovid platform is reported in [Appendix A](#). Following discussion with stakeholders and in keeping with existing systematic reviews, a 2007 date limit was applied as this allows for the inclusion of more recent research to reflect current practices and developments in the use of restorative materials in dentistry.^{287, 288} (We note here that there is some inconsistency in the reporting of date limits in Khangura et al. et al., which reports a 2007 date limit in the inclusion criteria for safety studies, but elsewhere in the review it reports the date limit for safety studies as 2006.²⁸⁷ The date limit for efficacy studies in Khangura et al. is reported as 2012 and the date limit for environmental studies is reported as 2006.²⁸⁷ For the purposes of the present review, we chose a single date limit of 2007 for both health and environmental studies, but the underlying rationale to focus on more recent evidence is the same in Khangura et al. and the present study). English language limits were also applied where available. The results of the bibliographic database searches were exported to EPPI-Reviewer 6 (EPPI Centre, UCL Social Research Institute, University College London) and de-duplicated.

Supplementary searches

We supplemented our bibliographic database searches by inspecting the Healthcare LCA database (<https://healthcarelca.com/>). This regularly updated resource indexes studies of life cycle assessments (LCA) of medical technologies and procedures, including carbon emissions. We undertook basic key word searching in Google Search (www.google.com) including search terms “amalgam” and “composite” combined with different combinations of “dentistry”, “dental”, “health outcome” “health impact”, “environmental outcome” and “environmental impact” (searches conducted by SB in December 2024 and January 2025). We consulted with stakeholders to identify any additional web sources to search, or studies which were not retrieved via other methods, but this did not lead to any additional sources or studies of interest. Forward and backward citation searches were conducted on the prioritised health outcome studies and all environmental outcome studies via EPPI-Reviewer 6 (EPPI Centre, UCL Social Research Institute, University College London). We also checked the included studies of any topically relevant systematic reviews that we identified during our scoping and screening processes.

Study selection

Six reviewers applied the inclusion and exclusion criteria listed below to the title and abstracts of a sample (n=100) of the bibliographic database search results (HML, LS, SB, NO, CMP, JTC). We discussed decisions in a group meeting to ensure consistent application of criteria and revised inclusion and exclusion criteria to enable more consistent reviewer interpretation and judgement. We applied these revised criteria to a second sample of 200 studies. Once finalised, two reviewers independently applied the inclusion and exclusion criteria to the title and abstract of each identified citation (HML, LS, SB, NO, CMP, JTC), with disagreements resolved through discussion or referral to a third reviewer as required. We assessed the full text of each article in the same way. We used EPPI Reviewer 6.0. online software to support study selection and produced a PRISMA-style flowchart detailing the study selection process and reasons for exclusion of each record retrieved at full text.

Inclusion criteria

The inclusion and exclusion criteria applied to studies identified through the search strategy is reproduced in full here: [Study identification](#).

Protocol deviations

In the protocol, we noted that we might prioritise some studies for analysis if there were too many studies to feasibly include within the timescale. Due to the high number of included health outcome studies, we utilised a prioritisation process to identify studies focussing on health outcomes with the

highest quantity of data relevant to our research questions for full data extraction, quality appraisal and synthesis.

As a first step, during title and abstract screening, we made a pragmatic decision to exclude studies that focused on pain, sensitivity, and secondary caries. This decision was based on the high number of such studies (n=201) and their primary focus on the clinical performance of dental restorative materials, rather than health or environmental impacts.

Secondly, following completion of full-text screening reviewers (LS, HML, SB, NO, CMP) extracted preliminary data for all included studies to inform prioritisation. The data extracted included: first author, publication year, title, aim, country, study design, population, dental materials evaluated, comparator, health and environmental outcome measured, whether the health outcome indicated exposure, impact, or both, length of follow-up, whether the dental material and health/environmental outcome relationship was the primary focus of the study, and summary of main findings. We then prioritised studies evaluating health outcomes category which met the following criteria:

- Studies where the primary focus is the link between dental material and health/environmental impact.
- Studies assessing health outcomes that indicate a health impact or both health impact and exposure variables. Thus, we deprioritised studies evaluating only exposure outcomes, for example, that examine mercury concentration or BPA concentration alone, without an associated health impact.
- All study designs except for cross-sectional studies with comparison groups, as these tend to take a broad exposure-wide and outcome-wide approach, often examining multiple influencing factors rather than a direct material-health link.

In contrast, we identified relatively few studies relating to environmental impacts. Thus, we made the following decisions to increase the number of studies which were eligible for inclusion:

- 1) We included lab-based studies, including studies with no human participants, i.e. in vitro studies.
- 2) We also made the decision to include animal studies, including both in real world and lab-based settings. (This was again made in view of the limited evidence-base, although the inclusion of animal studies is also appropriate from the point of view of wanting to assess the environmental impact – unlike health impacts, including animal studies did not compromise the relevance of the findings for the environmental part of the review).

- 3) Studies which included non-relevant materials were included if they also included relevant materials, even if the findings relating to relevant materials could not be disaggregated from the irrelevant materials.
- 4) Studies were included if they showed *potential* as well as *actual* environmental impact, e.g. if a study only reported the level of toxic chemicals in waste relating to dental restoration activity, without linking this to measurable environmental impact (e.g. animal toxicity, or compliance with guidance) studies would still be included as showing potential environmental impact.

Data extraction

The review team developed and piloted a standardised data extraction form (HML, LS, SB, NO, CMP) on a sample of health and environmental focussed studies (n=3) using Microsoft Excel. This data extraction form was designed to capture baseline and outcome data from included studies which related to population characteristics associated with social determinants of health, with reference to the PROGRESS+ framework.²⁹⁹ Initial decisions were discussed in a group meeting to ensure consistency across reviewers. Based on these discussions, the data extraction form was revised to improve clarity and support consistent judgement. The full data extraction form was used for prioritised health impact studies. This was undertaken by one reviewer (LS, HML, SB, NO, CMP) and checked by a second (LS, HML, SB, NO, CMP) using Microsoft Excel, with disagreements settled by a third reviewer if necessary. The same process was applied to environmental impact studies using a shorter data extraction form. The data extracted from included studies can be viewed in [Appendix B: Data extraction items for included studies](#).

Quality appraisal

We used separate quality appraisal tools for studies reporting health and environmental impact. We used the Effective Public Health Practice Project (EPHPP) Quality Assessment Tool for Quantitative Studies to assess the quality of studies focused on health impact.³⁰⁰ This tool is suitable for both randomised and non-randomised studies. Sections A–F (selection bias, study design, confounders, blinding, data collection methods, withdrawals and dropouts) were rated, and a global rating was assigned as follows:

- Strong (no weak ratings);
- Moderate (one weak rating);
- Weak (two or more weak ratings).

Where a study was reported across multiple articles, we selected the key index article for quality appraisal. In two instances, we appraised an article not included in the review as it provided essential methodological details for articles based on the NECAT and the Casa Pia randomised controlled trial.^{179, 181}

For environmental studies, we used the Collaboration for Environmental Evidence Critical Appraisal Tool (CEECAT) Version 0.3 (prototype) to assess methodological quality and risk of bias.²⁸⁴ Seven criteria were rated: risk of confounding biases, post-intervention/exposure selection biases, misclassified comparison biases, performance biases, detection biases, outcome reporting biases, and outcome assessment biases. A global rating was then determined as follows:

- Low risk of bias (all criteria rated as low);
- Medium risk of bias (at least one criterion rated as medium);
- High risk of bias (at least one criterion rated as high).

As with data extraction, quality appraisal of included studies was carried out by one reviewer (LS, HML, SB, NO, CMP) and checked by a second (LS, HML, SB, NO, CMP) using Microsoft Excel. Any disagreements were resolved through discussion, or by a third reviewer where necessary.

Synthesis

We synthesised data from studies evaluating health and environmental impact separately. We summarized data regarding study population, setting, intervention, methodological and quality characteristics of the included studies in tables and described these narratively.

Health impacts

For the narrative synthesis of studies evaluating health impact, we first grouped studies according to the type of restorative material evaluated, resulting in four groups of studies: 1) Studies comparing

health impact of amalgam versus composite resin restorations, 2) Studies evaluating amalgam, 3) Studies evaluating composite resin restorations and 4) Studies comparing health impact of glass ionomer vs composite resin restorations. Findings from studies which evaluated the health impact of both amalgam and non-amalgam restorative materials but did not statistically compare the health impact of the two materials were assigned to the amalgam and/or composite resin only categories according to which material the reported finding related. Results which only pertained to one restorative material within comparative studies were split in a similar way. Hence, a study evaluating several restorative materials could contribute to more than one of the four categories listed above.

Within these groups, we divided studies into categories based on the population group (dental professional, maternal exposure and patient) and then the broad health impact being evaluated. We developed these broad health impact categories inductively from the data and validated them with review stakeholders. The narrative synthesis within each of these broad health categories focused on identifying and explaining, where possible, patterns in the data regarding the health impact of the restorative materials, with reference to the quality and quantity of evidence available. Health impact was assessed in terms of the degree to which exposure to dental restorative materials were associated with (or causally related to) health conditions which formed the basis of the impact categories. Studies which only evaluated one type of restorative material were included to facilitate indirect comparison between amalgam and other types of restorative material.

Environmental impacts

The narrative synthesis of studies evaluating environmental impact mirrored that for health in the first instance, with studies grouped initially by the restorative material included in the studies. This resulted in four groups of studies: 1) studies which included a comparison of multiple restorative materials; 2) studies which included multiple materials without comparison; 3) studies which included amalgam restorative material only; 4) studies which included composite restorative material only. In contrast to health outcome studies, there were relatively few studies which included multiple restorative materials (including either with or without comparison), thus it was not desirable to categorise studies which compared restorative materials in separate categories based on the included materials. In keeping with the research question, all but one of the studies in the comparative group included amalgam in the analysis. Studies which only evaluated one type of restorative material were included to facilitate indirect comparison between amalgam and other types of restorative material.

Within each of the four groups of studies (i.e. comparative, multiple materials with no comparison, amalgam only, composite only), we categorised studies according to the broad impacts which were reported in the studies, which formed the categories within which studies were synthesised. As per

the health impact categories, the broad environmental impact categories were developed inductively from the data in the studies and validated with review stakeholders. As per the health outcome synthesis, the narrative synthesis within each of these broad environmental impact categories focused on identifying and explaining, where possible, patterns in the data regarding the environmental impact of the restorative materials, with reference to the quality and quantity of evidence available. Environmental impact could include harm to the natural environment, and also human exposure to harmful levels of toxic substances in the immediate environment of activity relating to restorative materials. We also categorised and presented studies according to the setting of studies, which included clinic-based settings, lab-based settings and crematorium settings.

Due to limitations in how environmental studies reported and analysed their data, it was not always clear whether the outcomes they described translated into actual environmental impact. For example, some studies only reported levels of toxic chemicals emitted during dental restorative procedures, without assessing whether or how these emissions impact the environment. We included studies reporting this more limited data because, although the impact was not quantified or evaluated, the findings remained broadly relevant to understanding environmental effects. This decision was also influenced by the relatively small number of studies identified on environmental impact. Studies which only reported levels of toxicity with no further analysis were reported as indicative of *potential* environmental impact.

To show actual environmental impact, studies were required to either (a) report compliance (or not) with guidance on levels of toxicity in the environment associated with restorative materials, or (b) report a measure of environmental impact such as animal toxicity or carbon footprint. With respect to the former, we inspected the results and discussion sections of included studies to identify whether findings were reported as compliant with recommended toxicity thresholds. This information was included in the narrative synthesis when explicitly reported in the studies themselves; however, we did not seek external benchmarks for independent comparison. The final section of the environmental narrative synthesis presents a summary and table of studies that assessed environmental impact through one or more of these approaches.

Stakeholder involvement

We consulted with and worked closely alongside several stakeholder groups throughout the conduct of this review. Stakeholders included those requesting the review from DHSC, people with expertise in dental restoration, the Cochrane Oral Health team and members of PERSPEX patient and public involvement group. The method of engaging with and respective impact on the review process, of each of these stakeholder groups on the review process and outputs is summarised in *Table 17* below.

Table 17: Stakeholder engagement and impact on review

Stage of review	Method of stakeholder involvement	Impact on review
Research question & protocol development	25.04.24/21.05.24/10.07.24: 3x1hr face-to face meetings via MT with government policy stakeholders, communication via email.	Clarification regarding policy context for the review, aim, intended use and identifying focused research question. Identified the need to include observational studies to understand safety outcomes and potentially under-researched impacts of alternatives to amalgam. Highlighted adverse outcomes of interest as opposed to clinical performance. Facilitated contact with individuals in the Cochrane Oral Health Team. Confirmation of timelines. Approved inclusion criteria, search terms and search strategy.
	1x20min face-to-face meeting via Zoom with members of PERSPEX.	Discussion of research questions and aims of review highlighted. Emphasised importance of consideration of patient outcomes alongside environmental evidence.
	23.05.24/1x 1hr face-to-face meeting via Zoom with clinical expert	Provided context regarding interest in non-amalgam restorative materials. Notes diversity in composite across countries which may impact the applicability of findings. Signposting to grey literature and other experts in dental restoration materials.
	26.06.24: 1x 45min face-to-face meeting via MT with clinical expert, communication via email.	Noted three major materials: amalgam, composite and glass ionomers and their differences for dental filling. Provided context with regards to amalgam and non-amalgam restorative materials vis a vis longevity and clinical performance and associated impact on current inequity in dental care access within the UK. Highlighted challenges in conducting high quality RCTs in dentistry. Sense check of protocol content and provided thoughts on potential date limits.
	29.10.24: 1x 30min face-to-face meeting via MT with Cochrane Oral Health team, government policy stakeholders, communication via email.	Queries regarding websites useful for searching grey literature discussed. Noted accessibility to experts who could help interpret tricky studies. Provided links to WHO commissioned reviews on mercury-free dental materials.
Screening	05.12.24: 1x 30min face-to-face meeting via MT with Cochrane Oral team, government policy stakeholders, communication via email	Provided updates on the review. Clarified studies focussed on bonding may not always have to do with restorative materials of interest.
	Email with government policy stakeholders, communication via email	Comment on summary of included studies as to whether these met expectations on type and range of evidence eligible for inclusion in review and if this aligned with their perception of the purpose of the review. Providing feedback on health outcome studies prioritised for inclusion.
Data extraction	07.03.25: 1x20min face-to-face meeting via Zoom with members of PERSPEX.	Provided updates on the review. Emphasised limited consideration of patients' choice in dental filling materials used for restoration by dentists,
	Email communication with government policy stakeholders.	Approved content of data extraction and quality appraisal forms.
Synthesis	08.05.25: 1x1hr face-to face MT meeting with government policy stakeholders, communication via email.	Checked decision to group by restorative material meets needs, and groupings make sense. Sense checking broad impact categories identified reflect needs for health studies. Resolved queries regarding grouping findings related to exposure to methacrylate within findings relevant to resin composites. Also resolved queries if colophony (resin derived from pine) a material relevant to dental restorations.
	06.06.25: 1x30min face-to-face Zoom meeting with PERSPEX members	Shared preliminary findings. Feedback shaped importance of clear definitions of different restoration materials within report glossary, production of summary pie charts which were incorporated into the descriptive results and important context which informed our recommendations for further research and dissemination strategy.

Write up	<p>Communication via email with clinical expert.</p> <p>Communication via email with government stakeholders.</p>	<p>Reviewed and provided feedback on draft internal report prior to it being sent to government stakeholders.</p> <p>Reviewed and provided feedback on draft report prior to it being finalised.</p>
Dissemination	<p>Communication via email with government stakeholders.</p> <p>Planned August/September 2025: 1x30min meeting via MT with members of PERSPEX. Communication via email.</p>	<p>Government stakeholders and PERSPEX members involved in identifying key audiences for potential dissemination products and pathways for sharing these. Reviewed dissemination materials, including a plain language summary and briefing paper.</p>

PERSPEX= Public Engagement in Research for Health and Social Policy at Exeter: Patient and public involvement and engagement group, Faculty of Health and Life Sciences, University of Exeter, RCT=Randomised Controlled Trials

Part 3: Full synthesis – health outcomes

This section details the full narrative syntheses for the 61 prioritised studies (88 articles) evaluating health outcomes. The synthesis comparing the health impact of amalgam versus composite resin restorations (n=6) is presented first, followed by the synthesis for studies evaluating the health impact of amalgam (n=52) then composite resin restorations (n=16) separately, then studies comparing health impact of glass ionomer with composite resin/compomer restorations (n=3). Tables supporting this section are provided in Supplementary Materials E, Tables 1 – 59.

Amalgam vs Composite Resin Restorations

Six studies (17 articles) statistically compare the health impact of amalgam with composite resin restorations for patients receiving dental restorations.^{177, 179-186, 188-193, 196, 258} The 18 broad impact categories supported by direct comparative evidence are: ADHD (n=1) adverse events (n=1), allergy (n=1), anthropomorphic (n=1), cardiovascular disease (n=1), dermatological (n=1), female health (n=1), gastrointestinal (n=1), general physical health (n=2), immune function (n=2), musculoskeletal (n=1), neurological (n=2), neuropsychological (n=2), oral health (n=3), psychosocial (n=1), renal (n=2), respiratory (n=1) and other (n=2). The majority of this evidence stemmed from the New England Children's Amalgam or Casa Pia randomized controlled trials.^{179, 181}

Evidence from studies which directly compare the impact of amalgam versus composite resin restorations on the health outcome of interest is presented within each of these broad outcome categories. This synthesis is supplemented by separate summaries of evidence from studies which separately evaluate the impact of 1) amalgam and then 2) composite resin restorations on the health outcome of interest where available. Thus, this section is intended to consolidate the evidence regarding health impact of amalgam versus composite resin restorations and enable comparison of the health impact for these restoration materials, even when no direct comparative evidence is available. The full syntheses of the supporting evidence for studies evaluating health outcomes for amalgam or composite resin restorations are presented in the *Amalgam* and

Composite resin sections below.

An overview of the overlap and gaps in the broad health outcome categories represented by each of these three groups of evidence (amalgam vs composite; amalgam; composite) is presented in *Table 2* in Part 1 of this report.

Eight of the broad impact categories are supported by evidence from studies evaluating the health impacts of amalgam and composite separately: ADHD/Autism, allergy, anthropomorphic, female health, immune function, neuropsychological, oral health and psychosocial. Ten of these categories were supplemented by studies evaluating only the health impact of amalgam: adverse events, cardiovascular disease, dermatological, female health, gastrointestinal, general physical health, musculoskeletal, neurological, renal and respiratory.

Below, the evidence supporting each broad outcome category is detailed narratively. For information regarding findings for specific outcome measures see Supplementary Materials E.

Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) and/or Autism

Amalgam vs Composite: direct comparative evidence

One retrospective cohort appraised as strong quality found no significant difference in ADHD incident rate or 10-year hazard probability between people who received amalgam, composite or glass ionomer restorations.¹⁸⁵ People with higher numbers of amalgam restorations were not significantly more at risk of ADHD than those with composite or glass ionomer restorations.¹⁸⁵

Summary: Amalgam only health impact evidence (patients)

One case-control study appraised as strong quality evaluated the link between urinary mercury level (both creatine adjusted/unadjusted) and other heavy metals and autism spectrum disorder.²⁵² No significant differences were found on any specific outcome measures between individuals with or without autism.²⁵² Associations between maternal exposure to amalgam/mercury and child autism outcomes are reported in Amalgam: *Maternal exposure*.

Summary: Composite resin only health impact evidence (patients)

One retrospective observational nested case-control study appraised as moderate quality compared the risk of ADHD symptoms between children with and without composite resin restorations.²⁵⁶ This study found a significantly higher risk of ADHD amongst children exposed to composite resin restorations versus those who were not, with the risk increasing over time until three years post first composite resin restoration, although no positive association with increased number of composite resin restorations was demonstrated.²⁵⁶

Comparative evidence summary: ADHD/Autism

The number of studies evaluating the link between different restorative materials and ADHD/autism outcomes was limited (n=3),^{185, 252, 256} with only one study directly comparing different restorative materials for this outcome.¹⁸⁵ This strong study reported no significant difference in ADHD prevalence risk between groups receiving amalgam, composite or glass ionomer restorations. Incidence of autism and ADHD diagnosis, linked to amalgam and composite resin restorations respectively, were appraised by one study each, with significant association between composite resin restorations and ADHD risk identified by one moderate quality study.

Adverse events

Amalgam vs Composite: direct comparative evidence

Two studies appraised as strong quality representing the NECAT and Casa Pia randomized controlled trials recorded the number and/or type of adverse events experienced during follow-up period by children who received amalgam and/or composite restorations.¹⁸¹ One study reported no significant difference in the number of adverse events between different treatment groups.¹⁷⁹ The other reported the number and type of adverse events in each treatment group narratively; there were four adverse events within the amalgam treatment group (death due to unintentional gunshot (n=1), one death due to hepatitis (n=1), brain aneurysm (n=1), kidney stones(n=1) and five adverse events within the composite resin group (2 diagnosed epilepsy, 1 hyperthyroidism, 1 asthma, 1 psychiatric hospitalization).¹⁸¹ Study authors could see no pattern to the adverse events within or between the two groups.¹⁸¹ See Supplementary Materials E, Table 1 for further information.

Summary: Amalgam only health impact evidence (patients)

All three studies (four articles) evaluating the relationship between amalgam removal/replacement and adverse events reported that patients experienced an aggravation of general health complaints following amalgam removal/replacement.^{199, 201, 211, 232} However, the limited number, lack of statistical comparison and generally low quality of the studies prevents firm conclusions being drawn. Two studies reported no serious adverse events (SAE), one appraised as moderate quality,¹⁹⁹ the other as weak, associated with the study.²³²

Summary: Composite resin only health impact evidence (patients)

No evidence to support this category.

Comparative evidence summary: adverse events

Two of the five studies within this category provided direct comparative evidence. Adverse events linked to composite resin restorations alone were not evaluated by any study. Direct comparisons,

both between and within groups, using statistical analysis was limited, limiting the usefulness of the data reported.

Allergy

Amalgam vs Composite: direct comparative evidence

One study representing findings from NECAT compared frequency of allergy occurrence during five-year follow up between children who received amalgam and those who received composite resin restorations.¹⁷⁹ This randomized controlled trial was appraised by reviewers as strong quality and reported no significant effect of treatment group.¹⁷⁹

Summary: Amalgam only health impact evidence (patients)

Eleven studies appraised the relationship between presence of oral health symptoms and allergy to amalgam or mercury, with six of these studies appraised as weak quality, four as moderate quality and one as strong quality.^{195, 210, 212, 213, 223, 229, 231, 238, 239, 242, 249} Findings from studies evaluating the association between allergy to amalgam/mercury and oral health symptoms varied, with two studies indicating a significant association between oral symptoms and mercury allergy.^{195, 213} and four studies reporting no significant relationship between amalgam,^{239, 249} or mercury allergy and oral health symptoms.^{212, 239, 249} Rates of allergy to mercury and/or amalgam varied widely between studies conducted with individuals with oral lichenoid lesions/reactions and oral lichen planus, possibly reflecting the heterogeneity in symptom aetiology, populations and methods used alongside the overall weak quality of evidence within this category.

Summary: Patient exposure to composite resin/methacrylates/acrylate

Three studies examined allergy outcomes and potential relationship with composite resin among individuals with oral lichenoid lesions,¹⁹⁵ allergic stomatitis,²¹³ and oral lichenoid reactions, compared to control groups,²⁴² one appraised as strong quality,²¹³ one moderate,²⁴² and one as weak quality.¹⁹⁵ No clear association was found between allergy to composite materials and symptom characteristics, although differences between population characteristics made comparison across different studies difficult.

Two of the above studies,^{213, 242} and another weak quality study compared rates of allergy to methacrylates and/or acrylates between patients with oral health conditions and control populations.²³⁹ Results varied across different studies and according to type methacrylate/acrylate exposure, with the strongest/most consistent evidence available for ethyl methacrylate and diurethane dimethacrylate, where two studies found no significant difference in sensitisation rate between population groups.^{213, 239} The following methacrylates were appraised by two studies which reported conflicting findings for each, with one study reporting significantly higher rates of

sensitisation for the “allergy” group compared to controls,²¹³ whereas the other study found no significant difference between groups.²³⁹ Ethylene glycol Di methacrylate (EGDMA),^{213, 239} Methyl methacrylate (MMA),^{213, 239} and 2-hydroxyethylmethacrylate (2-HEMA). The quantity of evidence evaluating allergy/sensitisation to other types of methacrylate/acrylates was extremely limited.

Comparative evidence summary: allergy

One of the sixteen studies supporting this category, appraised as strong quality, directly compared allergy outcomes between individuals receiving amalgam vs composite resin restorations, reporting no significant differences between treatment groups. Findings from evidence evaluating the link between amalgam (n=11), composite resin restorations (n=3) or methacrylates/acrylates (n=3) and allergy outcomes varied considerably, reflecting heterogeneity in population groups and outcomes measured used. Whilst more limited in quantity, the quality of evidence evaluating composite resin restorations was higher than that evaluating amalgam, although the evidence was similarly conflicting.

One moderate quality study reported sensitisation rates to amalgam and/or methacrylates/acrylates among dental professionals, finding that methacrylates/acrylates were the most frequently reported , with allergy to dental metals (including palladium chloride, amalgam, ammoniated mercury, tin chloride, gold sodium thiosulfate, amalgam alloy metals, ammonium tetra chloroplatinate, copper II sulphate pentahydrate) reported less frequently.²¹⁸

This broad health impact category closely relates to the *Oral health* category below.

Anthropomorphic

Amalgam vs Composite: direct comparative evidence

One article representing a secondary analysis from the NECAT randomised controlled trial appraised as strong quality compared anthropomorphic measurements between children who received amalgam and those who received composite resin restorations.¹⁸⁸ No significant differences in BMI for age and body fat percentage, nor height velocity was found between groups.¹⁸⁸

Summary: Amalgam only health impact evidence (patients)

One study appraised as moderate quality evaluated the impact of removal of amalgam restorations in individuals with medically unexplained physical symptoms attributed to amalgam in a before and after analysis. No significant changes in weight loss or weight gain measures were observed.²¹⁰

Summary: Composite resin only health impact evidence (patients)

Another article representing a secondary analysis from the NECAT randomised controlled trial appraised as strong quality examined effect of exposure to flowable sealant/preventative resin restorations and body mass index (BMI), percentage body fat and female health outcomes.¹⁸⁷ No

significant association between levels of restorative material and either outcome was demonstrated.¹⁸⁷

Comparative evidence summary: anthropomorphic

No significant associations were found between type of restorative material and anthropomorphic outcome measures. However, only two studies (one high and one moderate quality) evaluated this outcome, and the specific outcomes measured/reported varied considerably.

Cardiovascular Disease

Amalgam vs Composite: direct comparative evidence

One strong quality article reporting findings from the NECAT reported no significant difference in the number of children reporting cardiovascular disease outcomes between those who received amalgam versus those who received composite resin restorations during five-years of follow up.¹⁷⁹

Summary: Amalgam only health impact evidence (patients)

Six studies of variable quality examined the association between amalgam restorations in situ,^{179, 212, 240, 241, 251} and removal/replacement of amalgam restorations and cardiovascular symptoms.^{210, 228}

Three studies of weak to moderate quality using self-report measures of cardiovascular symptoms reported variable findings regarding individuals who attributed health complaints to amalgam versus those who attributed health complaints to another cause or healthy controls.^{240, 241, 251} Studies using more objective measures of exposure reported cardiovascular symptoms were not associated with urinary or blood mercury levels,²¹² and inconsistent findings relating to improvement of cardiovascular symptoms following amalgam removal/replacement.^{210, 228} Overall, the variability in quality of the evidence and findings pertaining to relationship between cardiovascular outcomes and amalgam exposure prevents identification of firm conclusions.

Summary: Composite resin only health impact evidence (patients)

No evidence to support this category.

Comparative evidence summary: Cardiovascular disease

One strong quality study from the NECAT reported no significant differences between treatment groups regarding cardiovascular outcomes. There was no evidence evaluating cardiovascular outcomes relating to composite resin restorations, and findings from the six studies of variable quality relating to amalgam were inconsistent.^{210, 212, 228, 240, 241, 251}

Dermatological

Amalgam vs Composite: direct comparative evidence

One article reporting findings associated with the NECAT study and appraised as strong quality reported no significant differences between amalgam and composite resin treatment groups in the number of children reporting skin disorders during a five year follow up period.¹⁷⁹

Summary: Amalgam only health impact evidence (patients)

Within the five studies evaluating the association between amalgam restorations and dermatological symptoms,^{210, 228, 240, 241, 251} findings were mixed. The heterogeneity of findings and weak to moderate quality of the studies overall prevents firm conclusions from being drawn.

Summary: Composite resin only health impact evidence (patients)

No evidence to support this category.

Comparative evidence summary: dermatological

The quantity of evidence supporting this category is extremely limited with only one study, appraised as strong providing direct comparative evidence. This study found no significant difference between treatment groups and number of children reporting skin disorders. No consistent findings were reported in studies evaluating association between amalgam and dermatological symptoms (n=5). No studies evaluating composite resin restorations were represented in this category.

Female health

Amalgam vs Composite: direct comparative evidence

One article associated with the NECAT appraised as strong quality reported that girls assigned to composite treatment were less likely to have reached menarche and have a lower risk of menarche during five-year follow up compared to girls who received amalgam.¹⁸⁸ No associations found between extent of BisGMA-based, UDMA-based or total composite treatment levels at baseline and onset of menarche during the follow up period.¹⁸⁸

Summary: Amalgam only health impact evidence (patients)

Two studies (one moderate, one weak quality) report on different specific outcomes relating to female health. The moderate study found no significant change in reports of menstrual disorders from baseline to follow-up after amalgam removal in a population attributing health complaints to amalgam.²¹⁰ The weak quality study found no association between number of maternal dental amalgams at first and third trimester or dental amalgam replacement within 12 months prior to first trimester or during pregnancy and gestational hypertension.²²⁵ This study reported that replacement of dental amalgam before or during pregnancy was associated with decreased systolic blood pressure, although associations with diastolic blood pressure were non-significant.²²⁵

Summary: Composite resin only health impact evidence (patients)

Another study associated with the NECAT appraised as strong quality found no association between greater exposure to flowable composite/preventative resin restorations and age of menarche in girls.²⁵⁸

Comparative evidence summary: female health

The quantity of evidence supporting this broad outcome category was limited, although there is tentative evidence to suggest that there is no link between type of restorative material and menstrual symptoms in children/young adults. Findings relating to other outcomes in pregnant women were only supported by one other study of weak quality.²²⁵

Gastrointestinal

Amalgam vs Composite: direct comparative evidence

One article reporting findings associated with the NECAT study and appraised as strong quality reported no significant differences between amalgam and composite resin restoration treatment groups in the number of children reporting gastrointestinal disorders during a five year follow up period.¹⁷⁹

Summary: Amalgam only health impact evidence (patients)

The seven studies contributing to the evidence base in this category were mostly of mixed moderate to weak quality.^{201, 210, 228, 240, 241, 251, 253} There appears to be some weak evidence to support the association between amalgam restorations and the occurrence and resolution of GI symptoms, although findings vary according to specific outcome of interest and may be outweighed by findings from a moderate quality study which indicates patients may experience both improvement and worsening of stomach symptoms.(Zwicker)

Summary: Composite resin only health impact evidence (patients)

No evidence to support this category.

Comparative evidence summary: gastrointestinal

No significant differences in gastrointestinal disorders between treatment groups were reported in a single strong quality article associated with the NECAT. Findings from studies evaluating amalgam were inconsistent, with studies evaluating composite resin restorations unrepresented in this category.

General physical health

Amalgam vs Composite: direct comparative evidence

Two studies (two articles) representing the NECAT,¹⁷⁹ and Casa Pia randomised controlled trials compared general physical health problems experienced by children with amalgam compared to composite restorations.¹⁹¹ Neither strong quality study found any significant association between type of restorative material and general physical health outcomes such as weakness fatigue or edema,¹⁷⁹ migraine,¹⁷⁹ or urinary bacteria.¹⁹¹

Summary: Amalgam only health impact evidence (patients)

Four studies of variable quality examined the relationship between exposure to **amalgam in situ** and general physical health symptoms.^{212, 240, 241, 251} Findings comparing levels of general health symptoms between individuals who attributed their health complaints to amalgam compared to those who did not were inconsistent. The relationship between objective measures of mercury exposure measured by blood or urine analysis and general health symptoms were similarly inconsistent and based on evidence of weak quality, with two studies reporting no significant association,^{211, 212} although one study reported larger reductions in mercury level in erythrocytes, blood plasma and urine following amalgam removal being associated with larger decreases in symptoms score.²⁵⁰

Five studies (nine articles), the majority of which were appraised as weak quality, examined the impact of **amalgam removal** on general health symptoms.^{72, 134, 199-201, 210, 211, 228, 253} Evidence from three studies (five articles) by the same authors indicates that amalgam removal is associated in improved scores on measures of overall general physical health symptoms at various time points from 12 months to five years follow-up post removal compared to control groups.^{199-201, 211, 250} However, these findings are inconsistent with another article related to Weidenhammer et al (2010),²⁵⁰ which used a different outcome measure, and a shorter follow-up period of 12-months.²³² Fatigue and headache symptoms were the most commonly evaluated specific symptoms, although findings for both outcomes were inconsistent; reflecting the use of different outcome measures and follow-up periods across different studies.^{210, 228, 253}

Summary: Composite resin only health impact evidence (patients)

No evidence to support this category.

Comparative evidence summary: general physical health

No significant differences in general physical health complaints between treatment groups were reported in two strong quality articles associated with the Casa Pia and NECAT randomised controlled trials. Findings from studies evaluating amalgam were inconsistent, with studies evaluating composite resin restorations unrepresented in this category.

Immune function

Amalgam vs Composite: direct comparative evidence

Two studies (three articles) compared immune function in patients who received amalgam restorations versus those who received composites. Two articles represent findings from the strong quality RCT supporting the NECAT.^{187, 192} The two articles from the same trial evaluated immune function using the same specific outcomes – both reporting no significant difference in immune function between treatment groups on all measures, aside from B-cell activation. For this specific outcome, one article reports an increase in B-cell responsiveness at 6-months and 1-year follow-up, but not five-year follow-up for children with bisGMA-based composite restorations, with the opposite finding for amalgam (B-cells decreased in responsiveness).¹⁸⁷ The other article reports no significant difference between treatment group for B-cell function measured as expression of CD69/CD23.¹⁹² This difference in findings may reflect differences in how follow-up periods were calculated across the two articles i.e. separate years vs whole follow-up period. The second study was a retrospective cohort study with control group appraised as moderate quality,¹⁸⁹ which reported no significant difference in the incidence rate of Systemic Lupus Erythematosus (SLE) between individuals with amalgam, composite and those with both types of restorative material.¹⁸⁹

Summary: Amalgam only health impact evidence (patients)

Three studies (four articles) examined the relationship between amalgam restorations in situ and patient immune function.^{187, 192, 204, 212} Two studies were strong quality,^{187, 192, 204} the other was weak.²¹² Overall, evidence indicated no statistically significant association between amalgam exposure, as measured by number of amalgams, and various indicators of immune function which included diagnosis of primary Sjögren's syndrome,²⁰⁴ and an array of blood chemistry variables in children with amalgams on **primary** teeth.¹⁸⁷ This finding was replicated with number of amalgam restorations on **permanent** teeth, aside from a significant association between number of amalgams and lymphocyte function.¹⁸⁷ Both articles reported non-significant associations between number of amalgam restorations and the following immune function outcomes: monocytes, neutrophils, responsiveness of t-cells (CD25) and B-cell (%CD69_PWM, CD23+PWM).^{187, 192} One article reported a significant association between number of amalgams and lymphocyte function (B-cell: %CD69+PWM & % CD23+PWM).¹⁸⁷

Four controlled before and after studies examined the relationship between amalgam removal/replacement and immune function outcomes: one appraised as moderate quality,¹⁹⁷ and three appraised as weak quality.^{215, 237, 238} Generally, studies demonstrated a significant improvement in immune function markers in individuals who had their amalgam removed in comparison to control groups where baseline measures were not statistically different between groups (this excludes the

article by Bjorkman et al., (2012) where patient group had significantly higher levels of some measures of immune function than control group),^{197, 215, 238} although one weak quality study indicated that self-reported susceptibility to infection was higher in patients who had amalgams removed versus those who did not.²³⁷

Summary: Composite resin only health impact evidence (patients)

Two articles reporting findings from the NECAT randomised controlled trial, appraised as strong quality examined association between composite resin and immune function outcomes.^{187, 192} No consistent associations were shown between type of restorative material, immune function outcome and time of follow up (six months, one- and five-years), although increased numbers of surfaces treated with non-flowable compomer restorations were positively associated with one out of two measures of monocyte function.¹⁸⁷ Higher numbers of tooth surfaces treated on permanent teeth treated with Bis-GMA based non-flowable composite fillings were associated with increased B-cell activation, higher numbers of flowable composites used in preventative treatment were associated with increased total white blood cell count, although findings pertaining to neutrophil function varied.¹⁸⁷ The other study found no significant differences in measures of immune function at different points of follow-up for children who received composite restorations.¹⁹² The limited number of studies and use of different outcome measures makes it difficult to draw firm conclusions regarding the relationship between composite resin restorations in children and immune function outcomes.

Comparative evidence summary: immune function

The majority of specific outcomes evaluated by two moderate-strong quality studies (three articles) directly comparing immune function impact for amalgam vs composite demonstrated no significant differences between treatment groups, aside from two measures of B-cell activation which favoured the amalgam group in one article but showed no significant differences between groups in another article from the same study. These same articles and an additional two studies indicated no significant association between amalgam exposure and immune function as measured by a variety of measures, aside from lymphocyte function, where higher number of amalgams was associated with increased scores. This result was replicated within individuals receiving composite resin restorations by the same two articles from NECAT, with greater exposure to non-flowable composite associated with increased monocyte function and increased exposure to GMA based composite filling with increased B-cell activation. Overall, there appears to be some evidence indicating that both amalgam and composite resin restorations can impact on immune function, although more research is needed to fully understand which specific health outcomes are impacted, the duration for which these effects can be observed and the comparative impact of different types of restoration material.

Musculoskeletal

Amalgam vs Composite: direct comparative evidence

One article reporting findings associated with the NECAT study and appraised as strong quality reported no significant differences between amalgam and composite resin restoration treatment groups in the number of children reporting musculoskeletal disorders during a five year follow up period.¹⁷⁹

Summary: Amalgam only health impact evidence (patients)

Overall, the findings suggest an association of higher number of musculoskeletal symptoms with increased amalgam exposure and suggest a reduction in symptoms after removal. Self-reported musculoskeletal symptoms were higher in individuals attributing health complaints to amalgam restorations compared to control groups in three out of four studies of variable quality which examined the relationship between amalgam/mercury exposure (n=1),²¹² or amalgam exposure (n=3),^{240, 241} and musculoskeletal symptoms. However one weak quality study found a lower number of symptoms within the patient group compared to a control group who attributed their symptoms to environmental causes.²⁵¹ Another weak quality study found no significant difference in blood or urinary mercury levels between those experiencing musculoskeletal complaints and those that did not.²¹² Four of five studies reported significant reductions on different measures of musculoskeletal symptoms in the treatment group following amalgam removal compared to non-removal group,^{201, 210, 228, 253} however, three of the four studies were appraised as weak quality, so confidence in the finding is limited.

Summary: Patient exposure to composite resin

No evidence to support this category.

Comparative evidence summary: Musculoskeletal

Only one strong quality article associated with the NECAT trial provided direct comparative evidence to support this category, indicating no significant difference between treatment groups. Findings from eight studies indicate that there appears to be some evidence indicating amalgam is associated with musculoskeletal symptoms, although evidence is predominantly based on self-report symptoms and appraised as weak quality. The absence of studies evaluating composite resin restorations precludes comparison between findings from separate groups of studies evaluating different types of restorative material for this health outcome.

Neurological

Amalgam vs Composite: direct comparative evidence

Two studies (three articles) reporting findings from the NECAT and Casa Pia randomised controlled trails compared neurological health outcomes between children with amalgam and composite resin

restorations.^{179, 181, 184} Both studies were appraised as strong quality and none found any significant difference between treatment groups for the following outcome measures: central nervous system disorder or neurological illness occurrence during five year follow up,¹⁷⁹ neurological hard or soft signs (NHS/NSS),¹⁸⁴ postural hand tremor,¹⁸⁴ and NSS severity (see Supplementary Materials E, Table 4).¹⁸⁴ The exception to this was one study which found a statistically significant difference in nerve conduction velocity at year seven between groups, with results favouring the amalgam group. However, due to inconsistency of estimates and large number of tests, study authors did not consider the findings a reliable estimate of treatment effect.¹⁸¹ One study observed an increase in occurrence of postural hand tremor over seven year follow up, but the increase was uniform in both groups, with group differences not significant nor consistent in direction in any year.¹⁸⁴ The same study observed a non-significant general trend for reduction in NSS severity over time, typical for normal development.¹⁸⁴

Summary: Amalgam only health impact evidence (patients)

Findings in the six studies examining the relationship between amalgam restorations in situ and patient neurological outcomes, the majority of which were appraised as strong quality, varied across the specific outcomes measured. Specific outcomes where no association with amalgam was reported included multiple sclerosis,^{212, 245} essential tremor,²⁴⁴ and paraesthesia.²⁵³ Findings for Parkinsons Disease (PD) varied between studies, with one study reporting incidence of PD was higher for individuals with amalgam restorations,²²¹ and the other finding no significant association.²⁰⁵ One study found worsening of hand-shakiness following amalgam removal.²⁵³

Summary: Composite resin only health impact evidence (patients)

No evidence to support this category.

Comparative evidence summary: neurological

Findings from three articles appraised as strong quality representing the Casa Pia and NECAT randomised controlled trials found no reliable significant differences in neurological symptoms between treatment groups. No comparison between separate groups of studies evaluating association between amalgam or composite resin restorations and this health impact was possible.

Neuropsychological

Amalgam vs Composite: direct comparative evidence

Two studies (three articles) appraised as strong quality which represent findings from the NECAT,^{178, 179} and Casa Pia randomised controlled trials compared the neuropsychological impact of children who received amalgam restorations with those who received composite resin restorations.¹⁸¹ Both studies administered an extensive battery of neuropsychological tests intended to evaluate different aspects

of children's cognitive functioning annually over four or five,^{178, 179} and seven years follow up (see Supplementary Materials E, Table 54.¹⁸¹ Aspects of child cognitive functioning appraised by both studies included IQ, visual memory, attention and concentration span and visuomotor skills.^{178, 179, 181}

The two studies used the same outcome measures for some specific outcomes, including those intended to measure attention and/or concentration (n=9 tests/subtests): Digit span (verbal/attention concentration),^{178, 181} coding (measure of performance/attention concentration),^{178, 181} symbol search (measure of performance/attention or concentration),^{178, 181} finger windows, Trails A/B and the Stroop Test; visual memory (n=2 tests/subtests): the visual and learning index of the Wide Range Assessment of Memory and Learning (WRAML),^{178, 181} and visuomotor skills (n=7 tests/subtests): WRAVMA drawing, matching and pegs subtests, finger-tapping and standard reaction time.^{178, 181} One study reported composite scores "General Memory Index" and "Visuomotor",¹⁷⁹ which summarised the individual subtests of memory and visuomotor function detailed in a sister article.¹⁷⁸ Only the finger windows subtest of the WRAML indicated a significant difference in performance between treatment groups in one study, with four year change scores in the amalgam group being significantly more positive than those in composite resin restorations group, indicating greater improvement over time.¹⁷⁸ This finding was not replicated in the other study.¹⁸¹ None of the other specific outcomes measured by the same neuropsychological tools indicated any significant differences in cognitive performance between treatment groups in either study.^{178, 181}

Other tests of IQ, memory, executive functioning, visuomotor functioning and processing speed which were only used by one of the studies (See Supplementary Materials E, Table 5), the majority indicated no-significant difference in cognitive performance between treatment groups at any time point during follow-up.^{178, 179, 181} The only exception to this was the Number-Letter memory subtest of the WRAML, which indicated a significantly greater improvement over four years within the amalgam group.¹⁷⁸

Summary: Amalgam only health impact evidence (patients)

None of the four variable quality studies (five articles) evaluating the relationship between amalgam restorations in situ and neuropsychological test performance found any significant association between the two variables,^{178, 196, 233, 241, 251, 259} aside from one strong quality study where increased amalgam exposure was associated with higher scores on memory and letter fluency tasks.¹⁹⁶

Five studies, three of moderate quality,^{210, 241, 253} and two of weak quality examined the relationship between amalgam removal/replacement and neuropsychological symptoms.^{201, 228} Self-reported non-specified neuropsychological symptoms were significantly higher in individuals who attributed health difficulties to amalgam rather than other causes.²⁴¹ Findings for specific self-reported memory difficulties varied across studies and different outcome measures,^{201, 210, 228, 253} whilst self-report

measures indicated amalgam removal was associated with improved concentration in three studies.^{201, 210, 228}

Summary: Composite resin only health impact evidence (patients)

Two articles from the NECAT study appraised as strong quality found few significant association between exposure to resin composite/compomers or flowable sealant/preventative resin restorations (PRR) in situ and the neuropsychological outcomes.^{187, 259} These findings are consistent with a strong quality retrospective observational study which found no link between number of composite resin restorations and risk of developing dementia.²³³ The limited number of studies supporting this category prevents firm conclusions being drawn from these findings.

Comparative evidence summary: neuropsychological

Overall, three articles representing the NECAT and Casa Pia randomised controlled trials, appraised as strong quality found no statistically significant differences between the treatment groups on most neuropsychological tests administered. Where group differences on specific subtests were observed, children in the amalgam group tended to perform better than those who received composite resin restorations. Due to the bias inherent in self-report measures and moderate-to-low quality of the studies evaluating the impact of amalgam removal/replacement on neuropsychological symptoms, it can be concluded that there is currently no evidence to indicate a link between amalgam restorations and neuropsychological test performance (n=7). One retrospective observational study appraised as strong quality found no significant association between number of amalgam or composite fillings and risk of developing dementia. This finding contrasts with two strong quality articles based on the NECAT which found a few significant associations between resin composite/compomer exposure and neuropsychological outcomes, however the heterogeneity in population characteristics and health impacts and limited number of studies prevents identification of firm conclusions.

Oral health

Amalgam vs Composite: direct comparative evidence

Three studies compared oral health outcomes between individuals with amalgam versus composite resin restorations. Two retrospective cohorts appraised as moderate quality,^{183, 190} and one a secondary analysis of data from the Casa Pia randomised controlled trial, appraised as strong quality.¹⁹¹ Specific outcomes were heterogeneous, with each of the following outcomes evaluated by only one study: probing pocket depth (PPD, distance from gingival margin to base of pocket) changes,¹⁸³ number of patients with pulpal disease,¹⁹⁰ and proportion of children with oral bacteria.¹⁹¹ Of the three studies which directly compared outcomes between groups,^{183, 190, 191} two found no significant difference between treatment groups for the outcome of interest.^{190, 191} One study found a significantly higher

proportion of PPD 5mm or greater adjacent to amalgam versus composite resin restorations, indicating poorer oral health in this group.¹⁸³ See Supplementary Materials E, Table 6 for further details.

Summary: Amalgam only health impact evidence (patients)

Seven studies of variable quality evaluated the association between amalgam exposure,^{190, 195, 207, 230, 239, 251} or blood mercury level and oral disease or symptoms.²¹² Measures of outcomes of interest, which included occurrence of oral lichenoid lesions, oral lichen planus and “metallic taste/mouth dryness”, and measures of amalgam exposure were heterogeneous, which likely contributed to inconsistent findings reported across different studies.

Six studies appraised the association between removal/replacement of amalgam restorations and patient oral health symptoms. Four studies, one moderate quality,²³¹ and three weak,^{223, 229, 234} reported that removal/replacement of amalgam reduced oral lichenoid lesion symptoms. However, one of these reported this affect for clinical not histological healing,²³⁴ with two studies indicating that patients with an allergy to mercury were more likely to experience healing following amalgam removal alone,²²⁹ or in combination with the oral lichenoid lesions being in strict contact with amalgam filling.²³⁴

These findings were mirrored in patients with oral lichenoid reactions, with complete resolution being the most common outcome in two studies,^{231, 238} especially when patients were allergic to mercury.²⁴² No significant impact was shown by one study of amalgam removal for individuals with oral lichen planus symptoms,²³¹ which aligns with findings from one strong quality study reporting that amalgam restorations were not associated with altered odds of oral lichen planus.²³⁰

Summary: Composite resin only health impact evidence (patients)

Five studies of variable quality examined association between composite resin restorations in situ and patient oral health outcomes.^{190, 195, 207, 230, 257} Populations and specific outcomes of interest across these studies were heterogeneous and non-comparable, but broadly indicated no significant association between composite resin exposure and oral health symptoms, although adjusted odds ratio for oral lichen planus was significantly increased for individuals receiving three to four composite fillings per year in one strong quality study.²³⁰

Comparative evidence summary: oral health

Three studies of variable quality provided direct comparative evidence to support this category. Outcomes were heterogeneous, preventing comparison across studies. Whilst the variable quality of evidence evaluating the association between amalgam restorations and oral health limits confidence in the findings, evidence indicates amalgam removal (n=6) may support resolution of oral lichenoid lesions and oral lichenoid reaction symptoms where amalgam is in close contact with lesions and individuals have a positive mercury patch test. A limited quantity of evidence available from two

studies also suggests that amalgam restorations may not be associated with oral lichen planus. This latter finding aligns with the finding from one strong quality study which found no significant association between composite resin restorations and oral lichen planus, apart from individuals receiving three to four composite fillings/year. No association was found between composite resin restorations and oral lichenoid lesions in one study appraised as weak quality. Otherwise, the two groups of studies largely evaluated different outcomes. Where comparable, the limited evidence base favours composite resin restorations.

Psychosocial

Amalgam vs Composite: direct comparative evidence

Two articles appraised as strong quality representing findings from the NECAT compared psychological or behavioural outcomes in children who received amalgam or composite restorations.^{179, 180} One article reported no significant differences between groups in number of psychological disorders reported during the five-year follow-up.¹⁷⁹ The other article reports significant differences on two of four global scales of the Children's Behaviour Checklist (internalising symptoms, total problem behaviours), with differences stemming from between group differences on the change scores on activities, anxious/depressed and delinquent behaviour subscales.¹⁸⁰ All findings favoured children who received amalgam, who showed greater improvement in all measures.¹⁸⁰

Summary: Amalgam only health impact evidence (patients)

Five studies of variable quality examined the relationship between amalgam restorations in situ and psychosocial functioning.^{209, 212, 240, 241, 251} The number of studies measuring the same psychosocial impact was limited, and where this did occur the population groups and specific tool used differed. Only the two studies which compared self-reported anxiety and depression between patients with amalgam-attributed complaints and matched controls found a significant difference in symptom scores between groups.^{240, 241} Studies which compared amalgam treated groups with control groups with health complaints not attributed to amalgam,²⁵¹ or studies which explored how objective measures of amalgam or mercury exposure related to self-reported mental health symptoms reported no significant association.^{209, 212}

Six studies, four of which were appraised as weak quality examined the association between amalgam removal/replacement and mental health symptoms.^{200, 201, 210, 232, 237, 250, 253} Studies using global measures of psychological wellbeing (n=4) tended to report no significant difference between groups when comparing individuals who underwent amalgam removal with those who did not, although one study did demonstrate a significant improvement in symptoms following amalgam removal in a within-group analysis.²⁰⁰ Findings from three studies using a before-and-after design evaluating specific

symptoms of anxiety and depression, individually and pooled together, varied across study and type of outcome measure used.^{210, 228, 253}

Overall, the current evidence does not indicate an association between amalgam restorations and patient psychosocial outcomes, although the low-to-moderate quality of studies evaluating the impact of amalgam removal/replacement means this finding should be interpreted with caution.

Summary: Composite resin only health impact evidence (patients)

Two articles from the NECAT study appraised as strong quality found eleven significant associations of the 53 outcomes measured between child exposure to resin composite/comonomers or flowable sealant/preventative resin restorations (PRR) in situ on primary or posterior teeth and psychosocial health outcomes.^{209, 258} The majority of these concerned use of BisGMA-based composite on permanent teeth, with specific measures focusing on clinical maladjustment, personal adjustment, and emotional symptoms index, interpersonal relations, and anxiety for posterior occlusal surface years only, where exposure to Bis-GMA-based composite on permanent teeth was measured in 10-surface years (SY) and posterior occlusal SY.²⁰⁹ BASC-SR year five T-scores also indicated significant change scores for depression, clinical maladjustment, interpersonal relation and the emotional symptoms index for the same restoration type on posterior teeth.²⁰⁹ These change scores indicated greater exposure to BisGMA-composite was linked to poorer psychosocial performance at follow-up. Further studies are needed to evaluate the reliability of these findings.

Comparative evidence summary: psychosocial

Two articles appraised as strong quality from the NECAT study provided direct comparative evidence to support this outcome. There was no significant difference between treatment groups for the majority of specific outcomes evaluated. Where significant differences were found, improved scores were found in children receiving amalgam restorations. Overall, the current evidence does not indicate an association between amalgam restorations and patient psychosocial outcomes (n=9) although the low to moderate quality of studies evaluating the impact of amalgam removal/replacement means this finding should be interpreted with caution. The quantity of evidence evaluating the association between composite resin /comonomer restorations and psychosocial functioning was more limited, evaluated by only two articles from the NECAT study. Eleven significant associations were identified of the 53 outcomes measured. The majority of these concerned use of BisGMA-based composite on permanent teeth. Change scores indicated greater exposure to BisGMA-composite was linked to poorer psychosocial performance at follow-up. Further studies are needed to evaluate the reliability of these findings. Overall, the evidence base for this outcome favours amalgam, although the limited evidence available evaluating composite resin restorations limits confidence in this conclusion.

Renal

Amalgam vs Composite: direct comparative evidence

Two strong quality randomised controlled trials (four articles) representing findings from the NECAT,^{177, 186} and Casa Pia trials compared amalgam and composite resin restorations impact on renal health outcomes.^{181, 193} Only one of the eighteen specific outcomes measuring renal function indicated a statistically significant difference between groups (see Supplementary Materials E, Table 7).¹⁷⁷ In this study, a higher number of occurrences of Microalbuminuria (MA, albumin urinary excretion) in year 3 or year 5 follow-up was found in children receiving amalgam restorations,¹⁷⁷ contrasting with findings with the Casa Pia trial where no difference in albumin excretion was found between treatment groups.¹⁸¹ There was no significant interaction between treatment group and gender in the first study, although the odds ratio for MA was significantly increased for boys. Number of amalgam fillings and urinary mercury were not independently associated with MA, however a model of blood lead x urinary mercury, with urinary mercury as a predictor, was a significant predictor of MA in year 5.¹⁷⁷

Summary: Amalgam only health impact evidence (patients)

One strong quality article supporting findings from the Casa Pia randomised controlled trial reported mixed findings relating to level of amalgam exposure and renal outcomes.²¹⁶ Urinary GST-alpha levels demonstrated a significant dose-dependent relationship, however the relationship between urinary GST-pi levels and amalgam exposure was non-significant.²¹⁶

Summary: Composite resin only health impact evidence (patients)

No evidence to support this category.

Comparative evidence summary: renal

Two studies (five articles) from the NECAT and Casa Pia trials found no significant differences between treatment groups for the majority of specific outcomes within this category. The exception to this was urinary albumin, where findings between studies were inconsistent. Findings relating to amalgam exposure and renal function were mixed. No evidence was available from studies evaluating composite resin restorations alone. Whilst findings indicate there is no significant impact of restorative material on renal functioning, this needs to be replicated in further high-quality studies.

Respiratory

Amalgam vs Composite: direct comparative evidence

One article reporting findings associated with the NECAT study and appraised as strong quality reported no significant differences between amalgam and composite resin restoration treatment groups in the number of children reporting respiratory disorders during a five year follow up period.¹⁷⁹

Summary: Amalgam only health impact evidence (patients)

Overall, findings from the three studies examining the association between amalgam restorations and respiratory symptoms were mixed. Two studies by the same author, appraised as moderate quality, indicated individuals with health symptoms attributed to amalgam reported significantly higher number of respiratory and airway problems than those who had no health complaints attributed to amalgam,^{240, 241} except for “shortness of breath” in one of the studies, where the difference between the two groups was non-significant.²⁴⁰ The other study, also appraised as moderate quality,²¹⁰ evaluated the impact of amalgam removal in individuals with medically unexplained physical symptoms attributed to amalgam, found dyspnoea symptoms did not significantly change pre-post intervention.²¹⁰

Summary: Composite resin only health impact evidence (patients)

No evidence to support this category.

Comparative evidence summary: respiratory

Overall, the evidence available to support this category was extremely limited, with only one study from the NECAT providing direct comparative evidence. There is no evidence to suggest difference in risk of respiratory symptoms between treatment groups. Comparison between separate groups of studies evaluating association between amalgam or composite resin restorations and this health outcome was not possible.

Other

Amalgam vs Composite: direct comparative evidence

One strong quality article representing the NECAT trial compared the amalgam and composite resin restorations on other health outcomes.¹⁷⁹ None of the following broad health outcomes differed significantly between treatment groups: blood disorders, cancer, endocrine, and sensory outcomes.

One strong quality article representing the Casa Pia trial compared amalgam and composite resin restorations on urinary porphyrins.¹⁸² A significant relationship between mercury exposure from dental amalgams and urinary porphyrins associated with mercury body burden was observed in children over the eight-year trial. A five to ten percent increases in mercury-associated porphyrins was found in

children receiving amalgam fillings compared to those receiving only composite fillings. No association was found with urinary porphyrins not associated with mercury body burden.¹⁸²

Overall Summary: amalgam vs composite resin restorations

The quantity of direct comparative evidence was extremely limited, with the majority of evidence comparing health outcomes associated with amalgam vs composite resin restorations stemming from the strong quality NECAT and Casa Pia trials.^{179, 181} Whilst this evidence could be supplemented by studies evaluating amalgam or composite separately, the quantity of evidence pertaining to amalgam was much larger than that relevant to composite resin restorations, which again limited comparisons which could be made between these two bodies of evidence for different health outcomes. Specific health outcomes associated with composite resin restorations where further high-quality trials would be particularly useful to support comparative analysis within the existing evidence base include: adverse events, cardiovascular disease, dermatological, gastrointestinal, general physical health, musculoskeletal, neurological, respiratory and visual ocular symptoms. The impact of both amalgam and composite resin restorations on renal symptoms was also under-represented within the synthesis.

Broad health outcomes with the highest quantity of data evaluating both amalgam and composite resin restorations available to support a comparative synthesis included immune function, neuropsychological, oral health and psychosocial symptoms, although confidence in reported findings is limited due to moderate-weak quality of evidence and heterogeneity of specific outcomes within specific categories.

Amalgam

Fifty-two studies (67 articles) evaluated the health impact of amalgam and/or mercury. The majority of these evaluated health outcomes of patients exposed to amalgam via restorations in situ or via removal and/or replacement of existing restorations (n=36).^{178, 187, 190, 192, 195-197, 199-205, 207, 209-213, 215, 216, 221, 223, 225, 228-234, 237-242, 244, 245, 249-254, 259} Ten studies (13 articles) explored the impact of maternal exposure to amalgam prior to or during pregnancy and child health impacts,^{194, 198, 206, 217, 222, 224, 226, 227, 235, 236, 246-248} and seven studies focused on the health impacts experienced by dental professionals occupationally exposed to amalgam and/or mercury.^{208, 214, 218-220, 222, 243} Twenty-two studies were appraised by the EPHPP tool as weak (n=22),^{194, 195, 197, 201-203, 207, 211, 212, 215, 219, 220, 222, 223, 225-229, 232, 234, 237-239, 250, 251} moderate (n=14),^{190, 198-200, 208, 210, 214, 218, 231, 240-243, 246-249, 253} or strong quality (n=15).^{178, 187, 192, 196, 204-206, 213, 216, 217, 221, 224, 230, 233, 235, 236, 244, 245, 252, 258, 259}

Below, these studies are grouped according to exposed population, firstly dental professionals exposed to amalgam/mercury due to their occupation (n=7),^{208, 214, 218-220, 222, 243} children exposed via maternal exposure to amalgam prior to or during pregnancy (n=10),^{194, 198, 206, 217, 222, 224, 226, 227, 235, 236, 246-248} and patients direct exposure via amalgam restorations (n=36). Within each of these population groups, the association between amalgam exposure and different health impacts is explored, with reference to whether amalgam exposure occurred via occupational exposure, amalgam restorations in situ or via placement/removal of amalgam restorations. For detail regarding the findings for each specific outcome from studies included in this section can be found in Supplementary Materials E, Tables 9 to 51.

Dental professionals

Seven studies examined the relationship between dental professional exposure to amalgam and different outcomes.^{208, 214, 218-220, 222, 243} Four studies were appraised by reviewers as moderate quality,^{208, 214, 218, 243} and three as weak quality.^{219, 220, 222} Below, the findings reported in these studies, grouped according to the following broad outcome category, are reported: general physical health (n=4),^{208, 219, 220, 222} musculoskeletal problems (n=2),^{220, 222} neurological symptoms (n=5),^{208, 214, 219, 220, 222} neuropsychological (n=5),^{208, 214, 219, 220, 222} psychological symptoms (n=4),^{208, 219, 220, 222} renal symptoms (n=2),^{220, 243} respiratory symptoms (n=2),^{220, 243} and other (n=4).^{208, 218, 222, 243} For further detail regarding findings related to specific outcomes, see Supplementary Materials E, Tables 9-16.

General physical health

Four studies examined the relationship between amalgam or mercury exposure and symptoms of general physical health of dental professionals. One cohort with control group study was appraised by reviewers as moderate quality.²⁰⁸ The remaining three were cross-sectional studies with control

groups, two by the same authors, appraised as weak quality.^{219, 220, 222} Specific outcomes of interest informed by more than one study include sleep disturbance (n=3),^{219, 220, 222} fatigue (n=2),^{219, 220} headache/migraine (n=2),^{220, 222} and overall health symptoms/symptom prevalence (n=3),^{219, 220, 222} [See Supplementary Materials E, Table 9].

Two of the three weak quality cross-sectional studies with control groups reported that dental professionals exposed to mercury (assumed to be amalgam as dental restorative material of interest) experienced statistically higher sleep disturbances.^{220, 222} The other reported no significant difference in sleep disturbances between exposed and non-exposed groups.²¹⁹ Results were similarly mixed for “fatigue” outcomes, from two studies by the same authors using similar methodology, both appraised as weak quality; one reported statistically significant fatigue symptomology in dental professionals versus controls,²²⁰ whilst the other reported no significant difference in fatigue between exposed and non-exposed groups.²¹⁹

For headache/migraine outcomes (n=2), one study reported significantly greater symptoms among dental professionals,²²² whilst the other reported no significant difference between exposed and control groups.²²⁰

Three studies appraised as weak quality provided summaries of symptom prevalence or overall physical health, all of which reported no significant difference in symptoms between dental professionals exposed to mercury and non-exposed controls.^{219, 220, 222} However one study indicated that whilst not-significant, female dentists between 41 and 60 years old had “slightly” higher sum score than controls-with stratification analysis by age groups prevented by small population numbers.²¹⁹

One study appraised as weak quality indicates dentists exposed to copper amalgam/mercury have significantly more symptoms of bloating and unsteadiness than unexposed controls.²²²

The cohort with control group study appraised as moderate quality indicated that dentists show higher frequency of pharmacy utilisation for specific illness medication than controls.²⁰⁸ These findings are explored within the relevant sections below.

[Summary: dental professionals amalgam exposure - General physical health](#)

Overall, the quality of evidence supporting this category was weak and demonstrated no consistent significant association between amalgam/mercury exposure among dental professionals and symptoms of general physical health.

[Musculoskeletal](#)

Two cross-sectional studies with controls appraised as weak quality,^{220, 222} did not provide evidence of a consistent association between amalgam/mercury exposure and musculoskeletal outcomes in dental

professionals. One study reported no association between musculoskeletal complaints and metallic mercury exposure,²²⁰ whilst the other study reported that dental professionals exposed to mercury reported significantly higher number of physical injuries and arthritis symptoms versus non-exposed controls.²²² [See Supplementary Materials E, Table 10]

Neurological

Five studies examined the association between dental professional exposure to mercury/amalgam and neurological symptoms.^{208, 214, 219, 220, 243} Two studies were appraised as weak quality,^{219, 220} with the remainder appraised as moderate [See Supplementary Materials E, Table 11].

Types of outcomes measure used to evaluate neurological symptoms were heterogenous across different studies, including number of prescriptions for neurological medication or frequency of use of such medications (n=1),²⁰⁸ measures of nerve function (n=1),²¹⁴ self-reported symptoms (n=2),^{219, 220} and hospital admission data.²⁴³

For studies appraised as moderate quality, one cross-sectional study with control indicated that dentists used a significantly higher number of prescriptions for neurological conditions than non-exposed controls,²⁰⁸ whilst another cross-sectional/longitudinal study indicates the association between nerve function of dental professionals exposed to amalgam and urinary mercury is not significant for outcomes of ulnar amplitude or median amplitude.²¹⁴ The same study indicates relationship between urinary Hg and median peak latency/ulnar peak latency is significant if subjects with imputed BMI included, but that this relationship is insignificant if these subjects are removed from the analysis.²¹⁴ One retrospective observational study showed no consistent pattern regarding the relationship between mercury exposure amongst dental assistants versus non-exposed control groups regarding hospital admission for neurological disease.²⁴³ However, the same study indicates a significant period effect for dentists, with increasing risk of admission for neurological disease for dentists versus non-exposed controls over time.²⁴³ Thygesen et al (2011) also indicate that dentists are at lower risk for hospital admission due to Parkinson's Disease than non-exposed controls, admission rates for dental assistant's vs non-exposed controls did not show any consistent pattern.²⁴³

Two cross-sectional studies with control group appraised as weak quality from the same authors reported inconsistent findings regarding relationship between mercury exposure among dental professionals and self-reported neurological symptoms,^{219, 220} with one study conducted with only female dental professionals and controls reporting a significant association following adjustment for age and education level,²²⁰ and one a non-significant association.²¹⁹

Summary: dental professionals amalgam exposure - Neurological symptoms

The majority of evidence supporting this category was appraised as moderate quality. A wide variety of outcome measures were used to examine the potential relationship between exposure and neurological symptoms. Overall, there seems to be no consistent association between dental professional exposure to mercury or amalgam and neurological outcomes.

Neuropsychological

There were three studies within this category,^{208, 219, 220, 222} two of which were appraised as weak quality, and one as moderate.²⁰⁸ [See Supplementary Materials E, Table 12] The study appraised as moderate quality indicated that dentists exposed to mercury/amalgam had a significantly higher rate of using neuropsychiatric medication than controls.²⁰⁸

Three studies appraised as weak quality evaluated memory outcomes, two cross-sectional studies with control groups by the same authors using self-report via the Euroquest questionnaire,^{219, 220} and one via the Rey-15 tool.²²² One study indicated that dental professionals exposed to metallic mercury had a significantly higher mean symptom score than non-exposed controls,²²⁰ whilst the other two studies did not identify significant differences between dental professional and control groups on the Euroquest,²¹⁹ or Rey-15/California Verbal Learning Test.²²²

Three studies appraised as weak quality evaluated ability to concentrate,^{219, 220, 222} with one cross-sectional study with control finding a significantly higher level of problems concentrating in female dental professionals exposed to amalgam/mercury versus the non-exposed control group,²²⁰ and the other two cross-sectional studies with control group finding no significant differences between dental professionals and non-exposed controls.^{219, 222}

Finally, one cross-sectional study with control appraised as weak quality found no difference between dental professional versus non-exposed control groups on a measure of executive function, concentration and attention.²²²

Summary: dental professionals - Neuropsychological

The majority of evidence supporting this category was appraised as weak quality and used a variety of neuropsychological outcome measures across different studies. Overall, there were no consistent associations between exposure to mercury among dental professionals and neuropsychological outcomes supported by more than one study.

Psychological

Four studies within this category.^{208, 219, 220, 222} All three cross-sectional studies with control groups were appraised as being weak quality,^{219, 220, 222} with the study using a cohort with control group design

appraised as moderate [See Supplementary Materials E, Table 13].²⁰⁸ The latter, indicated that dental professionals exposed to amalgam/mercury had greater utilisation of psychiatric medications.²⁰⁸

The two studies using similar methods by the same authors appraised as weak quality both used the Euroquest as a self-report measure for mood and psychosomatic symptoms, neither finding a significant difference in score for either outcome between dental professionals exposed to mercury/amalgam and non-exposed controls.^{208, 219, 220}

One study used the Profile of Mood States (POMS) questionnaire to compare psychological symptoms in dental professionals exposed to amalgam to non-exposed controls.²²² This study found a significant difference between the groups for the “Agreeable-hostile” and “Composed-anxious” subscale of the POMS, but non-significant differences between the groups on the “Elated-depressed”, “Confident-unsure”, “Clearheaded-confused” and “Energetic-tired” subscales.²²²

Summary: dental professionals amalgam exposure – Psychological

The majority of evidence supporting this category was appraised as weak quality. Only two studies conducted by the same authors, utilising similar methodologies and the same outcome measures indicated that there were no significant differences in score on “mood” items of the Euroquest self-report questionnaire between dental professionals exposed to mercury and non-exposed controls. Heterogenous outcome measures precluded comparison across other studies.

Renal

Two studies within this category, one retrospective observational cohort study appraised as moderate quality,²⁴³ the other cross-sectional with control group study was appraised as weak.²²⁰ One study compared hospital admission rates for renal disease between dental professionals occupational exposed to mercury and unexposed controls,²⁴³ and the other self-reported renal symptoms between female dental professionals and unexposed controls.²²⁰ Neither study found a significant difference between exposed and non-exposed groups for the outcome of interest [See Supplementary Materials E, Table 14]

Respiratory

Two studies within this category, one cohort with control group study appraised as moderate quality,²⁰⁸ the other cross-sectional with control group study as weak [See Supplementary Materials E, Table 15].²²⁰

Duplinsky et al (2012) report a non-significant difference between dental professionals exposed to mercury versus non-exposed controls and number of prescriptions for respiratory conditions, although they found that dentists used respiratory medications more frequently than non-exposed controls.²⁰⁸

The study appraised as weak quality by Hilt et al (2009) found no significant difference between dental professionals exposed to mercury and non-exposed controls regarding the number of respiratory symptoms reported.²²⁰

Other

Four studies supported this category,^{208, 218, 222, 243} one cohort with control group study, one retrospective observational cohort and one retrospective case-control study were appraised as moderate quality,^{208, 218, 243} and two cross-sectional with control group studies appraised as weak quality[See Supplementary Materials E, Table 16].²²²

One study per outcome examined the relationship between exposure to amalgam/mercury exposure and link to cancer,²²² cardiovascular symptoms,²⁰⁸ dermatological outcomes,²²² endocrine symptoms,²²² female health,²²² oral health,²²² serious adverse events.²⁴³

Studies reported significant differences between dental professionals exposed to amalgam/mercury and non-exposed groups regarding number of prescriptions and frequency of medication use for cardiovascular symptoms,²⁰⁸ dry skin,²²² hysterectomy,²²² and presence of metallic taste in mouth,²²² with individuals in dental professional groups exhibiting greater symptomology compared to controls for these outcomes.

One study reported non-significant differences between dental professionals exposed to amalgam/mercury regarding thyroid symptoms,²²² and breast cancer occurrence.²²² Another study reported number of deaths at follow-up, with higher rates reported for non-exposed comparator groups but it was unclear if this outcome related to dental restorative material, participants could belong to multiple job categories and no statistical comparison was made between the three groups.²⁴³

One study reports the proportion of dental professionals who tested positive to an allergy to amalgam, or amalgam alloying metals.²¹⁸

Summary: Dental professionals Hg exposure-health outcomes

Most of the evidence examining the association between dental professional occupational exposure to mercury compared to non-occupationally exposed populations was appraised as weak quality. Outcomes evaluated included general physical health (n=4), musculoskeletal (n=2), neurological (n=5), neuropsychological (n=5), psychological (n=4), renal (n=2), respiratory (n=2) and other (n=1). Specific outcome measures were heterogenous, often precluding meaningful comparisons across studies within the same broad outcome category. Regarding specific outcomes, very few consistent significant associations between dental professional exposure to mercury and health outcomes were found.

Maternal exposure

Ten studies (thirteen articles) examined the relationship between maternal exposure to amalgam and child health outcomes.^{194, 198, 206, 217, 222, 224, 226, 227, 235, 236, 246-248} Four studies were appraised as weak quality,^{194, 222, 226, 227} two as moderate quality,^{198, 246-248} and four as strong quality.^{206, 217, 224, 235, 236} Findings are grouped into the following outcome categories: ADHD/Autism (n=2),^{194, 226} neuropsychological (n=3),^{206, 235, 236, 246-248} and pregnancy outcomes (n=7).^{198, 206, 217, 222, 224, 227, 236} Three studies pertain to pregnancy outcomes for dental professionals exposed to amalgam/mercury during their occupational practice.^{217, 222, 236} Detail regarding findings for specific outcomes for each study within this section can be viewed in Supplementary Materials E, Tables 17-21.

ADHD/Autism outcomes

One case-control,¹⁹⁴ and one prospective cohort,²²⁶ appraised by reviewers as weak quality examined the potential association between maternal exposure to amalgam and child ADHD,²²⁶ or autism outcomes.¹⁹⁴ [See Supplementary Materials E, Table 17]

No significant relationship found between maternal amalgams placed before or during pregnancy and child ADHD symptoms at three- and five-years post-partum.²²⁶ This finding was consistent when boys and girls were analysed together and separately.²²⁶ The same study found no relationship between number of maternal amalgams removed during pregnancy and child ADHD symptoms in the 90th percentile.²²⁶

Regarding autism diagnosis, children with lower levels of Hg in hair were 2.5 times more likely to be diagnosed with autism (p<.05), however there was no statistically significant correlation between autism severity and level of mercury in baby hair.¹⁹⁴ There was no difference between children diagnosed with autism vs neurotypical children in the number of maternal amalgam fillings placed during pregnancy, with autism and control groups having similar values of mercury in hair.¹⁹⁴ Mercury in hair significantly correlated with number of maternal amalgam fillings for children with autism, but not controls.¹⁹⁴

Summary: Maternal exposure to amalgam – ADHD/Autism

The relationship between child ADHD and autism outcomes and maternal amalgam exposure were examined by one study each. Both studies were appraised as weak quality. No association was found between maternal amalgams placed/removed during pregnancy and ADHD outcomes. Autism diagnosis was found to be unrelated to level of mercury in child hair, with levels of hair mercury corresponding to number of amalgam fillings in children diagnosed with autism only. Firm conclusions regarding the relationship between maternal amalgam exposure and ADHD/Autism outcomes are not possible due to the paucity of research.

Neuropsychological outcomes

Three studies (five articles) examined the potential relationship between maternal amalgam exposure and child neuropsychological outcomes.^{206, 235, 246-248} Dental professionals occupationally exposed to amalgam/Hg were the population of one of these studies.²³⁵ Three articles associated with the Seychelles Child Development Nutrition (SCDN) study were appraised as moderate quality,^{206, 235, 246-248} whilst the remaining two studies were appraised as strong quality.^{206, 235}

Specific measures of child neuropsychological functioning were heterogenous and, aside from measures of expressive and receptive language ability and reading and arithmetic achievement used within two articles from the SCDN study,^{206, 235, 246-248} were not used within more than one study in this category. Of the two moderate quality articles reporting outcomes at different time-points during cohort follow-up, both found no association between number of pre-natal maternal amalgam surfaces and child performance on assessments of reading and arithmetic achievement [the letter word recognition and applied problems subtests of the Woodcock-Johnson Tests of Achievement] at 66-months and five years, either with or without adjustment for prenatal and recent postnatal amalgam exposure.^{247, 248} Both articles found no association between the secondary exposure metric, prenatal amalgam occlusal points, and child performance on any of the psychometric tests administered at the same time points (66-months and five years) (see Supplementary Materials E, Table 18). The exception to this was a significant negative association in males only on the Letter Word Recognition subtest of the Woodcock-Johnson Tests of Achievement (reading and arithmetic).²⁴⁷ The Upper Exposure Limit (UEL)³ within one study indicated worsening performance as number of occlusal points increased, and significant improvement on general cognitive index (GCI) (with Lower and Upper Exposure Limit), the Preschool Language Scales (expressive/receptive language ability) total score (UEL) and the W-J Applied Problem subtest for females.²⁴⁷

Regarding overall cognitive ability, two articles appraised as moderate quality from the SCDN study demonstrated no association between maternal amalgam exposure and overall cognitive ability of child at 30 and 66 months.^{246, 247} Each study used different measures of cognitive function (see Supplementary Materials E, Table 10). In Watson et al (2011), scores on the general cognitive index (GCI)-amalgam slope were positive for females, negative for males, but neither slope significantly different from zero.²⁴⁷ However, in LEL model, there was a significant amalgam surfaces by sex interaction for GCI outcome, indicating that for small numbers of amalgam surfaces, GCI score was similar for both sexes, but as maternal amalgam surfaces increased, males predicted to perform less well, whilst the reverse was found for females.²⁴⁷ Using UEL exposure scores, increasing recent

³Lower Exposure Limit: total number of amalgam surfaces or occlusal points *likely* present during gestation). Upper Exposure Limit: LEL and amalgams *possibly* present during gestation.

postnatal methylmercury exposure was associated with significant improvement among males and females on same outcomes and indicated fewer Bender Gestalt Errors with increasing postnatal methylmercury exposure.²⁴⁷

Regarding child language development, two studies (three articles) demonstrated no significant association between measures of language expression/comprehension at 15 and 66 months and maternal amalgam exposure both before,^{206,247,248} and during pregnancy.²⁰⁶ However, the second study demonstrated a significant association between occlusal amalgam points (using the UEL metric) and communication function for female participants only at 66 months, where males performed less well versus females as number of occlusal points increased.²⁴⁷ One study appraised as strong quality found no association between maternal exposure to elemental mercury via amalgam and adult male offsprings linguistic ability when the mothers were occupationally exposed dentists compared to non-exposed physicians.²³⁵ However, when mothers were occupationally exposed nursing assistants, the study found they scored significantly higher upon tests assessing linguistic understanding and ability to use oral and written language compared to non-exposed assistant nurses when adjusted for father's educational level, mother's age at time of birth, if they had older siblings and birth decade. Study authors attributed this to familial differences rather than employment-related maternal exposures as the estimate of difference was attenuated by adjustment for father's educational attainment. One of the aforementioned studies also found no association between maternal amalgam exposure during pregnancy and child social communication at 15 months.²⁰⁶

Two studies assessed the ability of offspring of amalgam-exposed mothers to mentally manipulate objects,²³⁵ and/or recognise patterns in visual information presented to them.²⁴⁷ Both found no association between maternal amalgam exposure and neuropsychological outcome of interest. One of the studies highlighted that offspring of dental nurses demonstrated a significantly higher score on spatial recognition and technical comprehension than offspring of assistant nurses, findings which were not replicated within the dentist versus physician comparisons.²³⁵ Another article demonstrated no significant association between children's visual-spatial ability at 66 months and maternal amalgam exposure. However, despite the quality of the studies being appraised as moderate,^{247,248} and strong,²³⁵ the difference in exposed populations, ages of children evaluated and types of outcome measure used, limit the confidence which can be placed in this finding.²³⁵

Maternal amalgam exposure as measured by occlusal points, but not amalgam surfaces, was found to be associated with child reading and arithmetic achievement at 66 months of age using a UEL exposure metric.²⁴⁷ However neither number of amalgam surfaces nor occlusal points were a significant predictor of psychomotor development at either 9 or 30 months of age.²⁴⁶

Summary: Maternal exposure to amalgam – Neuropsychological

There is some evidence to suggest that maternal amalgam exposure may impact on child neuropsychological test performance of overall cognitive ability, with some sex differences. However, whilst the three studies supporting this category were appraised as being of moderate or strong quality, heterogeneity in terms of the amalgam exposed mothers included in the studies, types of amalgam exposure metrics used, neuropsychological outcomes investigated and measures used, and age of child at testing prevent firm conclusions being drawn regarding the relationship between amalgam exposure and individual measures of neuropsychological function.

Pregnancy outcomes

Seven studies evaluated the relationship between maternal exposure to amalgam and pregnancy outcomes. Quality appraised by reviewers resulted in the following scores: weak quality (n=2),^{222, 227} moderate quality (n=1),¹⁹⁸ and strong quality (n=4).^{206, 217, 224, 236} Of these, three pertain to pregnancy outcomes for dental professionals exposed during their occupational practice [See Supplementary Materials E, Table 19].^{217, 222, 236}

Four studies, one weak quality cross-sectional with control,²²² one strong quality retrospective cohort with control,²³⁶ one strong quality retrospective cohort,²¹⁷ and one strong quality retrospective/cross-sectional with control group,²²⁴ reported no association between maternal occupational exposure to amalgam and childhood death outcomes which included stillbirth/miscarriage,^{222, 224} stillbirth/prenatal death,²¹⁷ and neonatal, infant or child mortality across the 1960's, 70's and 80's.²³⁶ The exception to this was that the latter study reported a significant association between maternal occupation and neonatal mortality in the 1960s, but this association was not present for the other decades as amalgam use was phased out.²³⁶ One study reported higher risk of miscarriage for intermediate than for the high-exposure and when intermediate-exposure and high-exposure categories were combined, the adjusted OR was 1.5 (95% CI 0.8 to 2.8).²²⁴ The same study found no association between number of years of mercury amalgam use and miscarriage.²²⁴

In non-occupationally exposed mothers, increased numbers of amalgam fillings were found to be significantly associated with increased risk for perinatal death in one moderate quality prospective longitudinal study.¹⁹⁸ This finding persisted even when the following groups were excluded from the analysis: mothers with over 20 teeth filled with amalgam, pregnancies 30 weeks or shorter, children with malformations, and mothers with preeclampsia/eclampsia, chronic hypertension, and gestational diabetes and who were small for gestational age.¹⁹⁸ When females and males were analysed separately there was an increased risk for girls not boys and the Odds Ratio was significantly increased for those in highest exposure group for maternal groups with 12 or fewer years of education. When only individuals with normal BMI (18.5-24.9) were included in the analysis, the significant association

disappeared, whereas if only individuals with BMI>25 were included in the analysis, the association was again significant although size of the odds ratio was small/moderate.¹⁹⁸ These findings were supported by a prospective cohort study appraised as weak quality which found a higher prevalence of stillbirth when others had a higher number of teeth with amalgam fillings, particularly in mothers with five or more teeth filled with amalgam. However, this odds ratio was reduced and finding non statistically significant following adjustment.²²⁷

Among dental professionals, two studies found no association between occupational amalgam exposure and low birthweight or small gestational age.^{217, 222} However, the latter study reported significantly lower risks of small gestational age during 1967–1976 for dental assistants overall and low birth weight during 1997–2006 for dental assistants in employment. However, the level of significance was not adjusted for multiple testing, so study authors recommend care when interpreting these findings.²¹⁷

One prospective cohort study appraised as weak quality found a significant positive association between birthweight and height and number of maternal amalgams in place during pregnancy.²²⁷ However the same study found no association between number of amalgams and low birth weight or being small for gestational age, although girls whose mother had one amalgam or more amalgams placed/removed during pregnancy had a slightly elevated risk for being small for gestational age.²²⁷ None of the other outcomes were influenced by amalgam placement/removal during pregnancy.²²⁷ A prospective cohort study appraised as strong quality found no association between low birthweight or preterm babies and amalgam placed/removed during pregnancy,²⁰⁶ although women with more amalgams in place at conception were found to have a significantly lower probability of a low birthweight infant at full-term.²⁰⁶

Three studies examined the relationship between maternal exposure to amalgam and childbirth malformations. Two studies involved occupational exposure for female dental health professionals, one a strong quality retrospective cohort,²¹⁷ the other a weak quality cross-sectional study with control.²²² These two studies found no significant difference between amalgam exposed and non-exposed professional groups for child birth malformations when controlling for potential confounders, expect for a reduced risk in clubfoot for dental assistants.²¹⁷ The other prospective cohort study, appraised as weak quality, found no significant association between number of teeth with amalgam fillings or amalgam placed/removed during pregnancy and birth malformations.²²⁷

Specific outcomes appraised by a single study include mercury concentration in umbilical cord at birth,²⁰⁶ conception difficulties,²²² child with learning difficulties/developmental delay,²²² and

early/late delivery.²²⁷ Findings relating to these specific outcomes are reported in Supplementary Materials E, Table 19.

Summary: Maternal exposure to amalgam – Pregnancy

Seven studies, the majority appraised as moderate or strong quality, supported this category. No significant association between maternal occupational amalgam exposure and childhood death outcomes were found by four studies reporting these outcomes, three of which were strong quality, although one study reported higher risk of miscarriage for individuals with intermediate vs high exposure. Findings for the same outcome in non-occupationally exposed mothers were contradictory in the two studies exploring this outcome, with one moderate quality study reporting increased numbers of amalgam filling significantly increased the risk of perinatal death. However, this increased risk was only present for girls when males and females were analysed separately. Characteristics which appeared to increase individuals risk included 12 or fewer years of maternal education and BMI over 25. Another weak quality study found no association between number of teeth with amalgam fillings and stillbirth. There was no convincing evidence regarding an association between number of amalgam fillings prior to/during pregnancy and weight/height birth outcomes. Three studies (one appraised as strong, two as weak quality) also found no association between maternal exposure to amalgam following occupational and non-occupational exposure to mercury/amalgam and malformations at birth, although the limited number of studies and their low-quality limit confidence in this finding.

Summary: Maternal exposure to amalgam-child health impact

Outcomes evaluated included: ADHD/Autism (n=2), neuropsychological (n=3), and pregnancy outcomes (n=7). Insufficient and weak quality evidence prevents conclusions pertaining to autism/ADHD outcomes in children following maternal exposure to amalgam. The quantity of evidence relating to child neuropsychological outcomes was larger and appraised as moderate to strong quality, but whilst there is some evidence to suggest maternal amalgam exposure may impact on tests of overall cognitive ability, with some sex differences, heterogeneity in terms of the amalgam exposed mothers included in the studies, types of amalgam exposure metrics used, neuropsychological outcomes investigated and measures used, and age of child at testing, similarly limits conclusions that can be drawn. The quality of evidence evaluating pregnancy outcomes was variable, but the majority were appraised as strong quality (n=4 of seven studies). Evidence suggests that there is no association between maternal amalgam exposure and childhood death outcomes for non-occupationally exposed mothers, although further research is required into the risk of miscarriage for individuals with higher amalgam exposure. Birth outcomes for dental professional were mixed, and further research is required. There is tentative evidence to suggest no association between maternal exposure via

occupational and non-occupational exposure to amalgam/mercury and birth malformations, but again the limited number of studies and their low-quality limit confidence in this finding.

Patients

Thirty-six studies (46 articles) evaluated the health impact of amalgam restorations and/or mercury exposure on the health of adults or children [See Part 1: [Health impacts: Amalgam](#) for references]. Thirty-five of these were appraised using the EPHPP tool, with quality appraisal scores being: weak (n=16),^{195, 197, 201-203, 207, 211, 212, 215, 223, 225, 228, 229, 232, 234, 237-239, 250, 251} moderate quality (n=8),^{190, 199, 200, 210, 231, 240-242, 249, 253} and strong (n=10).^{178, 187, 188, 192, 196, 204, 205, 209, 213, 216, 221, 230, 233, 244, 245, 252, 258, 259} One study was appraised as being at high risk of bias by the CEECAT tool.²⁵⁴

These studies are synthesised within the following broad outcome categories: adverse events (n=3),^{199, 211, 201, 232} allergy (n=11),^(195, 212, 223, 239, 229, 238, 210, 231, 213, 242, 249) cardiovascular disease (n=6),^{210, 212, 228, 240, 241, 251} dermatological (n=5),^{210, 228, 240, 241, 251} ear, nose and throat (ENT)(n=5),^{210, 228, 240, 241, 253} gastrointestinal (n=7),^{201, 210, 228, 240, 241, 251, 253} general physical health (n=9),^{199-201, 210-212, 228, 232, 237, 240, 241, 250, 251, 253} immune function (n=7),^{187, 192, 197, 204, 212, 215, 237, 238} musculoskeletal (n=9),^{201, 210, 212, 228, 237, 240, 241, 251, 253} neurological (n=6),^{205, 221, 244, 245, 253} neuropsychological (n=9),^{196, 201, 210, 228, 233, 241, 251, 253, 259} oral health (n=13),^{190, 195, 207, 212, 223, 229-231, 234, 238, 239, 242, 251} orofacial (n=4),^{201, 210, 211, 228} psychosocial (n=8),^{200, 209, 210, 212, 228, 232, 240, 250, 251, 253} respiratory, urinary and visual ocular (n=4),^{65, 210, 240, 241} and other (n=7).^{202, 203, 216, 225, 237, 252, 254}

Within each of these categories, findings relating to amalgam restorations in situ and findings relating to amalgam removal/replacement are considered separately.

Detail regarding findings for specific outcomes for each study within this section can be viewed in Supplementary Materials E, Tables 21-51.

Adverse events

Three studies (four articles) reported adverse events associated with **amalgam removal/replacement**. One was appraised as moderate quality,¹⁹⁹ with the others appraised as weak quality.^{201, 211, 232} See Supplementary Materials E, Table 21 for details on main adverse event findings.

Two articles from the same study examined the impact of amalgam removal and replacement on medically unexplained physical symptoms attributed to amalgam restorations, one presented as a before and after with comparison,²¹¹ the other presents findings of the treatment group as a before and after comparison.²⁰¹ Another prospective longitudinal study compared health complaints before and after amalgam restorations removals/replacement in population where health complaints were attributed to amalgam compared to individuals where complaints were not attributed to amalgam and healthy controls where no restoration replacement was conducted.¹⁹⁷ All three studies reported that a proportion of participants, ranging from 28%,¹⁹⁹ to 48%,²³² experienced an aggravation of general

health complaints following amalgam removal/replacement. However, this was generally presented narratively and rarely accompanied by statistical comparison of symptom levels between different groups (or before and after within the same group) where relevant. In an RCT comparing number of participants reporting “new” health complaints following amalgam removal, to those who underwent amalgam removal alongside biological detoxification and individuals who did not have their amalgam restorations removed, a higher proportion of the ‘no removal’ reported ‘new’ health symptoms than the two removal groups.²³² Bjorkman et al (2017) indicate that scores on the Depression, Hysteria and Psychopathic Deviate scales of the Minnesota-Multiphasic Personality Inventory-2 were significantly lower in individuals who did not report increased symptoms, although mean scores on the Psychopathology five scales did not differ between groups.²⁰¹ This study reported 18 (6.4%) of new restorations were revised during a five year follow-up period, with 14 of the new composites being replaced being polymer-based composites. The occurrence of secondary caries lesions was the main reason for revision.²⁰¹

Neither of the two studies, one appraised as moderate quality,¹⁹⁹ the other as weak,²³² reported any serious adverse events associated with the studies.

Summary: Amalgam only health impact evidence (patients) – Adverse Event

All three studies (four articles) evaluating the relationship between amalgam removal/replacement and adverse events reported that patients experienced an aggravation of general health complaints following amalgam removal/replacement.^{199, 201, 211, 232} However, the limited number, lack of statistical comparison and generally low quality of the studies prevents firm conclusions being drawn.

Allergy

Eleven studies appraised the relationship between presence of oral health symptoms and allergy to amalgam or mercury, five related to **amalgam restorations in situ**,^{195, 212, 213, 239, 249} and six to **removal and/or replacement of amalgam**.^{210, 223, 229, 231, 238, 242} Quality appraisal ratings were weak (n=6),^{195, 212, 223, 229, 238, 239} moderate (n=4),^{210, 231, 242, 249} and strong (n=1).²¹³ See Supplementary Materials E, Tables 22 and 23 for study findings.

Two studies indicated a significant association between oral symptoms and mercury allergy.^{195, 213} These included a weak quality case-control study examining how individuals with oral lichenoid lesions were more likely than dermatitis patients to have an allergy to mercury.¹⁹⁵ This study indicates that of nine oral lichenoid lesion patients who tested positive for mercury allergy (10.8%), all had an oral lichenoid lesion adjacent to an amalgam filling and the mean number of amalgam surfaces were significantly higher in patients allergic to mercury.¹⁹⁵ One strong quality retrospective record review indicated individuals with allergic stomatitis were significantly more likely to be sensitised to amalgam

and ammoniated mercury than individuals with noninflammatory oral complaints.²¹³ However, this latter study showed no difference in sensitization to amalgam alloy metals (silicon, copper, tin, zinc) between the two patient groups.²¹³

In contrast, four studies reported no significant relationship between amalgam,^{239, 249} or mercury allergy and oral health symptoms.^{212, 223, 239, 249} Two of these studies (retrospective record review and cross-sectional with control group) were appraised as weak quality and one prospective longitudinal study with control as moderate quality. One cross-sectional with control study appraised as weak quality found no relationship between individuals with allergy to mercury or nickel and presence of oral lichenoid lesions in direct contact with amalgam restoration.²²³ In this study, only 29% of patch tested individuals with oral lichenoid lesions tested positive for allergy to thimerosal (organic component of mercury) and/or nickel. A weak quality retrospective records review reported no significant difference in blood/urine mercury levels in those allergic to mercury compared to those without mercury allergy.²¹² In addition, one prospective cohort with control groups appraised as moderate quality found no change in non-specified allergy symptoms (as measured on the Munich Amalgam Scale) among study participants who had **amalgam fillings removed** at one-year follow-up.²¹⁰

Four studies only reported rates of allergy to mercury or amalgam materials; one retrospective cohort study with before/after comparison appraised as weak quality reported that 68% of participants with oral lichenoid lesions had a negative patch test reaction to mercury.²²⁹ Another moderate quality study of the same design, reported that 83% of patients with oral lichen planus and 58% of patients with lichenoid contact reactions were allergic to mercury. **Amalgam filling removal** only resulted in remission of oral symptoms for lichenoid contact reactions group (See *Oral health* section below).²³¹ One weak quality controlled retrospective cohort study reported that 80% of individuals with oral lichenoid reactions showed sensitisation to inorganic mercury or amalgam.²³⁸ Finally, a retrospective observational study with case control appraised as moderate quality, reported rates of allergy to ammoniated mercury (1%), amalgam and amalgam alloying metal (20%) as 27%, 23.5% and 3.5% respectively among individuals with oral lichenoid reaction.²⁴²

Summary: Amalgam only health impact evidence (patients) – Allergy

Eleven studies appraised the relationship between presence of oral health symptoms and allergy to amalgam or mercury, with six of these studies appraised as weak quality.^{195, 210, 212, 213, 223, 229, 231, 238, 239, 242, 249} Findings from studies evaluating the association between allergy to amalgam/mercury and oral health symptoms varied, with two studies indicating a significant association between oral symptoms and mercury allergy.^{195, 213} and four studies reporting no significant relationship between amalgam,^{239, 249} or mercury allergy and oral health symptoms.^{212, 239, 249} Rates of allergy to mercury and/or amalgam

varied widely between studies conducted with individuals with oral lichenoid lesions, oral lichenoid reactions and oral lichen planus, possibly reflecting the heterogeneity in symptom aetiology, populations and methods used alongside the overall weak quality of evidence within this category.

Cardiovascular Disease

Four studies examined the relationship between **amalgam restorations in situ** and cardiovascular outcomes; two studies by the same author using similar methods (both longitudinal and cross-sectional with control group) were appraised as moderate quality;^{240, 241} one retrospective records review,²¹² and one retrospective analysis of RCT and record data appraised as weak quality.²⁵¹ Two additional studies evaluated the impact of the **removal/replacement of amalgam restorations** on cardiovascular outcomes, one weak quality controlled before and after study,⁶⁵ one moderate quality prospective cohort with control group.²¹⁰ [See Supplementary Materials E, Tables 24 and 25 for detail on study findings].

In the two related studies of moderate quality examining the **impact of amalgam restorations in situ** on patients neuropsychological scores, patients with health complaints attributed to amalgam reported a significantly higher number of cardiovascular complaints compared to the group with no health complaints attributed to amalgam in one study,²⁴¹ as well as a higher number of oedema (legs) symptoms than the control group in another study, but not heart/chest symptoms.²⁴⁰ In contrast, the weak quality retrospective analysis found individuals who attributed health complaints to amalgam reported a significantly lower number of complaints relating to a “fluttering heart”, compared to those reported who attributed symptoms to environmental chemicals.²⁵¹

One retrospective records review appraised as weak quality found no significant difference in levels of blood or urinary mercury in people reporting cardiovascular symptoms compared to those who did not report such symptoms.²¹²

One controlled before and after study and one prospective cohort with control group found an inconsistent relationship between **removal/replacement of amalgam fillings** and resolution of cardiovascular symptoms. One study reported no significant change pre-treatment versus three-year follow-up,²²⁸ and one reported a significant reduction in cardiovascular complaints at one year follow-up for patients with medically unexplained physical symptoms attributed to amalgam, but not for patients with unexplained symptoms not attributed to amalgam or healthy controls.²¹⁰

Summary: Amalgam only health impact evidence (patients) – Cardiovascular disease

Six studies of variable quality examined the association between amalgam restorations in situ,^{212, 240, 241, 251} and removal/replacement of amalgam restorations and cardiovascular symptoms.^{210, 228} Three studies of weak to moderate quality using self-report measures of cardiovascular symptoms reported

variable findings regarding individuals who attributed health complaints to amalgam versus those who attributed health complaints to another cause or healthy controls.^{240, 241, 251} Studies using more objective measures of exposure reported cardiovascular symptoms were not associated with urinary or blood mercury levels,²¹² and inconsistent findings relating to improvement of cardiovascular symptoms following amalgam removal/replacement.^{210, 228} Overall, the variability in quality of the evidence and findings pertaining to relationship between cardiovascular outcomes and amalgam exposure prevents identification of firm conclusions.

Dermatological

Five studies examined the association between amalgam/mercury and dermatological health outcomes.^{210, 228, 240, 241, 251} In two related studies of moderate quality with similar populations and study design examining the **impact of amalgam restorations in situ** on patients neuropsychological scores, patients with health complaints attributed to amalgam reported a significantly higher number of dermatological symptoms compared to patients with no health complaints attributable to amalgam.^{240, 241} However, no statistically significant difference between number of skin reactions was reported by individuals attributing symptoms to amalgam restorations vs those reported by individuals who attributed symptoms to environmental chemicals by one weak quality study.²⁵¹

Two studies evaluating the **impact of amalgam removal/replacement** on dermatological symptoms.^{210, 228} One weak quality study reported no significant change from baseline to three year follow-up to general or facial skin problems.²²⁸ The other moderate quality study found a significant reduction in general skin problems at one but not five-year follow-up in a population who attributed their medically unexplained physical symptoms to amalgam,²¹⁰ a change which wasn't observed in the two control groups (patients with medically unexplained physical symptoms not attributed to amalgam or healthy controls).²¹⁰ However, regarding specific skin complaints, this study showed mixed effects within the amalgam cohort, with complaints of skin rash significantly reducing over time, but skin itching remaining unchanged. Details of specific findings from all studies evaluating dermatological symptoms potentially relating to amalgam restorations in patients can be found in Supplementary Materials E, Tables 26 and 27.

Summary: Amalgam only health impact evidence (patients) – Dermatological

Within the five studies evaluating the association between amalgam restorations and dermatological symptoms,^{210, 228, 240, 241, 251} findings were mixed. The heterogeneity of findings and weak-moderate quality of the studies overall prevents firm conclusions from being drawn.

Ear, Nose, Throat (ENT)

Five studies examined association between ENT symptoms and amalgam restorations.^{210, 228, 240, 241, 253}

In two related studies of moderate quality with similar populations and study design examining the **impact of amalgam restorations in situ** on patients neuropsychological scores, there was no significant difference in number of auditory symptoms compared to patients with no health complaints attributable to amalgam.^{240, 241}

Three studies evaluated the impact of **amalgam removal/replacement** on ENT symptoms: one controlled before and after study appraised as weak quality,⁶⁵ one retrospective cohort,²⁵³ and one prospective cohort with control, were appraised as moderate quality.²¹⁰ Within group analysis in one study showed no significant changes in auditory symptoms following amalgam removal for patients who attributed their medically unexplained physical symptoms to amalgam restorations.²¹⁰ The same study also showed no significant change for self-reported ENT symptoms which contrasts with findings from a “Low” quality controlled before and after study,²²⁸ and moderate quality retrospective cohort study,²⁵³ both of which reported significant improvement in ENT symptoms following amalgam removal. However, the significance level used for the finding reported in the latter study was set at $p \leq .1$, a higher threshold than typically used when accepting statistical significance. This study also reports that the odds ratio of treatment group patient experiencing symptom worsening at one year follow-up compared to non-treatment group was significant at $p < 0.05$ level.²⁵³ Specific findings from all studies evaluating ENT symptoms potentially relating to amalgam restorations in patients can be found in Supplementary Materials E, Tables 28 and 29.

Summary: Amalgam only health impact evidence (patients) – ENT

Overall, the five studies supporting this category indicate that there is no consistent evidence to support a significant association between amalgam removal and reduction in auditory or other ENT symptoms.^{210, 228, 240, 241, 253} Whilst two studies report some patients experience a reduction in ENT symptoms following amalgam removal,^{228, 253} the low study quality and/or high threshold used to determine statistical significance reduces confidence in their findings.

Gastrointestinal

Seven studies examined the relationship between amalgam restorations and patient gastrointestinal symptoms.^{201, 210, 228, 240, 241, 251, 253} In two related studies of moderate quality with similar populations and study design and examining the impact of **amalgam restorations in situ** on patients GI symptoms, there was a significantly higher number of gastrointestinal symptoms in patients with health complaints attributed to amalgam compared to patients with no health complaints attributable to amalgam.^{240, 241} However, findings from one weak quality study reported no difference between individuals attributing symptoms to amalgam restorations versus those who attributed symptoms to

environmental chemicals on item “frequent toilet urge”, but a significant difference between groups with regards to “vomiting”.²⁵¹

Four studies evaluated the impact of amalgam removal on patient gastrointestinal systems, three used a longitudinal design with pre-post element, two of which were appraised by reviewers as being weak quality,^{201, 228} and the other, alongside one retrospective cohort, were appraised as moderate quality.^{210, 253} Two studies highlighted significant reduction in gastrointestinal symptoms following amalgam removal.^{201, 228} However, one study highlighted that symptoms scores were still higher in the amalgam removal group than reference group at three year follow-up.²²⁸ One study showed mixed outcomes for different gastrointestinal symptoms as measured on a questionnaire of general health complaints including vomiting and constipation using the Munich Amalgam scale. It showed no significant reduction at follow-up compared to baseline but diarrhoea, urge to toilet and abdominal pain showed significant improvement at follow-up versus baseline post amalgam removal.²¹⁰ The other moderate quality study showed statistically significant odds ratio for patients experiencing both an improvement and worsening of stomach problems when compared to non-treatment group.²⁵³ Findings from all studies evaluating gastrointestinal outcomes potentially relating to amalgam restorations in patients can be found in Supplementary Materials E, Tables 30 and 31

[Summary: Amalgam only health impact evidence \(patients\) – Gastrointestinal](#)

The seven studies contributing to the evidence base in this category were mostly of mixed moderate to weak quality.^{201, 210, 228, 240, 241, 251, 253} There appears to be some weak evidence to support the association between amalgam restorations and the occurrence and resolution of gastrointestinal symptoms, although findings vary according to specific outcome of interest and may be outweighed by findings from a moderate quality study which indicates patients may experience both improvement and worsening of stomach symptoms.²⁵³

[General physical health](#)

Four studies examined the relationship between exposure to **amalgam restorations in situ** and general physical health symptoms: one weak quality retrospective record review,²¹² one study appraised as weak quality based on retrospective analysis of RCT data and historical records,²⁵¹ and two longitudinal studies with cross-sectional/control group component appraised as moderate quality from the same author.^{240, 241} Details of the specific findings in this category can be found in Supplementary Tables E, Tables 32 and 33.

On overall numbers of general health symptoms reported, two studies appraised as moderate quality based on similar populations and study design found that participants who attributed medically unexplained physical symptoms to amalgam, reported a significantly higher number of symptoms than

those who did not attribute symptoms to amalgam.^{240, 241} One of these studies reported specific symptoms which were significantly higher in participant groups attributing complaints to amalgam, including: dizziness, loss of appetite and tiredness/sleeplessness/loss of energy.²⁴⁰ In contrast, another weak quality retrospective analysis of RCT and historical record data stated that patients who attributed symptoms of fatigue, sweating, dizziness, appetite loss to amalgam reported statistically fewer symptoms than patients attributing symptoms to other causes.²⁵¹ This study also reported that headache symptoms were significantly lower in group attributing complaints to amalgam, whilst there was no difference between groups for number of individuals reporting sweating symptoms.²⁵¹ The difference in findings between these studies could possibly be attributed to the different control groups used in each study; one group had physical symptoms attributed to causes other than amalgam,²⁵¹ and the other control group were described as having no physical health symptoms attributed to amalgam.²⁴⁰

One study appraised as weak quality found no significant difference in blood/urine mercury exposure in those reporting health complaints compared to those who did not.²¹²

Six studies (10 articles) examined the impact of **amalgam removal** on general health symptoms.^{199-201, 210, 211, 228, 232, 237, 250, 253} Two studies (four articles) were appraised as moderate quality,^{199, 200, 210, 253} with the remainder appraised as weak.

In terms of overall health complaints, two studies with the same lead author, one of moderate and one of weak quality, reported a significant reduction of physical health complaints over time at 12-months,^{199, 200} and five-years post-amalgam removal.²⁰¹ Health symptoms were measured by the General Health Complaints index, in groups with physical health complaints attributed to amalgam and these changes which were not observed in comparison groups.^{199, 200} Another sister article appraised as weak quality, reported a significant reduction in health symptoms on a general index following amalgam removal in the treatment group, but a reduction was not observed in the control group, with changes in scores pre to three-years post-treatment being significantly different between the two groups.²¹¹ In contrast, an RCT and retrospective data analysis appraised as weak quality, found no significant difference between groups in change in total symptom score between baseline and 12 months follow-up.^{232, 250}

Two studies used the SF-36 physical component to measure general physical health.^{72, 200, 250} One moderate quality longitudinal with pre-post control study reported a significant improvement in physical health symptoms from baseline to 12-month follow-up post amalgam removal, where control groups showed no significant change from baseline.²⁰⁰ In contrast, an RCT and retrospective data analysis appraised as weak quality respectively, found no significant differences between intervention

and control groups in the size of difference in SF-36 scores between baseline and 12-month follow-up, although physical health symptoms decreased over time in all groups.^{232, 250} Another controlled before and after study appraised as weak quality which used the SF-36, reported no significant differences between replacement and non-replacement groups with respect to scores on the physical health component score (PCS), although study participants did score significantly lower on health-related quality of life, with a higher number receiving disability pensions, than the general population (23% and 10%, respectively).²³⁷ This study found that a significantly higher proportion of individuals who had their amalgam removed, reported improved health ratings over time compared to non-removal group at both two and three years post-application for removal.

Regarding specific health symptoms, one study appraised as moderate quality reported that 14 of the 23 symptoms evaluated significantly reduced at one year follow-up following amalgam removal, with symptoms for all except one item reduced against baseline at five year follow-up.²¹⁰ No change was observed in either of the control groups when the same outcome measure was used for all groups at follow up. For further detail see Supplementary Materials E, Table 33.

Two studies, one appraised as weak,²²⁸ the other as moderate quality,²¹⁰ examined the association between **amalgam removal** and dizziness, both reporting no significant change of dizziness pre-treatment versus follow-up.

Three studies examined the association between **amalgam removal** and fatigue and headache symptoms.^{210, 228, 253} One study reported a significant reduction in fatigue symptoms in the group where amalgam was removed on General Health Complaints questionnaire at one and five years follow-up, which was not replicated in the two control groups.²¹⁰ However, this significant reduction for the intervention group was not found in a within-group analysis using the Munich Amalgam Scale²¹⁰. One other study reported a reduction in fatigue symptoms from pre-treatment to three year follow-up following amalgam removal,²²⁸ whilst the final study reports that reduction in fatigue symptoms in comparison to non-treatment group was only significant at $p < .1$ level.²⁵³ Only one study reported a significant reduction in headache symptoms at five year follow-up only, not at one-year, for people with medically unexplained physical symptoms attributed to amalgam, whilst change in headache symptoms across one and five year follow-ups for individuals in control groups was not significant.²¹⁰ Two studies found no statistically significant change in headache symptoms in within,²²⁸ and between group analyses.²⁵³

One prospective cohort with control group study, appraised as moderate quality, singularly evaluated the impact of **amalgam removal** on the following health outcomes: trembling, sleeplessness, tiredness, susceptibility to infection, loss of appetite, headaches, coughing, hair loss, sweating and

sensitivity to cold, finding a significant reduction in symptoms only for the outcome “sensitivity to cold” post amalgam removal.²¹⁰

Two weak quality studies explored the relationship between mercury exposure and symptoms scores. One study reported larger reductions in mercury level in erythrocytes, blood plasma and urine after an intervention.²⁵⁰ However, the other study found no significant relationship between reduction in serum Hg levels and reduction in general health symptoms.²¹¹ This may potentially reflect differences in methods and outcome measures used.

Summary: Amalgam only health impact evidence (patients) – General physical health

Four studies of variable quality examined the relationship between exposure to amalgam and general physical health symptoms.^{212, 240, 241, 251} Findings comparing levels of general health symptoms between individuals who attributed their health complaints to amalgam compared to those who did not were inconsistent. The relationship between objective measures of mercury exposure measured by blood or urine analysis and general health symptoms were similarly inconsistent and based on evidence of weak to moderate quality, with two studies reporting no significant association,^{211, 212} although one weak quality study reported larger reductions in mercury level in erythrocytes, blood plasma and urine following amalgam removal being associated with larger decreases in symptoms score.²⁵⁰

Six studies (ten articles), the majority of which were appraised as weak quality, examined the impact of amalgam removal on general health symptoms.^{199-201, 210, 211, 228, 232, 237, 250, 253} Evidence from two studies (four articles) by the same authors indicates that amalgam removal is associated with improved scores on measures of overall general physical health symptoms at various time points from 12 months to five years follow-up post removal compared to control groups.^{199-201, 211} However, these findings are inconsistent with two other weak quality studies which used a different outcome measure,^{232, 237, 250} and may also have been influenced by the shorter follow-up period of 12-months in one of these studies.^{232, 250} Fatigue and headache symptoms were the most commonly evaluated specific symptoms, although findings for both outcomes were inconsistent, reflecting the use of different outcome measures and follow-up periods across different studies.^{210, 228, 253}

Immune Function

Three studies (four articles) examined the relationship between **amalgam restorations in situ** and patient immune function.^{187, 192, 204, 212} One study was appraised as weak quality,²¹² and the other studies (including two articles from the NECAT) were appraised as strong quality.^{187, 192, 204}

Two studies used diagnosis of specific autoimmune disease as outcome of interest. One strong quality study reported no association between number of amalgam restorations and risk of primary Sjögren’s syndrome,²⁰⁴ and another study appraised as weak quality found no association between blood

mercury level and diagnosis of autoimmune disease, although significantly more amalgams in subjects reporting autoimmune disease versus those who did not, with AI disease more common in in groups with over ten amalgam restorations.²¹²

Two strong quality articles representing secondary analysis of data from the NECAT examined association between specific blood chemistry measures and amalgam restorations at five year follow up,¹⁸⁷ or urinary mercury levels over follow up periods of six-, 12- and 60-months.¹⁹² One article found no association between the use of amalgam restorations on **primary** teeth and blood immune function measures (see Supplementary Materials E, Table 34).¹⁸⁷ This finding was replicated with number of amalgam restorations on **permanent** teeth, aside from a significant association between number of amalgams and lymphocyte function (B-cell: %CD69+PWM & % CD23+PWM).¹⁸⁷ Both articles reported non-significant associations between number of amalgam restorations,¹⁸⁷ or urinary mercury excretion,¹⁹² and the following immune function outcomes: monocytes, neutrophils, responsiveness of T-cells (CD25) and B-cell (%CD69_PWM, CD23+PWM).

Four controlled before and after studies examined the relationship between **amalgam removal/replacement** and immune function outcomes: one appraised as moderate quality,¹⁹⁷ and three appraised as weak quality^{77, 215, 238} (see Supplementary Materials E, Table 35).

Between group analysis in one study found no significant differences in levels of cytokines in serum over time between patients with physical health complaints attributed to amalgam before amalgam removal and 3 months and 1 year after amalgam removal, compared with data for a reference group.¹⁹⁷ However, this study indicated that select measures of cytokines (see Supplementary Materials E, Table 25) were found to be significantly higher than the reference group at baseline, with within-group analysis indicating significant reduction in levels of three blood cytokine outcomes (GM-CSF, IL-7, IL-8) following amalgam removal in the patient group.¹⁹⁷ One weak quality controlled before and after study reported a significant reduction in IL-6 and IL-18 cytokine markers following amalgam removal in patients with oral lichenoid reactions, whereas before and after measures in a health control group did not differ significantly.²³⁸ Another controlled before and after study, appraised as weak quality, demonstrated mixed findings, with a significant *reduction* in white blood cell count, neutrophil count, basophil count and lymphocyte count, and a significant *increase* in blood eosinophil and monocyte counts.²¹⁵ Finally, one weak quality study reported that a significantly higher proportion of the amalgam replacement group reported susceptibility to infection versus the non-replacement group.²³⁷

Summary: Amalgam only health impact evidence (patients) – Immune function

Three studies (four articles) examined the relationship between **amalgam restorations in situ** and patient immune function.^{187, 192, 204, 212} Two studies were strong quality,^{187, 204} the other as weak.²¹²

Overall, evidence indicated no statistically significant association between amalgam exposure, as measured by number of amalgams, and various indicators of immune function which included diagnosis of primary Sjögren's syndrome,²⁰⁴ and an array of blood chemistry variables in children with amalgams on primary teeth.¹⁸⁷ This finding was replicated with number of amalgam restorations on permanent teeth, aside from a significant association between number of amalgams and lymphocyte function.¹⁸⁷ Both articles reported non-significant associations between number of amalgam restorations and the following immune function outcomes: monocytes, neutrophils, responsiveness of t-cells (CD25) and B-cell (%CD69_PWM, CD23+PWM).^{187, 192} One article reported a significant association between number of amalgams on permanent teeth and lymphocyte function (B-cell: %CD69+PWM & % CD23+PWM).¹⁸⁷

Four controlled before and after studies examined the relationship between **amalgam removal/replacement** and immune function outcomes: one appraised as moderate quality,¹⁹⁷ and three appraised as weak quality.^{215, 237, 238} Generally, studies demonstrated a significant improvement in immune function markers in individuals who had their amalgam removed in comparison to control groups where baseline measures were not statistically different between groups,^{215, 238} although one weak quality study indicated that self-reported susceptibility to infection was higher in patients who had amalgams removed versus those who did not.²³⁷

Musculoskeletal

Four studies examined the relationship between amalgam/mercury exposure (n=1),²¹² or amalgam exposure (n=3).^{240, 241, 251} Two appraised as weak quality,^{212, 251} and two by the same author as moderate quality,^{240, 241} Two studies which examined frequency of self-reported symptoms between individuals with health complaints **attributed to amalgam in situ** compared to either a group with no health complaints attributed to amalgam, noted that patient groups reported significantly more musculoskeletal symptoms than the control groups.^{240, 241} In contrast, patients in one weak quality study who attributed health complaints to amalgam reported fewer symptoms.²⁵¹ (See Supplementary Materials E, Table 36) One weak quality study based on retrospective record review reported no significant difference in blood or urinary mercury levels between those experiencing musculoskeletal complaints and those that did not.²¹²

Five studies examined the impact of **amalgam removal/replacement** on patient musculoskeletal symptoms.^{201, 210, 228, 237, 253} Two were appraised as moderate quality,^{210, 253} with the remainder appraised as weak quality. Four studies, whilst using different outcome measures, reported significant reductions in musculoskeletal symptoms in treatment groups following amalgam removal.^{25, 210, 228, 253} One study reported that this reduction in symptoms was not seen in a control group with medically unexplained physical symptoms not attributed to amalgam or a healthy control group,²¹⁰ with another

study reporting significantly higher reports of musculoskeletal symptoms in a reference group compared to a treatment group at three-year follow-up (see Supplementary Materials E, Table 37).²²⁸ One weak quality study reported a higher number of individuals experiencing joint/muscle pain within the amalgam replacement group.²³⁷

Summary: Amalgam only health impact evidence (patients) – Musculoskeletal

Overall, the findings suggest an association of higher number of musculoskeletal symptoms with increased amalgam exposure and suggest a reduction in symptoms after removal. Self-reported musculoskeletal symptoms were higher in individuals attributing health complaints to amalgam restorations compared to control groups in three out of four studies of variable quality which examined the relationship between amalgam/mercury exposure (n=1),²¹² or amalgam exposure (n=3),^{240, 241} and musculoskeletal symptoms. However one weak quality study found a lower number of symptoms within the patient group compared to a control group who attributed their symptoms to environmental causes.²⁵¹ Another weak quality study found no significant difference in blood or urinary mercury levels between those experiencing musculoskeletal complaints and those that did not.²¹² Four of five studies reported significant reductions on different measures of musculoskeletal symptoms in the treatment group following amalgam removal compared to non-removal group,^{201, 210, 228, 253} however, three of the four studies were appraised as weak quality, so confidence in the finding is limited.

Neurological

Five retrospective observational studies explored the potential association between blood/urinary mercury levels,²¹² or **amalgam restorations in situ** and patient neurological symptoms.^{205, 221, 244, 245} All were appraised as strong quality, except for one appraised as weak quality.²¹² Levels of blood and urinary mercury,²¹² and number of amalgam restorations was found to be unrelated to symptoms of Multiple Sclerosis,²⁴⁵ or essential tremor.²⁴⁴ Findings were mixed with regard to Parkinson's Disease, with one strong quality study concluding that Parkinson's Disease diagnosis was unrelated to number of amalgam restorations,²⁰⁵ with another strong quality study reporting that overall incidence of the disease was higher in individuals with amalgam restorations versus those without,²²¹ with the effect remaining once individuals with diabetes were removed from analysis, and similar results found in patients without other comorbidities as listed in Supplementary Materials E, Table 38.

One retrospective cohort study, appraised as moderate quality, indicated that odds of individuals in the treatment group experiencing worsening symptoms of 'shakiness in hands' at one-year post-amalgam removal, were significant when compared to positive amalgam group, but no significant worsening or improvements when compared with positive amalgam group for paraesthesia.²⁵³

Summary: Amalgam only health impact evidence (patients) – Neurological

Findings in the six studies examining the relationship between amalgam restorations in situ and patient neurological outcomes, the majority of which were appraised as strong quality, varied across the specific outcomes measured. Specific outcomes where no association with amalgam was reported included multiple sclerosis,^{212, 245} essential tremor,²⁴⁴ and paraesthesia.²⁵³ Findings for Parkinsons Disease varied between studies, with one retrospective cohort study reporting incidence was higher in individuals with amalgam restorations,²²¹ and the other finding no significant association.²⁰⁵ One study found worsening of hand-shakiness following amalgam removal.²⁵³

Neuropsychological

Four studies (six articles) examined association between presence of **amalgam restorations in situ** and patient neuropsychological symptoms. One study appraised as moderate quality,²⁴¹ three articles appraised as strong quality related to NECAT,^{178, 196, 259} and a retrospective analysis of data from an RCT and historical records appraised as weak quality.²⁵¹ None of these studies found any significant association between neuropsychological symptoms and amalgam, where amalgam exposure was established via surface years¹⁹⁶, urinary mercury excretion,¹⁹⁶ posterior occlusal surface years,²⁵⁹ or exploring different test performance of individuals with health complaints attributed to amalgam versus those with no health complaints attributed to amalgam.^{241, 251} One study found a significantly higher neuropsychological self-reported symptom score in individuals with health complaints attributed to amalgam,²⁴¹ and one study found increased exposure to amalgam was associated with higher scores on picture and number-letter memory of the WRAML and letter fluency tasks (see Supplementary Materials E, Table 39).¹⁷⁸ Another retrospective observational study appraised as strong quality found no correlation between dementia development and number of amalgams.²³³

Four studies used patient self-report measures to examine the neuropsychological impact of **amalgam removal** on patients.^{201, 210, 228, 253} Two appraised as moderate quality,^{210, 253} and the remaining studies as weak.^{201, 228}

Four studies evaluated impact of amalgam removal and memory.^{201, 210, 228, 253} Three studies, one pre and post analysis,²⁰¹ one prospective cohort with control,²¹⁰ and one retrospective cohort study reported significant improvement in memory at one,^{210, 253} and five-,^{201, 210} year follow-up, although this affect wasn't present on a second measure of memory function in the latter study.²¹⁰ One controlled before and after study appraised as weak quality found no significant difference in reported memory complaints in a within-group analysis at three-year follow-up.²²⁸ Three of these studies also found amalgam removal was associated with an improvement in concentration compared to controls.^{201, 210, 228} Neuropsychological outcomes appraised in single studies included reaction time (no significant change following amalgam removal),²¹⁰ coordination and confusion (significant worsening

of symptoms following amalgam removal for coordination only) and dropping things (no significant change following amalgam removal)(see Supplementary Materials E, Table 40).²⁵³

Summary: Amalgam only health impact evidence (patients) – Neuropsychological

None of the four variable quality studies (five articles) evaluating the relationship between amalgam restorations in situ and neuropsychological test performance found any significant association between the two variables,^{178, 196, 233, 241, 251, 258} aside from one strong quality study where increased amalgam exposure was associated with higher scores on memory and letter fluency tasks.¹⁹⁶

Five studies, three of moderate quality,^{210, 241, 253} and two of weak quality examined the relationship between amalgam removal/replacement and neuropsychological symptoms.^{201, 228} Self-reported non-specified neuropsychological symptoms were significantly higher in individuals who attributed health difficulties to amalgam rather than other causes.²⁴¹ Findings for specific self-reported memory difficulties varied across studies and different outcome measures,^{201, 210, 228, 253} whilst self-report measures indicated amalgam removal was associated with improved concentration in three studies.^{201, 210, 228}

Due to the bias inherent in self-report measures and moderate-weak quality of the studies evaluating the impact of amalgam removal/replacement on neuropsychological symptoms, it can be concluded that there is currently no evidence to indicate a link between amalgam restorations and neuropsychological test performance.

Oral health

Seven studies explored relationship of patients with **amalgam restorations in situ** and oral health outcomes.^{190, 195, 207, 212, 230, 239, 251} one was appraised as strong quality,²³⁰ one appraised as moderate quality,¹⁹⁰ and five as weak quality (See Supplementary Materials E, Table 41).^{195, 207, 212, 239, 251}

Five studies explored the association between amalgam restorations in situ and oral disease.^{190, 195, 207, 230, 239} Three studies appraised as weak quality examined association between amalgam exposure and diagnosis of oral lichenoid lesions,^{195, 239} or mucosal lesions.²⁰⁷ The occurrence of an oral lichenoid lesions related to an amalgam restoration was reported narratively in one study,²³⁹ the other reports that 95.9% of patients with oral lichenoid lesions had amalgam adjacent to a lesion, with mean number of amalgams being significantly higher in patients with oral lichenoid lesions compared to dermatitis patients.¹⁹⁵ One strong quality study calculated the odds ratio comparing oral lichen planus participants with controls without oral lichen planus, stratified with the number of times amalgam restorations had been received.²³⁰ This study reported no association between amalgam and oral lichen planus.²³⁰ These findings were supported by a weak quality study which reported that the degree of association between mucosal lesions and amalgam did not differentiate between

presentation or clinical forms of oral lichen planus.²⁰⁷ One moderate quality study found no association between amalgam restorations and pupal disease.¹⁹⁰

One weak quality study based upon retrospective analysis of RCT/record data reported a significantly higher number of the oral symptoms “metallic taste” and “mouth dryness” among individuals with health complaints attributed to amalgam compared to those with health complaints attributed to environmental chemicals.²⁵¹ A significantly higher blood mercury level was found in participants reporting oral cavity complaints (type not specified) compared to those who did not in one retrospective records review also appraised as Weak quality.²¹²

Six studies appraised the association between **removal/replacement of amalgam restorations** and patient oral health symptoms.^{223, 229, 231, 234, 238, 242} Two studies were appraised by reviewers as moderate quality,^{231, 242} with the remainder appraised as weak (see Supplementary Materials E, Table 42). Three studies, one moderate quality,²³¹ two weak,^{223, 234} reported that **removal/replacement of amalgam** reduced oral lichenoid lesion symptoms. In one study, 71% of patients experienced symptom improvement at three month follow-up, with all lesions disappearing in all except one case by six month (although residual papules persisted in all other cases).²²³ One study reported impact of amalgam removal on oral lichenoid lesion symptoms according to whether patients had positive patch test to mercury.²²⁹ Of the patients with a positive patch test who had amalgam fillings removed, 75 percent reported complete resolution of oral lichenoid lesion symptoms compared to five percent complete resolution among those with a negative patch test and one patient whose symptoms resolved without amalgam removal. Partial resolution of symptoms was seen in 25% of positive patch test patients compared to 50% negative patch test patients who had amalgam removed and 7% of negative patch test patients who did not have amalgam removed. Thirty-three percent of patients with a negative patch test who had amalgams removed had unchanged symptoms, whilst fifty-percent of individuals with a negative patch test who didn't have amalgams removed had unchanged oral lichenoid lesion symptoms.²²⁹

One study appraised as weak quality examined clinical versus histological healing following amalgam removal in oral lichenoid lesion and oral lichen planus patients. Significantly higher levels of clinical healing (total regression of symptoms) observed in oral lichenoid lesion compared to oral lichen planus patients at three months post amalgam removal. However, there was no significant difference between the two groups regarding histological healing. Patients with a positive patch test for mercury were significantly more likely to demonstrate clinical healing than those with a negative patch test, although this difference only remained significant for patients with oral lichenoid lesion symptoms. Patients were also significantly more likely to show histological healing if their patch test for mercury was positive. Oral lichenoid lesion patients, who demonstrated a combination of positive patch test

and oral lichenoid lesion in strict contact with amalgam were significantly more likely to heal than all other patients. There was also a significant relationship in clinically healed oral lichenoid lesion patients between positive patch test and histological healing, but no relationship in clinically healed patients between histological healing and lesion proximity to amalgam restoration.²³⁴

Two studies appraised as moderate quality examined effect of amalgam removal on oral lichenoid reaction symptoms.^{238, 242} One study demonstrated that complete healing following full replacement of amalgam fillings was the major significant outcome among oral lichenoid reaction patients, compared to partial or no improvement.²³⁸ The other study indicated that oral lichenoid reaction symptoms were significantly more likely to resolve following amalgam removal versus those with no amalgam replacement in patients with a positive patch test reaction to an amalgam related allergen, but this relationship was not observed amongst individuals with a negative patch test.²⁴²

One study reported impact of amalgam removal on oral lichen planus symptoms and lichenoid contact reactions.²³¹ All seven patients with lichenoid contact reaction and positive reaction to mercury patch test showed lesion regression after total amalgam replacement, but this effect not seen in patients with oral lichen planus.²³¹

Summary: Amalgam only health impact evidence (patients) – Oral health

Seven studies of variable quality evaluated the association between **amalgam exposure**,^{190, 195, 207, 230, 239, 251} or blood mercury level and oral disease or symptoms.²¹² Measures of outcomes of interest, which included occurrence of oral lichenoid lesion, oral lichen planus and “metallic taste/mouth dryness”, and measures of amalgam exposure were heterogeneous, which likely contributed to inconsistent findings reported across different studies.

Six studies appraised the association between **removal/replacement of amalgam** restorations and patient oral health symptoms. Four studies, one moderate quality,²³¹ three weak,^{223, 229, 234} reported that removal/replacement of amalgam reduced oral lichenoid lesion symptoms, although one of these reported this affect for clinical not histological healing,²³⁴ with two studies indicated that patients with an allergy to mercury were more likely to experience healing following amalgam removal alone,²²⁹ or in combination with the oral lichenoid lesion being in strict contact with amalgam filling.²³⁴

These findings were mirrored in patients with oral lichenoid reaction, with complete resolution being the most common outcome in two studies,^{231, 238} especially when patients were allergic to mercury.²⁴² No significant impact was shown by one study of amalgam removal for individuals with oral lichen planus symptoms,²³¹ which aligns with findings from one strong quality study reporting that amalgam restorations were not associated with altered odds of oral lichen planus.²³⁰

Whilst the variable quality of evidence supporting this category limits confidence in the findings, evidence indicates that amalgam removal may support resolution of oral lichenoid lesion/reaction symptoms where amalgam is in close contact with lesions and individuals have a positive mercury patch test. A limited quantity of evidence available from two studies also suggests that amalgam restorations may not be associated with oral lichen planus.

Orofacial

Four studies (five articles) three appraised as weak quality,^{201, 211, 228, 237} one as moderate,²¹⁰ examined impact of **amalgam removal** on orofacial symptoms (see Supplementary Materials E, Table 43).

One study appraised as weak quality reported no significant difference in oral symptoms, which included dry mouth, jaw fatigue, pain in jaws and tenderness of teeth, in individuals with oral lichenoid reactions between amalgam removal and non-removal groups.²³⁷

Of the studies which reported on individual symptom differences between the two groups, “Burning sensation” was evaluated by all three. Two-studies appraised as weak quality reported a non-significant relationship between amalgam removal and symptom impact,^{25, 228} whilst the third moderate quality study reported a significant improvement in symptoms at one- and five-year follow-up in individuals with physical complaints attributable to amalgam, but not in healthy controls.²¹⁰ Orofacial pain/tenderness was reported in three studies, all of which reported a non-significant relationship between amalgam removal and outcome at follow-up.^{201, 210, 228} Two of the same studies also reported non-significant relationship between amalgam removal and stiffness/paraesthesia, pain in temporomandibular joints, facial skin problems,^{201, 228} with the other reporting significant improvements for all three symptoms at one year follow-up in individuals with health complaints attributed to amalgam, but not in healthy controls.²¹⁰ This study reported significant reduction in symptoms at five-year follow-up for stiffness/paraesthesia and facial skin problems, but not temporomandibular joint pain at five-year follow-up. Taste disturbance was evaluated in all three studies, two of which found significant reductions post-amalgam removal compared to pre-treatment,^{210, 228} with one reporting no significant change.²⁰¹ No significant change in symptoms of “dry mouth” following amalgam removal was reported by two studies,^{201, 228} whilst the third study reported a significant reduction at one and five year follow-up post intervention.²¹⁰ Two of the studies reported no significant impact on salivation,^{210, 228} whilst the third reported a significant reduction in salivation symptoms at five year follow-up.²⁰¹ Sinha et al (2024) found no significant difference at follow-up following amalgam removal for the following symptoms: bleeding gums, teeth grinding, loosening teeth and warned that some patients experienced oral ulcers as an adverse event following amalgam removal.²¹⁰

Summary: Amalgam only health impact evidence (patients) – Orofacial

The four studies of predominantly weak quality contributing to this category presented mixed findings with respect to the following specific symptoms: burning sensation, pain/tenderness, stiffness/paraesthesia, temporomandibular joint pain, facial skin problems, taste disturbance, dry mouth and salivation.

Psychosocial

Five studies examined the relationship between **amalgam restorations in situ** and psychological outcomes.^{209, 212, 240, 241, 251} Quality appraisal ratings were as follows: strong (n=1),²⁰⁹ moderate (n=2),^{240, 241} and weak.(n=2)^{212, 251}

The number of studies measuring the same psychosocial outcome were limited, and where this did occur the population groups and specific outcome measure used differed. Of the three studies measuring anxiety symptoms, one moderate quality study reported a significantly higher number of symptoms within subjects with health complaints attributed to amalgam than their matched controls,²⁴⁰ whereas the weak quality study found no significant difference in anxiety symptoms where population groups attributed symptoms to amalgam vs environmental chemicals.²⁵¹ Consistent with this latter finding, these strong quality article associated with the NECAT found no significant association between posterior occlusal surface years and anxiety symptoms.²⁰⁹ This pattern of findings was replicated for depression outcomes, with two moderate quality studies measuring frequency of symptoms between groups with health complaints attributed to amalgam versus not attributed to amalgam reporting significantly higher symptoms in the former group,^{240, 241} with one strong quality study finding no association between several different measures of depression symptoms and posterior-occlusal amalgam surface years,²⁰⁹ and one weak study finding no difference between groups where health symptoms were attributed to amalgam versus environmental chemicals. Another study appraised as weak quality reported no significant difference in blood/urinary mercury levels between individuals on a combined measure of anxiety and depression symptoms and those who did not.²¹²

Broad outcomes measured by only one study include behaviour,²⁰⁹ social wellbeing,²⁰⁹ loneliness,²⁴⁰ adjustment,²⁰⁹ emotional symptoms,²⁰⁹ and social wellbeing, the findings of which can be viewed in Supplementary Materials E, Table 44.²⁰⁹ None of these measures were found to be consistently associated with amalgam exposure, although there were three specific outcomes where significant associations between change scores and specific outcomes where amalgam was measured as posterior occlusal surface years: 10 surface years. These were delinquent behaviours and anxiety/depression as measured by the Children's Behaviour Checklist,²⁰⁹ and interpersonal relations as measured by the Behaviour Assessment System for Children-Revised.²⁰⁹ Caution is required when

interpreting these latter findings, as they represent only three of 24 outcomes from various time points evaluated in this study.

One study used the SCL-90-R to capture a variety of symptoms, including: somatization, obsessive compulsiveness, interpersonal sensitivity, depression, anxiety, hostility, phobic anxiety, paranoid ideation and psychosis, none of which were significantly different between groups with symptoms attributed to amalgam or environmental chemicals.²⁵¹

Six studies evaluated the association between **amalgam removal/replacement** and mental health symptoms.^{200, 201, 210, 228, 232, 237, 250, 253} All appraised by reviewers as being weak quality, aside from one prospective longitudinal study with a pre/post control appraised as moderate.²⁰⁰

Two studies used the SF-36: Mental Component Scores to evaluate the impact of amalgam removal on patient psychological symptoms.^{200, 232, 250} One was appraised as moderate quality,²⁰⁰ the other as weak.^{232, 250} One weak quality study used the SF-12 Mental Component Scores.²³⁷ All studies compared populations who had amalgam removed with populations who did not have amalgam removed and reported no significant association between amalgam removal and psychological symptoms, however one study did report significant improvement in physical and mental health symptoms between pre- and post-treatment for participants who had their amalgam fillings removed.²⁰⁰ One study reported that study participants had significantly lower scores on the MCS than corresponding age groups in the general population.

One study using RCT data appraised as weak quality used the SCL-90 Global Severity Index to evaluate psychological distress in individuals having amalgam restorations removed versus those who did not have amalgam removed,^{232, 250} reporting scores did not differ significantly between groups.^{232, 250}

Two studies evaluated the impact of amalgam removal/replacement on anxiety symptoms, both appraised as moderate quality.^{210, 253} One reported changes from pre to one year post amalgam removal were non-significant,²⁵³ with the other study reporting mixed findings depending on anxiety outcome of interest as measured by the Munich Amalgam Scale; with anxiety, worries and “stress at job” symptoms significantly improving,²¹⁰ but symptoms of “intense nervousness” not significantly different.²¹⁰

One moderate quality study reported depression outcomes as measured by the Munich Amalgam Scale.²¹⁰ Findings were mixed; with symptoms of sadness and depressed mood not significantly changing from baseline to follow-up, but symptoms of fluctuating mood and irritability significantly improving over time.²¹⁰ The other moderate quality study reported no significant odds of depression symptoms improving or worsening at one year post-amalgam removal.²⁵³

Two studies reported pooled anxiety/depression outcomes; with the moderate quality study reporting a significant reduction in symptoms at both one and five year follow-up in individuals with health complaints attributed to amalgam, but not in either control group (individuals with health complaints not attributed to amalgam/health controls).²¹⁰ The weak quality study reported no significant change from pre-treatment to three year follow-up in a within-group analysis.²²⁸

Details on the specific findings of these studies, including outcomes supported only by one study, can be viewed in Supplementary Materials E, Table 45.

Summary: Amalgam only health impact evidence (patients) – Psychosocial

Five studies of variable quality examined the relationship between **amalgam restorations in situ** and psychological outcomes.^{209, 212, 240, 241, 251} The number of studies measuring the same psychosocial outcome were limited, and where this did occur the population groups and specific outcome measure used differed. Only the two studies which compared anxiety and depression self-reported symptoms between patients with amalgam-attributed complaints and matched controls found a significant difference in symptom scores between groups.^{240, 241} Studies which compared amalgam treated groups with control groups with health complaints not attributed to amalgam,²⁵¹ or studies which explored how objective measures of amalgam or mercury exposure related to self-reported mental health symptoms, reported no consistent significant association.^{209, 212}

Six studies, four of which were appraised as weak quality and two as moderate, examined the association between **amalgam removal/replacement** and mental health symptoms.^{65, 200, 201, 210, 232, 237, 250, 253} Studies using global measures of psychological wellbeing (n=4) tended to report no significant difference between groups when comparing individuals who underwent amalgam removal with those who did not, although one study did demonstrate a significant improvement in symptoms following amalgam removal in a within-group analysis.²⁰⁰ Findings from three studies using a before-and-after design evaluating specific symptoms of anxiety and depression individually and pooled together varied across study and type of outcome measure used.²⁵³

Overall, the current evidence does not indicate an association between amalgam restorations and patient psychosocial outcomes, although the low-to-moderate quality of studies evaluating the impact of amalgam removal/replacement means this finding should be interpreted with caution.

Respiratory, urinary and visual/ocular

Overall, findings from the three studies examining the association between amalgam restorations and respiratory symptoms were mixed. Two studies by the same author, appraised as moderate quality, indicated individuals with health symptoms attributed to amalgam reported significantly higher number of respiratory and airway problems than those who had no health complaints attributed to

amalgam,^{240, 241} with one of these studies reporting non-significant differences for “shortness of breath” between the two groups.²⁴⁰ The other study, also appraised as moderate quality,²¹⁰ evaluating impact of amalgam removal in individuals with medically unexplained physical symptoms attributed to amalgam, found reported dyspnoea symptoms did not significantly change pre-post intervention.²¹⁰ [See Supplementary Materials E, Table 46]

Two of these studies reported that individuals with health symptoms attributed to amalgam did not have a significantly higher number of urinary symptoms than those who did not attribute health complaints to amalgam (See Supplementary Materials E, Table 47).^{240, 241}

Four studies studied the association between removal/replacement of amalgam restorations and visual/ocular outcomes. The above two moderate quality studies by the same author found a significantly higher number of visual problems in individuals with health complaints attributed to amalgam (See Supplementary Table E, Table 48).^{240, 241} The other two reported mixed findings, with both weak and moderate quality studies reporting no significant change in eye infection, visual disorder and intensity of visual disturbances from pretreatment to one,²¹⁰ or three year follow-up,²²⁸ but a significant reduction in visual disturbances on a different outcome questionnaire at one but not five year follow-up (see Supplementary Materials E, Table 49).²¹⁰

One weak quality controlled before and after study compared individuals who had their amalgams removed with those who did not for the following health impacts: low tolerance to environmental impacts and sensitivity to electric/magnetic fields, with only the latter differing significantly between groups following exclusion of subjects without approved applications for subsidized dental restoration replacement (n=81) and those in replacement group with approved applications who had not stated that they had proceeded with replacement of dental amalgam restorations (n=25).²³⁷

Other

Six studies examined the relationship between **amalgam restorations in-situ** and other health outcomes.^{202, 203, 216, 225, 252, 254} Quality scores included two appraised as strong quality,^{216, 252} and four as weak quality.^{121, 203, 225, 254} Each study contributed outcomes to one broad outcome category, including: Autism,²⁵² renal,²¹⁶ Oxidative stress,²⁰² Taurine levels (protective against oxidative stress),²⁰³ Gestational hypertension,²²⁵ and human health impact of exposure to mercury vapour from crematoriums (see Supplementary Materials E, Table 50).²⁵⁴ Heterogeneity of impacts measures precluded synthesis.

Four studies examined impact of **amalgam removal/replacement** on other health symptoms,^{210, 215, 225, 237} all were appraised as weak quality. Each study contributed outcomes to one broad outcome category including: Anthropomorphic,²¹⁰ Female health,²¹⁰ clinical blood chemistry variables,²¹⁵

maternal health,²²⁵ and tolerance to environmental factors or sensitivity to electric/magnetic fields (see Supplementary Materials E, Table 51).²³⁷

Summary: Amalgam only health impact evidence (patients)

Thirty-six studies (47 articles) evaluated the health impact of amalgam restorations and/or mercury exposure on the health of adults or children, with the quality of the studies fairly equally spread between weak, moderate and strong ratings. Overall, the heterogeneity in how amalgam exposure and health outcomes were measured and dominance of weak quality evidence within each broad outcome category prevented firm conclusions from being drawn regarding the impact of amalgam restorations on patient health. However, there appears to be tentative evidence that amalgam restorations on permanent teeth may have a detrimental influence on some blood chemistry markers of immune function, musculoskeletal symptoms, oral lichenoid lesions and oral lichenoid reaction symptoms, but is not associated with oral lichen planus symptoms or psychosocial difficulties, with no evidence to indicate a link between amalgam restorations and neuropsychological test performance. Further high-quality trials are needed to increase confidence in these findings.

Composite resin

Fifteen studies (19 articles) evaluated the health impact of patient exposure to composite resin restorations or methacrylate compounds on the health of adults or children.^{190, 192, 195, 207, 209, 213, 218, 230, 239, 242, 255-259, 261, 262} Quality appraisal scores were as follows: weak (n=8),^{195, 207, 239, 255, 257, 260-262} moderate (n=3),^{190, 242, 256} and strong (n=4).^{187, 192, 209, 213, 233, 258, 259} These studies are synthesised within the following broad outcome categories: allergy (n=4),^{195, 213, 239, 242} genotoxicity (n=3),^{255, 260, 261} immune function (n=1),^{187, 192} neuropsychological (n=2),^{233, 258, 259} oral health (n=5),^{190, 195, 207, 230, 257} psychosocial (n=1),^{209, 258} and other (n=3).^{187, 256, 262}

One moderate quality study appraised rates of sensitisation to methacrylates/acrylates in dental professionals.²¹⁸

Detail regarding findings for specific outcomes for each study within this section can be viewed in Supplementary Materials E, Tables 52-58.

Allergy

The content of this section also relates to the *Oral health* section below.

Three studies examined the relationship between composite resin or methacrylate compounds and patient allergy outcomes (see Supplementary Materials E, Table 52). Three studies examined allergy outcomes and potential relationship with composite resin; one retrospective review appraised as strong quality,²¹³ one retrospective case-control appraised as moderate quality,²⁴² and one cross-sectional study with control appraised as weak quality.¹⁹⁵ The study appraised as weak quality narratively compared the number of individuals with contact allergies to composite substances in patients with oral lichenoid lesions or dermatitis.¹⁹⁵ A higher number of contact allergies was observed in oral lichenoid lesions patients, with three of the eight patients with an allergy demonstrating oral lichenoid lesions adjacent to composite fillings and another three patients with oral lichenoid lesions and composite fillings in the same quadrant of the mouth.¹⁹⁵ However, no contact allergy to composite substances found in two oral lichenoid lesions patients with composite fillings but no amalgam adjacent to lichenoid lesions; indicating oral lichenoid lesions may not have been associated with composite restorations in the other patients.¹⁹⁵ This aligns with the findings of the second strong quality study, which found no significant difference between women with allergic stomatitis compared to women with noninflammatory oral complaints in the proportion allergic to epoxy and melamine formaldehyde resins.²¹³ The moderate quality study reported 0.9 percent of patients with oral lichenoid reactions were allergic to epoxy resin.²⁴²

Three studies examined allergy outcomes and potential relationships with methacrylates and/or acrylates. In these studies, the relationship between methacrylate substances and the restorative

material to which they were linked was not always clear. One of these was a retrospective review appraised as strong quality that compared rates of sensitisation between women with allergic stomatitis versus women with noninflammatory oral complaints.²¹³ One was a retrospective case control appraised as moderate quality which reports allergy to dental metals and synthetics in patients with oral lichenoid reactions.²⁴² The other was a cross-sectional study with control group appraised as weak quality which compares rates of allergy between those with atopic and non-atopic conditions, where atopic patients had at least two of the following: clinical history atopic dermatitis, allergic rhinitis, allergic asthma, or food allergies; each confirmed by prick test.²³⁹ Two studies that compared allergy rates between two population groups reported contradictory findings for the following methacrylates/acrylates: Ethylene glycol dimethacrylate (EGDMA),^{213, 239} Methyl methacrylate (MMA),^{213, 239} and 2-hydroxyethylmethacrylate (2-HEMA).^{213, 239} With all three methacrylates, one study found a significantly higher rate of sensitisation on the “allergy” group compared to controls,²¹³ whereas the other study found no significant difference between groups.²³⁹ Both of these studies found no significant difference in sensitization rates between the two groups for ethyl methacrylate and diurethane dimethacrylate.^{213, 239} One study found no difference between population groups for Bisphenol-A(BPA),²³⁹ Bisphenol-A Dimethacrylate (Bis-GMA),²³⁹ dimethyl toluidine,²³⁹ methyl acrylate,²¹³ tetrahydrofurfuryl methacrylate,²¹³ and 1-4-butanediol dimethacrylate (BUDMA).²¹³ One study reported women with allergic stomatitis were significantly more likely to experience sensitization to hydroxypropyl methacrylate (HMPA), and Pentaerythritol Tri Acrylate (PETA).²¹³

One study reporting patient rates of sensitisation to methacrylates is listed in Supplementary Materials E, Table 52,²⁴² alongside details of other allergies not clearly linked with dental materials reported within two studies.^{229, 242} Of note, one is moderate quality retrospective case-control study reporting rates of sensitisation to methacrylates/acrylates in dental professionals, see Supplementary Materials E, Table 16.²¹⁸

[Summary: Composite resin only health impact evidence \(patients\) /methacrylates/acrylate – Allergy](#)

Three studies examined allergy outcomes and potential relationship with composite resin among individuals with oral lichenoid lesions,¹⁹⁵ allergic stomatitis,²¹³ and oral lichenoid reactions, compared to control groups,²⁴² one appraised as strong quality,²¹³ one moderate,²⁴² and one as weak quality.¹⁹⁵ No clear association was found between allergy to composite materials and symptom characteristics, although differences between population characteristics made comparison across different studies difficult.

Two of the above studies,^{213, 242} and another weak quality study compared rates of allergy to methacrylates and/or acrylates between patients with oral health conditions and control populations.²³⁹ Results varied across different studies and according to type of methacrylate/acrylate

exposure, with the strongest/most consistent evidence available for ethyl methacrylate and diurethane dimethacrylate, where no significant difference in sensitization rate between population groups was found by two studies.^{213, 239} The following methacrylates were appraised by two studies which reported conflicting findings for each, with one study reporting significantly higher rates of sensitisation for the allergy group compared to controls,²¹³ whereas the other study found no significant difference between groups.²³⁹: Ethylene glycol dimethacrylate (EGDMA),^{213, 239} Methyl methacrylate (MMA),^{213, 239} and 2-hydroxyethylmethacrylate (2-HEMA).^{213, 239} The quantity of evidence evaluating allergy/sensitisation to other types of methacrylate/acrylates was extremely limited.

Genotoxicity

Three studies, one cross-sectional with control group,²⁶⁰ and two RCT's, all appraised as weak quality examined the impact of composite resins and/or compomers on genotoxicity outcomes.^{255, 261} The cross-sectional study found no significant difference between individuals with micro-hybrid/resin composite compared to those with no composite or amalgam restorations on the following outcomes: sister chromatid exchange (SCE), high frequency of SCE, chromosome aberration and proliferation rate index.²⁶⁰

One RCT compared genotoxicity outcomes for individuals with Kalore composite resin with those with flowable composite-Vertise flow.²⁶¹ Both tail length of DNA molecules in gingival cells and percentage of DNA tail in gingival cells were significantly higher than pre-treatment at 30- and 180-day follow-up. Exposure at 30 days was significantly higher than control and seven day exposures for tail length for the same group, with the highest values for both outcomes being measured at this timepoint.^{260, 261} Tail-length significantly impacted by time of exposure and smoking.²⁶¹ Percentage DNA in tail was significantly enhanced by exposure time, alcohol consumption and fruit consumption as individual variables. General linear regression model of age, gender, smoking alcohol, health, medication use, x-ray exposure and diet non-significant for both outcomes.²⁶¹ Between-group analysis indicated no significant differences for the following outcomes at same level of exposure: nuclear buds and karyolysis, but a significant difference for micronuclei frequency at seven and 30-day follow-up, where number of micronuclei was higher in the group receiving Kalore resin versus Vertise flow.²⁶¹

Two RCTs analysed within group differences for similar genotoxicity measures over time, although the resin composite/compomer being evaluated differed.²⁵⁵ One study demonstrated no significant changes over time for "Twinkly star" compomer for the following outcome measures: Micronuclei frequency, nucleoplasmic bridges, nuclear buds, pyknosis, condensed chromatin and karyorrhexis.²⁵⁵ This non-significant change over time for nucleoplasmic bridge frequency was also observed for both Kalore Composite resin and Vertise flow composite.²⁶¹ However, findings for binucleated cells frequency were inconsistent across the two studies, with one reporting a statistically significant

increase in number of binucleated cells after day seven and day 30,²⁵⁵ and the other reporting a significant increase at 180 days compared to baseline, with time of exposure and smoking exhibiting significant individual impact for Vertise flow, but no significant change for Kalore resin at any time point post intervention.²⁶¹ Findings for nuclear bud frequency within the latter study were also inconsistent with the first, with nuclear bud frequency significantly different compared to baseline at 180 days post restoration for Kalore, but not for Vertise flow at any time point post restoration.²⁶¹ Findings regarding micro nucleated cell frequency also differed between studies, with significant differences from pre-post intervention at seven and thirty days for both Kalore and Vertise flow composite resin.²⁶¹ Karyolysis frequency was significantly higher 30-days post-restoration versus day 0 and day seven for 'Twinkly star',²⁵⁵ and Kalore composite resin at all three follow-up points but not Vertise flow.²⁶¹

No significant difference in samples taken after 90 days were observed by one study,²⁵⁵ contrasting with the significant differences between baseline and 180-day follow-up observed by the other.²⁶¹ Further detail on specific genotoxicity outcomes relating to composite resins can be viewed in Supplementary Materials E, Table 53.

Summary: Composite resin only health impact evidence (patients) – Genotoxicity

Three studies, all appraised as weak quality, examined the impact of composite resins and/or compomers on genotoxicity outcomes. Population groups and/or specific outcome measures tended to be non-comparable across studies. Where outcome measured were the same across studies, findings were inconsistent, potentially reflecting differences in restorative material being evaluated and weak-quality of the evidence contributing this outcome.

Immune function

Two articles reporting findings from the NECAT randomised controlled trial, appraised as strong quality examined association between composite resin and immune function outcomes.^{187, 192} One study examined the effect of increased exposure to flowable composite sealant/preventative resin restorations, non-flowable compomer for primary teeth, non-flowable BisGMA-based composite for permanent teeth and immune function.¹⁸⁷ Dental sealants and composite restorations. No consistent associations were shown between type of restorative material, immune function outcome and time of follow up (six months, one- and five-years), with specific increases/decreases in activation of immune function markers shown in Supplementary Materials E, Table 54.¹⁸⁷ This study indicates that higher numbers of tooth surfaces treated on permanent teeth treated with Bis-GMA based non-flowable composite fillings were associated with increased B-cell activation, higher numbers of flowable composites used in preventative treatment were associated with increased total white blood cell count and negatively associated with one measure of neutrophil function (%DHE+PMA), although the other neutrophil measure had no significant association with number of surfaces treated (%Rho+PMA).

Increased numbers of surfaces treated with non-flowable compomer restorations on primary teeth were also positively associated with one out of two measures of monocyte function (%Rho+PMA).¹⁸⁷ All other measures of immune function were not significantly related to number of tooth surfaces with resin composites.¹⁸⁷ The other study found no consistent difference in children who had received composite fillings in distribution of lymphocytes, monocytes and neutrophils in blood at different points of follow up (five to seven days, six-, 12-, 60-months post-treatment).¹⁹²

Summary: Composite resin only health impact evidence (patients) – Immune function

Two articles reporting findings from the NECAT randomised controlled trial, appraised as strong quality examined association between composite resin and immune function outcomes.^{187, 192} No consistent associations were shown between type of restorative material, immune function outcome and time of follow up (six months, one- and five-years), although increased numbers of surfaces treated with non-flowable compomer restorations positively associated with one out of two measures of monocyte function.¹⁸⁷ Higher numbers of tooth surfaces treated on permanent teeth treated with Bis-GMA based non-flowable composite fillings were associated with increased B-cell activation, higher numbers of flowable composites used in preventative treatment were associated with increased total white blood cell count, although findings pertaining to neutrophil function varied.¹⁸⁷ The other article reported no significant differences in measures of immune function at different points of follow-up for children who received composite restorations. The limited number of studies and use of different outcome measures makes it difficult to draw firm conclusions regarding the relationship between composite resin restorations in children and immune function outcomes.¹⁹²

Neuropsychological

Two articles from the NECAT study appraised as strong quality found few significant associations between exposure to resin composite/compomers or flowable sealant/preventative resin restorations (PRR) in situ and the neuropsychological outcomes listed in Supplementary Materials E, Table 55.^{258, 259} One exception to this was the finding from a within-group analysis that children with greater exposure to composite or compomer had poorer change scores on a measure of verbal fluency at four-year follow-up (letter-fluency), with additional 10 posterior-occlusal surface years associated with a significantly decreased mean change score.²⁵⁹ Children receiving no sealants or preventative resin restorations during the study scored worse on five year changes on tests of full-scale IQ (WISC-III and WIAT) but had a smaller increase in errors on a test of executive function than children with flowable sealant/PRRs, where higher total exposure to compomer/composite material resulted in worse change scores on perseverate errors in Wisconsin Card sorting test.²⁵⁸ Another test of executive function, the Stroop colour naming task indicated that higher level of exposure to flowable sealant, preventative resin restoration and resin composite/compomer were associated with poorer ability to name

colours.^{258, 259} Another retrospective observational study, also appraised as being strong quality, found no association between dementia development and number of composite resin restorations.²³³

Summary: Composite resin only health impact evidence (patients) – Neuropsychological

Two articles from the NECAT study appraised as strong quality found few significant associations between exposure to resin composite/compomers or flowable sealant/preventative resin restorations (PRR) in situ and the neuropsychological outcomes.^{258, 259} These findings are consistent with a strong quality retrospective observational study which found no link between number of composite resin restorations and risk of developing dementia.²³³ The limited number of studies supporting this category prevents firm conclusions being drawn from these findings.

Oral health

Five studies examined association between composite resin restorations in situ and patient oral health outcomes. Three studies, two cross-sectional with control and one prospective pre-post intervention study were appraised as weak quality,^{195, 207, 257} one retrospective cohort was appraised as moderate quality,¹⁹⁰ and one retrospective nested case-control study appraised as strong quality.²³⁰ Populations and specific outcomes of interest across these studies were heterogenous and non-comparable (see Supplementary Materials E, Table 56).

One weak quality study reported that oral lichenoid lesions patients had a significantly higher number of surfaces with composite resin restorations than dermatitis patients.¹⁹⁵ However, all patients who had composite resin restorations also had amalgam restorations, with only two patients in the oral lichenoid lesion group with composite fillings next to lichen lesions with no amalgam in the same region.¹⁹⁵ Another weak quality study found no significant improvement in dental hypersensitivity following treatment of mild non carious cervical lesions with composite resin restorations.²⁵⁷ One moderate quality study found no significant association between large composite restorations and frequency of occurrence of pulpal disease.¹⁹⁰ Finally, findings relating to oral lichen planus were mixed, with one strong quality study stating composite resin restorations in anterior or posterior teeth were not associated with overall altered odds of oral lichen planus over five-years follow up,²³⁰ although adjusted odds ratio was significantly increased for individuals receiving 3-4 composite fillings per year,²³⁰ and one weak quality study reporting composite restorations were significantly correlated with local oral lichen planus, although these correlations were small and potentially not clinically significant.²⁰⁷

Summary: Composite resin only health impact evidence (patients) – Oral health

Five studies of variable quality examined association between composite resin restorations in situ and patient oral health outcomes.^{190, 195, 207, 230, 257} Populations and specific outcomes of interest across

these studies were heterogenous and non-comparable, but broadly indicated no significant association between composite resin exposure and oral health symptoms, although adjusted odds ratio for oral lichen planus was significantly increased for individuals receiving 3-4 composite fillings per year in one strong quality study.²³⁰

Psychosocial

Two articles from the NECAT study appraised as strong quality found few significant associations between child exposure to resin composite/comonomers or flowable sealant/preventative resin restorations (PRR) in situ on primary or posterior teeth and psychosocial health outcomes listed in Supplementary Materials E, Table 57.^{209, 258} Exceptions to these were a significant change score pre-post intervention on BASC-SR change scores among children age eight years or over at baseline: clinical maladjustment, personal adjustment, and emotional symptoms index, interpersonal relations, and anxiety for posterior occlusal surface years only, where exposure to Bis-GMA-based composite on permanent teeth was measured in 10-surface years (SY) and posterior occlusal SY.²⁰⁹ BASC-SR year five T-scores also indicated significant change scores for depression, clinical maladjustment, interpersonal relation and the emotional symptoms index for the same restoration type on posterior teeth.²⁰⁹ These change scores indicated greater exposure to BisGMA-composite was linked to poorer psychosocial performance at follow-up. The only significant change noted for the use of UDMA-based compomer on primary teeth was school maladjustment, and for posterior occlusal surfaces was attitude to school.²⁰⁹ Factors such as age, gender, race/ethnicity, socioeconomic status, geographic site, primary caregiver's marital status, blood lead level, and any maternal self-reported exposure during pregnancy to alcohol or illicit substances were considered in analysis. Authors report no interactions by age and gender were found.²⁰⁹

Summary: Composite resin only health impact evidence (patients) – Psychosocial

Two articles from the NECAT study appraised as strong quality found eleven significant associations of the 53 outcomes measured between child exposure to resin composite/comonomers or flowable sealant/preventative resin restorations (PRR) in situ on primary or posterior teeth and psychosocial health outcomes. The majority of these concerned use of BisGMA-based composite on permanent teeth, with specific measures focusing on clinical maladjustment, personal adjustment, and emotional symptoms index, interpersonal relations, and anxiety for posterior occlusal surface years only, where exposure to Bis-GMA-based composite on permanent teeth was measured in 10-surface years (SY) and posterior occlusal SY.²⁰⁹ BASC-SR year five T-scores also indicated significant change scores for depression, clinical maladjustment, interpersonal relation and the emotional symptoms index for the same restoration type on posterior teeth.²⁰⁹ These change scores indicated greater exposure to

BisGMA-composite was linked to poorer psychosocial performance at follow-up. Further studies are needed to evaluate the reliability of these findings.

Other

One retrospective observational nested case-control study appraised as moderate quality compared the risk of **ADHD symptoms** between children with and without composite resin restorations.²⁵⁶ This study found a significantly higher risk of ADHD amongst children exposed to composite resin restorations versus those who were not, with the risk increasing over time until three years post first composite resin restorations, although no positive association with increased number of composite resin restorations was demonstrated.²⁵⁶

One article representing a secondary analysis from the NECAT randomised controlled trial appraised as strong quality examined effect of exposure to flowable sealant/preventative resin restorations and **anthropomorphic** and **female health** outcomes.¹⁸⁷ No significant association between restoration material and either outcome was demonstrated.¹⁸⁷

One strong quality study associated with the Casa Pia trial reported slightly elevated **penta-, precopro- and coproporphyrins** mean urinary concentrations in children with amalgam, particularly at three year follow up corresponding with higher urinary Hg concentrations, which was particularly pronounced for younger participants at baseline (8-9 years).²⁶² These participants showed increases in penta-, precopro- and coproporphyrins, especially during years three and four of follow up compared to the group receiving composite restorations.²⁶² Treatment effects were comparable between boys/girls aged eight to nine at baseline. This study observed no significant effects on urinary porphyrin concentration.²⁶² See Supplementary Materials E, Table 58 for further details.

Summary: Composite resin and/or methacrylates only health impact evidence (patients)

Fifteen studies (19 articles) evaluated the health impact of patient exposure to composite resin restorations or methacrylate compounds on the health of adults or children. Quality appraisal scores were as follows: weak (n=8), moderate (n=3), and strong (n=4). Studies were synthesised within the following broad outcome categories: allergy (n=4), genotoxicity (n=3), immune function (n=1), neuropsychological (n=2) oral health (n=5), psychosocial (n=1), and other (n=3). One moderate quality study evaluated the rate of sensitisation to methacrylates/acrylates in dental health professionals.²¹⁸

The limited number of studies and heterogeneity of study populations and outcome measures limited the confidence in the few associations between composite resin restorations and health outcomes identified. The strongest, most consistent evidence was found for neuropsychological health outcomes which found few associations between composite resin restorations and performance on psychological tests, where greater exposure to BisGMA-composite was linked to poorer psychosocial health at

follow-up. However, both these broad health impact categories were only supported by two articles from the NECAT study.^{258, 259}

Glass ionomer vs composite resin/compomer

Three studies compared the health impact of glass ionomer restorations with composite/compomer resins (see Supplementary Materials E, Table 59).

One retrospective cohort study appraised as strong quality, reported no significant differences between groups receiving glass ionomer, amalgam or composite resin restorations with **ADHD incidence** or 10-year hazard probability.¹⁸⁵

One RCT appraised as moderate quality compared **gingival health** between glass ionomer Vitremer and composite resin Z250, with findings significantly favouring Vitremer at 12- and 24-months.²⁶³

Another RCT appraised as weak quality compared **genotoxicity outcomes**, including: micro nucleated/binucleated cells, cells with nucleoplasmic bridges, nuclear buds, pyknosis, condensed chromatin, karyorrhexis, among individuals who received one of two different types of glass ionomer restoration (Ketac Molar and Ionofil Molar) or a compomer restoration.²⁵⁵ Within-group comparisons for GIC materials showed no significant changes over time, aside for micronuclei and binucleated cell frequency for Ketac Molar and Ionofil Molar respectively.²⁵⁵ No significant differences were observed for any outcome between different types of restorative material, aside for number of binucleated cells at seven-day follow up for individuals receiving 'Twinkly Star' compomer and Ketac Molar, with age significantly impacting occurrence of binuclear cells.²⁵⁵

References

1. NHS Business Services Authority. In the spotlight. Article 2: Inlays and Onlays. 2019. [Available from: https://www.nhsbsa.nhs.uk/sites/default/files/2021-04/Article_2_Inlays_And_Onlays_Guidance_Final_V4.pdf].
2. Wong A, Subar PE, Young DA. Dental Caries: An Update on Dental Trends and Therapy. *Adv Pediatr*. 2017;64(1):307-30.
3. UN Environmental Programme. Phasing down the use of dental amalgam 2025 [Available from: <https://www.unep.org/globalmercurypartnership/our-work/mercury-products/phasing-down-the-use-of-dental-amalgam#:~:text=Uruguay-Overview,%2C%20longevity%20and%20cost%2Deffectiveness>].
4. National Dental Epidemiology Programme for England. Oral health survey of adults attending general dental practices 2018. London: Public Health England; 2020. [Available from: https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5ee0abb0d3bf7f1eb9646438/AiP_survey_for_England_2018.pdf].
5. U.S. Food and Drug Administration. Dental amalgam fillings 2021 [cited 2025 7th July]. Available from: <https://www.fda.gov/medical-devices/dental-devices/dental-amalgam-fillings>].
6. Houston MC. Role of mercury toxicity in hypertension, cardiovascular disease, and stroke. *J Clin Hypertens (Greenwich)*. 2011;13(8):621-7.
7. Saturday A. *Journal of Environment and Health Science Mercury and its Associated Impacts on Environment and Human Health: A Review* Citation: Saturday, A. Mercury and its Associated Impacts on Environment and Human Health: A Review. 2018:37-43.
8. Rathore M, Singh A, Pant VA. The dental amalgam toxicity fear: a myth or actuality. *Toxicol Int*. 2012;19(2):81-8.
9. Ge KX, Quock R, Chu CH, Yu OY. The preventive effect of glass ionomer restorations on new caries formation: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *J Dent*. 2022;125:104272.
10. Kapoor B, Ahmed L. The war between amalgam and composite: A critical review. *Journal of Oral Research & Review*. 2021;13(2):133-8.
11. UN Environment Programme. *Minamata Convention on Mercury - Text and Annexes*. 2013.
12. European Center for Environmental Medicine. *European Plans to Reduce and Eliminate Dental Amalgam Use*. 2022.
13. Department of Health and Social Care. *National plan to phase down use of Dental Amalgam in England* London: DHSC; 2019.
14. European Union. Commission Notice – Application of Regulation (EU) 2024/1849 of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Regulation (EU) 2017/852 on mercury as regards dental amalgam and other mercury-added products subject to export, import and manufacturing restrictions to and in the United Kingdom in respect of Northern Ireland: Publications Office of the European Union; 2024 [Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/C/2024/4675>].
15. International Institute for Sustainable Development. Summary report 3–7 November 2025,, *Minamata Convention on Mercury*. United Nations Environment Programme; 2024.
16. Lawal HM, Briscoe S, Martin Pintado C, et al. The health and environmental impact of dental amalgam and alternative restorative materials: a protocol for a systematic review. *PROSPERO 2024 PROSPERO2024* [Available from: <https://www.crd.york.ac.uk/PROSPERO/view/CRD42024608563>].
17. Centre for Reviews and Dissemination. *Systematic Reviews: CRD's guidance for undertaking reviews in health care*. University of York: CRD; 2008.
18. Abass K, Huusko A, Knutsen HK, et al. Quantitative estimation of mercury intake by toxicokinetic modelling based on total mercury levels in humans. *Environ Int*. 2018;114:1-11.
19. Al-Saleh I. Reference values for heavy metals in the urine and blood of Saudi women derived from two human biomonitoring studies. *Int J Hyg Environ Health*. 2020;225:113473.

20. Al-Saleh I, Coskun S, Mashhour A, et al. Exposure to heavy metals (lead, cadmium and mercury) and its effect on the outcome of in-vitro fertilization treatment. *Int J Hyg Environ Health*. 2008;211(5-6):560-79.
21. Baek HJ, Kim EK, Lee SG, et al. Dental amalgam exposure can elevate urinary mercury concentrations in children. *Int Dent J*. 2016;66(3):136-43.
22. Barregard L, Fabricius-Lagging E, Lundh T, et al. Cadmium, mercury, and lead in kidney cortex of living kidney donors: Impact of different exposure sources. *Environ Res*. 2010;110(1):47-54.
23. Bartel-Steinbach M, Lermen D, Gwinner F, et al. Long-term monitoring of mercury in young German adults: Time trend analyses from the German Environmental Specimen Bank, 1995-2018. *Environ Res*. 2022;207:112592.
24. Becker K, Schroeter-Kermani C, Seiwert M, et al. German health-related environmental monitoring: assessing time trends of the general population's exposure to heavy metals. *Int J Hyg Environ Health*. 2013;216(3):250-4.
25. Berge TLL, Lygre GB, Jonsson BAG, et al. Bisphenol A concentration in human saliva related to dental polymer-based fillings. *Clin Oral Investig*. 2017;21(8):2561-8.
26. Berge TLL, Lygre GB, Lie SA, et al. Bisphenol A in human saliva and urine before and after treatment with dental polymer-based restorative materials. *Eur J Oral Sci*. 2019;127(5):435-44.
27. Bjorkman L, Lundekvam BF, Laegreid T, et al. Mercury in human brain, blood, muscle and toenails in relation to exposure: an autopsy study. *Environ Health*. 2007;6(1):30.
28. Bocca B, Bena A, Pino A, et al. Human biomonitoring of metals in adults living near a waste-to-energy incinerator in ante-operam phase: Focus on reference values and health-based assessments. *Environ Res*. 2016;148:338-50.
29. Castano A, Sanchez-Rodriguez JE, Canas A, et al. Mercury, lead and cadmium levels in the urine of 170 Spanish adults: a pilot human biomonitoring study. *Int J Hyg Environ Health*. 2012;215(2):191-5.
30. Cesbron A, Saussereau E, Mahieu L, et al. Metallic profile of whole blood and plasma in a series of 106 healthy volunteers. *J Anal Toxicol*. 2013;37(7):401-5.
31. Chung SY, Kwon H, Choi YH, et al. Dental composite fillings and bisphenol A among children: a survey in South Korea. *Int Dent J*. 2012;62(2):65-9.
32. Dack K, Huang P, Taylor CM, et al. Environmental and genetic predictors of whole blood mercury and selenium concentrations in pregnant women in a UK birth cohort. *Environ Adv*. 2024;15:100469.
33. Diez S, Montuori P, Pagano A, et al. Hair mercury levels in an urban population from southern Italy: fish consumption as a determinant of exposure. *Environ Int*. 2008;34(2):162-7.
34. Dix-Cooper L, Kosatsky T. Blood mercury, lead and cadmium levels and determinants of exposure among newcomer South and East Asian women of reproductive age living in Vancouver, Canada. *Sci Total Environ*. 2018;619-620:1409-19.
35. Duncan A, O'Reilly DS, McDonald EB, et al. Thirty-five year review of a mercury monitoring service for Scottish dental practices. *Br Dent J*. 2011;210(3):E2.
36. Dunn JE, Trachtenberg FL, Barregard L, et al. Scalp hair and urine mercury content of children in the Northeast United States: the New England Children's Amalgam Trial. *Environ Res*. 2008;107(1):79-88.
37. Dutton DJ, Fyie K, Faris P, et al. The association between amalgam dental surfaces and urinary mercury levels in a sample of Albertans, a prevalence study. *J Occup Med Toxicol*. 2013;8(1):22.
38. Elli L, Rossi V, Conte D, et al. Increased Mercury Levels in Patients with Celiac Disease following a Gluten-Free Regimen. *Gastroenterol Res Pract*. 2015;2015:953042.
39. Forysova K, Pinkr-Grafnetterova A, Maly M, et al. Urinary Cadmium and Cotinine Levels and Hair Mercury Levels in Czech Children and Their Mothers Within the Framework of the COPHES/DEMOCOPHES Projects. *Arch Environ Contam Toxicol*. 2017;73(3):421-30.
40. France Stiglic A, Falnoga I, Briski AS, et al. Reference intervals of 24 trace elements in blood, plasma and erythrocytes for the Slovenian adult population. *Clin Chem Lab Med*. 2024;62(5):946-57.

41. Geer LA, Persad MD, Palmer CD, et al. Assessment of prenatal mercury exposure in a predominately Caribbean immigrant community in Brooklyn, NY. *J Environ Monit.* 2012;14(3):1035-43.
42. Geier DA, Carmody T, Kern JK, et al. A dose-dependent relationship between mercury exposure from dental amalgams and urinary mercury levels: a further assessment of the Casa Pia Children's Dental Amalgam Trial. *Hum Exp Toxicol.* 2012;31(1):11-7.
43. Geier DA, Geier MR. Dental amalgam fillings and mercury vapor safety limits in American adults. *Hum Exp Toxicol.* 2022;41:9603271221106341.
44. Geier DA, Geier MR. Estimated mercury vapor exposure from amalgams among American pregnant women. *Hum Exp Toxicol.* 2024;43:9603271241231945.
45. Gerhardsson L, Lundh T. Metal concentrations in blood and hair in pregnant females in southern Sweden. *J Environ Health.* 2010;72(6):37-41.
46. Golding J, Steer CD, Gregory S, et al. Dental associations with blood mercury in pregnant women. *Community Dent Oral Epidemiol.* 2016;44(3):216-22.
47. Goodrich JM, Chou HN, Gruninger SE, et al. Exposures of dental professionals to elemental mercury and methylmercury. *J Expo Sci Environ Epidemiol.* 2016;26(1):78-85.
48. Goodrich JM, Wang Y, Gillespie B, et al. Glutathione enzyme and selenoprotein polymorphisms associate with mercury biomarker levels in Michigan dental professionals. *Toxicol Appl Pharmacol.* 2011;257(2):301-8.
49. Grzunov Letinic J, Matek Saric M, Piasek M, et al. Use of human milk in the assessment of toxic metal exposure and essential element status in breastfeeding women and their infants in coastal Croatia. *J Trace Elem Med Biol.* 2016;38:117-25.
50. Halbach S, Vogt S, Kohler W, et al. Blood and urine mercury levels in adult amalgam patients of a randomized controlled trial: interaction of Hg species in erythrocytes. *Environ Res.* 2008;107(1):69-78.
51. Hrubá F, Černa M, Chen C, et al. A regional comparison of children's blood cadmium, lead, and mercury in rural, urban and industrial areas of six European countries, and China, Ecuador, and Morocco. *Int J Occup Med Environ Health.* 2023;36(3):349-64.
52. Hrubá F, Stromberg U, Černa M, et al. Blood cadmium, mercury, and lead in children: an international comparison of cities in six European countries, and China, Ecuador, and Morocco. *Environ Int.* 2012;41:29-34.
53. Kim DS, Kim GB, Kang T, Ahn S. Total and methyl mercury in maternal and cord blood of pregnant women in Korea. *Toxicology and Environmental Health Sciences.* 2012;3(4):254-7.
54. Kim DS, Kim JH, Yang W-H, et al. Biomonitoring of urinary mercury in Korean school children. *Molecular & Cellular Toxicology.* 2010;6(4):351-8.
55. Kingman A, Hyman J, Masten SA, et al. Bisphenol A and other compounds in human saliva and urine associated with the placement of composite restorations. *J Am Dent Assoc.* 2012;143(12):1292-302.
56. Knezović Z, Trgo M, Sutlović D. Monitoring mercury environment pollution through bioaccumulation in meconium. *Process Safety and Environmental Protection.* 2016;101:2-8.
57. Kobal AB, Snoj Tratnik J, Mazej D, et al. Exposure to mercury in susceptible population groups living in the former mercury mining town of Idrija, Slovenia. *Environ Res.* 2017;152:434-45.
58. Kruzikova K, Kensova R, Blahova J, et al. Using human hair as an indicator for exposure to mercury. *Neuro Endocrinol Lett.* 2009;30 Suppl 1:177-81.
59. Kruzikova K, Modra H, Kensova R, et al. Mercury in human hair as an indicator of the fish consumption. *Neuro Endocrinol Lett.* 2008;29(5):675-9.
60. Lee JH, Yi SK, Kim SY, et al. Salivary bisphenol A levels and their association with composite resin restoration. *Chemosphere.* 2017;172:46-51.
61. Letinic JG, Saric MM, Piasek M, et al. Use of human milk in the assessment of toxic metal exposure and essential element status in breastfeeding women and their infants in coastal Croatia. *Journal of Trace Elements in Medicine and Biology.* 2016;38:117-25.

62. Link B, Gabrio T, Piechotowski I, et al. Baden-Wuerttemberg Environmental Health Survey (BW-EHS) from 1996 to 2003: toxic metals in blood and urine of children. *Int J Hyg Environ Health.* 2007;210(3-4):357-71.
63. Link B, Gabrio T, Zollner I, et al. Decrease of internal exposure to chlororganic compounds and heavy metals in children in Baden-Wuerttemberg between 1996/1997 and 2008/2009. *Int J Hyg Environ Health.* 2012;215(2):196-201.
64. Lyapina MG, Dencheva MS, Krasteva AZ, et al. BIOMONITORING OF URINARY LEVELS OF BISPHENOL A. *COMPTE RENDUS DE L ACADEMIE BULGARE DES SCIENCES.* 2016;69(6):807-14.
65. Lye E, Legrand M, Clarke J, Probert A. Blood total mercury concentrations in the Canadian population: Canadian Health Measures Survey cycle 1, 2007-2009. *Can J Public Health.* 2013;104(3):e246-51.
66. MacAulay M, Tam LE, Santerre JP, Finer Y. In Vivo Biodegradation of bisGMA and Urethane-Modified bisGMA-Based Resin Composite Materials. *JDR Clin Trans Res.* 2017;2(4):397-405.
67. Maserejian NN, Trachtenberg FL, Assmann SF, Barregard L. Dental amalgam exposure and urinary mercury levels in children: the New England Children's Amalgam Trial. *Environ Health Perspect.* 2008;116(2):256-62.
68. Maserejian NN, Trachtenberg FL, Wheaton OB, et al. Changes in urinary bisphenol A concentrations associated with placement of dental composite restorations in children and adolescents. *J Am Dent Assoc.* 2016;147(8):620-30.
69. McKelvey W, Alex B, Chernov C, et al. Tracking Declines in Mercury Exposure in the New York City Adult Population, 2004-2014. *J Urban Health.* 2018;95(6):813-25.
70. McKinney C, Rue T, Sathyanarayana S, et al. Dental sealants and restorations and urinary bisphenol A concentrations in children in the 2003-2004 National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey. *J Am Dent Assoc.* 2014;145(7):745-50.
71. McKinney CM, Leroux BG, Seminario AL, et al. A Prospective Cohort Study of Bisphenol A Exposure from Dental Treatment. *J Dent Res.* 2020;99(11):1262-9.
72. Melchart D, Kohler W, Linde K, et al. Biomonitoring of mercury in patients with complaints attributed to dental amalgam, healthy amalgam bearers, and amalgam-free subjects: a diagnostic study. *Clin Toxicol (Phila).* 2008;46(2):133-40.
73. Michalak I, Chojnacka K, Saeid A, Mikulewicz M. Research on mercury levels in scalp hair. *Polish Journal of Environmental Studies.* 2014;23(3):793-800.
74. Michalak I, Mikulewicz M, Chojnacka K, et al. Exposure to nickel by hair mineral analysis. *Environ Toxicol Pharmacol.* 2012;34(3):727-34.
75. Michalak I, Wolowiec P, Chojnacka K. Determination of exposure to lead of subjects from southwestern Poland by human hair analysis. *Environ Monit Assess.* 2014;186(4):2259-67.
76. Michelsen VB, Kopperud HB, Lygre GB, et al. Detection and quantification of monomers in unstimulated whole saliva after treatment with resin-based composite fillings in vivo. *Eur J Oral Sci.* 2012;120(1):89-95.
77. Nicolae A, Ames H, Quinonez C. Dental amalgam and urinary mercury concentrations: a descriptive study. *BMC Oral Health.* 2013;13:44.
78. Nuvolone D, Aprea MC, Stoppa G, et al. Levels and determinants of urinary and blood metals in the geothermal area of Mt. Amiata in Tuscany (Italy). *Environ Sci Pollut Res Int.* 2023;30(13):38319-32.
79. Palkovicova L, Ursinyova M, Masanova V, et al. Maternal amalgam dental fillings as the source of mercury exposure in developing fetus and newborn. *J Expo Sci Environ Epidemiol.* 2008;18(3):326-31.
80. Parajuli RP, Goodrich JM, Chou HN, et al. Genetic polymorphisms are associated with hair, blood, and urine mercury levels in the American Dental Association (ADA) study participants. *Environ Res.* 2016;149:247-58.

81. Park SB, Kim EK, Sakong J, Park EY. Association between dental amalgam restoration and urine mercury concentrations among young women: a cross-sectional study. *J Yeungnam Med Sci.* 2023;40(4):373-80.
82. Pawlas N, Stromberg U, Carlberg B, et al. Cadmium, mercury and lead in the blood of urban women in Croatia, the Czech Republic, Poland, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, China, Ecuador and Morocco. *Int J Occup Med Environ Health.* 2013;26(1):58-72.
83. Pirard C, Compere S, Firquet K, Charlier C. The current environmental levels of endocrine disruptors (mercury, cadmium, organochlorine pesticides and PCBs) in a Belgian adult population and their predictors of exposure. *Int J Hyg Environ Health.* 2018;221(2):211-22.
84. Pirard C, Koppen G, De Cremer K, et al. Hair mercury and urinary cadmium levels in Belgian children and their mothers within the framework of the COPHES/DEMOCOPHES projects. *Sci Total Environ.* 2014;472:730-40.
85. Prokopowicz A, Pawlas N, Ochota P, et al. Blood Levels of Lead, Cadmium, and Mercury in Healthy Women in their 50s in an Urban Area of Poland: A Pilot Study. *Polish Journal of Environmental Studies.* 2014;23(1):167-75.
86. Richardson GM. Mercury Exposure and Risks from Dental Amalgam in Canada: The Canadian Health Measures Survey 2007–2009. *Human and Ecological Risk Assessment: An International Journal.* 2013;20(2):433-47.
87. Ryo K, Ito A, Takatori R, et al. Correlation Between Mercury Concentrations in Hair and Dental Amalgam Fillings. *Anti-Aging Medicine.* 2010;7(3):14-7.
88. Sharma BM, Komprdova K, Lorinczova K, et al. Human biomonitoring of essential and toxic trace elements (heavy metals and metalloids) in urine of children, teenagers, and young adults from a Central European Cohort in the Czech Republic. *J Expo Sci Environ Epidemiol.* 2024.
89. Sherman LS, Blum JD, Franzblau A, Basu N. New insight into biomarkers of human mercury exposure using naturally occurring mercury stable isotopes. *Environ Sci Technol.* 2013;47(7):3403-9.
90. Snoj Tratnik J, Falnoga I, Mazej D, et al. Results of the first national human biomonitoring in Slovenia: Trace elements in men and lactating women, predictors of exposure and reference values. *Int J Hyg Environ Health.* 2019;222(3):563-82.
91. Svendsen K, Syversen T, Melo I, Hilt B. Historical exposure to mercury among Norwegian dental personnel. *Scand J Work Environ Health.* 2010;36(3):231-41.
92. Trdin A, Falnoga I, Fajon V, et al. Mercury speciation in meconium and associated factors. *Environ Res.* 2019;179(Pt A):108724.
93. Trzcinka-Ochocka M, Gazewski A, Brodzka R. Exposure to mercury vapors in dental workers in Poland. *Int J Occup Med Environ Health.* 2007;20(2):147-53.
94. Tucek M, Busova M, Cejchanova M, et al. Exposure to mercury from dental amalgam: actual contribution for risk assessment. *Cent Eur J Public Health.* 2020;28(1):40-3.
95. Vervliet P, De Nys S, Duca RC, et al. Degradation products of resin-based materials detected in saliva in vivo. *Clin Oral Investig.* 2023;27(12):7189-98.
96. Vogel N, Murawski A, Schmied-Tobies MIH, et al. Lead, cadmium, mercury, and chromium in urine and blood of children and adolescents in Germany - Human biomonitoring results of the German Environmental Survey 2014-2017 (GerES V). *Int J Hyg Environ Health.* 2021;237:113822.
97. Vollset M, Iszatt N, Enger O, et al. Concentration of mercury, cadmium, and lead in breast milk from Norwegian mothers: Association with dietary habits, amalgam and other factors. *Sci Total Environ.* 2019;677:466-73.
98. Woods JS, Martin MD, Leroux BG, et al. The contribution of dental amalgam to urinary mercury excretion in children. *Environ Health Perspect.* 2007;115(10):1527-31.
99. Wranova K, Cejchanova M, Spevakova V, et al. Mercury and methylmercury in hair of selected groups of Czech population. *Cent Eur J Public Health.* 2009;17(1):36-40.
100. Yin L, Lin S, Summers AO, et al. Children with Amalgam Dental Restorations Have Significantly Elevated Blood and Urine Mercury Levels. *Toxicol Sci.* 2021;184(1):104-26.

101. Yin L, Yu K, Lin S, et al. Associations of blood mercury, inorganic mercury, methyl mercury and bisphenol A with dental surface restorations in the U.S. population, NHANES 2003-2004 and 2010-2012. *Ecotoxicol Environ Saf.* 2016;134P1:213-25.
102. Aalto-Korte K, Jungewelter S, Henriks-Eckerman ML, et al. Contact allergy to epoxy (meth)acrylates. *Contact Dermatitis.* 2009;61(1):9-21.
103. Aalto-Korte K, Alanko K, Kuuliala O, Jolanki R. Methacrylate and acrylate allergy in dental personnel. *Contact Dermatitis.* 2007;57(5):324-30.
104. Aalto-Korte K, Henriks-Eckerman ML, Kuuliala O, Jolanki R. Occupational methacrylate and acrylate allergy--cross-reactions and possible screening allergens. *Contact Dermatitis.* 2010;63(6):301-12.
105. Ahlgren C, Isaksson M, Moller H, et al. The necessity of a test reading after 1 week to detect late positive patch test reactions in patients with oral lichen lesions. *Clin Oral Investig.* 2014;18(5):1525-31.
106. Bergdahl IA, Ahlqvist M, Barregard L, et al. Mercury in serum predicts low risk of death and myocardial infarction in Gothenburg women. *Int Arch Occup Environ Health.* 2013;86(1):71-7.
107. Golding J, Rai D, Gregory S, et al. Prenatal mercury exposure and features of autism: a prospective population study. *Mol Autism.* 2018;9:30.
108. Hertz-Picciotto I, Green PG, Delwiche L, et al. Blood mercury concentrations in CHARGE Study children with and without autism. *Environ Health Perspect.* 2010;118(1):161-6.
109. Kim TW, Kim WI, Mun JH, et al. Patch Testing with Dental Screening Series in Oral Disease. *Ann Dermatol.* 2015;27(4):389-93.
110. Lomaga MA, Polak S, Grushka M, Walsh S. Results of patch testing in patients diagnosed with oral lichen planus. *J Cutan Med Surg.* 2009;13(2):88-95.
111. Mori T, Sato K, Kusaka Y, et al. Positive patch test for mercury possibly from exposure to amalgam. *Environ Health Prev Med.* 2007;12(4):172-7.
112. Orlando MS, Love T, Harrington D, et al. The association of auditory function measures with low-level methylmercury from oceanic fish consumption and mercury vapor from amalgam: The Seychelles Child Development Study Nutrition 1 Cohort. *Neurotoxicology.* 2023;95:46-55.
113. Raap U, Stiesch M, Reh H, et al. Investigation of contact allergy to dental metals in 206 patients. *Contact Dermatitis.* 2009;60(6):339-43.
114. Ramos L, Cabral R, Goncalo M. Allergic contact dermatitis caused by acrylates and methacrylates--a 7-year study. *Contact Dermatitis.* 2014;71(2):102-7.
115. Stejskal V, Reynolds T, Bjorklund G. Increased frequency of delayed type hypersensitivity to metals in patients with connective tissue disease. *J Trace Elem Med Biol.* 2015;31:230-6.
116. Ting S, Nguyen J, Palmer A, Rosemary Nixon AM. Contact sensitisation in oral lichen planus: An Australian perspective. *Contact Dermatitis.* 2023;89(5):335-44.
117. Torgerson RR, Davis MD, Bruce AJ, et al. Contact allergy in oral disease. *J Am Acad Dermatol.* 2007;57(2):315-21.
118. Al-Saleh I, Abduljabbar M, Al-Rouqi R, et al. The extent of mercury (Hg) exposure among Saudi mothers and their respective infants. *Environ Monit Assess.* 2015;187(11):678.
119. Bashore CJ, Geer LA, He X, et al. Maternal mercury exposure, season of conception and adverse birth outcomes in an urban immigrant community in Brooklyn, New York, U.S.A. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2014;11(8):8414-42.
120. Bloching M, Reich W, Schubert J, et al. Micronucleus rate of buccal mucosal epithelial cells in relation to oral hygiene and dental factors. *Oral Oncol.* 2008;44(3):220-6.
121. Camacho-Alonso F, Sanchez-Siles M, Gilbel-del Aguila O. No Evidence of Genotoxic Damage in a Group of Patients with Titanium Dental Implants and Different Metal Restorations in the Oral Cavity. *Clin Implant Dent Relat Res.* 2015;17(4):811-21.
122. Croes K, De Coster S, De Galan S, et al. Health effects in the Flemish population in relation to low levels of mercury exposure: from organ to transcriptome level. *Int J Hyg Environ Health.* 2014;217(2-3):239-47.

123. Emeny RT, Korrick SA, Li Z, et al. Prenatal exposure to mercury in relation to infant infections and respiratory symptoms in the New Hampshire Birth Cohort Study. *Environ Res.* 2019;171:523-9.
124. Ghezel-Ahmadi D, Engel A, Weidemann J, et al. Heavy metal exposure in patients suffering from electromagnetic hypersensitivity. *Sci Total Environ.* 2010;408(4):774-8.
125. Gundacker C, Frohlich S, Graf-Rohrmeister K, et al. Perinatal lead and mercury exposure in Austria. *Sci Total Environ.* 2010;408(23):5744-9.
126. Jarosinska D, Horvat M, Sallsten G, et al. Urinary mercury and biomarkers of early renal dysfunction in environmentally and occupationally exposed adults: a three-country study. *Environ Res.* 2008;108(2):224-32.
127. Lynde CB, Grushka M, Walsh SR. Burning mouth syndrome: patch test results from a large case series. *J Cutan Med Surg.* 2014;18(3):174-9.
128. Parkin Kullmann JA, Pamphlett R. A Comparison of Mercury Exposure from Seafood Consumption and Dental Amalgam Fillings in People with and without Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis (ALS): An International Online Case-Control Study. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2018;15(12).
129. Sekovanic A, Piasek M, Orct T, et al. Mercury Exposure Assessment in Mother-Infant Pairs from Continental and Coastal Croatia. *Biomolecules.* 2020;10(6).
130. Stejskal V, Ockert K, Bjorklund G. Metal-induced inflammation triggers fibromyalgia in metal-allergic patients. *Neuro Endocrinol Lett.* 2013;34(6):559-65.
131. Snoj Tratnik J, Falnoga I, Trdin A, et al. Prenatal mercury exposure, neurodevelopment and apolipoprotein E genetic polymorphism. *Environ Res.* 2017;152:375-85.
132. Tschudi-Madsen H, Kjeldsberg M, Natvig B, et al. Medically unexplained conditions considered by patients in general practice. *Fam Pract.* 2014;31(2):156-63.
133. Ursinyova M, Uhnakova I, Serbin R, et al. The relation between human exposure to mercury and thyroid hormone status. *Biol Trace Elem Res.* 2012;148(3):281-91.
134. Woods JS, Armel SE, Fulton DI, et al. Urinary porphyrin excretion in neurotypical and autistic children. *Environ Health Perspect.* 2010;118(10):1450-7.
135. Ditrichova D, Kapralova S, Tichy M, et al. Oral lichenoid lesions and allergy to dental materials. *Biomed Pap Med Fac Univ Palacky Olomouc Czech Repub.* 2007;151(2):333-9.
136. Goodrich JM, Basu N, Franzblau A, Dolinoy DC. Mercury biomarkers and DNA methylation among Michigan dental professionals. *Environ Mol Mutagen.* 2013;54(3):195-203.
137. Goodrich JM, Wang Y, Gillespie B, et al. Methylmercury and elemental mercury differentially associate with blood pressure among dental professionals. *Int J Hyg Environ Health.* 2013;216(2):195-201.
138. Lyapina M, Dencheva M, Krasteva A, et al. Concomitant contact allergy to formaldehyde and methacrylic monomers in students of dental medicine and dental patients. *Int J Occup Med Environ Health.* 2014;27(5):797-807.
139. Lyapina MG, Dencheva M, Krasteva-Panova A, et al. Concomitant sensitization to glutaraldehyde and methacrylic monomers among dentists and their patients. *Med Pr.* 2016;67(3):311-20.
140. Muris J, Goossens A, Goncalo M, et al. Sensitization to palladium and nickel in Europe and the relationship with oral disease and dental alloys. *Contact Dermatitis.* 2015;72(5):286-96.
141. Olms C, Yahiaoui-Doktor M, Remmerbach TW. Contact allergies to dental materials. *Swiss Dent J.* 2019;129(7-8):571-9.
142. Rothwell JA, Boyd PJ. Amalgam dental fillings and hearing loss. *Int J Audiol.* 2008;47(12):770-6.
143. Tillberg A, Stenberg B, Berglund A. Reactions to resin-based dental materials in patients--type, time to onset, duration, and consequence of the reaction. *Contact Dermatitis.* 2009;61(6):313-9.
144. Xu W, Park SK, Gruninger SE, et al. Associations between mercury exposure with blood pressure and lipid levels: A cross-sectional study of dental professionals. *Environ Res.* 2023;220:115229.

145. Crowe W, Doherty L, Watson G, et al. Mercury in Hair Is Inversely Related to Disease Associated Damage in Systemic Lupus Erythematosus. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2015;13(1):ijerph13010075.
146. Di Pietro A, Visalli G, La Maestra S, et al. Biomonitoring of DNA damage in peripheral blood lymphocytes of subjects with dental restorative fillings. *Mutat Res*. 2008;650(2):115-22.
147. Guzzi G, Fogazzi GB, Cantu M, et al. Dental amalgam, mercury toxicity, and renal autoimmunity. *J Environ Pathol Toxicol Oncol*. 2008;27(2):147-55.
148. Kristoffersen AE, Alraek T, Stub T, et al. Health Complaints Attributed to Dental Amalgam: A Retrospective Survey Exploring Perceived Health Changes Related to Amalgam Removal. *Open Dent J*. 2016;10(1):739-51.
149. Movassagh H, Halchenko Y, Sampath V, et al. Maternal gestational mercury exposure in relation to cord blood T cell alterations and placental gene expression signatures. *Environ Res*. 2021;201:111385.
150. Pigatto PD, Minoia C, Ronchi A, et al. Allergological and toxicological aspects in a multiple chemical sensitivity cohort. *Oxid Med Cell Longev*. 2013;2013:356235.
151. Visalli G, Baluce B, La Maestra S, et al. Genotoxic damage in the oral mucosa cells of subjects carrying restorative dental fillings. *Arch Toxicol*. 2013;87(1):179-87.
152. Al-Saleh I, Al-Sedairi AA. Mercury (Hg) burden in children: the impact of dental amalgam. *Sci Total Environ*. 2011;409(16):3003-15.
153. Al-Saleh I, Al-Sedairi A, Elkhatib R. Effect of mercury (Hg) dental amalgam fillings on renal and oxidative stress biomarkers in children. *Sci Total Environ*. 2012;431:188-96.
154. Albakry M. Alveolar Bone Loss, Plaque Index, and Gingival Index among Non-Diabetics Treated with Class II Amalgam Restorations for Different Service Lives. *American Journal of Biomedical Science & Research*. 2021;13(6):603-10.
155. M A. The Effect of the Different Service Lives of Class II Amalgam Restorations on Periodontal Health among Type 2 Diabetes Patients. *International Journal of Dentistry and Oral Health*. 2021;7(6).
156. Dulamea AO, Boscaiu V, Sava MM. Disability status and dental pathology in multiple sclerosis patients. *Mult Scler Relat Disord*. 2015;4(6):567-71.
157. Echeverria D, Woods JS, Heyer NJ, et al. The association between serotonin transporter gene promoter polymorphism (5-HTTLPR) and elemental mercury exposure on mood and behavior in humans. *J Toxicol Environ Health A*. 2010;73(15):1003-20.
158. Geier DA, Geier MR. Dental Amalgams and the Incidence Rate of Arthritis among American Adults. *Clin Med Insights Arthritis Musculoskelet Disord*. 2021;14:11795441211016261.
159. Geier DA, Geier MR. Reported asthma and dental amalgam exposure among adults in the United States: An assessment of the National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey. *SAGE Open Med*. 2021;9:20503121211048677.
160. Heyer NJ, Echeverria D, Farin FM, Woods JS. The association between serotonin transporter gene promoter polymorphism (5-HTTLPR), self-reported symptoms, and dental mercury exposure. *J Toxicol Environ Health A*. 2008;71(19):1318-26.
161. Heyer NJ, Echeverria D, Martin MD, et al. Catechol O-methyltransferase (COMT) VAL158MET functional polymorphism, dental mercury exposure, and self-reported symptoms and mood. *J Toxicol Environ Health A*. 2009;72(9):599-609.
162. Kindler S, Seebauer C, Mksoud M, et al. Impact of dental restorations and removable prostheses on potentially malignant oral mucosal disorders in the general population. *J Prosthet Dent*. 2023;129(1):89-95.
163. Lopez-Jornet P, Camacho-Alonso F. Do metal restorations in mouth alter clinical and histological appearance of oral lichen planus? *N Y State Dent J*. 2008;74(6):40-3.
164. Mittermuller P, Hiller KA, Schmalz G, Buchalla W. Five hundred patients reporting on adverse effects from dental materials: Frequencies, complaints, symptoms, allergies. *Dent Mater*. 2018;34(12):1756-68.

165. Moen B, Hollund B, Riise T. Neurological symptoms among dental assistants: a cross-sectional study. *J Occup Med Toxicol*. 2008;3:10.
166. Murariu A, Savin C, Feier R, Balan A. Study Regarding the Toxic Effects of Resin-based Dental Materials. *REVISTA DE CHIMIE*. 2016;67(9):1876-8.
167. Sletvold H, Svendsen K, Aas O, et al. Neuropsychological function and past exposure to metallic mercury in female dental workers. *Scand J Psychol*. 2012;53(2):136-43.
168. Stahlacke K, Soderfeldt B. Factors related to persons with health problems attributed to dental filling materials--part one in a triangular study on 65 and 75 years old Swedes. *Swed Dent J*. 2012;36(4):195-206.
169. Sun YH, Nfor ON, Huang JY, Liaw YP. Association between dental amalgam fillings and Alzheimer's disease: a population-based cross-sectional study in Taiwan. *Alzheimers Res Ther*. 2015;7(1):65.
170. Szklarek M, Kostka T. The impact of the use of amalgam in dental treatment on the prevalence of restless legs syndrome in older people. *Med Pr*. 2019;70(1):9-16.
171. Tillberg A, Marell L, Berglund A, Eriksson N. Replacement of restorations in subjects with symptoms associated with dental restorations; a follow-up study. *Eur J Oral Sci*. 2008;116(4):362-8.
172. Zhang X, Gelderblom HR, Zierold K, Reichart PA. Morphological findings and energy dispersive X-ray microanalysis of oral amalgam tattoos. *Micron*. 2007;38(5):543-8.
173. Geier DA, Kern JK, Geier MR. A prospective study of prenatal mercury exposure from maternal dental amalgams and autism severity. *Acta Neurobiol Exp (Wars)*. 2009;69(2):189-97.
174. Jaakkola MS, Leino T, Tammilehto L, et al. Respiratory effects of exposure to methacrylates among dental assistants. *Allergy*. 2007;62(6):648-54.
175. Zarra T, Lambrianidis T. Occupational ocular accidents amongst Greek endodontists: a national questionnaire survey. *Int Endod J*. 2013;46(8):710-9.
176. Anglen J, Gruninger SE, Chou HN, et al. Occupational mercury exposure in association with prevalence of multiple sclerosis and tremor among US dentists. *J Am Dent Assoc*. 2015;146(9):659-68 e1.
177. Barregard L, Trachtenberg F, McKinlay S. Renal effects of dental amalgam in children: the New England children's amalgam trial. *Environ Health Perspect*. 2008;116(3):394-9.
178. Bellinger DC, Daniel D, Trachtenberg F, et al. Dental amalgam restorations and children's neuropsychological function: the New England Children's Amalgam Trial. *Environ Health Perspect*. 2007;115(3):440-6.
179. Bellinger DC, Trachtenberg F, Barregard L, et al. Neuropsychological and renal effects of dental amalgam in children: a randomized clinical trial. *JAMA*. 2006;295(15):1775-83.
180. Bellinger DC, Trachtenberg F, Zhang A, et al. Dental amalgam and psychosocial status: the New England Children's Amalgam Trial. *J Dent Res*. 2008;87(5):470-4.
181. DeRouen TA, Martin MD, Leroux BG, et al. Neurobehavioral effects of dental amalgam in children: a randomized clinical trial. *JAMA*. 2006;295(15):1784-92.
182. Geier DA, Carmody T, Kern JK, et al. A significant relationship between mercury exposure from dental amalgams and urinary porphyrins: a further assessment of the Casa Pia children's dental amalgam trial. *Biometals*. 2011;24(2):215-24.
183. Halperin-Sternfeld M, Saminsky M, Machtei EE, Horwitz J. The association between dental proximal restorations and periodontal disease: A retrospective 10-18 years longitudinal study. *Quintessence Int*. 2016;47(3):249-59.
184. Lauterbach M, Martins IP, Castro-Caldas A, et al. Neurological outcomes in children with and without amalgam-related mercury exposure: seven years of longitudinal observations in a randomized trial. *J Am Dent Assoc*. 2008;139(2):138-45.
185. Lin PY, Wang J, Chiang YC, et al. Risk of subsequent attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder among children and adolescents with amalgam restorations: A nationwide longitudinal study. *Community Dent Oral Epidemiol*. 2018;46(1):47-53.

186. Martin MD, Woods JS, Leroux BG, et al. Longitudinal urinary creatinine excretion values among preadolescents and adolescents. *Transl Res.* 2008;151(1):51-6.
187. Maserejian NN, Shrader P, Brown OA, et al. Dental sealants and composite restorations and longitudinal changes in immune function markers in children. *Int J Paediatr Dent.* 2014;24(3):215-25.
188. Maserejian NN, Hauser R, Tavares M, et al. Dental composites and amalgam and physical development in children. *J Dent Res.* 2012;91(11):1019-25.
189. Perng WT, Ma KS, Hung HY, et al. Dental caries and risk of newly-onset systemic lupus erythematosus: a nationwide population-based cohort study. *Curr Med Res Opin.* 2023;39(2):307-17.
190. Ptak DM, Solanki A, Andler L, et al. The Pulpal Response to Crown Preparation and Cementation. *J Endod.* 2023;49(5):462-8.
191. Roberts MC, Leroux BG, Sampson J, et al. Dental amalgam and antibiotic- and/or mercury-resistant bacteria. *J Dent Res.* 2008;87(5):475-9.
192. Shenker BJ, Maserejian NN, Zhang A, McKinlay S. Immune function effects of dental amalgam in children: a randomized clinical trial. *J Am Dent Assoc.* 2008;139(11):1496-505.
193. Woods JS, Martin MD, Leroux BG, et al. Biomarkers of kidney integrity in children and adolescents with dental amalgam mercury exposure: findings from the Casa Pia children's amalgam trial. *Environ Res.* 2008;108(3):393-9.
194. Adams JB, Romdahlvik J, Levine KE, Hu LW. Mercury in first-cut baby hair of children with autism versus typically-developing children. *Toxicological & Environmental Chemistry.* 2008;90(4):739-53.
195. Ahlgren C, Axell T, Moller H, et al. Contact allergies to potential allergens in patients with oral lichen lesions. *Clin Oral Investig.* 2014;18(1):227-37.
196. Bellinger DC, Trachtenberg F, Daniel D, et al. A dose-effect analysis of children's exposure to dental amalgam and neuropsychological function: the New England Children's Amalgam Trial. *J Am Dent Assoc.* 2007;138(9):1210-6.
197. Bjorkman L, Brokstad KA, Moen K, Jonsson R. Minor changes in serum levels of cytokines after removal of amalgam restorations. *Toxicol Lett.* 2012;211(2):120-5.
198. Bjorkman L, Lygre GB, Haug K, Skjaerven R. Perinatal death and exposure to dental amalgam fillings during pregnancy in the population-based MoBa cohort. *PLoS One.* 2018;13(12):e0208803.
199. Bjorkman L, Musial F, Alraek T, et al. Mercury, silver and selenium in serum before and after removal of amalgam restorations: results from a prospective cohort study in Norway. *Acta Odontol Scand.* 2023;81(4):298-310.
200. Bjorkman L, Musial F, Alraek T, et al. Removal of dental amalgam restorations in patients with health complaints attributed to amalgam: A prospective cohort study. *J Oral Rehabil.* 2020;47(11):1422-34.
201. Bjorkman L, Sjursen TT, Dalen K, et al. Long term changes in health complaints after removal of amalgam restorations. *Acta Odontol Scand.* 2017;75(3):208-19.
202. Cabana-Munoz ME, Parmigiani-Izquierdo JM, Bravo-Gonzalez LA, et al. Increased Zn/Glutathione Levels and Higher Superoxide Dismutase-1 Activity as Biomarkers of Oxidative Stress in Women with Long-Term Dental Amalgam Fillings: Correlation between Mercury/Aluminium Levels (in Hair) and Antioxidant Systems in Plasma. *PLoS One.* 2015;10(6):e0126339.
203. Cabana-Munoz ME, Parmigiani-Izquierdo JM, Camacho Alonso F, Merino JJ. Increased Systemic Malondialdehyde Levels and Decreased Mo/Co, Co/Fe(2+) Ratios in Patients with Long-Term Dental Titanium Implants and Amalgams. *J Clin Med.* 2019;8(1).
204. Chen KH, Yu HC, Chang YC. Analysis of dental amalgam fillings on primary Sjogren's syndrome: A population-based case-control study in Taiwan. *Medicine (Baltimore).* 2021;100(47):e28031.
205. Chen KH. Association between Parkinson's Disease and Dental Amalgam Filling: A Study of Nationwide Population-Based Case Control in Taiwan. *Applied Ecology and Environmental Research.* 2020;18(5):7159-65.
206. Daniels JL, Rowland AS, Longnecker MP, et al. Maternal dental history, child's birth outcome and early cognitive development. *Paediatr Perinat Epidemiol.* 2007;21(5):448-57.

207. Daume L, Kreis C, Bohner L, et al. Clinical characteristics of oral lichen planus and its causal context with dental restorative materials and oral health-related quality of life. *BMC Oral Health*. 2021;21(1):262.
208. Duplinsky Thomas G, Cicchetti Domenic V. The Health Status of Dentists Exposed to Mercury from Silver Amalgam Tooth Restorations. *International Journal Of Statistics In Medical Research*. 2012;1(1):1-15.
209. Maserejian NN, Trachtenberg FL, Hauser R, et al. Dental composite restorations and psychosocial function in children. *Pediatrics*. 2012;130(2):e328-38.
210. Sinha N, Hamre HJ, Musial F, et al. Health complaints before and at one and five years after removal of dental amalgam restorations - data from a prospective cohort study in Norway. *Acta Odontol Scand*. 2024;83:219-29.
211. Sjursen TT, Lygre GB, Dalen K, et al. Changes in health complaints after removal of amalgam fillings. *J Oral Rehabil*. 2011;38(11):835-48.
212. Eyeson J, House I, Yang YH, Warnakulasuriya KA. Relationship between mercury levels in blood and urine and complaints of chronic mercury toxicity from amalgam restorations. *Br Dent J*. 2010;208(4):E7; discussion 162-3.
213. Forkel S, Schubert S, Corvin L, et al. Contact allergies to dental materials in patients. *Br J Dermatol*. 2024;190(6):895-903.
214. Franzblau A, d'Arcy H, Ishak MB, et al. Low-level mercury exposure and peripheral nerve function. *Neurotoxicology*. 2012;33(3):299-306.
215. Frisk P, Danersund A, Hudecek R, Lindh U. Changed clinical chemistry pattern in blood after removal of dental amalgam and other metal alloys supported by antioxidant therapy. *Biol Trace Elem Res*. 2007;120(1-3):163-70.
216. Geier DA, Carmody T, Kern JK, et al. A significant dose-dependent relationship between mercury exposure from dental amalgams and kidney integrity biomarkers: a further assessment of the Casa Pia children's dental amalgam trial. *Hum Exp Toxicol*. 2013;32(4):434-40.
217. Heggland I, Irgens A, Tollanes M, et al. Pregnancy outcomes among female dental personnel - a registry-based retrospective cohort study. *Scand J Work Environ Health*. 2011;37(6):539-46.
218. Heratizadeh A, Werfel T, Schubert S, et al. Contact sensitization in dental technicians with occupational contact dermatitis. Data of the Information Network of Departments of Dermatology (IVDK) 2001-2015. *Contact Dermatitis*. 2018;78(4):266-73.
219. Hilt B, Svendsen K, Syversen T, et al. Occurrence of cognitive and neurological symptoms in norwegian dentists. *Saf Health Work*. 2011;2(2):176-82.
220. Hilt B, Svendsen K, Syversen T, et al. Occurrence of cognitive symptoms in dental assistants with previous occupational exposure to metallic mercury. *Neurotoxicology*. 2009;30(6):1202-6.
221. Hsu YC, Chang CW, Lee HL, et al. Association between History of Dental Amalgam Fillings and Risk of Parkinson's Disease: A Population-Based Retrospective Cohort Study in Taiwan. *PLoS One*. 2016;11(12):e0166552.
222. Jones L, Bunnell J, Stillman J. A 30-year follow-up of residual effects on New Zealand School Dental Nurses, from occupational mercury exposure. *Hum Exp Toxicol*. 2007;26(4):367-74.
223. Lartitegui-Sebastian MJ, Martinez-Revilla B, Saiz-Garcia C, et al. Oral lichenoid lesions associated with amalgam restorations: a prospective pilot study addressing the adult population of the Basque Country. *Med Oral Patol Oral Cir Bucal*. 2012;17(4):e545-9.
224. Lindbohm ML, Ylostalo P, Sallmen M, et al. Occupational exposure in dentistry and miscarriage. *Occup Environ Med*. 2007;64(2):127-33.
225. Louopou RC, Trottier H, Arbuckle TE, Fraser WD. Dental amalgams and risk of gestational hypertension in the MIREC study. *Pregnancy Hypertens*. 2020;21:84-9.
226. Lygre GB, Aase H, Haug K, et al. Prenatal exposure to dental amalgam and risk of symptoms of attention-deficit and hyperactivity disorder (ADHD). *Community Dent Oral Epidemiol*. 2018;46(5):472-81.

227. Lygre GB, Haug K, Skjaerven R, Bjorkman L. Prenatal exposure to dental amalgam and pregnancy outcome. *Community Dent Oral Epidemiol.* 2016;44(5):442-9.
228. Lygre GB, Sjursten TT, Svahn J, et al. Characterization of health complaints before and after removal of amalgam fillings--3-year follow-up. *Acta Odontol Scand.* 2013;71(3-4):560-9.
229. Lynch M, Ryan A, Galvin S, et al. Patch testing in oral lichenoid lesions of uncertain etiology. *Dermatitis.* 2015;26(2):89-93.
230. Ma KS, Thota E, Huang JY, et al. Onset of oral lichen planus following dental treatments: A nested case-control study. *Oral Dis.* 2023;29(3):1269-81.
231. Marell L, Tillberg A, Widman L, et al. Regression of oral lichenoid lesions after replacement of dental restorations. *J Oral Rehabil.* 2014;41(5):381-91.
232. Melchart D, Vogt S, Kohler W, et al. Treatment of health complaints attributed to amalgam. *J Dent Res.* 2008;87(4):349-53.
233. Mikhailichenko N, Yagami K, Chiou JY, et al. Exposure to Dental Filling Materials and the Risk of Dementia: A Population-Based Nested Case Control Study in Taiwan. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2019;16(18).
234. Montebugnoli L, Venturi M, Gissi DB, Cervellati F. Clinical and histologic healing of lichenoid oral lesions following amalgam removal: a prospective study. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol Oral Radiol.* 2012;113(6):766-72.
235. Naimi-Akbar A, Sandborgh Englund G, Ekbom A, et al. Cognitive function among sons of women who worked in dentistry. *Scand J Work Environ Health.* 2012;38(6):546-52.
236. Naimi-Akbar A, Sandborgh-Englund G, Ekbom A, et al. Mortality among sons of female dental personnel--a national cohort study. *J Perinat Med.* 2014;42(5):655-61.
237. Naimi-Akbar A, Svedberg P, Alexanderson K, et al. Health-related quality of life and symptoms in patients with experiences of health problems related to dental restorative materials. *Community Dent Oral Epidemiol.* 2013;41(2):163-72.
238. Pezelj-Ribaric S, Prpic J, Miletic I, et al. Association between oral lichenoid reactions and amalgam restorations. *J Eur Acad Dermatol Venereol.* 2008;22(10):1163-7.
239. Rojas-Alcayaga G, Carrasco-Labra A, Danus P, et al. Determination of susceptibility to sensitization to dental materials in atopic and non-atopic patients. *Med Oral Patol Oral Cir Bucal.* 2012;17(2):e320-4.
240. Sundstrom A, Bergdahl J, Nyberg L, et al. Stressful negative life events and amalgam-related complaints. *Community Dent Oral Epidemiol.* 2011;39(1):12-8.
241. Sundstrom A, Bergdahl J, Nyberg L, et al. Cognitive status in persons with amalgam-related complaints. *J Dent Res.* 2010;89(11):1236-40.
242. Suter VG, Warnakulasuriya S. The role of patch testing in the management of oral lichenoid reactions. *J Oral Pathol Med.* 2016;45(1):48-57.
243. Thygesen LC, Flachs EM, Hanehoj K, et al. Hospital admissions for neurological and renal diseases among dentists and dental assistants occupationally exposed to mercury. *Occup Environ Med.* 2011;68(12):895-901.
244. Tseng CF, Chen KH, Yu HC, Chang YC. Association between Dental Amalgam Filling and Essential Tremor: A Nationwide Population-Based Case Control Study in Taiwan. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2020;17(3).
245. Tseng CF, Chen KH, Yu HC, et al. Dental Amalgam Fillings and Multiple Sclerosis: A Nationwide Population-Based Case-Control Study in Taiwan. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2020;17(8).
246. Watson GE, Evans K, Thurston SW, et al. Prenatal exposure to dental amalgam in the Seychelles Child Development Nutrition Study: associations with neurodevelopmental outcomes at 9 and 30 months. *Neurotoxicology.* 2012;33(6):1511-7.
247. Watson GE, Lynch M, Myers GJ, et al. Prenatal exposure to dental amalgam: evidence from the Seychelles Child Development Study main cohort. *J Am Dent Assoc.* 2011;142(11):1283-94.

248. Watson GE, van Wijngaarden E, Love TM, et al. Neurodevelopmental outcomes at 5 years in children exposed prenatally to maternal dental amalgam: the Seychelles Child Development Nutrition Study. *Neurotoxicol Teratol.* 2013;39:57-62.
249. Weber ME, Yiannias JA, Hougeir FG, et al. Intraoral metal contact allergy as a possible risk factor for oral squamous cell carcinoma. *Ann Otol Rhinol Laryngol.* 2012;121(6):389-94.
250. Weidenhammer W, Bornschein S, Zilker T, et al. Predictors of treatment outcomes after removal of amalgam fillings: associations between subjective symptoms, psychometric variables and mercury levels. *Community Dent Oral Epidemiol.* 2010;38(2):180-9.
251. Weidenhammer W, Hausteiner C, Zilker T, et al. Does a specific dental amalgam syndrome exist? A comparative study. *Acta Odontol Scand.* 2009;67(4):233-9.
252. Wright B, Pearce H, Allgar V, et al. A comparison of urinary mercury between children with autism spectrum disorders and control children. *PLoS One.* 2012;7(2):e29547.
253. Zwicker JD, Dutton DJ, Emery JC. Longitudinal analysis of the association between removal of dental amalgam, urine mercury and 14 self-reported health symptoms. *Environ Health.* 2014;13:95.
254. Piagno H, Afshari R. Mercury from crematoriums: human health risk assessment and estimate of total emissions in British Columbia. *Can J Public Health.* 2020;111(6):1011-9.
255. Gavic L, Gorseta K, Glavina D, et al. In vivo assessment of genotoxicity in buccal cells of children undergoing tooth restoration. *Cent Eur J Public Health.* 2019;27(4):312-9.
256. Hu CJ, Yu HC, Chang YC. Investigation of the Impact of Dental Care via Composite Resin Restoration among Children with Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder: A Registry-Based Nested Case-Control Study. *Healthcare (Basel).* 2021;9(7).
257. Leybovich M, Bissada NF, Teich S, et al. Treatment of noncarious cervical lesions by a subepithelial connective tissue graft versus a composite resin restoration. *Int J Periodontics Restorative Dent.* 2014;34(5):649-54.
258. Maserejian NN, Shrader P, Trachtenberg FL, et al. Dental sealants and flowable composite restorations and psychosocial, neuropsychological, and physical development in children. *Pediatr Dent.* 2014;36(1):68-75.
259. Maserejian NN, Trachtenberg FL, Hauser R, et al. Dental composite restorations and neuropsychological development in children: treatment level analysis from a randomized clinical trial. *Neurotoxicology.* 2012;33(5):1291-7.
260. Pettini F, Savino M, Corsalini M, et al. Cytogenetic genotoxic investigation in peripheral blood lymphocytes of subjects with dental composite restorative filling materials. *J Biol Regul Homeost Agents.* 2015;29(1):229-33.
261. Tadin A, Galic N, Mladinic M, et al. Genotoxicity in gingival cells of patients undergoing tooth restoration with two different dental composite materials. *Clin Oral Investig.* 2014;18(1):87-96.
262. Woods JS, Martin MD, Leroux BG, et al. Urinary porphyrin excretion in children with mercury amalgam treatment: findings from the Casa Pia Children's Dental Amalgam Trial. *J Toxicol Environ Health A.* 2009;72(14):891-6.
263. Dermata A, Papageorgiou SN, Fragkou S, Kotsanos N. Comparison of resin modified glass ionomer cement and composite resin in class II primary molar restorations: a 2-year parallel randomised clinical trial. *Eur Arch Paediatr Dent.* 2018;19(6):393-401.
264. Al-Kawas S, Abu-Yousef IA, Kanan S, et al. Analysis of mercury in wastewater of some dental clinics in United Arab Emirates. *Journal of International Environmental Application & Science.* 2008;3(1):21-8.
265. Binner H, Kamali N, Harding M, Sullivan T. Characteristics of wastewater originating from dental practices using predominantly mercury-free dental materials. *Sci Total Environ.* 2022;814:152632.
266. Duane B, Lee MB, White S, et al. An estimated carbon footprint of NHS primary dental care within England. How can dentistry be more environmentally sustainable? *Br Dent J.* 2017;223(8):589-93.

267. Gioda A, Hanke G, Elias-Boneta A, Jimenez-Velez B. A pilot study to determine mercury exposure through vapor and bound to PM10 in a dental school environment. *Toxicol Ind Health*. 2007;23(2):103-13.
268. Kim HJ, Park JH, Sakong J. Estimation of Mercury Emission from Incineration of Extracted Teeth with Dental Amalgam Fillings in South Korea. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2018;15(7).
269. Kontogianni S, Xirogiannopoulou A, Karagiannidis A. Investigating solid waste production and associated management practices in private dental units. *Waste Manag*. 2008;28(8):1441-8.
270. Majstorovic M, Babic Brcic S, Malev O, et al. Environmental implications of dental restorative materials on the zebrafish *Danio rerio*: Are dental chair drainage systems an emerging environmental threat? *Environ Toxicol Pharmacol*. 2024;110:104499.
271. Mandalidis A, Topalidis A, Voudrias EA, Iosifidis N. Composition, production rate and characterization of Greek dental solid waste. *Waste Manag*. 2018;75:124-30.
272. Marquardt W, Seiss M, Hickel R, Reichl FX. Volatile methacrylates in dental practices. *J Adhes Dent*. 2009;11(2):101-7.
273. Mourouzis P, Andreasidou E, Arhakis A, et al. Release of monomers in dental wastewater during treatment. A comparative in vitro and in vivo study based on Fabric phase Sorptive extraction. *Microchemical Journal*. 2022;183.
274. Olivera DS, Morgan MT, Tewolde SN, et al. Clinical Evaluation of a Chairside Amalgam Separator to Meet Environmental Protection Agency Dental Wastewater Regulatory Compliance. *Oper Dent*. 2020;45(2):151-62.
275. Paryag A, Paryag AS, Rafeek RN, Pilgrim A. Mercury pollution from dental amalgam waste in Trinidad and Tobago. *Journal of Water Resource and Protection*. 2010;2(8):762-9.
276. Polydorou O, Schmidt OC, Spraul M, et al. Detection of Bisphenol A in dental wastewater after grinding of dental resin composites. *Dent Mater*. 2020;36(8):1009-18.
277. Shraim A, Alsuhaimei A, Al-Thakafy JT. Dental clinics: a point pollution source, not only of mercury but also of other amalgam constituents. *Chemosphere*. 2011;84(8):1133-9.
278. Simu MR, Borzan C, Mesaros M, et al. COMPLEX CHARACTERIZATION OF DENTAL OFFICE AEROSOLS REVEALS IMPORTANT LOADS OF RISK ELEMENTS FOR THE HUMAN HEALTH. *DIGEST JOURNAL OF NANOMATERIALS AND BIOSTRUCTURES*. 2014;9(4):1429-38.
279. Stone ME, Scott JW, Schultz ST, et al. Comparison of chlorine and chloramine in the release of mercury from dental amalgam. *Sci Total Environ*. 2009;407(2):770-5.
280. Takaoka M, Oshita K, Takeda N, Morisawa S. Mercury emission from crematories in Japan. *Atmospheric Chemistry & Physics Discussions*. 2009;9(6):27195-214.
281. Van Landuyt KL, Hellack B, Van Meerbeek B, et al. Nanoparticle release from dental composites. *Acta Biomater*. 2014;10(1):365-74.
282. Warwick D, Young M, Palmer J, Ermel RW. Mercury vapor volatilization from particulate generated from dental amalgam removal with a high-speed dental drill - a significant source of exposure. *J Occup Med Toxicol*. 2019;14(1):22.
283. Warwick R, O'Connor A, Lamey B. Mercury vapour exposure during dental student training in amalgam removal. *J Occup Med Toxicol*. 2013;8(1):27.
284. Konno K, Livoreil B, Pullin AS. Collaboration for Environmental Evidence Critical Appraisal Tool version 0.3. 2021 [Available from: <https://environmentalevidence.org/cee-critical-appraisal-tool/>].
285. Bartelt K, Lipman R, Estrich C, et al. Mercury-Containing Amalgam Fillings Account for Less Than 6% of Posterior Tooth Fillings in 2022-2023 [Available from: <https://www.epicresearch.org/articles/mercury-containing-amalgam-fillings-account-for-less-than-6-of-posterior-tooth-fillings-in-2022>].
286. Worthington HV, Khangura S, Seal K, et al. Direct composite resin fillings versus amalgam fillings for permanent posterior teeth. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*. 2021;8(8):Cd005620.
287. Khangura SD, Seal K, Esfandiari S, et al. CADTH Health Technology Assessments. Composite Resin Versus Amalgam for Dental Restorations: A Health Technology Assessment. Ottawa (ON): Canadian Agency for Drugs and Technologies in Health

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288. Gallusi G, Libonati A, Piro M, et al. Is Dental Amalgam a Higher Risk Factor rather than Resin-Based Restorations for Systemic Conditions? A Systematic Review. *Materials (Basel)*. 2021;14(8).
289. Rasines Alcaraz MG, Veitz-Keenan A, Sahrman P, et al. Direct composite resin fillings versus amalgam fillings for permanent or adult posterior teeth. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*. 2014(3):Cd005620.
290. Heintze SD, Loguercio AD, Hanzen TA, et al. Clinical efficacy of resin-based direct posterior restorations and glass-ionomer restorations - An updated meta-analysis of clinical outcome parameters. *Dent Mater*. 2022;38(5):e109-e35.
291. Heintze SD, Rousson V, Hickel R. Clinical effectiveness of direct anterior restorations--a meta-analysis. *Dent Mater*. 2015;31(5):481-95.
292. Bezerra IM, Brito ACM, de Sousa SA, et al. Glass ionomer cements compared with composite resin in restoration of noncarious cervical lesions: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Heliyon*. 2020;6(5):e03969.
293. Tibau A, Grube B. Mercury Contamination from Dental Amalgam. *Journal of health & pollution*. 2019;Volume 9:1-11.
294. MacLeod M, Arp HPH, Tekman MB, Jahnke A. The global threat from plastic pollution. *Science*. 2021;373(6550):61-5.
295. Martínez G, Merinero M, Pérez-Aranda M, et al. Environmental Impact of Nanoparticles' Application as an Emerging Technology: A Review. *Materials (Basel)*. 2020;14(1).
296. Mourouzis P, Andreasidou E, Arhakis A, et al. Release of monomers in dental wastewater during treatment. A comparative in vitro and in vivo study based on Fabric phase Sorptive extraction. *Microchemical Journal*. 2022;183:107999.
297. Sekovanić A, Piasek M, Orct T, et al. Mercury Exposure Assessment in Mother-Infant Pairs from Continental and Coastal Croatia. *Biomolecules*. 2020;10(6).
298. The World Bank. World Bank Country and Lending Groups 2024 [cited 2025 7th July]. Available from: <https://datahelpdesk.worldbank.org/knowledgebase/articles/906519-world-bank-country-and-lending-groups>].
299. Cochrane Methods. PROGRESS-Plus 2025 [Available from: <https://methods.cochrane.org/equity/projects/evidence-equity/progress-plus>].
300. Effective Public Health Practice Project. EPHPP Quality Assessment Tool for Quantitative Studies 2010 [Available from: https://merst.healthsci.mcmaster.ca/wp-content/uploads/2022/08/quality-assessment-tool_2010.pdf].
301. Brookings. Global manufacturing scorecard: How the US compares to 18 other nations 2018 [cited 2025 14th July]. Available from: <https://www.brookings.edu/articles/global-manufacturing-scorecard-how-the-us-compares-to-18-other-nations/>].
302. Ha E, Basu N, Bose-O'Reilly S, et al. Current progress on understanding the impact of mercury on human health. *Environ Res*. 2017;152:419-33.
303. Bayne S, Petersen PE, Piper D, et al. The challenge for innovation in direct restorative materials. *Adv Dent Res*. 2013;25(1):8-17.
304. Myers DE, Hutz RJ. Current status of potential bisphenol toxicity in dentistry. *Gen Dent*. 2011;59(4):262-5.
305. Environment Canada. Performance report : pollution prevention notice for dental amalgam waste. Gatineau, Quebec: Environment Canada; 2015.
306. World Health Organization & Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. Joint FAO/WHO expert meeting to review toxicological and health aspects of bisphenol A : final report, including report of stakeholder meeting on bisphenol A, 1-5 November 2010, Ottawa, Canada. World Health Organisation; 2011. [Available from: <https://iris.who.int/handle/10665/44624>].
307. Canada EaCC. Canadian Mercury Science Assessment Report. Environment and Climate Change Canada; 2016.

308. Baird HM, Mulligan S, Webb TL, et al. Exploring attitudes towards more sustainable dentistry among adults living in the UK. *Br Dent J.* 2022;233(4):333-42.

Appendix A: Search report

Bibliographic database searches

Database: MEDLINE

Host: Ovid

Issue: 1946 to November 05, 2024

Date Searched: 6th November 2024

Searcher: SB

Hits: 5604

Strategy:

1. ((canine* or cavity or cavities or caries or dental or dentist* or fill* or incisor* or molar* or premolars or tooth or teeth or repair* or restor*) and amalgam).tw.
2. Dental Amalgam/
3. ("bisphenol A-Glycidyl methacrylate" or "Bis-GMA").tw.
4. (resin* and composite* and (canine* or cavity or cavities or caries or dental or dentist* or fill* or incisor* or molar* or premolars or tooth or teeth or repair* or restor*)).tw.
5. ("bulk fill*" and (canine* or cavity or cavities or caries or dental or dentist* or fill* or incisor* or molar* or premolars or tooth or teeth or repair* or restor*)).tw.
6. exp Composite Resins/
7. ("glass ionomer" or "ionomer cement" or giomer*).tw.
8. (GIC and (canine* or cavity or cavities or caries or dental or dentist* or fill* or incisor* or molar* or premolars or tooth or teeth or repair* or restor*)).tw.
9. Glass Ionomer Cements/
10. (compomers or "polyacid modified resin based" or PAMRC).tw.
11. Compomers/
12. or/1-11
13. (ae or co or to or po).fs.
14. (adverse* or bioacc* or bioavail* or breakage* or "clinically accept*" or "clinically unaccept*" or complication* or discomfort* or harm* or poison* or safe* or "side effect*" or tolerated or tolerance or toxic*).tw.

15. Pregnancy complications/dt
16. ("Bisphenol A" or BPA or mercury).tw.
17. (monomer* adj3 concentration).tw.
18. or/13-17
19. (incidence or prognos* or risk* or survival).tw.
20. exp *Prognosis/
21. exp *risk/
22. exp *Incidence/
23. or/19-22
24. ("global warming" or pollut*).tw.
25. ((biohazard* or dangerous or hazard* or waste) adj4 (chemical* or discharge* or emission* or material* or product* or release or substance*)).tw.
26. (environment* adj4 (affect* or effect* or damag* or hazard* or impact* or sustainab*)).tw.
27. ((carbon or CO2 or CO2e) adj4 (emission* or footprint or impact* or output* or green* or sustainab*)).tw.
28. (greenhouse adj1 (effect* or gas*)).tw.
29. (("life cycle" or lifecycle) adj1 (analysis or analyses or assessment*)).tw.
30. (wastewater or (waste adj2 water)).tw.
31. or/24-30
32. 18 or 23 or 31
33. 12 and 32
34. limit 33 to (english language and yr="2007 -Current")

Database: [CAB Abstracts](#)

Host: Ovid

Issue: 1973 to 2024 Week 44

Date Searched: 6th November 2024

Searcher: SB

Hits: 193

Strategy: as per MEDLINE without MeSH terms

Database: CINAHL

Host: EBSCO

Issue: n/a

Date Searched: 6th November 2024

Searcher: SB

Hits: 1425

Strategy:

1. TI (((canine* or cavity or cavities or caries or dental or dentist* or fill* or incisor* or molar* or premolars or tooth or teeth or repair* or restor*) and amalgam*)) OR AB (((canine* or cavity or cavities or caries or dental or dentist* or fill* or incisor* or molar* or premolars or tooth or teeth or repair* or restor*) and amalgam*))
2. (MH "Dental Amalgam")
3. TI (("bisphenol A-Glycidyl methacrylate" or "Bis-GMA")) OR AB (("bisphenol A-Glycidyl methacrylate" or "Bis-GMA"))
4. TI ((resin* and composite* and (canine* or cavity or cavities or caries or dental or dentist* or fill* or incisor* or molar* or premolars or tooth or teeth or repair* or restor*))) OR AB ((resin* and composite* and (canine* or cavity or cavities or caries or dental or dentist* or fill* or incisor* or molar* or premolars or tooth or teeth or repair* or restor*)))
5. (MH "Composite Resins")
6. TI (("bulk fill*" and (canine* or cavity or cavities or caries or dental or dentist* or fill* or incisor* or molar* or premolars or tooth or teeth or repair* or restor*))) OR AB (("bulk fill*" and (canine* or cavity or cavities or caries or dental or dentist* or fill* or incisor* or molar* or premolars or tooth or teeth or repair* or restor*)))
7. TI (("glass ionomer" or "ionomer cement" or giomer*)) OR AB (("glass ionomer" or "ionomer cement" or giomer*))
8. (MH "Glass Ionomer Cements")
9. TI ((GIC and (canine* or cavity or cavities or caries or dental or dentist* or fill* or incisor* or molar* or premolars or tooth or teeth or repair* or restor*))) OR AB ((GIC and (canine* or

- cavity or cavities or caries or dental or dentist* or fill* or incisor* or molar* or premolars or tooth or teeth or repair* or restor*)))
10. TI (compomers or "polyacid modified resin based" or PAMRC) OR AB ((compomers or "polyacid modified resin based" or PAMRC))
 11. S1 OR S2 OR S3 OR S4 OR S5 OR S6 OR S7 OR S8 OR S9 OR S10
 12. TI (adverse* or bioacc* or bioavail* or breakage* or "clinically accept*" or "clinically unaccept*" or complication* or discomfort* or harm* or poison* or safe* or "side effect*" or tolerated or tolerance or toxic*) OR AB (adverse* or bioacc* or bioavail* or breakage* or "clinically accept*" or "clinically unaccept*" or complication* or discomfort* or harm* or poison* or safe* or "side effect*" or tolerated or tolerance or toxic*)
 13. (MH "Pregnancy Complications/DT")
 14. TI (("Bisphenol A" or BPA or mercury)) OR AB (("Bisphenol A" or BPA or mercury))
 15. TI (monomer* n2 concentration) OR AB (monomer* n2 concentration)
 16. TI ((incidence or prognos* or risk* or survival)) OR AB ((incidence or prognos* or risk* or survival))
 17. (MM "Prognosis+")
 18. (MM "Risk Factors")
 19. (MM "Incidence")
 20. TI ("global warming" or pollut*) OR AB ("global warming" or pollut*)
 21. TI ((biohazard* or dangerous or hazard* or waste) n3 (chemical* or discharge* or emission* or material* or product* or release or substance*)) OR AB ((biohazard* or dangerous or hazard* or waste) n3 (chemical* or discharge* or emission* or material* or product* or release or substance*))
 22. TI (environment* n3 (affect* or effect* or damag* or hazard* or impact* or sustainab*)) OR AB (environment* n3 (affect* or effect* or damag* or hazard* or impact* or sustainab*))
 23. TI ((carbon or CO2 or CO2e) n3 (emission* or footprint or impact* or output or green* or sustainab*)) OR AB ((carbon or CO2 or CO2e) n3 (emission* or footprint or impact* or output or green* or sustainab*))
 24. TI (greenhouse n0 (effect or gas*)) OR AB (greenhouse n0 (effect or gas*))

25. TI (("life cycle" or lifecycle) n0 (analysis or analyses or assessment*)) OR AB (("life cycle" or lifecycle) n0 (analysis or analyses or assessment*))
26. TI ((wastewater or (waste n1 water))) OR AB ((wastewater or (waste n1 water)))
27. S12 OR S13 OR S14 OR S15 OR S16 OR S17 OR S18 OR S19 OR S20 OR S21 OR S22 OR S23 OR S24 OR S25 OR S26
28. S11 AND S27

Database: [Environment Complete](#)

Host: EBSCO

Issue: n/a

Date Searched: 6th November 2024

Searcher: SB

Hits: 518

Strategy:

1. TI (((canine* or cavity or cavities or caries or dental or dentist* or fill* or incisor* or molar* or premolars or tooth or teeth or repair* or restor*) and amalgam*)) OR AB (((canine* or cavity or cavities or caries or dental or dentist* or fill* or incisor* or molar* or premolars or tooth or teeth or repair* or restor*) and amalgam*))
2. TI (("bisphenol A-Glycidyl methacrylate" or "Bis-GMA")) OR AB (("bisphenol A-Glycidyl methacrylate" or "Bis-GMA"))
3. TI ((resin* and composite* and (canine* or cavity or cavities or caries or dental or dentist* or fill* or incisor* or molar* or premolars or tooth or teeth or repair* or restor*))) OR AB ((resin* n3 composite* and (canine* or cavity or cavities or caries or dental or dentist* or fill* or incisor* or molar* or premolars or tooth or teeth or repair* or restor*)))
4. TI ("bulk fill*" and (canine* or cavity or cavities or caries or dental or dentist* or fill* or incisor* or molar* or premolars or tooth or teeth or repair* or restor*)) OR AB ("bulk fill*" and (canine* or cavity or cavities or caries or dental or dentist* or fill* or incisor* or molar* or premolars or tooth or teeth or repair* or restor*))
5. TI (("glass ionomer" or "ionomer cement")) OR AB (("glass ionomer" or "ionomer cement"))
6. TI ((GIC and (canine* or cavity or cavities or caries or dental or dentist* or fill* or incisor* or molar* or premolars or tooth or teeth or repair* or restor*))) OR AB ((GIC and (canine* or

cavity or cavities or caries or dental or dentist* or fill* or incisor* or molar* or premolars or tooth or teeth or repair* or restor*)))

7. TI ((compomers or "polyacid modified resin based" or PAMRC) OR AB ((compomers or "polyacid modified resin based" or PAMRC))
8. S1 OR S2 OR S3 OR S4 OR S5 OR S6 OR S7
9. DE "AMALGAMS (Alloys)"
10. DE "SYNTHETIC gums & resins"
11. DE "IONOMERS"
12. S9 OR S10 OR S11
13. TI (canine* or cavity or cavities or caries or dental or dentist* or fill* or incisor* or molar* or premolars or tooth or teeth or repair* or restor*) OR AB (canine* or cavity or cavities or caries or dental or dentist* or fill* or incisor* or molar* or premolars or tooth or teeth or repair* or restor*)
14. S12 AND S13
15. S8 OR S14

Database: [GreenFILE](#)

Host: EBSCO

Issue: n/a

Date Searched: 6th November 2024

Searcher: SB

Hits: 213

Strategy:

1. TI (((canine* or cavity or cavities or caries or dental or dentist* or fill* or incisor* or molar* or premolars or tooth or teeth or repair* or restor*) and amalgam*)) OR AB (((canine* or cavity or cavities or caries or dental or dentist* or fill* or incisor* or molar* or premolars or tooth or teeth or repair* or restor*) and amalgam*)
2. TI (("bisphenol A-Glycidyl methacrylate" or "Bis-GMA")) OR AB (("bisphenol A-Glycidyl methacrylate" or "Bis-GMA"))
3. TI (resin* and composite*) OR AB (resin* and composite*)

4. TI ("bulk fill*" and (canine* or cavity or cavities or caries or dental or dentist* or fill* or incisor* or molar* or premolars or tooth or teeth or repair* or restor*)) OR AB ("bulk fill*" and (canine* or cavity or cavities or caries or dental or dentist* or fill* or incisor* or molar* or premolars or tooth or teeth or repair* or restor*))
5. TI (("glass ionomer" or "ionomer cement")) OR AB (("glass ionomer" or "ionomer cement"))
6. TI ((GIC and (canine* or cavity or cavities or caries or dental or dentist* or fill* or incisor* or molar* or premolars or tooth or teeth or repair* or restor*))) OR AB ((GIC and (canine* or cavity or cavities or caries or dental or dentist* or fill* or incisor* or molar* or premolars or tooth or teeth or repair* or restor*)))
7. TI ((compomers or "polyacid modified resin based" or PAMRC)) OR AB ((compomers or "polyacid modified resin based" or PAMRC))
8. S1 OR S2 OR S3 OR S4 OR S5 OR S6 OR S7

Database: [Science Citation Index](#)

Host: Clarivate Analytics

Issue: n/a

Date Searched: 6th November 2024

Searcher: SB

Hits: 5755

Strategy:

1. TS=(((canine* or cavity or cavities or caries or dental or dentist* or fill* or incisor* or molar* or premolars or tooth or teeth or repair* or restor*) and amalgam*))
2. TS=((resin* and composite* and (canine* or cavity or cavities or caries or dental or dentist* or fill* or incisor* or molar* or premolars or tooth or teeth or repair* or restor*)))
3. TS=(((“bulk fill*” and (canine* or cavity or cavities or caries or dental or dentist* or fill* or incisor* or molar* or premolars or tooth or teeth or repair* or restor*)))
4. TS=((GIC and (canine* or cavity or cavities or caries or dental or dentist* or fill* or incisor* or molar* or premolars or tooth or teeth or repair* or restor*))
5. TS=(compomers or "polyacid modified resin based" or PAMRC or "bisphenol A-Glycidyl methacrylate" or "Bis-GMA" or "glass ionomer" or "ionomer cement" or giomer*)
6. #1 OR #2 OR #3 OR #4 OR #5

7. TI=(adverse* or bioacc* or bioavail* or breakage* or "clinically accept*" or "clinically unaccpet*" or complication* or discomfort* or harm* or poison* or safe* or "side effect*" or tolerated or tolerance or toxic*) OR AB=(adverse* or bioacc* or bioavail* or breakage* or "clinically accept*" or "clinically unaccpet*" or complication* or discomfort* or harm* or poison* or safe* or "side effect*" or tolerated or tolerance or toxic*)
8. TI=("Bisphenol A" or BPA or mercury) OR AB=("Bisphenol A" or BPA or mercury)
9. TI=((monomer* near/2 concentration)) OR AB=((monomer* near/2 concentration))
10. TI=((incidence or prognos* or risk* or survival)) OR AB=((incidence or prognos* or risk* or survival))
11. TI(("global warming" or pollut*)) OR AB(("global warming" or pollut*))
12. TI((((biohazard* or dangerous or hazard* or waste) near/3 (chemical* or discharge* or emission* or material* or product* or release or substance*))) OR AB((((biohazard* or dangerous or hazard* or waste) near/3 (chemical* or discharge* or emission* or material* or product* or release or substance*)))
13. TI=((environment* near/3 (affect* or effect* or damag* or hazard* or impact* or sustainab*))) OR AB=((environment* near/3 (affect* or effect* or damag* or hazard* or impact* or sustainab*)))
14. TI((((carbon or CO2 or CO2e) near/2 (emission* or footprint or impact* or output* or green* or sustainab*))) OR AB((((carbon or CO2 or CO2e) near/2 (emission* or footprint or impact* or output* or green* or sustainab*)))
15. TI=((greenhouse near/0 (effect* or gas*))) OR AB=((greenhouse near/0 (effect* or gas*)))
16. TI((((("life cycle" or lifecycle) near/0 (analysis or analyses or assessment*))) OR AB((((("life cycle" or lifecycle) near/0 (analysis or analyses or assessment*)))
17. TI=(wastewater or (waste near/1 water)) OR AB=(wastewater or (waste near/1 water))
18. #7 OR #8 OR #9 OR #10 OR #11 OR #12 OR #13 OR #14 OR #15 OR #16 OR #17
19. #6 AND #18

Notes: date limited 2007 to date of search.

Appendix B: Data extraction items for included studies

Study details	Sample characteristics	Restorative material characteristics	PROGRESS-PLUS (detail relevant to below categories extracted)	Methods	Outcome
First author, date of study	Population age [Mean (SD), [Range]	Total Patient (No): Patients receiving intervention (No); Patients receiving control treatment (No)	Place of residence	Study design	Outcome category
Title of article	Pre-existing restorative material	Dental materials evaluated/implicated (intervention)	Race/ethnicity/culture /language	Setting	Specific relevant outcome measured (Unit of measurement)
Publication type	Number approached/Number in DATABASE vs number eligible to participate vs number consented to participate	Intervention or Exposure of interest (description)	Occupation	Recruitment method (Health) /Sampling strategy (Environmental)	Outcome details (including mean, SD, Range, N included in analysis per group, if reported)
Country	Missing data	Comparator (description)	Gender/Sex	Total duration of study [Duration of follow up]	
Aim of study	Attrition rate/Reasons for withdrawal	Allocation procedure	Religion	Inclusion criteria	
Summary of findings (from abstract)	Patient current/previous health characteristics	Concealment attempts	SES	Method of data collection	
	Condition requiring restoration		Social capital	Analysis method	
	Health or environmental impact being evaluated		Personal characteristics associated with discrimination		
			Features of relationships		
			Time-dependent relationships		
			Others not listed		

Blue shaded cell=data collected from studies evaluating health and/or environmental impact. N=No, No=Number, SD=Standard Deviation, SES=Socioeconomic status, Y=Yes

Appendix C: List of studies excluded at full-text from both bibliographic database and supplementary searches

Language (n=3)

1. Mir L (2008) Contribution of dental amalgam in mercury urinary excretion in children. ENVIRONNEMENT RISQUES & SANTE 7(2), 92-92
2. Tucek M and Bencko V; Krysl S; (2007) Health hazard of dental amalgams. CHEMICKÉ LISTY 101(12), 1038-1044
3. Willershausen-Zönnchen B and Zimmermann Margot; Defregger A; Oren Ram; Hamm Grégory; (2008) Quecksilberkonzentration der Mundschleimhaut bei Patienten mit Amalgamfüllungen. DMW - Deutsche Medizinische Wochenschrift 117(46), 1743-1747

Country (n=65)

1. Ahangaran Fatemeh and Navarchian Amir H; (2022) Towards the development of self-healing and antibacterial dental nanocomposites via incorporation of novel acrylic microcapsules.. Dental materials : official publication of the Academy of Dental Materials 38(5), 858-873
2. Akgul Nilgun and Gul Pinar; Alp Hamit Hakan; Kiziltunc Ahmet; (2015) Effects of composite restorations on nitric oxide and uric acid levels in saliva.. Contemporary clinical dentistry 6(3), 381-5
3. Akhtar N and Tahir A; Qadir A; Masood R; Gulzar Z; Arshad M; (2024) Profusion of microplastics in dental healthcare units; morphological, polymer, and seasonal trends with hazardous consequences for humans. JOURNAL OF HAZARDOUS MATERIALS 479,
4. Aktas Bora and Basyigit Sebahat; Yuksel Osman; Akkan Tolga; Atbasi Suna Tulin; Uzman Metin; Yilmaz Baris; Simsek Gulcin; Nazligul Yasar; (2015) The impact of amalgam dental fillings on the frequency of Helicobacter pylori infection and H. pylori eradication rates in patients treated with concomitant, quadruple, and levofloxacin-based therapies.. Comment in: Eur J Gastroenterol Hepatol. 2015 Oct and27(10):1231 PMID: 26327504 [https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/26327504] 27(7), 769-75
5. Balbinot Gabriela de Souza and Collares Fabricio Mezzomo; Herpich Tiago Luis; Visioli Fernanda; Samuel Susana Maria Werner; Leitune Vicente Castelo Branco; (2020) Niobium containing bioactive glasses as remineralizing filler for adhesive resins.. Dental materials : official publication of the Academy of Dental Materials 36(2), 221-228

6. Banomyong Danuchit and Messer Harold; (2013) Two-year clinical study on postoperative pulpal complications arising from the absence of a glass-ionomer lining in deep occlusal resin-composite restorations.. *Journal of investigative and clinical dentistry* 4(4), 265-70
7. Bedir Findik and Rahime; Celik Huseyin Tugrul; Ersoy Ali Ozgur; Tasci Yasemin; Moraloglu Ozlem; Karakaya Jale; (2016) Mercury concentration in maternal serum, cord blood, and placenta in patients with amalgam dental fillings: effects on fetal biometric measurements.. *Comment in: J Matern Fetal Neonatal Med.* 2017 Mar and 30(5):594 PMID: 27090019 [<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/27090019>] 29(22), 3665-9
8. Behrooz R D and Sari A E; Mishmast-Nehi A; Sepehriki S; Barghi M; (2013) Mercury concentration in the milk of mothers living near the southern coast of the Caspian Sea during different stages of lactation period.. *Toxicological and Environmental Chemistry* 95(5), 860-869
9. Bilak S and Onderci M; Simsek A; (2019) Evaluation of amalgam-related retinal neurotoxicity with optical coherence tomography findings.. *Human & experimental toxicology* 38(7), 814-822
10. Cakir Filiz Yalcin and Ergin Esra; Gurgan Sevil; Sabuncuoglu Suna; Arpa Cigdem Sahin; Tokgoz Ilknur; Ozgunes Hilal; Kiremitci Arlin; (2015) Effect of bleaching on mercury release from amalgam fillings and antioxidant enzyme activities: a pilot study.. *Journal of esthetic and restorative dentistry : official publication of the American Academy of Esthetic Dentistry ... [et al.]* 27(1), 29-36
11. Chandwani Neelam D and Pawar Mansing G; Tupkari Jagdish V; Yuwanati Monal; (2014) Histological evaluation to study the effects of dental amalgam and composite restoration on human dental pulp: an in vivo study.. *Medical principles and practice : international journal of the Kuwait University and Health Science Centre* 23(1), 40-4
12. Corralo D J and Maltz M; (2013) Clinical and ultrastructural effects of different liners/restorative materials on deep carious dentin: a randomized clinical trial.. *Caries research* 47(3), 243-50
13. da Silva Marjully Er and de Sena Marina D; Colombo Natalia H; Pereira Jesse A; Chrisostomo Daniela A; de Aguiar Sandra Mhca; Cunha Robson F; Duque Cristiane; (2023) Short-term Clinical and Microbiological Performance of Resin-modified Glass Ionomer Cement Containing Chlorhexidine for Atraumatic Restorative Treatment.. *International journal of clinical pediatric dentistry* 16(Suppl 1), S27-S32

14. de Fátima Rezende Elisângela and Mendes-Costa Maria Cristina; Fonseca Johnson Campideli; de Oliveira Ribeiro Alex; (2011) Nuclear anomalies in the buccal cells of children under dental treatment. *RSBO Revista Sul-Brasileira De Odontologia* 8(2), 182-188
15. de Fátima Rezende Elisângela and Mendes-Costa Maria Cristina; Fonseca Johnson Campideli; de Oliveira Ribeiro Alex; (2012) Nuclear anomalies in the buccal cells of children under dental treatment. *RSBO* 8(2), 182-8
16. de Oliveira Marcelo Tomas and Pereira Jefferson Ricardo; Ghizoni Janaina Salomon; Bittencourt Sandra Teixeira; Molina Gustavo Otoboni; (2010) Effects from exposure to dental amalgam on systemic mercury levels in patients and dental school students.. *Photomedicine and laser surgery* 28 Suppl 2, S111-4
17. Farahat S A and Rashed L A; Zawilla N H; Farouk S M; (2009) Effect of occupational exposure to elemental mercury in the amalgam on thymulin hormone production among dental staff.. *Toxicology and industrial health* 25(3), 159-67
18. Favetti Morgana and Montagner Anelise Fernandes; Fontes Silvia Terra; Martins Thiago Marchi; Masotti Alexandre Severo; Jardim Patricia Dos Santos; Correa Fernanda Oliveira Bello; Cenci Maximiliano Sergio; Muniz Francisco Wilker Mustafa Gomes; (2021) Effects of cervical restorations on the periodontal tissues: 5-year follow-up results of a randomized clinical trial.. *Journal of dentistry* 106, 103571
19. Girgin G and Palabiyik-Yücelik SS; Sipahi H; Kilicarslan B; Ünüvar S; Tutkun E; Yilmaz ÖH; Baydar T; (2022) Mercury exposure, neopterin profile, and tryptophan degradation in dental technicians. *PTERIDINES* 33(1), 32-38
20. Goncalves Rafael Simoes and Scaffa Polliana Mendes Candia; Shinohara Mirela Sanae; de Andrade Carvalho Paulo Roberto Marao; Buzalaf Marilia Afonso Rabelo; Fagundes Ticiane Cestari; (2022) Two-year randomized clinical trial of different restorative techniques in non-carious cervical lesions and MMP activity in gingival crevicular fluid.. *Clinical oral investigations* 26(2), 1889-1902
21. Gong Haihuan and Guo Xiaowei; Cao Danfeng; Gao Ping; Feng Dan; Zhang Xiaomeng; Shi Zuosen; Zhang Yingchao; Zhu Song; Cui Zhanchen; (2019) Photopolymerizable and moisture-curable polyurethanes for dental adhesive applications to increase restoration durability.. *Journal of materials chemistry. B* 7(5), 744-754
22. Gul P and Akgul N; Alp HH; Kiziltunc A; (2015) Effects of composite restorations on oxidative stress in saliva: An *in vivo* study. *JOURNAL OF DENTAL SCIENCES* 10(4), 394-400
23. Gul Nayab and Khan Sardar; Khan Abbas; Nawab Javed; Shamshad Isha; Yu Xinwei; (2016) Quantification of Hg excretion and distribution in biological samples of mercury-dental-

- amalgam users and its correlation with biological variables.. *Environmental science and pollution research international* 23(20), 20580-20590
24. Gul Pinar and Celik Neslihan; Ozgeris Fatma Betul; Demirkaya-Miloglu Fatma; Kiziltunc Ahmet; Seven Nilgun; (2021) Effects of Bisphenol A Released From Composite Fillings on Reproductive Hormone Levels in Men.. *International dental journal* 71(4), 343-351
 25. Gul Pinar and Karatas Ozcan; Sagsoz Omer; Askin Seda; Turkeri Ozge; Kiziltunc Ahmet; (2023) Release of mercury from amalgam filling and its relationship with metallothionein and superoxide dismutase.. *European oral research* 57(1), 16-21
 26. Ilday Nurcan Ozakar and Celik Neslihan; Dilsiz Alparslan; Alp Hamit Hakan; Aydin Tuba; Seven Nilgun; Kiziltunc Ahmet; (2016) The effects of overhang amalgam restoration on levels of cytokines, gingival crevicular fluid volume and some periodontal parameters.. *American journal of dentistry* 29(5), 266-270
 27. Irum Bushra and Asif Muhammad; Mumtaz Bakhtawar; Aslam Naveed; (2022) Effect Of Dental Proximal Restorations On Periodontal Health In Patients.. *Journal of Ayub Medical College and Abbottabad : JAMC* 34(Suppl 1)(4), S987-S990
 28. Karatasli Burcin and Karatasli Gokcen; Mete Ozgur; Erdem Mehmet Ali; Cankaya Abdulkadir Burak; (2018) Healing of Oral Lichenoid Lesions following Replacement of Dental Amalgam Restorations with Feldspathic Ceramic Inlay-Onlay Restorations: Clinical Results of a Follow-Up Period Varied from Three Months up to Five Years.. *BioMed research international* 2018, 7918781
 29. Kisakol G (2014) Dental amalgam implantation and thyroid autoimmunity.. *Bratislavske lekarske listy* 115(1), 22-4
 30. Luiz A C and Hirota S K; Dal Vecchio A; Reis V M; Spina R; Migliari D A; (2012) Diagnosing oral lichenoid contact reaction: clinical judgment versus skin-patch test.. *Minerva stomatologica* 61(7-8), 311-7
 31. Manojlovic Dragica and Radisic Marina; Vasiljevic Tatjana; Zivkovic Slavoljub; Lausevic Mila; Miletic Vesna; (2011) Monomer elution from nanohybrid and ormocer-based composites cured with different light sources.. *Dental materials : official publication of the Academy of Dental Materials* 27(4), 371-8
 32. Mary S Jeslin and Girish K L; Joseph T Isaac; Sathyan Pradeesh; (2018) Genotoxic Effects of Silver Amalgam and Composite Restorations: Micronuclei-Based Cohort and Case-Control Study in Oral Exfoliated Cells.. *Contemporary clinical dentistry* 9(2), 249-254
 33. Mendes da Silva, Cassia and Figueiredo Marcia Cancado; Casagrande Luciano; Larissa Lenzi; Tathiane; (2020) Survival and Associated Risk Factors of Atraumatic Restorative Treatment

- Restorations in Children with Early Childhood Caries.. *Journal of dentistry for children (Chicago and Ill.)* 87(1), 12-17
34. Milosevic Natasa and Milanovic Maja; Sazdanic Velikic; Danica; Sudji Jan; Jovicic-Bata Jelena; Spanovic Milorad; Sevo Mirjana; Lukic Sarkanovic; Mirka; Torovic Ljilja; Bijelovic Sanja; Milic Natasa; (2024) Biomonitoring Study of Toxic Metal(loid)s: Levels in Lung Adenocarcinoma Patients.. *Toxics* 12(7),
 35. Mortazavi S M J and Daiee E; Yazdi A; Khiabani K; Kavousi A; Vazirinejad R; Behnejad B; Ghasemi M; Mood M Balali; (2008) Mercury release from dental amalgam restorations after magnetic resonance imaging and following mobile phone use.. *Pakistan journal of biological sciences : PJBS* 11(8), 1142-6
 36. Mortazavi S M J and Neghab M; Anoosheh S M H; Bahaeddini N; Mortazavi G; Neghab P; Rajaeifard A; (2014) High-field MRI and mercury release from dental amalgam fillings.. *The international journal of occupational and environmental medicine* 5(2), 101-5
 37. Nassar Carlos Augusto and de Moraes Renata Carvalho; Secundes Mayron Barros; Bernardon Paula; Nassar Patricia Oehlmeyer; Camilotti Veridiana; (2014) The Effect of Resin Composites and Polishing Procedure on Periodontal Tissue Parameters in Patients with Diabetes Mellitus.. *The European journal of prosthodontics and restorative dentistry* 22(4), 146-51
 38. Neves Sheyla Omonte and Magalhaes Luisa Mourao Dias; Correa Joice Dias; Dutra Walderez Ornelas; Gollob Kenneth John; Silva Tarcilia Aparecida; Horta Martinho Campolina Rebello; Souza Paulo Eduardo Alencar; (2019) Composite-derived monomers affect cell viability and cytokine expression in human leukocytes stimulated with *Porphyromonas gingivalis*.. *Journal of applied oral science : revista FOB* 27, e20180529
 39. Nur Ozdabak and H; Karaoglanoglu Serpil; Akgul Nilgun; Polat Fevzi; Seven Nilgun; (2008) The effects of amalgam restorations on plasma mercury levels and total antioxidant activity.. *Archives of oral biology* 53(12), 1101-6
 40. Oliveira Marcelo Tomas and Constantino Henrique Vieira; Molina Gustavo Otoboni; Milioli Elysa; Ghizoni Janaina Salomon; Pereira Jefferson Ricardo; (2014) Evaluation of mercury contamination in patients and water during amalgam removal.. *The journal of contemporary dental practice* 15(2), 165-8
 41. Peskersoy Cem and Oguzhan Aybeniz; Gurlek Onder; (2022) The Effect of Flowable Composite Resins on Periodontal Health, Cytokine Levels, and Immunoglobulins.. *BioMed Research International* , 1-11

42. Prabhu R and Bhaskaran S; Geetha Prabhu; K R; Eswaran M A; Phanikrishna G; Deepthi B; (2015) Clinical evaluation of direct composite restoration done for midline diastema closure - long-term study.. *Journal of pharmacy & bioallied sciences* 7(Suppl 2), S559-62
43. Rios Cristian Camilo and Campino Jorge Ivan; Posada-Lopez Adriana; Rodriguez-Medina Carolina; Botero Javier Enrique; (2021) Occlusal trauma is associated with periodontitis: A retrospective case-control study.. *Journal of periodontology* 92(12), 1788-1794
44. Rolim Tatiane Zahn Cardoso and da Costa Thays Regina Ferreira; Wambier Leticia Maira; Chibinski Ana Claudia; Wambier Denise Stadler; da Silva Assuncao Luciana Reichert; de Menezes Jose Vitor Borges Nogara; Feltrin-Souza Juliana; (2021) Adhesive restoration of molars affected by molar incisor hypomineralization: a randomized clinical trial.. *Clinical oral investigations* 25(3), 1513-1524
45. Saadatmand P and Shaneie A; Amouheidari A; Abedi I; (2019) Evaluation of the effects of dental filling material artifacts on IMRT treatment planning in patient with nasopharyngeal cancer. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RADIATION RESEARCH* 17(3), 477-483
46. Saatchi Masoud and Shadmehr Elham; Talebi Seyed Morteza; Nazeri Mohsen; (2013) A Prospective Clinical Study on Blood Mercury Levels Following Endodontic Root-end Surgery with Amalgam.. *Iranian endodontic journal* 8(3), 85-8
47. Saber-Tehrani M and Givianrad M H; Hashemi-Moghaddam H; (2007) Determination of total and methyl mercury in human permanent healthy teeth by electrothermal atomic absorption spectrometry after extraction in organic phase.. *Talanta* 71(3), 1319-25
48. Saghiri Mohammad Ali and Banava Sepideh; Sabzian Mohamad Amin; Gutmann James L; Asatourian Armen; Ramezani Golam H; Garcia-Godoy Franklin; Sheibani Nader; (2014) Correlation between long-term in vivo amalgam restorations and the presence of heavy elements in the dental pulp.. *Journal of trace elements in medicine and biology : organ of the Society for Minerals and Trace Elements (GMS)* 28(2), 200-204
49. Sahani M and Sulaiman N S; Tan B S; Yahya N A; Anual Z F; Mahiyuddin W R Wan; Khan M F; Muttalib K A; (2016) Mercury in dental amalgam: Are our health care workers at risk?.. *Journal of the Air & Waste Management Association* (1995) 66(11), 1077-1083
50. Sakallioğlu Elif Eser and Lutfioglu Muge; Sakallioğlu Umur; Ceylan Gozlem Koca; Pamuk Ferda; Dede Figen Ongoz; Dede Dogu; (2015) Gingival crevicular fluid levels of neuropeptides following dental restorations.. *Journal of applied biomaterials & functional materials* 13(2), e186-93

51. Samir Aisha Mohamed and Aref Wael Mohamed; (2011) Impact of occupational exposure to elemental mercury on some antioxidative enzymes among dental staff.. *Toxicology and industrial health* 27(9), 779-86
52. Santos Vanessa Renata and Lucchesi Juliana Antico; Cortelli Sheila Cavalca; Amaral Cristiane Mariote; Feres Magda; Duarte Poliana Mendes; (2007) Effects of Glass Ionomer and Microfilled Composite Subgingival Restorations on Periodontal Tissue and Subgingival Biofilm: A 6-Month Evaluation. *Journal Of Periodontology* 78(8), 1522-1528
53. Sharma Rajneesh and Handa Sanjeev; De Dipankar; Radotra Bishan Dass; Rattan Vidya; (2015) Role of dental restoration materials in oral mucosal lichenoid lesions.. *Indian journal of dermatology and venereology and leprology* 81(5), 478-84
54. Shir Khanloo Hamid and Fallah Mehrjerdi; Mohammad Ali; Hassani Hamid; (2017) Identifying occupational and nonoccupational exposure to mercury in dental personnel.. *Archives of environmental & occupational health* 72(2), 63-69
55. Sousa R P and Zanin I C J; Lima J P M; Vasconcelos S M L C; Melo M A S; Beltrao H C P; Rodrigues L K A; (2009) In situ effects of restorative materials on dental biofilm and enamel demineralisation.. *Journal of dentistry* 37(1), 44-51
56. Tercanli Humeyra and Yavuz Esra; Yilmaz Sevcihan Gunen; Yardimci Selmi; (2024) Mercury Concentration in Saliva and the Impact of Chewing: An Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry Study.. *Biological trace element research* 202(5), 1965-1971
57. Thomas Maria and George Liza; Mathew Josey; Mathew Deepu George; Thomas Priya; (2023) Comparative evaluation of genotoxicity and cytotoxicity of flowable, bulk-fill flowable, and nanohybrid composites in human gingival cells using cytome assay: An in vivo study.. *Journal of conservative dentistry : JCD* 26(2), 182-187
58. Wei Fei and Bai Tingting; Chen Huan; Sun Guangdi; Chen Xue; Zhu Song; (2024) Light-curable urushiol enhanced bisphenol A glycidyl dimethacrylate dentin bonding agent.. *Journal of dentistry* 148, 105261
59. Yalçın SS and Yurdakök K; Yalçın S; Engür-Karasimav D; Coskun T; (2010) Maternal and environmental determinants of breast-milk mercury concentrations. *TURKISH JOURNAL OF PEDIATRICS* 52(1), 1-9
60. Yildiz Mehmet and Alp Hamit Hakan; Gul Pinar; Bakan Nuri; Ozcan Mutlu; (2017) Lipid peroxidation and DNA oxidation caused by dental filling materials.. *Journal of dental sciences* 12(3), 233-240
61. Yu B and Liu F; He JW; He YC; Lin ZM; (2015) Preparation of Bis-GMA-Free Dental Restorative Composites with Dendritic Macromer (G-IEMA). *ADVANCES IN POLYMER TECHNOLOGY* 34(4),

62. Yushau US and Almofeez L; Bozkurt A; (2019) Aminotriazole functional silica incorporated BisGMA/TEGDMA resins as dental nanocomposites. *POLYMERS & POLYMER COMPOSITES* 27(8), 488-495
63. Zhang JH and Guo XW; Zhang XM; Wang HM; Zhu JF; Shi ZS; Zhu S; Cui ZC; (2020) Hydrolysis-resistant and stress-buffering bifunctional polyurethane adhesive for durable dental composite restoration. *ROYAL SOCIETY OPEN SCIENCE* 7(7),
64. Zhu Lingxin and Zhang Jie; Xiao Lan; Liu Shan; Yu Jingjing; Chen Weihai; Zhang Xianzheng; Peng Bin; (2015) Autophagy in resin monomer-initiated toxicity of dental mesenchymal cells: a novel therapeutic target of N-acetyl cysteine.. *Journal of materials chemistry. B* 3(33), 6820-6836
65. Zhu Xiaomiao and Zhang Yidan; Wang Juan; Wang Zhihua; Wang Xiaoli; Liu Xin; Cooper Paul Roy; Cheng Xiaogang; He Wenxi; (2023) Effect of full pulpotomy using a calcium silicate-based bioactive ceramic in adult permanent teeth with symptoms indicative of irreversible pulpitis: A retrospective study.. *Journal of the American Dental Association (JADA)* 154(6), 486-494

Population (n=14)

1. Abdulrazzaq Abdo Mohammed Mohammed (2024) Advancing Diabetic Dental Restorations: A Comparative Analysis of Alveolar Bone Loss in Class II Composite Resin Versus Amalgam Fillings.. *Cureus* 16(10), e72642
2. Astolfi Maria Luisa and Vitali Matteo; Marconi Elisabetta; Martellucci Stefano; Mattei Vincenzo; Canepari Silvia; Protano Carmela; (2020) Urinary Mercury Levels and Predictors of Exposure among a Group of Italian Children.. *International journal of environmental research and public health* 17(24),
3. Farzan SF and Howe CG; Chen Y; Gilbert-Diamond D; Korrick S; Jackson BP; Weinstein AR; Karagas MR; (2021) Prenatal and postnatal mercury exposure and blood pressure in childhood. *ENVIRONMENT INTERNATIONAL* 146,
4. Garí M and Grimalt JO; Torrent M; Sunyer J; (2013) Influence of socio-demographic and diet determinants on the levels of mercury in preschool children from a Mediterranean island. *ENVIRONMENTAL POLLUTION* 182, 291-298
5. Jiranek I and Cervený V; Barek J; Rychlovský P; (2010) COMPARISON OF MERCURY VAPOR PRESSURE OF SILVER AMALGAM-BASED ELECTRODE MATERIALS USING AAS. *ANALYTICAL LETTERS* 43(7-8), 1387-1399
6. Lizenboim K and Dodiuk H; Iuster N; Kidan T; Suvorov I; Kenig S; Zalsman B; (2013) Bisphenol-A free dental polymeric materials. *JOURNAL OF ADHESION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY* 27(4), 354-370

7. Maserejian Nancy (2014) Possible Association Between Dental Sealants and Urinary Bisphenol A Levels in Children Warrants Additional Biomonitoring and Safety Research.. *Journal of Evidence-Based Dental Practice* 14(4), 200-202
8. Ohno Tomoko and Sakamoto Mineshi; Kurosawa Tomoko; Dakeishi Miwako; Iwata Toyoto; Murata Katsuyuki; (2007) Total mercury levels in hair, toenail, and urine among women free from occupational exposure and their relations to renal tubular function.. *Environmental research* 103(2), 191-7
9. Pizza Alfredo and Metz Renaud; Hassanzadeh Mehrdad; Bantignies Jean-Louis; (2014) Life cycle assessment of nanocomposites made of thermally conductive graphite nanoplatelets.. *International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment* 19(6), 1226-1237
10. Puklová Vladimíra and Krsková Andrea; Černá Milena; Čejchanová Mája; Řehůřková Irena; Ruprich Jiří; Kratzer K; Kubínová Růžena; Zimová Magdaléna; (2010) The mercury burden of the Czech population: An integrated approach. *International Journal Of Hygiene And Environmental Health* 213(4), 243-251
11. Smith Lucy and Ali Mustafa; Agrissais Manon; Mulligan Steven; Koh Lenny; Martin Nicolas; (2023) A comparative life cycle assessment of dental restorative materials.. *Dental materials : official publication of the Academy of Dental Materials* 39(1), 13-24
12. Somers Emily C and Ganser Martha A; Warren Jeffrey S; Basu Niladri; Wang Lu; Zick Suzanna M; Park Sung Kyun; (2015) Mercury Exposure and Antinuclear Antibodies among Females of Reproductive Age in the United States: NHANES.. *Environmental Health Perspectives* 123(8), 792-798
13. Sun Qi and Cornelis Marilyn C; Townsend Mary K; Tobias Deirdre K; Eliassen A Heather; Franke Adrian A; Hauser Russ; Hu Frank B; (2014) Association of Urinary Concentrations of Bisphenol A and Phthalate Metabolites with Risk of Type 2 Diabetes: A Prospective Investigation in the Nurses' Health Study (NHS) and NHSII Cohorts.. *Environmental Health Perspectives* 122(6), 616-623
14. van Wijngaarden E and Davidson PW; Smith TH; Evans K; Yost K; Love T; Thurston SW; Watson GE; Zareba G; Burns CM; Shamlaye CF; Myers GJ; (2013) Autism Spectrum Disorder Phenotypes and Prenatal Exposure to Methylmercury. *EPIDEMIOLOGY* 24(5), 651-659

Intervention (n=17)

1. Accorinte Maria de Lourdes R and Holland Roberto; Reis Alessandra; Bortoluzzi Marcelo C; Murata Sueli S; Dezan Eloy Jr; Souza Valdir; Alessandro Loguercio Dourado; (2008) Evaluation of mineral trioxide aggregate and calcium hydroxide cement as pulp-capping agents in human teeth.. *Journal of endodontics* 34(1), 1-6

2. Ahlgren Camilla and Bruze M; MÅllner H; Gruvberger B; Axell T; Liedholm Rolf; Nilner Krister; (2012) Contact Allergy to Gold in Patients with Oral Lichen Lesions. *Acta Dermato Venereologica* 92(2), 138-143
3. Barot Tejas and Rawtani Deepak; Kulkarni Pratik; (2020) Physicochemical and biological assessment of silver nanoparticles immobilized Halloysite nanotubes-based resin composite for dental applications.. *Heliyon* 6(3), e03601
4. Borglin Linnea and Pekarski Stephanie; Saget Sophie; Duane Brett; (2021) The life cycle analysis of a dental examination: Quantifying the environmental burden of an examination in a hypothetical dental practice. *Community Dentistry And Oral Epidemiology* 49(6), 581-593
5. Duane Brett and Hyland John; Rowan John S; Archibald Bruce; (2012) Taking a bite out of Scotland's dental carbon emissions in the transition to a low carbon future. *Public Health* 126(9), 770-777
6. Konradsson Katarina and Claesson Rolf; van Dijken Jon W V; (2007) Dental biofilm, gingivitis and interleukin-1 adjacent to approximal sites of a bonded ceramic.. *Journal of clinical periodontology* 34(12), 1062-7
7. Kontakiotis Evangelos G and Filippatos Christos G; Stefopoulos Spyridon; Tzanetakakis Giorgos N; (2014) A prospective study of the incidence of asymptomatic pulp necrosis following crown preparation. *International Endodontic Journal* 48(6), 512-517
8. Love R M and Firth N; (2009) Histopathological profile of surgically removed persistent periapical radiolucent lesions of endodontic origin.. *International endodontic journal* 42(3), 198-202
9. Lundh T and Axmon A; Skerfving S; Broberg K; (2016) Cadmium and mercury exposure over time in Swedish children.. *Environmental research* 150, 600-605
10. Marino R and Capaccio P; Pignataro L; Spadari F; (2009) Burning mouth syndrome: the role of contact hypersensitivity.. *Oral diseases* 15(4), 255-8
11. Oxborrow Delbert G and Dong Chaoyang; Lin Ivy F; (2024) Simulation clinic waste audit assessment and recommendations at the University of Washington School of Dentistry. *Journal Of Dental Education* 88(5), 623-630
12. Rooney James P K and Woods Nancy F; Martin Michael D; Woods James S; (2018) Genetic polymorphisms of GRIN2A and GRIN2B modify the neurobehavioral effects of low-level lead exposure in children.. *Environmental research* 165, 1-10
13. Stocker Larissa and Zervou Sevasti-Kiriaki; Papageorgiou Spyridon N; Karakousoglou Stephania; Triantis Theodoros; Hiskia Anastasia; Eliades George; Eliades Theodore; (2024)

- Salivary levels of eluents during Invisalign TM treatment with attachments: an in vivo investigation.. *Progress in orthodontics* 25(1), 22
14. Suresh Peter and Crotty John; Tesanovic Sonja; Alaweed Othman; Doyle Sadhbh; Kiandee Mikra; Hayes Emily; Umeh Vanessa; Khalilinejad Bitia; Duane Brett; (2024) A life cycle analysis of the environmental impact of procurement, waste and water in the dental practice. *BDJ* 236(7), 545-551
 15. Surkan Pamela J and Zhang Annie; Trachtenberg Felicia; Daniel David B; McKinlay Sonja; Bellinger David C; (2007) Neuropsychological function in children with blood lead levels <10 microg/dL.. *Neurotoxicology* 28(6), 1170-7
 16. Voudrias EA and Topalidis A; Mandalidis A; Iosifidis N; (2018) Variability of Greek dental solid waste production by different dentist groups. *ENVIRONMENTAL MONITORING AND ASSESSMENT* 190(7),
 17. Zane A and Zuo RF; Villamena FA; Rockenbauer A; Foushee AMD; Flores K; Dutta PK; Nagy A; (2016) Biocompatibility and antibacterial activity of nitrogen-doped titanium dioxide nanoparticles for use in dental resin formulations. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF NANOMEDICINE* 11, 6459-6470

Outcome (n=37)

1. Abdulrazzaq Abdo Mohammed Mohammed and Alanazi Sultan; (2024) Evaluation of alveolar bone loss among diabetic patients with class II amalgam restorations. *Bioinformation* 20(7), 798-801
2. Al-Ali Khalid and Hashim Raghad; (2012) Occupational health problems of dentists in the United Arab Emirates. *International Dental Journal* 62(1), 52-56
3. Aprea Maria Cristina and Apostoli Pietro; Bettinelli Maurizio; Lovreglio Piero; Negri Sara; Perbellini Luigi; Perico Andrea; Ricossa Maria Cristina; Salamon Fabiola; Scapellato Maria Luisa; Iavicoli Ivo; (2018) Urinary levels of metal elements in the non-smoking general population in Italy: SIVR study 2012-2015.. *Toxicology Letters* 298, 177-185
4. Ayers K M. S and Thomson W Murray; Newton Tim; Morgaine Kate C; Rich Alison M; (2009) Self-reported occupational health of general dental practitioners. *Occupational Medicine* 59(3), 142-148
5. Ballal Nidambur Vasudev and Duncan Henry F; Wiedemeier Daniel B; Rai Namith; Jalan Prateek; Bhat Vinutha; Belle Vijetha Shenoy; Zehnder Matthias; (2024) 4-Year Pulp Survival in a Randomized Trial on Direct Pulp Capping.. *Journal of endodontics* 50(1), 4-9

6. Bayram Merve and Akgol Beyza Balli; Ustun Nilufer; (2021) Longevity of posterior composite restorations in children suffering from early childhood caries-results from a retrospective study.. *Clinical oral investigations* 25(5), 2867-2876
7. Chadwick R G and Alatsaris M; Ranka Meena Satish; (2007) Eye care habits of dentists registered in the United Kingdom. *BDJ* 203(4), E7-E7
8. Gordan Valeria V and Riley III; Joseph L; Blaser Paul K; Mondragon Eduardo; Garvan Cynthia W; Mjr Ivar A; (2011) Alternative treatments to replacement of defective amalgam restorations.. *Journal of the American Dental Association (JADA)* 142(7), 842-849
9. Han Dong-Hun and Kim Min-Ji; Jun Eun-Joo; Kim Jin-Bom; (2012) Salivary bisphenol-A levels due to dental sealant/resin: a case-control study in Korean children.. *Journal of Korean medical science* 27(9), 1098-104
10. Katsonouri A and Gabriel C; Lopez ME; Namorado S; Halldorsson TI; Tratnik JS; Martin LR; Karakoltzidis A; Chatzimpaloglou A; Giannadaki D; Anastasi E; Thoma A; Dominguez-Morueco N; Portilla AIC; Jacobsen E; Assuncao R; Peres M; Santiago S; Nunes C; Pedraza-Diaz S; Iavicoli I; Leso V; Lacasana M; Gonzalez-Alzaga B; Horvati M; Sepai O; Castano A; Kolossa-Gehring M; Karakitsios S; Sarigiannis D; (2023) HBM4EU-MOM: Prenatal methylmercury-exposure control in five countries through suitable dietary advice for pregnancy-Study design and characteristics of participants. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF HYGIENE AND ENVIRONMENTAL HEALTH* 252,
11. Lamu Admassu N and Bjorkman Lars; Hamre Harald J; Alraek Terje; Musial Frauke; Robberstad Bjarne; (2022) Is amalgam removal in patients with medically unexplained physical symptoms cost-effective? A prospective cohort and decision modelling study in Norway.. *PloS one* 17(4), e0267236
12. Lyapina Maya and Krasteva Assya; Dencheva PhD Maria; Tzekova PhD Mariana; Deliverska PhD Mariela; Kisselova Angelina; (2013) Prevalence and Risk Factors of Occupational Contact Dermatitis to Formaldehyde and Glutaraldehyde and their Co-Reactivity in Dental Professionals. *DOAJ (DOAJ: Directory Of Open Access Journals)* ,
13. Lygre Gunvor Bentung and Bjorkman Lars; Haug Kjell; Skjaerven Rolv; Helland Vigdis; (2010) Exposure to dental amalgam restorations in pregnant women.. *Comment in: J Evid Based Dent Pract.* 2011 Sep and11(3):162-3 PMID: 21855822 [<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/21855822>] 38(5), 460-9
14. Maeno Misato and Tamagawa-Mineoka Risa; Arakawa Yukiyasu; Masuda Koji; Adachi Tetsuya; Katoh Norito; (2020) Metal patch testing in patients with oral symptoms. *The Journal Of Dermatology* 48(1), 85-87

15. Martín Nicolás and Mulligan Steven; Fuzesi Peter; Hatton Paul V; (2022) Quantification of single use plastics waste generated in clinical dental practice and hospital settings. *Journal Of Dentistry* 118, 103948-103948
16. Maserejian Nancy Nairi and Tavares Mary A; Hayes Catherine; Soncini Jennifer A; Trachtenberg Felicia L; (2009) Prospective study of 5-year caries increment among children receiving comprehensive dental care in the New England children's amalgam trial.. *Community dentistry and oral epidemiology* 37(1), 9-18
17. Mendonca Juliano Sartori and Neto Ranulfo Gianordoli; Santiago Sergio Lima; Lauris Jose Roberto Pereira; Navarro Maria Fidela de Lima; de Carvalho Ricardo Marins; (2010) Direct resin composite restorations versus indirect composite inlays: one-year results.. *The journal of contemporary dental practice* 11(3), 025-32
18. Monteagudo Celia and Tellez Francisco; Heras-Gonzalez Leticia; Ibanez-Peinado Diana; Mariscal-Arcas Miguel; Olea-Serrano Fatima; (2015) SCHOOL DIETARY HABITS AND INCIDENCE OF DENTAL CARIES.. *Nutricion hospitalaria* 32(1), 383-8
19. Naimi-Akbar Aron and Svedberg Pia; Alexanderson Kristina; Ekstrand Jan; Sandborgh-Englund Gunilla; (2012) Reliance on social security benefits by Swedish patients with ill-health attributed to dental fillings: a register-based cohort study.. *BMC public health* 12, 713
20. Ogawa Taiji and Ikebe Kazunori; Murai Shunsuke; Enoki Kaori; Maeda Yoshinobu; Imazato Satoshi; Ebisu Shigeyuki; (2012) Clinically acceptable restorations may be a hotbed for cariogenic microbes.. *Gerodontology* 29(2), e845-50
21. Pontoriero Denise Irene Karin and Grandini Simone; Spagnuolo Gianrico; Discepoli Nicola; Benedicenti Stefano; Maccagnola Valerio; Mosca Alberto; Ferrari Cagidiaco; Edoardo; Ferrari Marco; (2021) Clinical Outcomes of Endodontic Treatments and Restorations with and without Posts Up to 18 Years.. *Journal of clinical medicine* 10(5),
22. Rosen Eyal and Volmark Yael; Beitlitum Ilan; Nissan Joseph; Nemcovsky Carlos E; Tsisis Igor; (2020) Dental implant placement is a possible risk factor for the development of multiple cracks in non-endodontically treated teeth.. *Scientific reports* 10(1), 8527
23. Sarapultseva Maria and Sarapultsev Alexey; (2019) Long-term results of crown fragment reattachment techniques for fractured anterior teeth: A retrospective case-control study.. *Journal of esthetic and restorative dentistry : official publication of the American Academy of Esthetic Dentistry ... [et al.]* 31(3), 290-294
24. Sato Takaaki and Matsuyama Yusuke; Fujiwara Takeo; Tagami Junji; (2020) Pulp survival after composite resin restoration of caries lesions in adults.. *Journal of oral science* 63(1), 27-30

25. Soncini Jennifer Ann and Maserejian Nancy Nairi; Trachtenberg Felicia; Tavares Mary; Hayes Catherine; (2007) The longevity of amalgam versus compomer/composite restorations in posterior primary and permanent teeth: findings From the New England Children's Amalgam Trial.. *Journal of the American Dental Association* (1939) 138(6), 763-72
26. Surkan and Wypij; Trachtenberg; Daniel Daniel; (2009) Neuropsychological function in school-age children with low mercury exposures.. *Environmental Research* ,
27. Surkan Pamela J and Wypij David; Trachtenberg Felicia; Daniel David B; Barregard Lars; McKinlay Sonja; Bellinger David C; (2009) Neuropsychological function in school-age children with low mercury exposures.. *Environmental research* 109(6), 728-33
28. Suzuki Kayoko and Matsunaga Kayoko; Ito Akiko; Yagami Akiko; Ito Takashi; Miyazawa Hitoshi; Sugiura Mariko; Adachi Atsuko; Kubota Yumiko; Watanabe Yuko; Kato Atsuko; Nishioka Kazue; Fukunaga Atsushi; Mochizuki Masako; Ikezawa Y; Tsunoda Takahiko; Takayama Kaoru; Washizaki Kumiko; Yokozeki Hiroo; Ishihara Takuma; Asada Hideo; Kanto Hiromi; (2021) Multicenter 1-month follow-up study of the patch test reaction to the gold sodium thiosulfate of the TRUE Test and its association with piercings and dental metal history. *Contact Dermatitis* 85(2), 154-163
29. Vahasarja Niko and Montgomery Scott; Sandborgh-Englund Gunilla; Ekbohm Anders; Ekstrand Jan; Nasman Peggy; Naimi-Akbar Aron; (2016) Neurological disease or intellectual disability among sons of female Swedish dental personnel.. *Journal of perinatal medicine* 44(4), 453-60
30. Wang Yi and Goodrich Jaclyn M; Werner Robert; Gillespie Brenda; Basu Niladri; Franzblau Alfred; (2013) Relationship of estimated dietary intake of n-3 polyunsaturated fatty acids from fish with peripheral nerve function after adjusting for mercury exposure.. *The Science of the total environment* 454-455, 73-8
31. Woods JS and Martin MD; Leroux BG; DeRouen TA; Bernardo MF; Luis HS; Leitao JG; Simmonds PL; Rue TC; (2009) Urinary porphyrin excretion in normal children and adolescents. *CLINICA CHIMICA ACTA* 405(1-2), 104-109
32. Woods James S and Heyer Nicholas J; Echeverria Diana; Russo Joan E; Martin Michael D; Bernardo Mario F; Luis Henrique S; Vaz Lurdes; Farin Federico M; (2012) Modification of neurobehavioral effects of mercury by a genetic polymorphism of coproporphyrinogen oxidase in children.. *Neurotoxicology and teratology* 34(5), 513-21
33. Woods James S and Heyer Nicholas J; Russo Joan E; Martin Michael D; Pillai Pradeep B; Farin Federico M; (2013) Modification of neurobehavioral effects of mercury by genetic polymorphisms of metallothionein in children.. *Comment in: Neurotoxicol Teratol.* 2014 Jul-

Aug and 44:126 PMID: 24882565 [<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/24882565>] 39, 36-44

34. Woods James S and Heyer Nicholas J; Russo Joan E; Martin Michael D; Pillai Pradeep B; Bammler Theodor K; Farin Federico M; (2014) Genetic polymorphisms of catechol-O-methyltransferase modify the neurobehavioral effects of mercury in children.. *Journal of toxicology and environmental health. Part A* 77(6), 293-312
35. Woods James S and Heyer Nicholas J; Russo Joan E; Martin Michael D; Farin Federico M; (2014) Genetic polymorphisms affecting susceptibility to mercury neurotoxicity in children: summary findings from the Casa Pia Children's Amalgam clinical trial.. *Neurotoxicology* 44, 288-302
36. Rossato Amanda and Fernandes Mathias-Santamaria Ingrid; Ferreira Ferraz; Laís Fernanda; Gomez Bautista; Cristhian Reynaldo; Viana Miguel Manuela Maria; Pedrine Santamaria; Mauro; () Xenogeneic Acellular Dermal Matrix for the Treatment of Multiple Gingival Recessions Associated with Partially Restored Noncarious Cervical Lesions.. *International Journal of Periodontics & Restorative Dentistry* 42(6), 817-824
37. Yeoh Samuel and Bourdamis Yani; Saker Adam; Marano Nina; Maundrell Liam; Ramamurthy Poornima; Sharma Dileep; (2024) An Investigation Into Contaminated Waste Composition in a University Dental Clinic: Opportunities for Sustainability in Dentistry. *Clinical And Experimental Dental Research* 10(6)

Study design (n=27)

1. Anderson Lindsey (2016) Occupational health exposure to mercury in dental personnel.. *Dental Health* 55(5), 34-36
2. Barregard L (2008) Neuropsychological and renal effects of low dose exposure to elemental mercury exposure from amalgam in children. *CELL BIOLOGY AND TOXICOLOGY* 24(5), 442-445
3. Berglund Fredrik and Carlmark Bjorn; (2011) Titanium, sinusitis, and the yellow nail syndrome.. *Biological trace element research* 143(1), 1-7
4. Bjorkman Lars (2024) Adverse reactions to dental biomaterials: Experiences from a specialty clinic.. *Dental materials : official publication of the Academy of Dental Materials* 40(3), 563-572
5. Brown Ian A and Austin David W; (2012) Maternal transfer of mercury to the developing embryo/fetus: is there a safe level?. *Toxicological & Environmental Chemistry* 94(8), 1610-1627
6. CDA User (2013) Do Amalgam Fillings Affect Mercury Levels in Urine? A Canadian Study. *JOURNAL OF THE CANADIAN DENTAL ASSOCIATION* 79,

7. Dobson Marianne Louise and Cousins Matthew; (2021) Can removal of amalgam restorations reduce health complaints in patients with medically unexplained physical symptoms?.. Comment on: J Oral Rehabil. 2020 Nov and47(11):1422-1434 PMID: 32810306 [<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/32810306>] 22(3), 118-119
8. Duncan A and O'Reilly DS; McDonald EB; Watkins TR; Taylor M; (2011) Summary of: Thirty-five year review of a mercury monitoring service for Scottish dental practices. BRITISH DENTAL JOURNAL 210(3), 122-123
9. Elli Luca and Pigatto P D.M; Ronchi A; Minoia Carla; Guzzi G; Bardella M T; (2010) Increased Mercury Levels in Patients with Celiac Disease. United European Gastroenterology Journal 59,
10. K K S (2021) POS0791 DOSE-DEPENDENT RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN HISTORY OF DENTAL CARIES AND INCREASED RISK OF NEWLY-ONSET SYSTEMIC LUPUS ERYTHEMATOSUS: A NATIONWIDE POPULATION-BASED COHORT STUDY. Annals Of The Rheumatic Diseases 80(Suppl 1), 648.1-648
11. Mackert J Rodway Jr (2010) Randomized controlled trial demonstrates that exposure to mercury from dental amalgam does not adversely affect neurological development in children.. Comment on: J Am Dent Assoc. 2008 Feb and139(2):138-45 PMID: 18245680 [<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/18245680>] 10(1), 25-9
12. Maserejian Nancy N and Trachtenberg Felicia L; Hauser Russ; McKinlay Sonja; Shrader Peter; Tavares Mary; Bellinger David C; (2012) Dental composite restorations and psychosocial function in children.. Comment in: J Esthet Restor Dent. 2013 Dec and25(6):433-7 PMID: 24320063 [<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/24320063>] 130(2), e328-38
13. McGinley Emma Louise (2014) Summary of: dental composite materials and renal function in children.. Comment on: Br Dent J. 2014 Jan and216(2):E4 PMID: 24457893 [<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/24457893>] 216(2), 80-1
14. Mortazavi Ghazal and Mortazavi S M J; (2015) Should pregnant women with dental amalgam fillings limit their exposure to electromagnetic fields to prevent the toxic effects of mercury in their foetuses?.. Technology and health care : official journal of the European Society for Engineering and Medicine 23(3), 369-71
15. Mortazavi Seyed Mohammad Javad and Mortazavi Ghazal; Paknahad Maryam; (2017) Quantification of Hg excretion and distribution in biological samples of mercury-dental-amalgam users and its correlation with biological variables.. Environmental science and pollution research international 24(9), 8889-8890

16. Nett Randall J and Cummings Kristin J; Cannon Brenna; Cox-Ganser Jean; Nathan Steven D; (2018) Dental Personnel Treated for Idiopathic Pulmonary Fibrosis at a Tertiary Care Center - Virginia, 2000-2015.. MMWR: Morbidity & Mortality Weekly Report 67(9), 270-273
17. Pigatto P D and Mazzi B; Fleischhauer K; Guzzi G; (2007) Linking allergy to mercury to HLA and burning mouth syndrome.. Journal of the European Academy of Dermatology and Venereology : JEADV 21(8), 1118-20
18. Pigatto P D.M and Brambilla L; Ferrucci S M; Minoia Carla; Ronchi A; Guzzi Gianpaolo; (2010) Allergy and Adverse Reactions to Dental Amalgam: an Epidemiological Assessment. 63, 95-95
19. Pigatto P D.M and Brambilla L; Ferrucci Silvia; Guzzi Gianpaolo; (2010) Adverse Effects of Antioxidants in Patients with Dental Metal Allergy. ,
20. Stejskal Vera (2014) Metals as a common trigger of inflammation resulting in non-specific symptoms: diagnosis and treatment.. The Israel Medical Association journal : IMAJ 16(12), 753-8
21. Stockman J A (2007) Neurobehavioral Effects of Dental Amalgam in Children: A Randomized Clinical Trial. Yearbook Of Pediatrics 2007, 89-91
22. Stockman J A (2007) Neuropsychological and Renal Effects of Dental Amalgam in Children: A Randomized Clinical Trial. Yearbook Of Pediatrics 2007, 87-89
23. Svendsen Kristin and Syversen Tore; Melo Inger; Hilt Bjorn; (2010) Historical exposure to mercury among Norwegian dental personnel.. Comment in: Scand J Work Environ Health. 2010 Sep and36(5):430-1 PMID: 20169292 [<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/20169292>] 36(3), 231-41
24. Sysalová Jiřina and Zvěřina Ondřej; Červenka Rostislav; Komárek Josef; (2020) Occurrence and transformation of mercury in formerly contaminated soils due to operation of amalgamation techniques and assessment of consequences.. Human & Ecological Risk Assessment 26(8), 2189-2202
25. Trachtenberg FL and Shrader P; Barregard L; Maserejian NN; (2014) Summary of: Dental composite materials and renal function in children. BRITISH DENTAL JOURNAL 216(2),
26. Trachtenberg F L and Shrader P; Barregard L; Maserejian N N; (2014) Dental composite materials and renal function in children.. Comment in: Br Dent J. 2014 Jan and216(2):80-1 PMID: 24457873 [<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/24457873>] 216(2), E4
27. Woods James S and Martin Michael D; Leroux Brian G; DeRouen Timothy A; Leitao Jorge G; Bernardo Mario F; Luis Henrique S; Simmonds P Lynne; Kushleika John V; Huang Ying; (2007) The contribution of dental amalgam to urinary mercury excretion in children.. Comment in: Environ Health Perspect. 2008 Mar and116(3):A107-8; author reply A108-9 PMID: 18335073

[<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/18335073>] Comment in: Environ Health Perspect. 2008 Jul;116(7):A286-A287 PMID: 18629336
[<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/18629336>] 115(10), 1527-31

Systematic review (n=1)

- Alcaraz M Graciela Rasines and Veitz-Keenan Analia; Sahrman Philipp; Schmidlin Patrick R; Davis Dell; Iheozor-Ejiofor Zipporah; (2014) Direct composite resin fillings versus amalgam fillings for permanent or adult posterior teeth. Cochrane Library

Duplicate (n=11)

1. (2012) Dental Composite Restorations and Psychosocial Function in Children. PEDIATRICS 130(2), X27-X27
2. Bellinger David C and Trachtenberg Felicia; Daniel David B; Zhang Annie; Tavares Mary; McKinlay Sonja M; (2007) A Dose-Effect Analysis of Children's Exposure to Dental Amalgam and Neuropsychological Function. The Journal Of The American Dental Association 138(9), 1210-1216
3. Bellinger DC and Trachtenberg F; Daniel D; Zhang A; Tavares MA; McKinlay S; (2007) A dose-effect analysis of children's exposure to dental amalgam and neuropsychological function. The New England Children's Amalgam Trial.. Journal of the American Dental Association (JADA) 138(9), 1210-1216
4. Echeverria Diana and Woods James S; Heyer Nicholas J; Martin Michael D; Rohlman Diane S; Farin Federico M; Li Tingting; (2010) The Association Between Serotonin Transporter Gene Promotor Polymorphism (5-HTTLPR) and Elemental Mercury Exposure on Mood and Behavior in Humans. Journal Of Toxicology And Environmental Health 73(15), 1003-1020
5. Luiz Ana Cláudia and Hirota S K; Vechio A Dal; Reis Víctor Machado; Spina R J; Migliari Dante Antônio; (2012) Diagnosing oral lichenoid contact reaction: clinical judgment versus skin-patch test.. Pubmed 61(7-8), 311-7
6. Shenker Bruce J and Maserejian Nancy N; Zhang Annie; McKinlay Sonja M; (2008) Immune Function Effects of Dental Amalgam in Children. The Journal Of The American Dental Association 139(11), 1496-1505
7. Shenker Bruce J and Maserejian Nancy N; Zhang Annie; McKinlay Sonja; (2008) Immune function effects of dental amalgam in children: a randomized clinical trial.. Comment in: J Esthet Restor Dent. 2013 Dec and25(6):433-7 PMID: 24320063
[<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/24320063>] 139(11), 1496-505

8. Stejskal Věra and Ockert Karin; Bjørklund Geir; (2013) Metal-induced inflammation triggers fibromyalgia in metal-allergic patients.. Pubmed 34(6), 559-65
9. Takaoka M and Oshita K; Takeda N; Morisawa S; (2010) Mercury emission from crematories in Japan.. Atmospheric Chemistry & Physics 10(8), 3665-3671
10. Warwick David and Young Matt; Palmer Joe; Ermel Robin Warwick; (2019) Mercury vapor volatilization from particulate generated from dental amalgam removal with a high-speed dental drill - a significant source of exposure.. Journal of occupational medicine and toxicology (London and England) 14, 22
11. Watson Gene E and Lynch Miranda L; Myers Gary J; Shamlaye Conrad F; Thurston Sally W; Zaręba Grażyna; Clarkson Thomas W; Davidson Philip W; (2011) Prenatal exposure to dental amalgam. The Journal Of The American Dental Association 142(11), 1283-1294

Lab (n=12)

1. Bjorkman Lars and Lundekvam Birgitte F; Laegreid Torgils; Bertelsen Bjorn I; Morild Inge; Lilleng Peer; Lind Birger; Palm Brita; Vahter Marie; (2007) Mercury in human brain, blood, muscle and toenails in relation to exposure: an autopsy study.. Environmental health : a global access science source 6, 30
2. Chin David W H and Treister Nathaniel; Friedland Bernard; Cormack Robert A; Tishler Roy B; Makrigiorgos G Mike; Court Laurence E; (2009) Effect of dental restorations and prostheses on radiotherapy dose distribution: a Monte Carlo study.. Journal of applied clinical medical physics 10(1), 80-89
3. Cokic S M and Duca R C; Godderis L; Hoet P H; Seo J W; Van Meerbeek B; Van Landuyt K L; (2017) Release of monomers from composite dust.. Journal of dentistry 60, 56-62
4. Gonzalez-Lopez Jose Abraham and Perez-Mondragon Alma Antonia; Cuevas-Suarez Carlos E; Trejo-Carbajal Nayely; Herrera-Gonzalez Ana M; (2020) Evaluation of dental composites resins formulated with non-toxic monomers derived from catechol.. Journal of the mechanical behavior of biomedical materials 104, 103613
5. Huang Fu-Mei and Kuan Yu-Hsiang; Lee Shiuan-Shinn; Chang Yu-Chao; (2015) Cytotoxicity and genotoxicity of triethyleneglycol-dimethacrylate in macrophages involved in DNA damage and caspases activation.. Environmental toxicology 30(5), 581-8
6. Kim Kyungsun and Kim Jeong Nam; Lim Bum-Soon; Ahn Sug-Joon; (2021) Urethane Dimethacrylate Influences the Cariogenic Properties of Streptococcus Mutans.. Materials (Basel and Switzerland) 14(4),
7. Krstic Dejan and Dunjic Momir; Zigar Darko; Stanisic Siavisa; Rajevic Bojan; Mirkovic Milos; Ignjatic Z Jovanovic; Dunjic Marija; Stefanovic Branislav; Dunjic Katarina; Krstic Mina; (2019)

ELECTRO-MAGNETIC FIELD RADIATION OF MOBILE PHONES AS A CAUSE OF INCREASED RELEASE OF MERCURY FROM AMALGAM FILLINGS AND RISK OF HARMFUL EFFECTS ON HEALTH.. *Acupuncture & Electro-Therapeutics Research* 44(1), 39-51

8. Michelsen Vibeke B and Moe Grete; Strøm Morten B; Jensen Einar; Lygre Henning; (2007) Quantitative analysis of TEGDMA and HEMA eluted into saliva from two dental composites by use of GC/MS and tailor-made internal standards. *Dental Materials* 24(6), 724-731
9. Mulligan Steven and Ojeda Jesús J; Kakonyi Gabriella; Thornton Steven F; Moharamzadeh Keyvan; Martín Nicolás; (2021) Characterisation of Microparticle Waste from Dental Resin-Based Composites. *Materials* 14(16), 4440-4440
10. Zhang Wei and Luo Xiao-Juan; Niu Li-Na; Liu Si-Ying; Zhu Wan-Chun; Epasinghe Jeevanie; Chen Liang; Li Guo-Hua; Huang Cui; Mao Jing; Pashley David H; Tay Franklin R; (2014) One-pot synthesis of antibacterial monomers with dual biocidal modes.. *Journal of dentistry* 42(9), 1078-95
11. Zhang N and Weir MD; Romberg E; Bai YX; Xu HHK; (2015) Development of novel dental adhesive with double benefits of protein-repellent and antibacterial capabilities. *DENTAL MATERIALS* 31(7), 845-854
12. Zhang DX and Li ST; Zhao HY; Li K; Zhang YW; Yu YJ; Yang XP; Cai Q; (2022) Improving antibacterial performance of dental resin adhesive via co-incorporating fluoride and quaternary ammonium. *JOURNAL OF DENTISTRY* 122

Appendix D: Study overview table: Prioritised health impact studies

Table 18. Study overview table: Prioritised health impact studies

Study [Country]: Publication status	Study design	Aim	Dental material [Intervention/ control]	Health or environmental impact evaluated	Summary of Findings
Health impact: Dental professional studies (n=10)					
Duplinsky 2012, [USA]; JAP ²⁰⁸	Cohort with control group	Evaluate health of sample of 600 dentists, matched to control subjects, for gender, age, geographical area, and insurance plan structure	Exposure: amalgam	General physical health, neuropsychological, neurological, cardiovascular, psychological, respiratory	Dentists used significantly more prescriptions of specific illness medications than controls.
Heggland 2011, [Norway]; JAP ²¹⁷	Retrospective cohort study (records review)	Investigate risk of having children with congenital malformations/adverse pregnancy outcomes greater in females experienced as dental personnel with possible previous exposure to mercury vapour vs general population	Exposure: amalgam/Hg vapour	Pregnancy outcomes	Female dental personnel: no increased occurrence of congenital malformations (malformations of the central nervous system, hip dysplasia, clubfoot, heart malformations or great vessels), low birth weight, preterm birth, small for gestational age, changed gender ratio, multiple birth, stillbirth, or prenatal death.
Heratizadeh 2018, [Germany, Switzerland, Austria]; JAP ²¹⁸	Case control	Describe current spectrum of occupational sensitisation in dental technicians (DTs) with occupational contact dermatitis (OCD)	Amalgam and/or composite restorations	Allergy	Study group (226 DTs with OCD) diagnosed significantly more often with allergic contact dermatitis (37.6% versus 18.5%; p=0.0002) than patients of control group (124 DTs without OCD). In study group, positive reactions most frequently observed to methacrylates and/or acrylates (n=67). Of these, 61 patients showed positive reactions to min.1 of five most frequent allergens in this group: 2-hydroxyethyl methacrylate, 2-hydroxypropyl methacrylate, methyl methacrylate, ethyl methacrylate, and/or ethylene glycol dimethacrylate. No positive reactions to diurethane dimethacrylate (DUDMA) occurred. Among allergens of German Contact Dermatitis Research Group series 'dental metals', positive reactions were less frequent and mainly to palladium chloride (n=6).

Study [Country]: Publication status	Study design	Aim	Dental material [Intervention/ control]	Health or environmental impact evaluated	Summary of Findings
Hilt 2009, [Norway]; JAP ²²⁰	Cross-sectional with control group	Examine correlation between mercury exposure and cognitive effects in Norwegian dental workers	Assume amalgam: exposure to metallic mercury	Cardiovascular, general physical health, neurological, neuropsychological, psychological, respiratory	Dental assistants reported more cognitive symptoms than the controls but reported having each symptom 'less frequently'. 4.4% of dental assistants vs 2.8% controls reporting three or more of seven symptoms experienced them 'often' or 'more frequently'. Five or more of seven symptoms: 1.0% and 0.5% respectively.
Hilt, 2011, [Norway]; JAP ²¹⁹	Cross-sectional with control group	Investigate if Norwegian dentists have increased prevalence of symptoms consistent with neurological and/or cognitive malfunction	Copper amalgam: exposure to mercury	General physical health, neurological, neuropsychological, psychological	Dentists reported no more cognitive symptoms than controls, with low average symptom scores from 1.16 for neurological symptoms in males to 1.73 for fatigue in females. Corresponding figures for controls were 1.22 and 1.77. Total 1.2 % dentists vs 1.8 % controls reported having three or more of seven symptoms "often" or more frequently. Groups equivalent on cognitive tasks and four of the six mood subscales. Significant between-group differences for current health symptoms and reproductive health, especially early hysterectomy experience. Reporting of Occupational Overuse Syndrome strongly positively correlated with years of work.
Jones, 2007, [New Zealand]; JAP ²²²	Cross-sectional with control group	Test null hypothesis: no differences in health survey and neurobehavioral assessments between women who worked in NZ School Dental Service before withdrawal of copper amalgam or introduction of encapsulated silver, and matched women never occupationally exposed to mercury. Reporting cognitive, mood, general health and reproductive health findings	Copper amalgam: exposure to mercury	Dermatological, endocrine, female health, general physical health, musculoskeletal, neuropsychological pregnancy outcomes psychological	
Lindbohm, 2007, [Finland]; JAP ²²⁴	Retrospective/cross- sectional with control	Investigate whether dental workers exposed to acrylate compounds, mercury amalgam, solvents or disinfectants are at an increased risk of miscarriage	Exposure: dental restorative materials containing acrylate compounds, mercury amalgam.	Pregnancy outcomes	The ORs adjusted for confounding factors were increased for moderate-exposure and high-exposure categories of mercury amalgam (OR 2.0, 95% CI 1.0 to 4.1 and OR 1.3, 95% CI 0.6 to 2.5, respectively). The risk was slightly increased for the highest- exposure category of 2-hydroxyethylmethacrylate (OR 1.4, 95% CI 0.7 to 2.6) and polymethylmethacrylate dust (OR 1.4, 95% CI 0.8 to 2.4). A slightly increased risk was also detected for likely exposure to organic solvents (OR 1.4, 95% CI 0.8 to 2.3) and disinfectants (OR 1.5, 95% CI 0.9 to 2.7).

Study [Country]: Publication status	Study design	Aim	Dental material [Intervention/ control]	Health or environmental impact evaluated	Summary of Findings
Naimi-Akbar, 2012, [Sweden]; JAP ²³⁵	Retrospective cohort with control	Investigate cognitive function among offspring of women working in dentistry during their pregnancy	Occupational amalgam exposure	Neuropsychological	Linear regression showed that sons of dental workers had similar or higher cognitive function test results compared to their matched cohort.
Naimi-Akbar 2014, [Sweden]; JAP ²³⁶	Retrospective cohort with control	Examine increased mortality risk in offspring of mothers working in dentistry	Occupational amalgam exposure	Pregnancy outcomes	During 1960s: statistically significant increase in risk of neonatal mortality for sons of dental nurses vs sons of assistant nurses (HR: 1.82, 95% CI: 1.04– 3.22). No increased risk in subsequent decades. Trend test demonstrated consistent decrease in risk over three decades (HR: 0.63, 95% CI: 0.44–0.90). Raised mortality risk limited to neonatal mortality. Insufficient statistical power for comparison dentists vs physicians.
Thygesen 2010, [Finland]; JAP ²⁴³	Retrospective Observational: Cohort Study	Compare hospital admissions due to neurological and renal diseases among dentists and dental assistants to admissions in controls	Occupational mercury exposure via amalgam	Neurological, renal, serious adverse events	Cohort consisted of 122,481 workers including 5,371 dentists and 33,858 dental assistants. For neurological diseases, no association was observed for dental assistants, while for dentists an increasing risk for periods with less mercury exposure was observed. Among dental assistants, a negative association between employment length and risk of neurological disease was observed. Admissions for renal disease among dental assistants were increased during periods with less mercury exposure compared with controls. For dentists a non- significant increased risk was observed between employment length and renal disease risk. Conclusions: nationwide study does not indicate that occupational exposure to mercury increases the risk of hospital admissions for neurological, Parkinson's or renal diseases.

Health impact: Patient studies (n=77)

Study [Country]: Publication status	Study design	Aim	Dental material [Intervention/ control]	Health or environmental impact evaluated	Summary of Findings
Adams, 2008, [USA]; JAP ¹⁹⁴	Case control	Investigate role of mercury in aetiology of autism. Two objectives: (1) compare level of Hg in first-cut baby hair of children with autism vs controls and (2) compare factors in medical history that affect Hg body burden in children with autism vs controls	Exposure: received amalgam restoration	Child-Maternal exposure: autism, exposure	Children with higher levels of mercury (above 0.55 mcg g ⁻¹) were 2.5-fold more likely to manifest with autism vs children with lower mercury levels in hair (below 0.55 mcg g ⁻¹). Both groups had similar mercury exposure from maternal seafood and maternal dental amalgams. Hg in baby hair of children with autism showed a significant correlation with no. maternal dental amalgams. Lower level of Hg in baby hair of children with autism indicates altered metabolism of Hg and may be due to decreased ability to excrete Hg.
Ahlgren, 2014, [USA]; JAP ¹⁹⁵	Case control	Investigate relationship between contact allergies to potential allergens and oral lichen lesions	Exposure: amalgam or composite restorations	Allergy and oral health	Frequencies of contact allergy to mercury and carvone statistically higher in OLL group than DP group. Surfaces of amalgam and composite restorations statistically more frequent in the OLL group compared to the DP group. Contact allergy to nickel and colophony, latter statistically significant difference, more common in DP group. Difference found for nickel allergy was not significant between OLL and PSFF groups.
<i>New England Children's Amalgam Trial</i>					
Bellinger, 2006, [USA]; JAP ¹⁷⁹	RCT	Compare neuropsychological and renal function of children whose dental caries were restored using amalgam or mercury-free materials	Amalgam restorations	Adverse events, allergy, blood disorder, cancer, cardiovascular, dermatological, endocrine, exposure, gastrointestinal, general physical health, musculoskeletal, neurological, neuropsychological, psychological, renal, respiratory, sensory disorder	Amalgam associated with significantly higher mean urinary mercury level (0.9 vs 0.6 µg/g of creatinine at yr 5, (P<.001). After adjusting for randomisation stratum and other covariates, no statistically significant differences between amalgam vs composite in 5-yr change in full-scale IQ score (3.1 vs 2.1, P=.21). Difference in treatment change scores was 1.0 (95% confidence interval, -0.6 to 2.5) full-scale IQ score point. No statistically significant differences for 4-yr change in general memory index (8.1 vs 7.2, P=.34), 4-yr change in visuomotor composite (3.8 vs 3.7, P=.93), or yr 5 urinary albumin (median, 7.5 vs 7.4 mg/g of creatinine, P=.61)
Barregard, 2008, [USA], JAP ¹⁷⁷	RCT	Report the results on markers of possible effects of mercury on kidneys in New England Children's Amalgam Trial (NECAT)	Amalgam restorations	Renal	No significant differences between treatment groups in average levels of renal biomarkers, nor sig. effects of no. dental amalgams on these markers. Significantly increased prevalence of MA among children in amalgam group yrs 3–5 (adjusted odds ratio 1.8; 95% CI, 1.1–2.9). Most of these cases are

Study [Country]: Publication status	Study design	Aim	Dental material [Intervention/ control]	Health or environmental impact evaluated	Summary of Findings
Bellinger 2007, [Dose effect analysis] [USA]: JAP ¹⁹⁶	RCT (secondary analysis)	Present additional analyses of the primary and secondary neuropsychological outcomes (NECAT) (Bellinger 2006) in which two continuously distributed indexes (surface-years of amalgam, urinary mercury excretion) were used to characterise children's exposure to mercury from amalgam.	Amalgam [Resin composite] restorations	Neuropsychological, dental treatment, exposure,	likely to be temporary MA, but 10 children in amalgam group had MA in both yrs 3+5, vs 2 children in composite group (p = 0.04). No differences in occurrence of high levels of renal tubular markers (A1M, γ-GT, or NAG) Neither index of mercury exposure was significantly associated with any of the three outcomes - Full scale IQ, General Memory Index, Visual Motor Composite. No evidence that exposure to mercury from dental amalgam was associated with any adverse neuropsychological effects over the five-year period after placement of amalgam restorations.
Bellinger 2007, [[Dental amalgam restorations, neuropsychological function]] [USA]; JAP ¹⁷⁸	RCT	Compare the neuropsychological function of children, without prior exposure to dental amalgam, whose caries were repaired using either dental amalgam or mercury free composite materials.	Amalgam [Resin composite] restorations	Neuropsychological	Although the mean urinary mercury concentration was greater among children in the amalgam group than the composite group (0.9 vs. 0.6 µg/g creatinine), few significant differences were found between the test scores of children in the two groups. The differences found were inconsistent in direction. Analyses using two cumulative exposure indices—surface years of amalgam and urinary mercury concentration—produced similar results.
Bellinger 2008, [[Psychosocial]] [USA]; JAP ¹⁸⁰	RCT	Evaluate the hypothesis that, by parent- and self-report, the psychosocial health of children in the amalgam group is worse than that of children in the composite resin group	Amalgam [Resin composite] restorations	Psychosocial	No significant differences between treatment groups in average levels of renal biomarkers, nor significant effects of number of dental amalgams on these markers. Significantly increased prevalence of MA among children in amalgam group yrs 3–5 (adjusted odds ratio 1.8; 95% CI, 1.1–2.9). Most of these cases were likely to be temporary MA, but 10 children in amalgam group had MA in both yrs 3+5, vs 2 children in composite group (p = 0.04). No differences in occurrence of high levels of renal tubular markers (A1M, γ-GT, or NAG).
Maserejian 2012, [dental composites, amalgam, physical health] [USA]; JAP ¹⁸⁸	RCT (secondary analysis)	Test hypothesis that dental restoration materials affect children's growth	Amalgam [Resin composite] restorations	Anthropomorphic, female health	No significant differences between treatment groups and changes in physical development in boys [(composites vs. amalgam) Body Fat%, 4.9 vs. 5.7, p = 0.49; (BMI-z-score) 0.13 vs. 0.25, p = 0.36] or girls (8.8 vs. 7.7, p = 0.95; 0.36 vs. 0.21, p = 0.49). Children with more treatment on primary teeth had

Study [Country]: Publication status	Study design	Aim	Dental material [Intervention/ control]	Health or environmental impact evaluated	Summary of Findings
Maserejian 2012, [Neuro] [USA]; JAP ²⁵⁹	RCT	Present secondary analysis examining whether exposure to resin-based composite restorations is associated with neuropsychological development in children	Composite/compomer resin restorations	Neuropsychological	<p>greater increases in Body Fat% regardless of material type. Girls assigned to composites had lower risk of menarche during follow-up (hazard ratio = 0.57, 95% CI 0.35-0.95). Overall, no significant differences in physical development over 5 years in children treated with composites or amalgam.</p> <p>With greater exposure to either dental composite material, results indicated slightly poorer changes in tests of intelligence, achievement or memory (not significant). For four executive function measures, scores slightly worse with greater total composite exposure, but statistically significant only for Letter Fluency (10-surface-years $\beta = -0.8$, SE=0.4, P=0.035), and colour naming ($\beta = -1.5$, SE=0.5, P=0.004) in Stroop Color-Word Interference Test. Multivariate analysis of variance confirmed negative associations between composite level and executive function not statistically significant (MANOVA P=0.18). Results for greater amalgam exposure were mostly nonsignificant in opposite direction of slightly improved scores over follow-up.</p>
Maserejian 2012, [Dental composite restorations and psychosocial function] [USA]; JAP ²⁰⁹	RCT	Present secondary analysis examining whether greater exposure to dental composites is associated with psychosocial problems in children	Amalgam [Composite resin] restorations	Psychosocial	<p>Children with higher cumulative exposure to BisGMA-based composite had poorer follow-up scores on 3 of 4 BASC-SR global scales: Emotional Symptoms (b = 0.8, SE = 0.3, P = .003), Clinical Maladjustment (b = 0.7, SE = 0.3, P = .02), and Personal Adjustment (b = -0.8, SE = 0.2, P = .002). Associations stronger with posterior-occlusal (chewing) surfaces, where degradation of composite more likely. For CBCL change, associations not statistically significant. At-risk or clinically significant scores more common among children with greater exposure for CBCL Total Problem Behaviors (16.3% vs 11.2%, P-trend = .01) and numerous BASC-SR syndromes (e.g, $\\$13$ vs 0 surface-years, Interpersonal Relations 13.7% vs 4.8%, P-trend = .01). No associations found with compomer, nor with amalgam exposure levels among children randomised to amalgam.</p>

Study [Country]: Publication status	Study design	Aim	Dental material [Intervention/ control]	Health or environmental impact evaluated	Summary of Findings
Maserejian 2014, [Dental sealants and flowable composite restorations] [USA]; JAP ²⁵⁸	RCT	Present secondary analysis examining sealant/PRR exposure in association with psychosocial and other health outcomes	Sound pits and fissures of posterior teeth (sealants); shallow, incipient caries that did not extend into dentin (flowable composite); restoration (composite, permanent teeth); compomer (primary teeth)	Psychological neuropsychological and physical development	Cumulative exposure level to sealants and/or PRRs was not associated with psychosocial assessments (e.g. total problems: Child Behavior Checklist, 10-SY $\beta=-0.2$, $SE=0.3$, $P=0.6$) or neuropsychological tests (e.g. full-scale IQ, 10-SY $\beta=0.1$, $SE=0.2$, $P=0.6$). There were no associations for changes in BMI-for-age z- score ($P=0.4$), BF% (girls 10-SY $\beta=-0.2$ $SE=0.3$; boys 10-SY $\beta=-0.1$ $SE=0.3$), or menarche (10-SY hazard ratio=0.91, 95%CI 0.83–1.01, $P=0.08$). Conclusions— This analysis showed no significant associations between exposure level of dental sealants or PRRs and behavioural, neuropsychological, or physical development in children during 5-year follow-up. Total white blood cell counts and responsiveness of T-cells or neutrophils not altered by composite treatment levels. Changes in B-cell responsiveness greater throughout follow-up among children with more BisGMA-based composite restorations, opposing findings for amalgam treatment levels. Monocyte responsiveness changes decreased at 6- months with greater treatment, but not over longer follow-up.
Maserejian 2014, [Dental sealants and composite restorations] [USA]; JAP ¹⁸⁷	RCT	Present secondary analysis exploring children's immune function changes in relation to resin-composites treatment	Three classes resin-composite materials: (i) flowable composites [preventive sealants and preventive resin restorations (PRR)], (ii) non-flowable standard BisGMA-based composite [restoration of permanent tooth caries], (iii) non-flowable polyacid-modified UDMA-based composite (compomer)	Immune function	Amalgam: non-statistically significant, decline in responsiveness of T-cells and monocytes at 5–7 days post treatment; no differences consistently observed at 6, 12 or 60 months.
Shenker 2008, [USA]; JAP ¹⁹²	RCT (secondary analysis)	Present secondary analysis evaluating sub-population for in vitro manifestations of immunotoxic effects of dental amalgam	Amalgam [composite resin] restorations	Exposure, immune function	
Bjorkman 2018, [Norway]; JAP ¹⁹⁸	Prospective longitudinal	Gain knowledge regarding the risk of perinatal death related to exposure to dental amalgam fillings in the mother	Exposure: teeth restored with amalgam [no amalgam restorations]	Pregnancy outcomes	Absolute risk of perinatal death ranged from 0.20% in women with no amalgam-filled teeth to 0.67% in women with 13 or more teeth filled with amalgam. Analyses indicated an increased risk of perinatal death by increasing number of teeth filled with dental amalgam (crude OR 1.065, 95% CI 1.034 to 1.098, $p<0.001$). After adjustment for potential confounders (mothers' age, education, body mass index, parity, smoking during pregnancy, alcohol consumption during pregnancy), still an increased risk for perinatal death associated with increasing number of teeth filled with amalgam (OR _{adj} 1.041,

Study [Country]: Publication status	Study design	Aim	Dental material [Intervention/ control]	Health or environmental impact evaluated	Summary of Findings
<i>Bergen Amalgam Trial</i>					
Bjorkman 2020, [Norway]; JAP ²⁰⁰	Prospective longitudinal with pre- post and control	Evaluate changes of general health complaints in patients who participated in the project and had all amalgam restorations removed	Amalgam restorations removal [medically unexplained symptoms not attributed to amalgam/healthy cohorts]	General physical health, psychological	95% CI 1.008 to 1.076, p = 0.015). By an increased exposure from 0 to 16 teeth filled with amalgam, the model predicted an almost doubled odds ratio (OR _{adj} 1.915, 95% CI 1.12 to 3.28). In groups with 1 to 12 teeth filled with amalgam the adjusted odds ratios were slightly, but not significantly, increased. The group with the highest exposure (participants with 13 or more teeth filled with amalgam) had an adjusted OR of 2.34 (95% CI 1.27 to 4.32; p = 0.007).
Bjorkman 2023, [Norway]; JAP ¹⁹⁹	Prospective longitudinal	Provide and evaluate experimental treatment to patients with health complaints attributed to dental amalgam fillings	Amalgam restorations removal [medically unexplained symptoms not attributed to amalgam/healthy cohorts]	General physical health, exposure, adverse events, serious adverse events	In the Amalgam cohort, a significant reduction of GHC index from 43.3 (SD 17.8) at baseline to 30.5 (SD 14.4) at follow-up (mean reduction 12.8, SD 15.9; n = 32; P < .001) was observed. The change scores for GHC index indicated that the reduction of complaints was significantly higher (P = .004) in the Amalgam cohort compared with the MUPS cohort (mean reduction 1.2, SD 12.3, n = 28). After adjustment for age, gender, education and baseline GHC index, the mean adjusted difference was -8.0 (95% confidence interval from -15.4 to -0.5; P = .036). Concentration of I-Hg and Ag in serum decreased significantly after removal of all amalgam restorations. Concentration of MeHg and Se in serum were not changed. Intensity of health complaints was significantly reduced after amalgam removal, but there were no statistically significant correlations between exposure indicators and health complaints.
Sinha 2024, [Norway]; JAP ²¹⁰	Prospective longitudinal (with control groups)	Evaluate the changes of health complaints after removal of amalgam restorations in patients with health complaints attributed to dental amalgam fillings	Amalgam restorations removal [medically unexplained symptoms not attributed to amalgam/healthy cohorts]	Allergy, Anthropomorphic, Auditory, cardiovascular, dermatological, ENT, female health, gastrointestinal, general physical health, musculoskeletal, neuropsychological, oral health, orofacial,	In the Amalgam cohort, mean symptom intensity was lower for all 23 health complaints at follow-up at 1 year compared to baseline. Statistically significant changes were observed for specific health complaints with effect sizes between 0.36 and 0.68. At the 5-year follow-up, the intensity of symptoms remained consistently lower compared to before the amalgam removal. In the comparison groups, no significant changes of intensity of symptoms of health complaints were observed.

Study [Country]: Publication status	Study design	Aim	Dental material [Intervention/ control]	Health or environmental impact evaluated	Summary of Findings
				psychological, respiratory, visual/ocular	
Bjorkman 2012, [Norway]; JAP ¹⁹⁷	Prospective cohort with before and after component	Test the hypothesis of no change over time in concentrations of a number of immune mediators in serum after removal of all dental amalgam restorations in patients with health complaints attributed to their amalgam restorations and compare with a healthy reference group	Amalgam restorations removal [amalgam free group]	Exposure, immune function	At baseline, the patient group had slightly higher values for GM-CSF, IL-6, IL-2R, IFN-alpha, IL-7, and IL- 12p40/p70 compared with the reference group. After amalgam removal a decrease towards the median value of the reference group was found for GM-CSF, IL-8, and IL-7. In conclusion, removal of all dental amalgam restorations and replacement with other dental restorative materials was associated with decreased concentrations of Th1 type proinflammatory markers in serum.
Bjorkman 2017, [Norway]; JAP ²⁰¹	Prospective cohort with before and after component	Present data on long term changes in intensity of health complaints after amalgam removal in patients with health complaints self- attributed to dental amalgam. Data from five years follow-up in a clinical trial presented and related to potential determinants of change	Amalgam restorations removal	Adverse events, exposure, gastrointestinal, general physical health, musculoskeletal, neuropsychological, oral health, psychological,	At follow-up five years after amalgam removal, intensity of general health complaints significantly reduced (p<.001), but symptom load still high. Reduction significantly correlated with pre- treatment concentration urinary mercury. No significant correlations with personality variables.
Sjursen 2011, [Norway]; JAP ²¹¹	Prospective cohort with before and after component	Investigate whether removal of all amalgam fillings was associated with long-term changes in health complaints in a group of patients who attributed subjective health complaints to amalgam fillings	Amalgam restorations removal [no intervention in the reference group]	Adverse events, exposure, general physical health, orofacial	Subjective health complaints were measured by numeric rating scales in both groups. Analysis of covariance was used to compare changes in health complaints over time in the two groups. In the treatment group, there were significant reductions in intra-oral and general health complaints from inclusion into study to the 3-year follow-up. In the reference group, changes in the same period were not significant. Comparisons between the groups showed that reductions in intra-oral and general health complaints in the treatment group were significantly different from the changes in the reference group. The mechanisms behind this remain to be identified. Reduced exposure to dental amalgam, patient centred treatment and follow-ups, and elimination of worry were factors that may have influenced the results.

Study [Country]: Publication status	Study design	Aim	Dental material [Intervention/ control]	Health or environmental impact evaluated	Summary of Findings
Cabana-Munoz 2015, [Spain]; JAP ²⁰²	Cross-sectional with control	Determine whether heavy metals (in hair), antioxidant enzymes (SOD-1) and glutathione levels could be affected by the chronic presence of heavy metals in women who had dental amalgam fillings	Amalgam restorations [no amalgam restorations]	Oxidative stress	Hg, Ag, Al and Ba were higher in the amalgam group but without significant differences for most of the heavy metals analysed. Increased SOD-1 activity and glutathione levels (reduced form) were observed in the amalgam group. Aluminium (Al) correlated with glutathione levels while Hg levels correlated with SOD-1. The observed Al/glutathione and Hg/SOD-1 correlation could be adaptive responses against the chronic presence of mercury.
Cabana-Munoz 2019, [Spain]; JAP ²⁰³	Cross-sectional with control	Evaluate whether patients who had long-term dental titanium implants and amalgams had systemic oxidative stress due to rising malondialdehyde (MDA) levels and lower Mo/Hg ²⁺ , Mo/Co, Mo/Fe ²⁺ ratios than those with long-term dental amalgams alone.	Amalgam restorations and amalgam restorations with titanium implants [no amalgam restorations]	Oxidative stress	The A + I group had lower molybdenum levels (A + I) and reduced Mo/Co and Mo/Fe ²⁺ ratios, which could predispose them to oxidative stress by raising MDA levels as compared to the A group alone. The findings suggest that higher Co levels could enhance oxidative stress in the A + I group. However, there were no differences on metals from titanium alloy (Ti-6Al), Cr from crowns or Hg ²⁺ , Sn, Zn ²⁺ , Cu ²⁺ levels between the A + I and A groups.
Chen 2020, [Taiwan]; JAP ²⁰⁵	Case control	Investigate relationship between Parkinson's disease development and amalgam use	Amalgam restorations [no amalgam restorations]	Neurological	No significant association between Parkinson's disease and amalgam restorations in Taiwanese people.
Chen 2021, [Taiwan]; JAP ²⁰⁴	Case control	Investigate association of amalgam filling and risk of primary Sjögren's syndrome (pSS)	Amalgam restorations [no amalgam restorations]	Immune function	No statistically significant differences between amalgam restorations and pSS (odds ratio [OR]: 0.974, 95% confidence interval [CI]=0.904–1.049). pSS not associated with AMF for women (OR: 0.743, 95% CI=0.552–1.000) and men (OR: 1.006, 95% CI=0.670–1.509).
Daniels 2007, [UK]; JAP ²⁰⁶	Prospective cohort	Evaluate maternal dental history prior to and during pregnancy in relation to birth outcomes and early communicative development among offspring in a large cohort (n=7375) of British children born in 1991– 1992.	Amalgam restorations	Exposure, neuropsychological, pregnancy outcomes	Overall, dental care, including amalgam fillings, was not associated with birth outcomes or language development. Having x-rays taken during pregnancy was not associated with birthweight measured continuously ($\beta=14.7$, $p=0.4$), but was associated with slightly increased odds of having a term, low birthweight baby (OR 1.9, 95%CI 1.0–3.4). More detailed evaluation of the potential adverse effects of elective dental treatment during pregnancy, particularly dental x-rays, may be warranted.

Study [Country]: Publication status	Study design	Aim	Dental material [Intervention/ control]	Health or environmental impact evaluated	Summary of Findings
Dermata 2018, [Greece]; JAP ²⁶³	RCT	Compare two-year success rates of Resin Modified Glass Ionomer Cement (RMGIC) with composite resin in Class II primary molar restorations	Resin modified glass ionomer cement (Vitremmer) Class II restorations [Composite resin (Z250) Class II restorations]	Oral health	All-cause failure rate for both materials was 3% after 1 yr (4% and 2% for Z250 and Vitremmer, respectively) and 16% after 2 years (16% for both Z250 and Vitremmer). No difference between materials at 2 years (RR=1.4; 95% CI=0.8,2.4; P=0.30). Vitremmer associated with more favourable gingival health vs composite (RR=0.2; 95% CI=0.1,0.9; P=0.03), but also occlusal wear, observed exclusively for Vitremmer. The average OHIP-14 (Oral Health Impact Profile) score was 13.54. A high correlation was seen between OHIP and pain. Higher OHIP-values were seen for male patients, and for those patients with non-reticular forms of oral lichen planus (OLP). A local form of OLP was more often seen on female patients, such as with the presence of reticular lichen. In relation to restorations, the presence of composite restorations was correlated with a local lichen, whereas the presence of gold restorations was often seen with a generalised lichen. The grading of strength of association between mucosal lesion and amalgam/metal was tested and no significant differences revealed the analysis of the relationship between gender, clinical form of OLP, age, and presentation form between the 4 gradings of Thornhill.
Duame, 2021; [Germany]; JAP ²⁰⁷	Cross-sectional with control group	Investigate influence of clinical characteristics and dental restorative materials (specifically amalgam and metals) on oral health-related quality of life in patients with oral lichen planus	Amalgam and composite restorations	Oral health	None had elevated mercury levels in blood or urine above normal threshold. Subjects with oral lesions, autoimmune disorders and multiple sclerosis had significantly higher mercury levels within this cohort, but within threshold values. When tested by multiple logistic regression adjusted for age and gender, mercury levels in blood or urine, numbers of amalgams were not significant for multiple sclerosis or autoimmune disease.
Eyeson 2010, [UK]; JAP ²¹²	Retrospective record review	Determine whether patients complaining of oral and medical symptoms perceived to be associated with chronic mercury toxicity have elevated mercury levels in their blood and urine	Amalgam restorations [no amalgam restorations]	Allergy, cardiovascular, exposure, general physical health, immune function, musculoskeletal, neurological, oral health, psychological	None had elevated mercury levels in blood or urine above normal threshold. Subjects with oral lesions, autoimmune disorders and multiple sclerosis had significantly higher mercury levels within this cohort, but within threshold values. When tested by multiple logistic regression adjusted for age and gender, mercury levels in blood or urine, numbers of amalgams were not significant for multiple sclerosis or autoimmune disease.

Study [Country]: Publication status	Study design	Aim	Dental material [Intervention/ control]	Health or environmental impact evaluated	Summary of Findings
Forkel 2024, [Germany, Switzerland and Austria]; JAP ²¹³	Retrospective record review	Analyse current sensitisation patterns to dental materials in patients with suspected contact allergy	Dental restoration materials considered problematic: of relevance - methacrylates, amalgam [restorations]	Allergy	The sensitisation rates with confirmed allergic contact stomatitis in women (n=444) highest for metals (nickel 28.6%, palladium 21.4%, amalgam 10.9%), (meth)acrylates [2-hydroxyethyl methacrylate (HEMA) 4.8%] and substances propolis (6.8%) and 'balsam of Peru' (11.4%). Most relevant acrylates were HEMA, 2-hydroxypropyl methacrylate, methyl methacrylate, ethylene glycol dimethacrylate and pentaerythritol Tri acrylate. Few men were diagnosed with allergic contact stomatitis (n=68); sensitisation rates in men highest for propolis (14.9%) and amalgam (13.6%).
Frisk 2007, [Sweden]; JAP ²¹⁵	Controlled before and after	Investigate the connection between dental amalgam restorations removal, supported by antioxidant therapy, and indicative changes of clinical chemistry parameters	Amalgam and other metal alloys restorations removal	Clinical chemistry variables, exposure, immune function	Hg and Se values decreased (p<0.05) in plasma, and Hg concentration decreased (p<0.05) in erythrocytes after amalgam removal. Serum lactate dehydrogenase Serum LDH and serum sodium differed significantly when comparing Control with Before (p<0.01) and Before with After (p<0.01). White blood cell count (WBC, blood neutrophil count, blood eosinophil count, blood basophil count, blood lymphocyte count, blood monocyte count, serum potassium, and serum creatinine differed in Before/After test (p<0.05).
Franzblau 2012, [USA]; JAP ²¹⁴	Longitudinal with cross-sectional element	Examine the association between urinary mercury concentration and peripheral nerve function as assessed by sensory nerve conduction studies in a large group of dental professionals	Amalgam restorations placed and removed	Exposure, neurological	3594 observations from 2656 subjects were analysed. Urine mercury levels in the study population were higher than, but substantially overlapped with, the general population. The only stable significant positive association involved median (not ulnar) sensory peak latency, and only for the model that was based on initial observations and exclusion of subjects with imputed BMI. No significant association between median or ulnar amplitudes and urine mercury was found.

Study [Country]: Publication status	Study design	Aim	Dental material [Intervention/ control]	Health or environmental impact evaluated	Summary of Findings
Gavic 2019, [Croatia]; JAP ²⁵⁵	RCT	Evaluate possible DNA damage to buccal cells exposed to dental materials	Glass ionomer cement (2x types: Ketac Molar and Ionofil Molar) or compomer (1 type) restorations [Class II restorations]	Genotoxicity	In patients treated with Ketac Molar, a significant frequency of micronuclei ($p = 0.027$) and binucleated cells in samples taken 30 days following restoration ($p = 0.029$) was confirmed. In patients treated with Twinkly Star, a statistically significant increase in the number of binucleated cells in samples taken after 7- and 30-days following restoration ($p = 0.001$ and $p < 0.001$, respectively) was observed. In all samples collected 90 days after treatment, there was no statistical difference in the number of any cell changes.
<i>Casa Pia Trial</i>					
De Rouen 2006, [Portugal]; JAP ¹⁸¹ (De Rouen, 2002)	RCT	Assess safety of dental amalgam restorations in children	Amalgam [composite resin] restorations	Adverse events, exposure, neurological, neurobehavioral, neuropsychological, renal	During 7-year trial period, children had mean 18.7 tooth surfaces (median, 16) restored in amalgam group vs 21.3 (median, 18) restored in composite group. Baseline mean creatinine-adjusted urinary mercury levels: 1.8 $\mu\text{g/g}$ in amalgam group vs 1.9 $\mu\text{g/g}$ in composite group, but during follow-up were 1.0 to 1.5 $\mu\text{g/g}$ higher in amalgam group than composite group ($P < .001$). No statistically significant differences in memory, attention, visuomotor function, or nerve conduction velocities for amalgam vs composite groups over all 7 years of follow-up, with no statistically significant differences observed at any time point (P values from .29 to .91).
Geier 2011, [USA]; JAP ¹⁸²	Prospective cohort (using data from RCT)	Determine whether there was a significant dose-dependent correlation between increasing Hg exposure from dental amalgams and specific urinary porphyrins associated with Hg body-burden	Amalgam [composite resin] restorations	Other: urinary porphyrins	Significant dose-dependent correlations between cumulative exposure to Hg from dental amalgams and urinary porphyrins associated with Hg body-burden (pentacarboxyporphyrin, precoproporphyrin, and coproporphyrin) were observed. 5–10% increases in Hg-associated porphyrins for subjects receiving an average number of dental amalgam fillings in comparison to subjects receiving only composite fillings were observed over the 8-year course of the study. No significant correlations were observed between cumulative exposure to Hg from dental amalgams and urinary porphyrins not associated with Hg body-burden (uroporphyrin, heptacarboxyporphyrin, and hexacarboxyporphyrin). In contrast to the no-effect results published from

Study [Country]: Publication status	Study design	Aim	Dental material [Intervention/ control]	Health or environmental impact evaluated	Summary of Findings
Geier 2013, [USA]; JAP ²¹⁶	Prospective cohort (using data from RCT)	Examine Casa Pia children's amalgam data as the potential dose-dependent relationship focusing on link between cumulative Hg exposure from dental amalgam fillings and urinary GST-a and -p levels. Hypothesis: GST-a levels more related to Hg exposure from amalgams than levels of GST-p	Amalgam [composite resin] restorations	Renal	the parent study, this study established the sensitivity and specificity of specific urinary porphyrins as a biomarker for low-level Hg body-burden and revealed that dental amalgams are a significant chronic contributor to Hg body-burden. Statistically significant dose-dependent correlation between cumulative exposure to Hg from dental amalgams and urinary levels of GST-a, after covariate adjustment. Nonsignificant relationship urinary levels of GST-p. Urinary GST-a levels increased approximately 10% over 8-year study among individuals with average exposure to amalgams among study subjects from amalgam group, vs subjects with no amalgam exposure. Results suggest dental amalgams contribute to ongoing kidney damage at level of PTs in dose-dependent fashion. No significant differences between treatment groups in any neurological measures (presence of neurological hard signs (NHSs), tremor, nor presence/absence/severity of neurological soft signs (NSSs) at any point. NSS severity scores reduced with increasing age.
Lauterbach 2008, [Portugal]; JAP ¹⁸⁴	RCT	Examine safety of dental amalgam	Amalgam [composite resin] restorations	Neurological	Urinary creatinine excretion increases with age for both sexes and for both races (P < 0.0001). No significant sexual difference was observed, although a race difference occurs, with blacks showing higher excretion levels than whites (p = 0.0003). Longitudinal urinary creatinine excretion data for ages 9–17 in which creatinine excretion increases with age throughout the time period were presented. No sexual differences were observed, although blacks excrete significantly higher levels of urinary creatinine than do whites.
Martin 2008, [USA & Portugal]; JAP ¹⁸⁶	RCT	Characterise creatinine excretion in a population of developmentally "normal" children who were followed annually for a 7-year period, from ages 9–12 until ages 15–19	Amalgam [Resin composite] restorations	Renal	No evidence amalgam fillings on posterior teeth influenced level of antibiotic- or mercury-resistant oral or urinary bacteria as detected by culture.
Roberts 2008, [Portugal]; JAP ¹⁹¹	Prospective cohort (using RCT data - amalgam arm only)	Verify whether dental amalgam increases levels of mercury- and antibiotic-resistant bacteria from baseline levels vs composite fillings and examine link between acquisition of antibiotic and Hg resistance in bacteria	Amalgam [composite resin] restorations	Exposure, general physical health, oral health	

Study [Country]: Publication status	Study design	Aim	Dental material [Intervention/ control]	Health or environmental impact evaluated	Summary of Findings
Woods 2008, [Portugal]; JAP ¹⁹³	RCT	Assess potential kidney injury associated with prolonged HgO exposure	Amalgam [composite resin] restorations	Renal	GST-a concentrations similar between treatment groups in each sex and race group in each follow-up year. GST-p levels tended upward over follow-up by four- to six-fold in all groups irrespective of the treatment, race, or gender. Female GST-p levels approx. 2xmales at all ages. Albumin concentrations constant throughout follow-up period and did not differ by treatment, although females had 39% higher albumin levels than males. No significant effects amalgam treatment on proportion of children with microalbuminuria (430 mg/g creatinine). Unadjusted urinary concentrations (µg/l) of all 5 porphyrins remained relatively constant throughout ages 8–18 y for both genders. Creatinine-adjusted urinary porphyrin concentrations declined significantly throughout age range (both genders). Boys had significantly higher pentacarboxyl- and copro- porphyrin levels vs girls both before and after creatinine adjustment.
Woods 2009, [Portugal]; JAP ²⁶²	RCT	To determine urinary porphyrins in relation to Hg exposure in children and adolescents, 8–18 yr of age, over the 7-yr course of a clinical trial designed to evaluate the neurobehavioral and renal effects of dental amalgam in children.	composite resin restorations	Urinary	
Halperin-Sternfeld 2016, [Israel]; JAP ¹⁸³	Retrospective cohort (records review)	Evaluate the long-term association between proximal restorations and the incidence and progression of periodontal disease in well-maintained patients	Amalgam and/or composite restorations	Dental treatment, oral health	1,301 teeth were examined. Mean Probing pocket depths (PPD) in unrestored surfaces was 3.7 ± 1.7 mm, 3.1 ± 1.3 mm, and 2.8 ± 1 mm at T0, T1, and T2, respectively. Deeper pockets were found in restored surfaces at those time points with PPD values of 4.4 ± 1.8 mm, 3.6 ± 1.4 mm, and 3.2 ± 1.1 mm, respectively (P < .001). Higher PPD values were found in restored surfaces exhibiting inadequate restorations when compared to restored surfaces with adequate restorations at all time points. These values were 4.9 ± 1.9 mm, 4.1 ± 1.5 mm, and 4 ± 1.7 mm vs 4.3 ± 1.8 mm, 3.6 ± 1.4 mm, and 3.1 ± 1.1 mm, respectively (P < .001). Amalgam restorations were associated with higher prevalence of PPD ≥ 5 mm, a higher extraction rate, and more frequent restorative procedures when compared with composite restorations.

Study [Country]: Publication status	Study design	Aim	Dental material [Intervention/ control]	Health or environmental impact evaluated	Summary of Findings
Hsu 2016, [Taiwan]; JAP ²²¹	Retrospective cohort – nested case control	Evaluate whether patients aged 55 years who have dental amalgam filling(s) have an increased risk of acquiring Parkinson's Disease (PD) afterwards	Amalgam [no amalgam] restorations	Neurological	The individuals who received amalgam fillings had a significantly higher risk of PD afterward (adjusted hazard ratio [HR]=1.583, 95% confidence interval [CI]=1.122–2.234, p=0.0089) than those who did not. In the individuals who received amalgam fillings, being diagnosed with diabetes or hyperlipidaemia demonstrated a significantly lower HR of PD occurrence than in the patients without diabetes or hyperlipidaemia (HR=0.449, 95% CI=0.254–0.794, p=0.0059; HR=0.445, 95% CI=0.260–0.763, p=0.0032) after adjusting for comorbidities and Charlson-Deyo Comorbidity Index (CCI) scores. Meanwhile, hypertension increased the hazard risk of PD(HR=1.645, 95% CI=1.098–2.464, p=0.0159). The patients exposed to dental amalgam fillings were 1.583 times more likely to have PD afterward compared to their non-exposed counterparts after adjusting for comorbidities and CCI scores.
Hu 2021, [Taiwan]; JAP ²⁵⁶	Cross-sectional with control	Investigate the relationship between ADHD and composite resin restorations among children from the Taiwan's National Health Insurance Research Database	Composite resin [no composite resin] restorations	ADHD	The patients who received composite resin restorations had higher risk of ADHD than those who had never received them (aOR (adjusted odds ratio) = 1.25; 95% CI (confidence interval) = 1.13–1.38). Males had a higher risk of ADHD (aOR = 1.29; 95% CI = 1.14–1.43). Taken together, this nested case–control study demonstrated a positive association between ADHD and dental care via composite resin restoration in Taiwanese children.
Lartitegui-Sebastian 2012, [Spain], JAP ²²³	Prospective Clinical Observational Study with a Pre-post design	Analyse prevalence of mucosal lesions associated with silver amalgam restorations (SARs) in a group of SAR carrying patients in the Basque Country	Amalgam restorations removal [Individuals without oral lichenoid lesions with min.1 silver amalgam]	Allergy and oral health	Oral lichenoid lesions (OLs) were found in 7 patients whose predominant lesion was bilateral, asymmetrical and asymptomatic white papule-macule. Lesions were related to old and corroded SARs. Patch testing was positive in two cases. SAR substitution produced an improvement in 5 cases.

Study [Country]: Publication status	Study design	Aim	Dental material [Intervention/ control]	Health or environmental impact evaluated	Summary of Findings
Leybovich 2014, [USA]; JAP ²⁵⁷	RCT (1-arm relevant)	Compare two treatments for mild noncariou cervical lesions (NCCL): a subepithelial connective tissue graft (CTG) vs Class V composite resin restoration	Composite resin restorations [not relevant to review]	Oral health	Significant improvement all periodontal health parameters in CTG treatment. The CTG treatment attained a mean 82% defect coverage with 75% of sites achieving complete coverage. Patients rated the CTG treatment to be significantly more aesthetic (P = .03), while a clinician panel did not see an aesthetic difference (P = .86). There was no difference in DH reduction between the two treatments (P = .81). Overall, CTG treatment is superior to CRR treatment for NCCLs based on periodontal health parameters. From a patient point of view, CTG is more aesthetic treatment.
Lin 2017, [Taiwan]; JAP ¹⁸⁵	Retrospective cohort	Investigate association of dental amalgam restoration with risk of attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder	Amalgam [other types including resin composite, glass ionomer] restorations	ADHD	2073 people (2.4%) received an ADHD diagnosis=incidence rate of 32.4 per 100 000 person-years. Those with 6 or more amalgam restorations had higher risk of future ADHD in the unadjusted Cox proportional hazard regression model (hazard ratio=1.20, 95% confidence interval [CI]=1.04-1.38, p=.015) than those who received composite resin or glass ionomer restorations. However, after adjustment for potential confounding factors, the result was found to be confounded by age
Louopou 2020, [Canada]; JAP ²²⁵	Prospective cohort	Assess association between presence or replacement of dental amalgams and risk of gestational hypertension (GH)	Mercury-silver restorations	Exposure, maternal health	Dental amalgam status was weakly statistically correlated with mercury concentrations but there was no evidence of an association with GH in women having 1–4 (aOR = 1.31 (0.92, 1.85)) or ≥ 5 dental amalgams (aOR = 1.32 (0.86, 2.04)), compared to women without amalgam reported at first trimester. Dental amalgam replacement reported in the first or third trimester was similarly not associated with GH (aOR = 0.75 (0.40, 1.42) and 0.73 (0.39, 1.34), respectively) but with SBP (beta = -1.58 (-2.95, -0.02)).

Study [Country]: Publication status	Study design	Aim	Dental material [Intervention/ control]	Health or environmental impact evaluated	Summary of Findings
Lygre 2013, [Norway]; JAP ²²⁸	Controlled before and after	Characterise the changes of different health complaints after replacement of amalgam fillings and compare with an external reference group from the general population	Amalgam restorations removal [external reference group - general population]	Cardiovascular, dermatological, ENT, gastrointestinal, general physical health, musculoskeletal, neuropsychological, orofacial, psychological, visual ocular	Before treatment mean intensity of complaints higher in treatment group vs reference group. Most frequently reported complaints treatment group: gastrointestinal symptoms, fatigue, muscle/joint pain, ENT symptoms, difficulty concentrating. From pre-treatment examination to 3-year follow-up, 20/23 health complaints decreased, statistically significant for taste disturbances, Muscle/joint pain, gastrointestinal complaints, complaints from ear/nose/throat and fatigue.
Lygre 2016, [Norway]; JAP ²²⁷	Prospective cohort	Assess associations between exposure to amalgam fillings in pregnant women and adverse pregnancy outcome	Amalgam restoration or removal	Pregnancy outcomes	Logistic regression models, including mothers age, education, BMI, parity, smoking during pregnancy, and alcohol consumption during pregnancy revealed no significant associations between the number of teeth with amalgam fillings and early preterm delivery, late preterm delivery, low birthweight, malformation or stillbirth.
Lygre 2018, [Norway]; JAP ²²⁶	Prospective cohort	Investigate associations ADHD symptoms in 3-5yr old children and prenatal exposure to amalgam	Amalgam restoration or removal	ADHD	No significant associations between no of teeth, amalgam filling, amalgam fillings placed or removed during pregnancy, and symptoms related to ADHD in children of three and five years of age.
Lynch 2015, [Ireland]; JAP ²²⁹	Retrospective cohort with before and after component	Assess results of patch testing in patients with multiple amalgams and multiple OLL, where aetiology of oral mucosal disease unclear	Amalgam restorations, partial or complete replacement [no amalgams removed/replaced]	Allergy, oral health	Thirty-one patients with OLL referred for patch testing. Ten (32%) patients tested positively to mercury. Eight patients with positive reactions to mercury had amalgam removal, with complete/partial resolution of the OLL in all cases (100%).
Ma 2021, [Taiwan]; JAP ²³⁰	Retrospective observational: nested case control	Identify whether patients who received restorative/endodontic treatments, or tooth extraction, have altered odds of developing oral lichen planus (OLP)	Amalgam and composite resin restorations with OLP [Amalgam and composite resin restorations without OLP]	Oral health	No significantly different odds of OLP for those who underwent amalgam (aOR = 0.948, 95% CI = 0.853– 1.053, p = 0.3170) or resin restorations (aOR = 1.007, 95% CI = 0.978–1.037, p = 0.6557) in both anterior and posterior teeth during 5yr observation period post restorations.
Marell 2014, [Sweden]; JAP ²³¹	Retrospective cohort with before and after component	Determine the prognosis and to evaluate the regression of lichenoid contact reactions (LCR) and oral lichen planus (OLP) after replacement of dental restorative materials suspected as causing the lesions	Dental restorations, partial or complete replacement (amalgam most frequently replaced) [no replacements]	Allergy, oral health	There were seven LCR patients with positive reactions to mercury: all lesions regressed after total replacement of amalgams. Most frequently allergens among OLP group with positive patch test reactions: mercury (5/6 = 83%), gold (1/6 = 17%), nickel (2/6 = 33%). No lesion remissions seen after dental

Study [Country]: Publication status	Study design	Aim	Dental material [Intervention/ control]	Health or environmental impact evaluated	Summary of Findings
					amalgam removal, although 5/6 patients= positive Hg reaction.
German Amalgam Trial					
Melchart 2008, [Germany]; JAP ²³²	RCT	Compare reduction of subjective complaints by 3 treatment strategies in 90 "amalgam patients" whose complaints could not be explained by a medical or psychological disorder	Amalgam restorations removal and replacement [1. Removal+ - high doses of vitamins and trace elements. 2. No removal of amalgam restorations]	Adverse events, exposure, general physical health, psychological, serious adverse events	Between baseline and month 12, the sum score of main complaints decreased by 3.5 (SD = 2.2) points on average in the removal group as well as in the removal-plus group, and by 2.5 (SD = 2.4) points in the no-removal group (p = 0.152). Both removal groups showed a significant decrease in steady-state levels of inorganic mercury compared with the no-removal group. Thus, all 3 interventions were associated with clinically relevant improvements. The samples differed in age, sex, and educational level. No statistically significant differences between either of the groups were found in overall psychological distress, intensity of the symptoms, or in numbers of self-reported symptoms in the Symptom Check List after controlling for age, sex, and education (Mean Global Severity Index 0.62 versus 0.63). Patients from the amalgam group showed mean values for private and public self-consciousness similar to the population norm, while patients from the comparison group had statistically significantly decreased mean values. While the amalgam group more frequently reported mental symptoms, patients from the comparison group had a higher prevalence of somatic symptoms.
Weidenhammer 2009, [Germany]; JAP ²⁵¹	Retrospective data analysis- (sample 1 retrospective data analysis of RCT and sample 2 historical records)	Investigate whether there was evidence for a specific syndrome of health problems attributed to dental amalgam	Amalgam restorations (symptoms attributed to) [symptoms attributed to environmental chemicals e.g. solvents, pesticides]	Dermatological, gastrointestinal, general physical health, musculoskeletal, oral health, neuropsychological, psychological	

Study [Country]: Publication status	Study design	Aim	Dental material [Intervention/ control]	Health or environmental impact evaluated	Summary of Findings
Weidenhammer 2010, [Germany]; JAP ²⁵⁰	RCT (retrospective analysis)	Study predictors of different treatment outcomes and associations between subjective symptoms, psychometric variables and mercury levels in patients who subjectively attributed their health problems to dental amalgam	Amalgam restorations removal [no removal of amalgam restorations]	Exposure, general physical health, psychological	The patients' personality profile at study onset was characterised by slightly reduced extraversion and slightly elevated emotional instability. Overall, subjective symptoms decreased slightly and there were no statistically significant differences in the decrease of symptoms after intervention between both groups. Decrease of mercury levels after intervention was closely associated with removal of amalgam fillings (rmult = 0.64 in regression analysis). Statistically significant correlations could be found between mercury levels and subjective symptoms with respect to baseline (r = 0.29–0.39) and to changes after intervention (r = 0.24–0.42), but not for psychological distress (r = 0.05–0.25) and health related quality of life (r =)0.03–0.18). Prediction of symptom improvement after intervention was poor (rmult = 0.44).
Mikhailichenko 2019, (Taiwan); JAP ²³³	Nested case-control	Determine risk factors for developing dementia when filling materials containing amalgam used	Exposure: Amalgam and composite resin restorations	Neuropsychological	No direct relationship between development of dementia and volume of filling material containing amalgam. Among people with dementia, some people experienced accelerated progression where a large volume of dental filling material containing amalgam present.
Montebugnoli 2012, [Trinidad and Tobago]; JAP ²³⁴	Before and after	Investigate if clinical healing after amalgam removal corresponds to histologic healing, i.e., a complete disappearance of any histologic sign of lichenoid lesion	Amalgam restorations replaced with composite resin restorations	Oral health	After amalgam removal, complete clinical healing in 14 patients (22%), significantly related to lesion topography (2 4.7; P < .05) and positive patch test (2 6.3; P < .01). Complete histologic healing occurred in 7 cases (50% of clinically healed patients), and was significantly related to the combination of positive patch test and strict contact with amalgams (Fisher's exact test P < .01).
Naimi-Akbar 2013, [Sweden]; JAP ²³⁷	Controlled before and after	Investigate symptoms, perceived health changes over time and health related quality of life (HRQoL) in subjects with subjective health impairment, allegedly because of dental materials and compare HRQoL with general population	Amalgam and composite restorations removed [and other dental materials] and replaced	General health, immune function, oral health, psychological, musculoskeletal, other	The response rate: 54.4% (n=280). 83.2% had undergone replacement of restorative materials because of impaired health, perceived to be related to dental restorative materials. Most common symptoms: musculoskeletal pain (67.5%), sleep disturbance (60.0%) and fatigue (58.6%). HRQoL of study subjects was significantly lower than that of Swedish population in general. Conclusions: Subjects

Study [Country]: Publication status	Study design	Aim	Dental material [Intervention/ control]	Health or environmental impact evaluated	Summary of Findings
Perng 2023, [Taiwan]; JAP ¹⁸⁹	Retrospective cohort with control	Investigate whether patients with history of dental caries were associated with an increased risk of newly-onset systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE)	Composite resin only restorations and amalgam + composite resin restorations [amalgam restorations]	Immune function	who had undergone subsidised dental restoration replacement reported persistent subjective symptoms and low HRQoL. Replacement of restorative materials alone insufficient to achieve improved health in patients with symptoms allegedly attributable to dental restorations SLE risk significantly higher in carious patients (HR ¼ 1.98, 95% confidence interval [CI] ¼ 1.65–2.38) vs controls. Dose-dependent relationship between caries and risk of SLE identified. SLE risk higher among those who had dental visits greater or equal to 11 (HR ¼ 2.53, 95% CI ¼ 1.86–3.43), followed by those with 3–10 dental visits (HR ¼ 1.86, 95% CI ¼ 1.36–2.54), vs those with 1–2 visits, and was higher among those who had carious teeth extractions greater than or equal to 5 (HR ¼ 1.88, 95% CI ¼ 1.19–2.97), followed by those with 1–4 carious teeth extractions (HR ¼ 1.36, 95% CI ¼ 1.17–1.59) vs those without extraction. SLE risk for dental caries management among different restorative materials, including amalgam, composite resins, or both, were not statistically different.
Pettini 2015, [Italy]; JAP ²⁶⁰	Cross-sectional with control group	Evaluate genotoxicity of dental composite Enamel Plus-HFO in subjects with average 13 filled teeth with same material vs control group with no amalgam or composite resin fillings	Composite resin (Enamel-Plus- HFO (Micerium S.p.A., Avegno, Italy, Microhybrid) [no amalgam, composite resin exposure]	Genotoxicity	Correlation/multiple regression analyses confirmed no relationship between SCE/cell, high frequency of SCE (HFC) or CA frequencies and exposure to dental composite materials. These results indicate that composite resins used for dental restorations differ extensively in vivo in their cytotoxic and genotoxic potential and in their ability to affect chromosomal integrity, cell-cycle progression, DNA replication and repair.
Pezelj-Ribaric 2008, [Croatia]; JAP ²³⁸	Controlled before and after	Perform a clinical assessment of association between oral lichenoid reactions and amalgam restorations and determine salivary concentrations of interleukin-6 (IL-6) and IL-8 before/after replacement of amalgam restorations	Amalgam restorations replacement with composite resin, gold, porcelain or combination of these [healthy control with no OLR]	Allergy, Immune function, oral health	16/20 patch-tested patients showed sensitisation to inorganic mercury or amalgam. Total replacement of all amalgam fillings conducted on 20 patients with fillings based on composite resin, gold, porcelain or combination of these. 16/ 20 patients showed complete healing of OLR: 3 patients had marked improvement; 1 patient showed no improvement. Levels of IL-6 detected before replacement significantly higher than IL-6 levels following

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					replacement (P = 0.003). IL-8 levels- measured before replacement procedure significantly higher than IL-8 levels after replacement of fillings (P < 0.001).
Ptak 2023, [USA]; JAP ¹⁹⁰	Retrospective cohort	Evaluate the risk factors and occurrence of pulpal disease in patients who received either full-coverage (crowns) or large non-crown restorations (fillings, inlays, or onlays involving 3 surfaces)	Exposure: amalgam and composite resin	Oral health	Over the course of the study, 8.77% (n = 5,191) of patients developed pulpal disease. Pulpal disease was slightly more common in the large non-crown group than the full-coverage group (9.05% vs 7.54%, respectively). For patients who received large fillings, there was not a statistically significant difference based on operative material (amalgam vs composite: odds ratio 5 1.32 [95% confidence interval, 0.94–1.85], p = .05) or the number of surfaces involved (3 vs 4: odds ratio 5 0.78 [95% confidence interval, 0.54–1.12], p = .05). The association between the restoration type and the pulpal disease treatment performed was statistically significant (p < .001).
Rojas-Alcayaga 2012, [Chile]; JAP ²³⁹	Cross-sectional study with control group	Determine influence of atopic condition on delayed sensitisation to dental materials	Exposure: dental materials - amalgam and methacrylates.	Allergy and oral health	61.25% patients positive for delayed-type sensitisation to one or more allergens; the most frequent were palladium chloride (21.25%), ammoniated mercury (20%), benzoyl peroxide (12.5%) and amalgam (10%). The frequency of sensitisation was 67.5% in the group of atopic patients, compared to 55% in the non-atopic group (p>0.05). The materials with the greatest difference of sensitisation in atopic compared to non-atopic patients were ammoniated mercury, benzoyl peroxide, amalgam and Bisphenol A Dimethacrylate (BIS-GMA).

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Sundstrom 2010, [Sweden]; JAP ²⁴¹	Longitudinal and cross-sectional with control group	Examine a symptom profile and whether participants with amalgam- related complaints have cognitive deficits in comparison with control individuals	Amalgam restorations (presence of health complaints [control with no health complaints attributed to amalgam restorations])	Cardiovascular, dermatological, ENT, gastrointestinal, general physical health, musculoskeletal, neuropsychological, psychological, respiratory, urinary, visual/ocular	The participants with amalgam-related complaints reported more symptoms, mainly musculoskeletal and neuropsychological, compared with control individuals ($p < 0.001$). The results revealed no significant difference between the amalgam and control group, either cross-sectionally or longitudinally, for any of the cognitive tests. These results suggest that cognitive decline is not associated with amalgam-related complaints.
Sundstrom 2011, [Sweden]; JAP ²⁴⁰	Longitudinal and cross-sectional with control group	Examine relationship between life events and amalgam-related complaints	Amalgam restorations (presence of health complaints, case group) [no complaints attributed to amalgam restorations, control group]	Cardiovascular, dermatological, ENT, gastrointestinal, general physical health, musculoskeletal, psychological, respiratory, urinary, visual/ocular	Many participants with amalgam related complaints experienced negative life events before and at onset of amalgam-related complaints. They reported more unexpected and uncontrollable events difficult to adjust to vs controls. Groups did not differ on positive or neutral life events. Somatic illness or surgical operation most common life event. Death of a very close family member and major change in financial situation commonly reported.
Suter 2016, [UK]; JAP ²⁴²	Case control	Ascertain utility of patch testing to confirm association of oral lichenoid reactions with dental restorations and identify benefits of replacement of restorations, primarily made of amalgam	Amalgam restorations replaced [amalgam not replaced]	Allergy, oral health	Among 115 patients, 67.8% patients reacted positive to a dental material and nearly 25% to mercury or amalgam. No correlation found between pathology and skin patch testing results ($P = 0.44$). 87 patients were followed up in clinic, and among 26 patch-test- positive patients who had their amalgam fillings replaced, moderate to complete resolution noted in 81%.
Tadin 2014, [Croatia]; JAP ²⁶¹	RCT	Evaluate DNA damage to gingival cells exposed to resin composite dental materials	Kalore (nano-hybrid resin composite) restorations [Vertise flow (self-adhering flowable composite) restorations]	Genotoxicity	Significantly higher comet assay parameters (tail length and % DNA in tail) within periods of 30 and 180 days. Micronucleus test for same exposure time: higher number of cells with micronuclei, karyolysis, and nuclear buds. No significant difference between two composite materials for same exposure time.

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Tseng 2020a [MS], [Taiwan]; JAP ²⁴⁵	Case control	Investigate this putative association using the Taiwan National Health Insurance Research database (NHIRD)	Exposure: amalgam restorations [no amalgam restorations]	Neurological	Case (n = 612) and control (n = 612) groups were matched by sex, age, urbanisation level, monthly income, and Charlson comorbidity index by propensity score matched with a 1:1 ratio from 2000 to 2013. Differences between cases and controls were not statistically significant (OR: 0.82, 95% CI = 0.65–1.05). In subjects stratified by gender, MS was also not associated with AMF for women (OR: 0.743, 95% CI = 0.552–1.000) and men (OR: 1.006, 95% CI = 0.670–1.509), respectively. This Taiwanese nationwide population-based case–control study did not find an association between MS and AMF. The results from this nationwide population-based case-control study did not indicate any association between ET and AMF in Taiwan. Although the results were not significantly statistical, the findings may be worthy to be valued.
Tseng 2020b [ET], [Taiwan]; JAP ²⁴⁴	Case control	Evaluate the relationship between amalgam restorations and ET in Taiwan	Exposure: amalgam restorations [no amalgam restorations]	Neurological	Mean maternal amalgams present during gestation were 5.1 surfaces (range 1-22) in the 42% of mothers with amalgams. No significant adverse associations were found between the number of prenatal amalgam surfaces and any of the 6 outcomes, with or without adjustment for prenatal and postnatal methylmercury exposure. Analyses using the secondary metric, prenatal amalgam occlusal point scores, showed an adverse association in males only on the Letter Word Recognition subtest of the Woodcock-Johnson Tests of Achievement, and several apparently beneficial associations for females only. The number of amalgam surfaces was not significantly ($p>0.05$) associated with either PDI or MDI scores. Similarly, secondary analysis with occlusal points showed no effect on the PDI or MDI scores for boys and girls combined. However, secondary analysis of the 9-month MDI was suggestive of an adverse association present only in girls.
Watson 2011, [Republic of Seychelles]; JAP ²⁴⁷	Prospective longitudinal cohort study	Examine the association between children's prenatal Hg0 exposure (using maternal amalgam status as a biological marker) and test results from their 66-month test battery. Examine the association with adjustment for prenatal and recent postnatal MeHg exposures to determine whether co-exposure to the inorganic (Hg0) and organic (MeHg) forms of mercury influenced the analyses	Exposure: amalgam restorations	Exposure, neuropsychological	
Watson 2012, [Republic of Seychelles]; JAP ²⁴⁶	Prospective longitudinal cohort study	Determine if prenatal mercury vapour exposure from maternal dental amalgam is associated with adverse effects to cognition and development in children	Exposure: amalgam restorations	Exposure, neuropsychological	

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Watson 2013, [Republic of Seychelles]; JAP ²⁴⁸	Prospective longitudinal cohort study	Investigate whether prenatal exposure to Hg0 from maternal dental amalgam was associated with adverse neurodevelopmental outcomes in a cohort of children participating in the Seychelles Child Development Nutrition Study (SCDNS)	Exposure: amalgam restorations	Exposure, neuropsychological	Maternal amalgam status evaluation yielded an average of 7.0 surfaces (range 0–28) and 11.0 occlusal points (range 0–40) during pregnancy. Neither the number of maternal amalgam surfaces nor occlusal points were associated with any outcome. The findings do not provide evidence to support a relationship between prenatal exposure to Hg0 from maternal dental amalgam and neurodevelopmental outcomes in children at 5 years of age.
Weber 2012, [USA]; JAP ²⁴⁹	Prospective longitudinal with control	Investigate the relationship of intraoral metal contact allergy to epithelial carcinogenesis	Amalgam/mercury restorations (patch testing for allergens in participants diagnosed/history of oral squamous cell carcinoma [patch testing in control patients with no history oral disease])	Allergy/Cancer (oral)	Of the 65 patients with oral SCC, 34% were allergic to at least 1 adjacent metal. They were 1.57 times as likely as control patients to have metal contact allergy (odds ratio, 1.57; 95% confidence interval, 0.65 to 3.80) and more than 3 times as likely to react to mercury (odds ratio, 3.20; 95% confidence interval, 0.42 to 33.20). Of the patients with a history of oral SCC, 12% (8 of 65) were allergic to mercury and amalgam compounds (“mercury or amalgam”).
Wright 2012, [UK]; JAP ²⁵²	Case control	Test whether mercury concentrations in the urine of children with autism were significantly increased or decreased compared to controls or siblings	Exposure: amalgam restorations/mercury in urine and autism [amalgam restorations/mercury in urine and no autism]	Autism	There were no statistically significant differences in creatinine levels, in uncorrected urinary mercury levels or in levels of mercury corrected for creatinine, whether or not the analysis was controlled for age, gender and amalgam fillings. This study lends no support for the hypothesis of differences in urinary mercury excretion in children with autism compared to other groups. Some of the results, however, do suggest further research in the area may be warranted to replicate this in a larger group and with clear measurement of potential confounding factors.

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Zwicker 2014, [Canada]; JAP ²⁵³	Retrospective cohort study	Determine if mercury exposure from amalgam fillings is associated with risk of adverse health effects	Amalgam restorations [no amalgam restorations]	ENT, Exposure, GI, general physical health, musculoskeletal, neurological, neuropsychological, psychological	At baseline, individuals with dental amalgam fillings doubled the measured urine mercury compared to a control group of persons who never had amalgam fillings. Removal of amalgam fillings decreased measured urine mercury to levels in persons without amalgam fillings. Although urine mercury levels in the sample were considered by Health Canada to be too low to pose health risks, removal of amalgam fillings reduced the likelihood of self-reported symptom deterioration and increased the likelihood of symptom improvement in comparison to people who retained their amalgam fillings.
Environmental impact: All studies (n=21)					
Al-Kawas 2008, [United Arab Emirates]; JAP ²⁶⁴	Cross-sectional with comparator	Assess mercury burden in wastewater of dental clinics	Amalgam, comparator groups include amalgam, composite and GIC, and composite/GIC (other not relevant treatments) [Restorations, removals]	Mercury levels in wastewater	Total Hg concentration in clinic wastewater ranged from 25 to 146 µg d-1. Hg concentration in wastewater samples varies depending on type of dental treatment: average Hg concentration in samples of only amalgam restoration: 39 µg per sample (std. dev. 37, range 4-142); amalgam restoration plus other types of dental treatment: 24 µg per sample (std. dev. 24, range <MDL-77); sample with no amalgam restoration: 18 µg per sample (std. dev. 16, range <MDL-33).
Binner 2022, [Ireland]; JAP ²⁶⁵	Cross-sectional	Analyse dental wastewater streams from three dental facilities in Ireland with differing amalgam separators. The potential overall toxicity, particulate load and physicochemical properties were analysed. The overall risk posed by these new materials was discussed.	Mercury-free dental filling materials: resin composite, glass ionomer, resin-modified glass ionomer cements [NR]	Animal toxicity of restorative materials	Analysis of the physicochemical aspects of DWW from different dental facilities indicated that DP2 (n = 6) had a wide range of pH values and DP1 (n = 19) had the highest specific electrical conductivity range. DP2 had the highest mean specific conductivity and the highest mean TSS and TDS results. TSS and TDS results were restricted by the analytical balance to 4 significant figures. Particulates in DWW: the two main observations were: (1) most particles were small in size (1.2 to 5 µm ²) and few large particles (50 to 500 µm ²) remained in the DWW, and (2) particle angularity overall was low during LM observation, but showed higher angularity under the SEM.

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Duane 2017, [UK]; JAP ²⁶⁶	Secondary analysis of dataset	Analyse carbon footprint of key dental procedures	Amalgam, composite, glass ionomer [Restorations]	Carbon footprint of restorative materials	The carbon footprint of the NHS dental service is 675 kilotonnes carbon dioxide equivalents (CO ₂ e). Examinations contributed the highest proportion to this footprint (27.1%) followed by scale and polish (13.4%) and amalgam/composite restorations (19.3%). From an emissions perspective, nearly 2/3 (64.5%) of emissions related to travel (staff and patient travel), 19% procurement (the products and services dental clinics buy) and 15.3% related to energy use.
Gioda 2007, [USA]; JAP ²⁶⁷	Before and after study	Evaluate the amount of Hg in PM10 in two dentistry working environments	Amalgam [Restorations, extractions]	Mercury levels in vapour	Indoor levels of PM10 in the DSL ranged from 9.2 to 41.6g/m ³ and 35.0 to 68.2g/m ³ in the DC. Levels of particle-bound Hg ranged from 0.1 to 1.2g/m ³ and in vapor 1.1 to 3.3mg/m ³ at the DSL; the DC levels ranged from 0.01 to 0.2g/m ³ for particle bound Hg and 13.6 to 102.7g/m ³ in vapor. PM10 concentrations were below Indoor Air Quality suggested limits for total dust (100g/m ³). Levels of mercury bound to PM10 were low; however, mercury vapor was several times higher than the suggested OSHA (permissible exposure limit – 100g/m ³) in the DSL.
Kim 2018, [South Korea]; JAP ²⁶⁸	Cross-sectional	Estimate the levels of mercury emission related to amalgam fillings at dental institutions	Amalgam [Incineration]	Mercury levels in emissions	48.86 kg (95% confidence interval [CI] 41.53–58.63 kg) of mercury had been incinerated along with the extracted teeth. After applying dental institution weights, the estimated amount of mercury was 42.53 kg (95% CI 34.11–52.17 kg). The amount of mercury incinerated with extracted posterior teeth at Korean dental institutions is therefore about 42.53–48.86 kg/year.
Kontogianni 2008, [Greece]; JAP ²⁶⁹	Cross-sectional survey	Investigates the production and composition of solid waste generated within Private Dental Offices (PDOs) of Thessaloniki, Greece. Long-term goal of the research was the planning of an integrated DW management system that could be implemented within any dental unit regardless of its size (PDO, clinic, lab or school)	Amalgam [NR]	Mercury levels in solid waste	Infectious waste (contains materials contaminated with blood and other infectious fluids of the mouth which carry pathogens (bacteria, viruses, parasites, or fungi) in sufficient concentration or quantity to cause disease in susceptible hosts) constitutes approximately 3/4 of the total waste generation; an average of 158.12 kg/yr. Total infectious waste is constituted by 15.12%, 84.78% and 0.1% metal-bearing, non-metal-bearing and amalgam-bearing waste, respectively. Amalgam waste corresponds to

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Majstorovic 2024, [Croatia]; JAP ²⁷⁰	Cross-sectional (clinic setting) and controlled trial (lab-based)	Address existing knowledge gap regarding environmental exposure and impact of residual monomers and Hg released from dental practices. Objective: evaluate embryotoxic potential of basic filling materials+drain water samples collected from dental practices using zebrafish Danio rerio model organism. Specific focus on: (i) quantifying residual monomers leached from resin-based materials after 48h and 7 d incubation in aqueous solution, and (ii) residual monomers present in water samples collected from dental chair drainage system using high-performance liquid chromatography; (iii) measuring Hg concentration leached from dental amalgam in aqueous solution and present in collected samples using cold vapor atomic absorption spectrometry (CV-AAS); (iv) assessing lethal and sub-lethal effects of dental materials and drainage samples on	Commercial composite Tetric EvoCeram®, glass ionomer Equia Forte® HT Fil, laboratory- prepared composite, alkasite Cention® Forte, amalgam Amalcap® Plus, and samples [Leaching, NR]	Animal toxicity of restorative materials	the smallest infectious waste fraction in a PDO-Th (0.10%) reflecting relatively small quantity of amalgam used for the process of a tooth obstruction (about 1 g). In a typical PDO, 5 g of solid amalgam waste are disposed daily, while the rate of amalgam over resin-use in restorative procedures is one-third. None of the dental units used amalgam traps or separators installed in chairside washstands or wastewater pipes to properly avoid amalgam disposal to sewage. Some had the appropriate mechanical equipment but used the traps only to avoid clogging in the pipes, and the contents were washed out in the washstands of the dental units. Methacrylate monomers were detected in eluates of experimental and commercial composites, and alkasite. In DCDS samples solely mercury found at concentrations of 0.08–1.86 µg/L. Experimental composite (48 h incubation) exhibited highest toxicity on zebrafish Danio rerio (LC50=0.70 g/L), followed by amalgam (LC50=8.27 g/L) < Tetric EvoCeram® (LC50=10.94 g/L) < Equia Forte® HT Fil (LC50=24.84 g/L) < Cention® Forte (LC50=32.22 g/L). Exposure of zebrafish to DCDS samples caused decreased larval body length and increased occurrences of edema and blood accumulation.

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Mandalidis 2008, [Greece]; JAP ²⁷¹	Cross-sectional	zebrafish embryos and larvae, with emphasis on monitoring physiological/behavioural alterations Determine composition, characterisation and production rate of Greek dental solid waste	Amalgam [Restorations, removals] (In the private practices selected, all dental activities (tooth extractions, fillings, endodontic therapy, dentures, crowns and bridges) were performed. In the public dental clinic, only tooth extractions and removable appliance works were performed)	Mercury levels in solid waste	141kg DSW produced by 2542 patients in 20 dental practices from Xanthi, Greece, was collected, manually separated and weighed over four working weeks. Waste was separated in 19 sub fractions, classified in 2 categories, according to Greek regulations: Domestic type waste (8%) and hazardous waste (92%). HW: infectious waste, toxic waste and mixed type waste (infectious and toxic together), accounting for 88.5%, 3.5% and 0.03% of total DSW by weight, respectively. Overall unit production rates (mean \pm standard error of the mean) were 381 ± 15 g/practice/d and 53.3 ± 1.4 g/patient/d for total DSW, 337 ± 14 g/practice/d and 46.6 ± 1.2 g/patient/d for total infectious DSW, 13.4 ± 0.7 g/practice/d and 2.1 ± 0.1 g/patient/d for total toxic DSW and 30.4 ± 2.5 g/practice/d and 4.6 ± 0.4 g/patient/d for domestic-type waste.
Marquardt 2009, [Germany]; JAP ²⁷²	Cross-sectional	Investigate the exposure of dental personnel to volatile methacrylates in dental practices during dental filling treatments while bonding agents were used	Materials found in composite resin restorations: Methyl methacrylate (MMA), 2-hydroxyethyl methacrylate (HEMA), ethylene glycol dimethacrylate (EGDMA), and Tri ethylene glycol dimethacrylate (TEG-DMA)	Monomer levels in emissions	The methacrylates methyl methacrylate (MMA), 2-hydroxyethyl methacrylate (HEMA), ethylene glycol dimethacrylate (EGDMA), and Tri ethylene glycol dimethacrylate (TEG-DMA) were identified in the air of dental practices. The exposure levels of the four methacrylates varied during the filling treatments. The maximum concentrations found were 0.4 mg/m ³ for MMA, 45 μ g/m ³ for HEMA, 13 μ g/m ³ for EGDMA, and 45 μ g/m ³ for TEG-DMA. The detection of TEG-DMA correlated with the application of bonding agents during performance of dental fillings.
Mourouzis 2022, [Greece]; JAP ²⁷³	Controlled trial (clinic and lab settings)	Detect monomers released during dental restorative procedures related to oral cavity and discharged into environment through dental unit drainage	Resin composite materials (for direct restorations), core build-up material and polymer infiltrated ceramic CAD/CAM material composed of the same monomers as the two resin composites [Restorations]	Monomers levels in wastewater	Resin monomers that were released during the grinding and milling procedures of different dental restorative materials were detected in the wastewater of dental units. The H01 hypothesis was accepted because resin monomers were detected in the wastewater after the milling of dental materials; H02 hypothesis was rejected because the amount of monomers detected in the wastewater of a dental

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Olivera 2020, [USA]; JAP ²⁷⁴	Prospective longitudinal	Evaluate the performance of a commercially available chairside amalgam separator (CAS) in a clinical setting in which a relatively high number of amalgam restorations are placed	Amalgam restorations (Valiant Ph.D contains 40% to 45% Hg per capsule) [Restorations]	Mercury levels in wastewater and in solid waste	unit after the grinding procedure of dental materials in vivo exceeded the amount of monomers detected in vitro. In in vivo phase, core build-up material released an amount of BPA (0.42 ± 0.14 ng/ μ L) while after 7 days, the amount of BPA increased (0.97 ± 0.07 ng/ μ L). The resin composite indicated for direct restoration material released the highest amount of TEGDMA ($p < 0.001$). The CAS evaluated met minimum EPA compliance requirements when used in a military dental treatment facility. The solids removal efficiency at the end of service life was 99.82% \pm 0.14% (n=4). The mean service life (n=8) was 131.6 \pm 45.1 calendar days (67.1637.6 workdays). Effluent mercury concentrations ranged from 0.05 to 11.93 mg/L. Total solids accumulated in each CAS (n=6) at the end of service life was 195.4 \pm 63.4 g. The mean number of amalgam surfaces placed per workday during the service life span of each CAS was 8.4 \pm 1.4.
Paryag 2010 [Trinidad and Tobago]; JAP ²⁷⁵	Modelling study	Assess knowledge and attitudes of dental practitioners regarding disposal of amalgam waste from dental practices and assess level of mercury released via dental amalgam waste into environment in Trinidad and Tobago	Amalgam [Removals]	Mercury levels in wastewater	Mean concentration 0.0759 ppm (or mg/L) mercury found in filtrate from wastewater samples. Total concentration of 3.4 g mercury/dentist/day released into environment via dental amalgam waste in Trinidad and Tobago.
Piagno 2020 [Canada]; JAP ²⁵⁴	Modelling study	Estimate the quantity of mercury emitted to atmosphere from crematoriums in British Columbia (BC) and assess human health risk	Amalgam [Incineration]	Mercury levels in emissions	In BC, it is estimated approximately 1.20g of mercury is emitted to atmosphere/body cremated and about 30,000 cremations were conducted in the province in 2016. It is estimated almost 36kg of elemental mercury was released to atmosphere as a result. The max. estimated peak short-term and long-term average ground-level mercury vapour concentrations associated with crematorium emissions were 0.31 μ g/m ³ and 7.9×10^{-3} μ g/m ³ respectively, which are far lower than the reference concentration (hazard quotient of less than 1).

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Polydorou 2023 [Germany]; JAP ²⁷⁶	Controlled trial	Evaluate the release of bisphenol A (BPA) in wastewater after grinding of resin composites and tested three filtration materials	Resin composite materials [Dental grinding procedures]	Monomer levels in wastewater	BPA was detected in all composite solutions: Ceram X and Filtek Supreme XTE showed similar findings ($p > 0.05$) which were significantly higher than the control ($p < 0.001$) and Core-X flow ($p = 0.001$). The efficacy of the filtration materials was: Katalox Light (5.09%) < Zeosorb (7.91%) < Catalytic Carbon (99.38%). Only Catalytic Carbon caused a clinically significant reduction of BPA ($p < 0.05$).
Shraim 2011, [Saudi Arabia]; JAP ²⁷⁷	Prospective longitudinal with comparator	Quantify the amount of soluble mercury in the wastewater of some dental clinics in AlMadinah Al-Munawarah (KSA) and to examine if any of the other dental amalgam constituents is found in the clinics' wastewater	Location 1&2: Amalgam or composite [Restorations], glass ionomer [endodontic treatment], Location 3a+3b: Amalgam, composite or glass ionomer [Restorations], Location 3c: Composite [Restorations]	Mercury levels in wastewater	Mean concentrations of Hg, Ag, Sn, Cu, and Zn in samples 5.3 ± 11.1 , 0.49 ± 0.96 , 3.0 ± 10.7 , 10.0 ± 14.5 , and 76.7 ± 106 mg L ⁻¹ , respectively. High concentrations of other metals such as Mg (14.4 ± 15.2 mg L ⁻¹), Mn (3.0 ± 4.6 mg L ⁻¹), Fe (3.0 ± 4.5 mg L ⁻¹), Sr (1.6 ± 2.4 mg L ⁻¹), and Ba (6.9 ± 10.3 mg L ⁻¹) found. These values > local permissible limits. Most metals of interest also detected in influent of wastewater treatment plant.
Simu 2014, [Romania]; JAP ²⁷⁸	Cross-sectional	Determine to which extent powders released after removal of fillings, preparing dental tissue for prosthetic, endodontic or restorative treatment were close to airways and to which level of respiratory tree can reach depending on their dimension. Investigate the morphology and elemental composition of released particles during dental procedures	Amalgam/Composite/GIC/Others [ultrasound scaling, root canal preparation, cavity preparation and filling, removal of silver amalgam, composite, glass ionomer fillings, teeth preparation for prosthetic purpose, orthodontic controls, etc.]	Mercury levels in particulate matter	Results underline the potential of aerosols deeply penetrating into the respiratory system, even to the level of pulmonary alveoli, and thereby they represent serious health threats for the practitioners and patients...
Stone 2009, [USA]; JAP ²⁷⁹	Prospective longitudinal with control	Compare ability of chlorine (HOCl/OCl ⁻) and monochloramine (NH ₂ Cl) to mobilise mercury from dental amalgam	Dental amalgam [NR]	Mercury levels in wastewater	When the two sample types were combined, the mean mercury level in the 1 mg/L chlorine group was 0.020 mg/L (n= 25, SD = 0.008). The 10 mg/L chlorine group had a mean mercury concentration of 0.59 mg/L (n= 25, SD= 1.06). The 1 mg/L chloramine group had a mean mercury level of 0.023 mg/L (n= 25, SD = 0.010). The 10 mg/L chloramine group had a mean mercury level of 0.024 mg/L (n= 25, SD = 0.011). Independent samples t-tests showed that there was a significant difference between the natural log mercury measurements of 10 mg/L chlorine compared to those of 1 mg/L and 10 mg/L chloramine. Changing from chlorine to chloramine

Study [Country]: Publication status	Study design	Aim	Dental material [Intervention/ control]	Health or environmental impact evaluated	Summary of Findings
Takaoka 2010, [Japan]; JAP ²⁸⁰	Modelling study	Measure actual emission levels, estimate emissions from crematories in Japan using measurement data and clarify the behaviour of mercury in crematory flue gas with the goal of predicting the environmental fate of the mercury in the surrounding area. Estimate future trends in emissions	Amalgam [Incineration]	Mercury levels in emissions	disinfection at water treatment plants would not be expected to produce substantial increases in dissolved mercury levels in dental-unit wastewater. The total mercury concentrations in stack gases were a few µg/Nm ³ (normal cubic meters). Considering the time profile of mercury and its species in cremations, the findings confirmed that the mercury in stack gas originated from dental amalgam. The amount of mercury emissions was calculated using the total concentration and gas flow rate. Furthermore, the annual amount of mercury emission from crematoriums in Japan was estimated by using the total number of corpses. The emission amount was considerably lower than that estimated in the United Kingdom. From statistical analyses on population demographics and measurements, future total emissions from crematoriums were also predicted. As a result, the amount of mercury emitted by crematories will likely increase by 2.6-fold from 2007 to 2037.
Van Landuyt 2014, [Belgium]; JAP ²⁸¹	Controlled trial	Investigate more thoroughly the release of airborne nanoparticles from composites with measuring devices suited to assessing airborne nanoparticles. This study involved both measurement of dentists' personal exposure as well as laboratory investigations to characterise the particles released from dental composites during grinding	Resin composite [grinding material to simulate abrasive procedures, including restorations]	Monomer levels in particulate matter	Exposure measurements of dust in a dental clinic revealed high peak concentrations of nanoparticles in the breathing zone of both dentist and patient, especially during aesthetic treatments or treatments of worn teeth with composite build-ups. Further laboratory assessment confirmed that all-tested composites released very high concentrations of airborne particles in the nanorange (>10 ⁶ cm ³). The median diameter of airborne composite dust varied between 38 and 70 nm. Electron microscopic and energy dispersive X-ray analysis confirmed that the airborne particles originated from the composite and revealed that the dust particles consisted of filler particles or resin or both. Though composite dust exhibited no significant oxidative reactivity, more toxicological research is needed.
Warwick 2013, [Canada]; JAP ²⁸³	Controlled trial (lab based)	Duplicate the conditions of mercury exposure commonly experienced by dental students in Canada	Amalgam removal - Amalgam removals were performed from upper or lower posterior (molar)	Mercury levels in vapour	When water spray and suction were used, mercury vapor levels ranged from 4.0 to 19.0 µg/m ³ (arithmetic mean = 8.0 µg/m ³); when suction only

Study [Country]: Publication status	Study design	Aim	Dental material [Intervention/ control]	Health or environmental impact evaluated	Summary of Findings
Warwick 2019, [Canada]; JAP ²⁸²	Prospective longitudinal with control	Quantify mercury that may vaporise from surface of freshly ground dental amalgam particulate	Amalgam [removals]	Mercury levels in vapour	Drilling dental amalgam generates particulate that volatilizes significant amounts of mercury vapor generally for more than an hour after removal. Mercury vapor levels frequently exceeded safety thresholds of several jurisdictions and agencies.

Appendix E: Descriptive tables: Environmental studies

Table 19. Key characteristics: Environmental studies

Study, Country	Setting	Sampling strategy	Duration of study/follow-up	Restorative material: treatment/activity (n of treatment/activity)
<i>Clinical setting only (n=11)</i>				
Al-Kawas 2008; United Arab Emirates ²⁶⁴	Dental clinics (n=3)	<p>Wastewater samples collected from dental chair outlets at three dental clinics over 3-17 days.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Samples 1-19: waste collected after amalgam restoration treatment (1-10 collected from clinic 1, 11-18 from clinic 3, and 19 from clinic 2). • Samples 20-31: waste from amalgam restoration + other types of treatment (collected from clinic 2); • Samples 32-36: waste from treatments other than restorations (collected from clinic 2). <p>Clinic 1 samples all collected directly from dental chair outlets onto collection containers at end of each treatment. Clinics 2 & 3 samples all collected from single chair, each belonging to one patient</p>	Collection over 3-17 days.	Amalgam vs comparator groups including amalgam, composite, and glass ionomer cement + other: restorations, removals+ other (root canal treatment, cavity preparation, pulpotomy, scaling plus polishing, fissure sealant, bridge cementation) (NR)
Binner 2022, Ireland ²⁶⁵	Dental practices (DP) in Ireland (n=3): 1 private, 1 public, 1 public dental school	<p>DPs: chosen based on ease of access and permissions granted for sampling and type of installed amalgam separators. Largely deemed typical of local dental facilities in terms of volumes of patients treated, procedures undertaken and awareness and compliance with good dental practices and waste disposal.</p> <p>Dental wastewater (DWW) samples: collected once the DWW had passed through the dental spittoon, dental chair tubing, amalgam separation unit, and before the wastewater entered the sewerage system.</p>	Samples were collected over a 24 h period in DP1, and over 36–48 h in DP2 and DP3.	Hg-free dental filling materials: Resin composite, glass ionomer, resin-modified glass ionomer cements: NR (NR; each DP had 1-2 clinical interventions on each of the sampling days)
Duane 2017, UK ²⁶⁶	Primary care dental clinics across NHS England	<p>Total greenhouse gas emissions (GHG) of NHS primary care dental services in England estimated using data from the NHS BSA, ISD Scotland, accounting data originating from NASDA and recent published Scottish papers.</p> <p>Data includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • carbon emissions from staff travel (both commuting and travel for work) 	GHG emissions for period April 2013 to March 2014	Amalgam, composite, glass ionomer cement: restorations: amalgam (n=4,443,000); composite (n=4,325,000) glass ionomer (n=1,170,000)

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • patient travel • energy • water • procurement (materials and services procured to run a dental practice) 			
Kim 2018, South Korea ²⁶⁸	Daegu: including dental clinic of general hospital + dental hospital + 5 private dental clinics (1 in South & 4 in the North Gyeongsang Province)	Dental settings selected using convenience sampling. Extracted posterior teeth claimed for insurance under code "extraction-posterior teeth (U4413)".	10 months		Amalgam: incinerations (NR)
Kontogianni 2008, Greece ²⁶⁹	Private dental offices (PDO) from the 1st municipal department of the Thessaloniki municipality PDO population (n=27)	Within Thessaaloniki Urban Area (TUA), 1300 PDOs were in operation. Research focused on 1st municipal department which is the actual town and centre and hosts 592 PDOs (i.e., 45.52% of TUA's overall PDO population). A PDO sample size of 27 was addressed within the research, chosen by statistical random analysis.	Waste generation assessed: 2005-2006		Amalgam: NR (NR)
Mandalidis 2018, Greece ²⁷¹	Dental practices (DPs) from the prefecture of Xanthi (n=20; 19 private and 1 public). All operated by a single dentist and daily number of patients <25.	Waste collection from DPs randomly selected from 101 private dental practices in the prefecture of Xanthi, Greece.	NR		Amalgam: removals + restorations [NR]
Marquardt 2009, Germany ²⁷²	Dental practices in Munich, Germany (n=4)	Practices in Munich, Germany, chosen randomly to ensure results as ranges of methacrylate concentrations, independent of the materials used, the work technique of the dentist, ventilation, or other factors	NR		Composite resin: restorations (5 different restoration treatments carried out in each of the four clinics)
Olivera 2020, USA ²⁷⁴	Dentistry providers within a large military dental group practice (n=4) (Budge Dental Clinic, Fort Sam Houston DENTAC, JBSA FortSam Houston, Texas)	Dentistry providers in a military dental group practice identified from a review (previous 6 months) with highest n. of amalgam restorations. 6 chairs selected/sampled from within these providers and CAS units attached to chairs. Effluent samples were collected from CAS units (n=9) every 2 weeks for up to a 12-month period. Providers 1 and 2, each performed the work on two dedicated chairs and Providers 3 and 4 each operated on a single chair.	Samples collected up to 1 year		Amalgam: restorations (mean n. of amalgam surfaces placed per workday during the service life of each CAS=8.46 (1.4 SD) (n=9); Mean n. of total amalgam surfaces placed: 539 (263 SD)

Shraim 2012, Saudi Arabia ²⁷⁷	<p>Location1: Al-Madinah Al-Munawarah: Al-Azhari Health Centre</p> <p>Location 2: Al-Harrah Al-Sharqiya Health Centre</p> <p>Location 3: King Fahd Hospital (location 3A and 3B from two dental nerve clinics and location 3C from a denture clinic)</p>	<p>Dental wastewater samples collected from 3 public dental clinics. Samples also collected from the water entering the dental chairs. The source of this water is onsite tanks fed by the mains water and is used as a mouth wash and a coolant during dental operations. This water is used without any treatment.</p> <p>Additionally, influent samples collected from the wastewater treatment plant in Al-Madinah Al-Munawarah. All wastewater discharged from the dental chairs was continuously collected in 5 L polyethylene plastic bottles, which were checked daily and replaced before being full.</p>	<p>60 days (May-June, 2009); influent samples wastewater treatment plant (March- June, 2010)]</p>	<p>Amalgam + composite resin + glass ionomer: extractions + restorations + others (endodontic treatment, periodontal treatment, pulpectomy/pulpotomy, cementation, oral examination, gingivectomy, crown, bridges)</p> <p>Restorations, n (%): Amalgam-Location 1: 79 (11), Location 2: 75 (5), Location 3a: 14(4), Location 3b: 40(18); Composite-: Location 1: 66(10), Location 2: 232(17), Location 3a: 16(5), Location 3b: 24(11), Location 3c: 29(9); Glass ionomer- Location 3a: 92(28), Location 3b: 36(16).</p> <p>Extractions, n (%): Location 1- 216 (31); Location 2- 192 (14); Location 3a- 66 (20); Location 3b- 29 (13)]</p>
Simu 2014, Romania ²⁷⁸	Dental offices	Double-sided adhesive carbon tape (5mm x2.5mm) and discs of 5mm diameter to accumulate particles for analysis attached to dentist's, gloves, mask, protection shield, glasses or rubber dam of patient during various treatments. 35 samples collected from 5 dentists with different specialties	NR	Amalgam + composite + glass ionomer: restorations + others (ultrasound scaling, root canal preparation, prosthetics, orthodontic controls) (NR)
Warwick 2019, Canada ²⁸²	Dental offices (n=2)	Particulate sampled from dental drill head with 5x5 cm cotton wipe during regularly scheduled clinical procedure following standard of care. Controls to minimize drilling, particulate formation, and Hg vapor generation: copious water, reduced drilling of amalgam by cross-hatching material+removing bulk pieces, high-volume suction with a custom isolation tip, secondary air evacuation (additional venting to the dental suction providing approximately 9–20 cubic meters/min laminar airflow evacuation through 8–12 cm hose from operative site exhausted to outside or through Hg-rated filters	Patients seen Oct 2016- April 18	Amalgam: removals (21)

Clinic and laboratory setting (n=5)

Gioda 2007, USA ²⁶⁷	University of Puerto Rico School of Dentistry, Dental Simulation Laboratory + Dental Clinic	<p>PM10 and Hg vapor samples.</p> <p>PM10: collected in Teflon filters for 36 hrs.</p> <p>Hg vapor: collected using passive samplers (SKC) over 8hrs. Passive sampler devices are a plastic and reusable holder containing an Hg vapor sorbent which has been approved by OSHA and is worn in the breathing zone of individuals for a recommended time period.</p>	<p>For lab and clinic, A five-day (7 h each) dental restoration class was monitored. For dental clinic, air monitoring was scheduled during two three-hour sections.</p>	<p>Amalgam: restorations + removals (lab=358 amalgam capsules; clinic=51 amalgam capsules)</p>
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Majstorovic 2024, Croatia ²⁷⁰	Dental practices + lab based; wastewater collected at Department of Endodontics and Restorative Dentistry at the School of Dental Medicine in Zagreb	Wastewater (500 mL) collected from waste containers of dental chairs (n=3) equipped with sedimentation-type amalgam separators. Effluents filtered (pore size 0.22 µm) and frozen until further analysis.	NR	Amalgam (Amalcap® Plus) + composite (commercial: Tetric EvoCeram®; lab-prepared) + glass ionomer (Equia Forte® HT Fil) + alkasite (Cention® Forte): NR (NR)
Mourouzis 2022, Greece ²⁷³	Phase 1: Laboratory simulation; Phase 2: Dental unit (Planmenca Compact a, Asentajankatu, Helsinki, Finland)	Phase 1: 30 specimens manufactured from 3 representative dental materials. (i) 2 resin composites for direct restorations (n = 10) (Clearfil Majesty Posterior PLT; (ii) a core-build up material (n = 10) (Clearfil Photo Core PLT); Wastewater collection from the spray-system of the handpiece during milling was collected. Phase 2: Water suction used to collect water intraorally, while rubber-dam isolation was removed. Two time periods for sample collection: (i) collection of wastewaters on the same day as that of the placement of the restorations. (ii) 1 week after bonding of specimens.	Phase 2 - Wastewater collection after placement of restorations and in 7 days	Resin composite + other (core-build up material and a polymer infiltrated ceramic CAD/CAM material): milling of restorations (30 specimens were milled, 10 of each material)
Stone 2008, USA ²⁷⁹	Clinic + laboratory simulation	Clinically obtained samples: over 24 h with sampling intervals of 0 h, 2 h, 4 h, 8 h, and 24 h from dental-unit wastewater (5-dental chairs) + Laboratory obtained amalgam samples were prepared.	Samples obtained over 24 hrs	Amalgam: NR (NR)
Van Landuyt 2014, Belgium ²⁸¹	University dental office (Restorative Dental Clinic) + lab	A miniDiSC used to analyse the release of nanoparticles in real time which measures the n. concentration, alveolar lung deposited surface area concentration and mean particle size in the size range 10–300 nm and for concentrations ranging from 103 to 106 cm ⁻³ . The miniDiSC sampled through an electrically conductive, flexible tube ~50 cm long. The tube inlet was attached to the collar of the dentist, while the instrument itself rested in the pocket of the dentist. The flexible tube attached to the miniDiSC prohibited the use of the impactor that is delivered with the instrument to remove larger particles. A second personal aerosol monitor device placed in the same dental cabinet on a bench ~5 m away from the patient recorded background concentrations, which served as the control.	NR	Resin composite: restorations (+ grinding of restorative material) + other (aesthetic treatments, veneering, crowns) (NR)
<i>Laboratory setting only (n=3)</i>				
Paryag 2010, Trinidad and Tobago ²⁷⁵	Lab-based simulation	Collection of wastewater samples from a typical dental chair unit with a CAS following clinical simulation of amalgam restoration in anatomical replica teeth.	NR	Amalgam: removal after restoration – anatomical replica teeth prepared for and restored with n=1, 2, 3 and 4 surface amalgam restorations (four groups each consisting of n=40)

Polydorou 2020, Germany ²⁷⁶	Laboratory setting	<p>Part 1. Wastewater samples with resin composite: A dental unit (disconnected from the waterflow) used to obtain the wastewater samples. Resin composite samples: prepared in a metal mold plate and polymerized by LED light-curing unit. Grinding of samples carried out under standardized conditions, ground for 90 s with diamond bur with a standard grit size of 106µm at 200,000 rpm with a red contra-angle handpiece. To avoid a possible contamination of the water samples with BPA-containing particles from previous experiments, a wash-out phase of the dental unit for 5min took place between each grinding procedure. The water flow was kept stable, so after grinding each sample 750mL of water were collected in a 1 L brown glass bottle.</p> <p>Control wastewater samples: 10 negative control samples prepared, by collecting water samples after performing the same procedure without grinding a composite sample. All parameters same as composite samples.</p> <p>For both sample groups: Bottles stored in darkness at 7 °C for 6 months, to simulate a long storage of composite dust in wastewater. After storage period, water bottles were dispersed at 23 °C room temp. in an ultrasonic bath for 20min.</p>	6 months after storage	Resin composites including Ormocer (Ceram X®; Dentsply Sirona, Bensheim, Germany), a nano filled resin composite (Filtek™ Supreme XTE; 3M ESPE, Seefeld, Germany) and a dual-cure core build-up material (Core-X® flow; Dentsply Sirona, Bensheim, Germany) + comparator was wastewater with no composite restorations: grinding of restorations + filtration efficacy of 3 materials (Zeosorb, Katalox Light and Catalytic Carbon) (for grinding of restorations: 10 resin composite samples + 10 control samples; for filtration materials: 6 samples analysed)
Warwick 2013, Canada ²⁸³	Laboratory setting (Dental school in University of Alberta, Canada)	<p>Part 2. Preparation of BPA-solution samples for filtration methods: 3 different materials were used for filtration of BPA-containing water samples: Zeosorb, Katalox Light and Catalytic Carbon. The materials differ in particle size, matrix, kind of reactive surface and separation process. All water samples for filtration tests prepared simultaneously in advance, to keep initial BPA concentration constant for all three filtration materials, so 50 L of ultrapure water used for BPA solution. BPA first dissolved in 1mL ethanol (≥99%) and then added to the ultrapure water. BPA load of the starting samples corresponded to the worst-case concentration from previous measurements (0.192mg/L). To prevent contamination, only instruments and vessels made of glass, metal or BPA-free plastic used during sample preparation and measurement. The experimental methodology was identical for all tests of the different filter materials. For each material three separate replicates with two extracted test samples were analysed (n = 6). 500 g of each filter granulate was used per run.</p>	NR	Amalgam: removal (NR)*

collect Hg vapor measurements in the ambient air surrounding the dental student performing the removals.

Crematorium setting (n=2)

Piagno 2020, Canada ²⁵⁴	Crematoriums in British Columbia in 2016 (sample size not specified)	<p>Total annual Hg emissions from crematoriums in BC, Canada: based on all cremations conducted in BC in 2016 (based on province's age-stratified population and mortality rates and cremation rate of 82%).</p> <p>Health risk assessment: analysis was conducted for generic facility with cremation gas properties and stack specifications typical of the industry, based on a cursory review of publicly available permits and approvals for facilities located outside BC.</p>	Emissions for 1 year period.	Amalgam: incinerations (estimated n cremations per year: 29,848)
Takaoka 2010, Japan ²⁸⁰	Crematories (n=7)	<p>1) Since there is a large difference in Hg emissions between a body with or without Hg amalgam, we conducted many measurements at two facilities (No. 6 and 7) to determine an accurate average Hg concentration. In other crematories, flue gas was sampled twice for each crematory. Since bodies are cremated individually, flue gas was sampled throughout a cremation, from ignition of the secondary burner to extinction of the main burner.</p> <p>2) Selected three crematories (No. 1, 2, and 3) constructed after 2000. In these facilities, bag filters used as dust collectors and advanced APCDs had been installed. Additionally, Facility No. 7 also has a bag filter system, although it was constructed in 1998. Conversely, Facilities No. 5 and 6 were not equipped with even a dust collector.</p>	NR	Amalgam: incinerations [87 bodies cremated: Facility 1-5; 2 each, Facility 6 - 44; Facility 7- 33]

Abbreviations: APCDs: air pollution control devices; BC: British Columbia; BPA: Bisphenol-A; BSA: Business Service Authority, CAD: computer aided design, CAM: computer-aided manufacturing, CAS: chairside amalgam separators, cm: centimetres, COT: courses of treatment, DP: dental practices, DSL: dental simulation laboratory, DWW: dental wastewater, GHG: greenhouse gas, GIC: glass ionomer cement, Hg: mercury, ISD: Information Services Division, L: litres, LED: Light Emitting Diode, mg: milligrams, miniDiSC: miniature diffusion size classifier, mL: millilitre, mm: millimetres, µm: micrometres, NASDA: National Association of Specialist Dental Accountants, NHS: National Health Service, nm: nanometres, NR: not reported; OSHA: occupational safety and health administration, PDO: private dental office, Pm: particulate matter, rpm: revolutions per minute, SD: standard deviation, SKC: passive samplers,

Footnotes: *Amalgam removals were conducted until a total of 75 Hg vapor readings were performed

Table 20. Methods: Environmental studies

Study	Data collection methods	Data analysis
<i>Clinic setting only (n=11)</i>		
Al-Kawas 2008 ²⁶⁴	Dental wastewater: Amount of Hg in wastewater from outlets of dental chairs from 3 x dental clinics collected over 3-17 days using CV-AAS. Samples 1-19 are the waste collected after amalgam restoration treatment. Samples 20-31, collected from clinic 2, amalgam restoration plus other types of treatment (e.g. composite filling, root canal treatment, cavity preparation plus temporary filling, glass ionomer filling, pulpotomy, scaling plus polishing, fissure sealant, and bridge cementation). Samples 32-36, collected from clinic 2: treatments other than amalgam restoration. Clinic 1: samples all collected directly from dental chair outlets onto collection containers at end of each treatment. Clinics 2 & 3: samples all collected from single chair, each belonging to one patient.	Samples digested according to modified USEPA Method 245.1. Samples' containers vigorously shaken before taking subsamples for analysis. 50.0 mL of filtered sample (gravity filtration) placed in 150 mL clean plastic bottle followed by 5.0 mL conc. H ₂ SO ₄ , 2.5 mL conc. HNO ₃ , 5.0 mL K ₂ S ₂ O ₈ (5 %), and 5.0 mL KMnO ₄ (5 %). Samples kept inside oven for 2.0 hours at 95 °C. After cooling to room temp., hydroxyl amine hydrochloride (12% in 12% NaCl) added drop wise to each bottle until colour of KMnO ₄ disappeared. More hydroxyl amine hydrochloride added if KMnO ₄ colour reappeared before elapse of 15 min after 1st addition. Approx. 1 mL of hydroxyl amine hydrochloride enough to completely reduce excess KMnO ₄ . Water added to each bottle to obtain volume of 100.0 mL. All calibration solutions, blanks, and CRM have been treated in the same way. Total Hg determined using CV-AAS (See Table 1 in paper for instrument parameters). Accuracy of the calibration curve was checked by CVC concept, where 20.0 and 50.0 µg/L Hg solutions prepared from stock standard solution but using different working solutions from those used to construct calibration curves. Method detection limit (calculated from "3 x SD" of 9 blank replicates) =0.2 µg/L. CRM was analysed after every 10 runs and accuracy was better than 96.4%. Method accuracy checked by spiking two wastewater samples each with 20.0 µg/L Hg and the spike recovery was between 106 and 112%.
Binner 2022 ²⁶⁵	Dental wastewater (DWW): Sample collection was carried out by one individual. Samples collected once the DWW had passed through the dental spittoon, dental chair tubing, amalgam separation unit, and before it entered the sewerage system. Dental practice 1: samples collected over 24-h; Dental practices 2 and 3: samples collected over 36-48h. Once collected, samples were transported to the lab and stored (4 °C) and analysed within 36 h.	<p>Physicochemical parameters - pH and specific conductivity: measurements obtained by submerging calibrated probes into 200 mL of the DWW samples (at ambient temp.) and by recording the values once stabilised. Regular blanks obtained by submerging the probes in lab. and dental tap water (pH 6 to 7) and by comparing the obtained measurements with reference values. TSS and TDS: measurements carried out in triplicate according to standardised procedures.</p> <p>Inorganic particulate analysis - Particle detection: samples obtained by a series of centrifugation processes. Microscope images from resulting sample. Particle size and shape: assessed by a) light microscopy for circularity, particle area and particle number using ImageJ/Fiji b) SEM using the bleached material from the light microscopy preparation and by re-suspending this material in EtOH at increasing concentrations and centrifuging. Sample material was mounted on 10 mm Al stubs with C tape and sputter coated with Au. SEM was used for analysis.</p> <p>Ecotoxicity testing of DWW - Only DWW samples containing Hg-free dental filling materials used for ecotoxicity testing. <i>Daphnia magna</i> immobilisation test was carried out. The growth medium used for <i>D. magna</i> culturing was the ADaM and batch cultures of the algae <i>Chlamydomonas reinhardtii</i> were grown in controlled lab conditions and fed to <i>D. magna</i> in line with their respective growth. The testing was carried out in 48 h darkness periods. Test concentrations were established using range-finding tests. Immobilisation recorded when neonates remained immobilised 15s after agitation had occurred. Tests were valid when immobilisation of the control groups was <10%. Data was normalised and nonlinear regression with curve fit was carried out using the dose-response data: EC50 was calculated, with 95% CI</p>

Duane 2017 ²⁶⁶	Carbon emissions: (staff travel (commuting and travel for work)), patient travel, energy, water, and procurement (materials and services procured to run a dental practice) aggregated from April 2013-March 2014. Process-based LCA used. No practice level information for representative sample of NHS dental practices in England available for travel, procurement, energy and water use, waste, nitrous oxide uses and volume of activity per dental procedure. Estimates using data from NHS BSA, ISD Scotland, accounting data from NASDA and recent Scottish papers. Data source for each aspect of carbon footprint provided.	Carbon emissions excluded from carbon embedded in capital items within a dental practice. Conversion factors originated from DEFRA, World Business Council on Sustainable Development and Small World Consulting Ltd's carbon calculator. Followed GGP developed by WRI and WBCSD.
Kim 2018 ²⁶⁸	A dental hygienist verified and classified the extracted teeth (N = 1208) as either anterior (incisors and canines) or posterior teeth. The amalgam filling rate of the posterior teeth was assessed. The amalgam-filled posterior teeth were cut out with a dental disk bur, and the amalgam was separated for weight measurement.	Emissions calculation: Data from the National Health Insurance (n of extracted posterior teeth per year and n of dental clinics in Korea), dental institution weights, and the results of the amalgam analyses (amalgam filling rate and mean amalgam weight) were used to calculate the estimated amount of Hg emitted from extracted teeth into the environment. According to data from the National Health Insurance, there were 265 general hospitals, 217 dental hospitals, and 16,575 dental clinics in Korea as of November 2015. As the study included a general hospital, a dental hospital, and five DCs, the dental institution weights were 265/1, 217/1, and 16,575/5 for the general hospital, dental hospital, and DCs, respectively. The amalgam filling rate at each dental institution is shown as the arithmetic mean, and the amalgam weight is presented as the geometric mean and 95% CI. The weight for each type of dental institution is calculated separately because the amalgam filling rate differs between them.
Kontogianni 2008 ²⁶⁹	Survey; structured questionnaire administered via face-to-face interviews with dentists, including detail on activity patterns (n of operation days and appointments) and dental waste quantity.	Solid waste analysis: The survey data, along with the Thessaaloniki Urban Area and PDO data were statistically analysed by: (i) average annual generation per PDO (kg/yr and PDO) (Eq: $Q_{\text{annual}} = qt/ai$); and (ii) average daily waste generation per PDO as a result of a patient's appointment (g per PDO daily appointment) (Eq: $Q_{\text{daily}} = qt/(ai \times ci)$). qt is the total quantity of DW generated by PDOs participating in the research (kg/yr), ai is the number of PDOs that participated in the research and ci is the average number of appointments of a PDO within a year.
Mandalidis 2018 ²⁷¹	Dental solid waste: Waste collection took place for 20 working days, from 22 April to 5 July 2013. Dentists instructed to collect total amount of waste they produced and separate into two fractions. Fraction 1: sharps, such as needles, syringes, broken glass, used cartridges, extracted teeth, dental tools, etc.. Fraction 2: plastic gloves, cotton, paper, paper towels, plastic glasses, gypsum, etc. All waste placed in plastic yellow bags. Total daily n. patients/ each practice recorded. Waste collected for 4 weeks, 5 working days a week and transferred to Laboratory for Solid and Hazardous Waste Management of Department of Environmental Engineering of Democritus University of Thrace.	The following were calculated: the daily production by each practice, the average total daily production by all practices, the average practice-based unit production rate, the average patient-based unit production rate. Determination of moisture, volatile solids and bulk density: the moisture content of the dental solid waste was determined by weighing the sample before and after drying at 70 ± 5 C until constant weight, and expressing the difference in % moisture, ww. The dried mass was, then, burnt in a muffle furnace (550 C) for 2 h and the VS content (% dw) was determined by weight difference. The bulk density in loose form was determined by filling without pressure a 39 L box with dental solid waste of each category and weighing. Then, bulk density in loose form was calculated by dividing the sample weight by its volume. Density values are necessary for volume-weight conversions.
	Waste separation, weighing and reporting: At lab, waste manually separated in 19 subfractions and each sub-fraction was weighed, using electronic balance of 1 g accuracy. Total 141 kg dental solid waste produced by 2542 patients. At end of collection period all amalgam capsules collected opened and amalgam content emptied/weighed +all extracted teeth with amalgam fillings collected and placed in sodium hypochlorite solution to be disinfected. Amalgam fillings then removed+ weighed. Lab. personnel involved in waste handling and separation took all necessary measures for their health and safety.	Determination of calorific value: The HHV on wet weight basis of dental solid waste was measured using a Parr model 1341 oxygen bomb calorimeter. The LHV was calculated.

Marquardt 2009 ²⁷²	Air sampling: samples taken directly in work range of dentist. 4 individual sampling fibers used during each treatment, one after another to investigate temporary changes in concentrations of methacrylates during treatment. Each fiber sampled 15 min (total 1 hour with 1st sample) before start of filling treatments. Sampling performed with SPME and using carbowax/divinyl benzene fibres. Temperature during indoor sampling was 22°C ± 2°C in all dental practices. Treatment rooms varied in size between 35 m3 and 50 m3. GC-MS Analysis: analytes desorbed from fiber surface for 5 minutes in the injector of gas chromatograph. Samples analyzed by GC-MS on a Finnigan Trace DSQ mass spectrometer and Finnigan Trace GC Ultra gas chromatograph. Calibration: GC-MS was calibrated to quantify the identified methacrylates MMA, HEMA, EGDMA, and TEG-DMA. Performed with headspace SPME analysis in 1.11-liter glass flasks sealed with a Teflon-coated septum and filled with different methacrylate concentrations. Performed in same manners as sampling in dental practices (carbowax/divinyl benzene fibers, 15 min, 22°C). Calibration ranges- HEMA: 5 to 54 µg/m3; EGDMA: 5 to 225 µg/m3; TEG-DMA: 9 to 45 µg/m3.	Descriptive statistics. All values were expressed in µg methacrylate/m3 air. Results in Figs 1 to 5 (In study) are represented with 95% CI.
Olivera 2020 ²⁷⁴	<p>Clinical Procedural Data: procedural data were collected from individual providers for one year at end of study. Procedures which used amalgam were tabulated to calculate the average n. of amalgam surfaces placed per workday per chair in the study, beginning with the date the CAS was installed and continuing through to the end of its service life. For providers 1 and 2, the rate was divided by two as they each performed the work on two dedicated chairs. Providers 3 and 4 each operated on a single chair; therefore, all procedures were attributable to their single respective chair.</p> <p>Effluent Sample Collection from HVE System/CASs: Effluent samples were collected from CAS units (n=9) every 2 weeks for up to a 12-month period to characterize Hg concentrations in the effluent. Prior to effluent sample collection, sample containers, tubing, and connection fittings were cleaned per EPA standard test method guidelines. Two sequential 1 L volumes of Ultrapure, Type 1 water were aspirated through the HVE system of each of the six dental chairs and collected from the outlet of each CAS unit into containers. From each 1 L flush, three 50-mL aliquots were prepared and preserved with Fisher Chemical Trace Metal grade HNO3 per the EPA standard test methods indicated for aqueous total Hg and aqueous total metals. To ensure compliance with UFC 4-510-01, vacuum levels through the HVE aspirator were measured with a Flowcheck vacuum meter immediately after each effluent sample collection.</p> <p>Mass of Total Solids Accumulated by CASs: The tare weight of each CAS unit was measured prior to installation in the DTF by drying at 103-1058C for 1 hour, cooling in a desiccator at 238C, and then weighing the CAS. This desiccation and weighing cycle was repeated until a consistent weight (<4% difference) was observed. After each separator reached the end of its service life, the desiccation and weighing process was performed again to determine the final weight of each CAS. Total solids accumulated for each CAS were calculated by subtracting the tare weight from the final weight.</p> <p>Composition of Solids Accumulated by CASs: Six CAS units collected from the DTF were randomly selected for solids composition analysis. CAS inlet and outlet ports were capped, transported to the Naval Medical Research Unit. The ISO Method 11143:2008 testing apparatus was assembled with the CAS installed in reverse orientation to generate backflush. Each CAS was flushed from outlet to inlet with 1 L deionized H2O and the effluent containing captured sediment was</p>	The Hg concentration means with SDs were calculated from the concentrations of the 3 aliquots collected from each HVE system effluent collection. Data distribution of the Hg concentration means was assessed for normality using the Shapiro-Wilk test. Statistical difference in the pooled mean Hg concentrations between the first and second HVE effluent samples was assessed using a Student t-test with the type I error rate, significance level at 0.05

collected and combined in a single 6-L container. Sediment and effluent were homogenized by orbital shaking, and then the solids were allowed to sediment at the bottom of the container. Sediment was dried overnight using a Thermo Scientific Heratherm laboratory benchtop incubator. Metals composition was determined by homogenising the sediment to a uniform mixture, then three 250-mg aliquots were taken and digested per EPA Method 3051A: microwave assisted acid digestion of sediments, sludges, soils, and oils. Digested samples were then diluted by serial dilution to concentrations of 1/100, 1/10,000, 1/100,000, and 1/1,000,000. ICP-MS was used as described previously to determine concentration of Hg, Ag, Cu, and Sn

Shraim
2012²⁷⁷

Dental wastewater: All wastewater discharged from dental chairs continuously collected in 5 L polyethylene plastic bottles. HNO₃ solution (50% v/v) added to samples to maintain pH<2. Samples refrigerated 4°C and analyzed within 28 days.

ICP-MS used for metal content in samples. Operational parameters: Table 1 in paper. H meter used after calibration. Samples analyzed twice; 1xHg & 1x for other metals using different experimental parameters (e.g. washing time and dilution factor). Known volume from supernatant solution measured and diluted (100 times) with L-cysteine (0.5% in 2% HNO₃). Each subsample introduced to the ICP-MS for 10 s and counts recorded. Washing solutions run between samples for sufficient time to reduce counts back to blank levels. Standard metals solution (10 µg L⁻¹) introduced/ processed in same way. Approximate metals concentration/sample calculated, and values used to calculate dilution factors needed for subsequent proper and accurate analysis. Fresh subsamples prepared with appropriate dilution factors. Hg memory effect: to reduce Hg memory effect: Diluted solutions of HNO₃, Triton X-100/EDTA/ammonia, and 2-mercaptoethanol were investigated in the analysis of Hg by FI-ICP-MS. Although EDTA, KBr, Na₂S, and Na₂S₂O₃ showed promising result, they were excluded because of their deposition on the ICPMS cones, whereas the use of 2-mercaptoethanol and L-cysteine was shown to be effective in washing out 50 µg Hg L⁻¹ to background levels in about 2 min when Hg solution was introduced for 3.8 min. However, due to its toxicity and bad odour, 2-mercaptoethanol was excluded. Quality control: CVC performed using 25.0 µg/L solution prepared from different stock standard than one used for calibration. LOD=3xSD of 5–8 reagent blank replicates analyzed at different time intervals between samples, while the LOQ was calculated as 3.3x the LOD. CRMs analyzed +replicate sample analyses. Calibration solutions for Hg included blank, 1, 5, 10, 25, and 50 µg/L. Other elements included blank, 1, 5, 10, 25, 50, and 100 µg/L. Calibration curves obtained all linear, with R²> 0.999. ICP-MS system analyzed each sample 3 times. RSD) values all results below 5%, except for samples with concentrations<1 µg/L, where RSD range 5% and 10%

Simu 2014²⁷⁸

The SEM and EDX: shape, surface morphology and size distribution of the particles collected on tape. SEM images recorded with Quanta 3D FEG SEM (FEI). Sample elemental composition: EDX carried out on few micrometres in depth of sample (2-5µm). Qualitative analysis carried out in 6 points/sample. Powders metallised with Pt-Pd thin layer of 5nm in a Q150R ES automatic Sputter Coater, in argon atmosphere. The XPS: analyse elemental composition at surface samples performed by SPECS XPS instrument with monochromatic Al Kα source, operated with 280W power. Samples mounted for spectroscopy directly on sample holder using double-sided adhesive carbon tape on which collected. Background pressure during measurements: 7x 10⁻¹⁰mbar. Low-energy charge neutralizer used to remove charge shifts during photoelectron emission. BE scale calibrated to C 1s photoelectron peak (284.6eV). Survey scans recorded at pass energy E_{pass} = 100eV, in steps of 1eV

Analysis of data carried out with Casa XPS software.

Warwick
2019²⁸²

2 × 2 gauze containing particulate placed 1cm from inlet hose of recently calibrated Mercury Instruments Mercury Vapor Monitor 3000 (Model VM 3000), and 1s increment readings of localized mercury vapor concentration recorded. Relative size of amalgams recorded (large, medium, small), and no. amalgams removed in session to generate "Total Filling Size Score." Mercury vapor measurements taken until localized level fell below 10 µg/m³. After vapor measurements, particulate wipe placed in container using new gloves and shipped to AGAT labs in Canada. Mass of Hg determined using ICP/MS analytical technique.

Data/patient sample: 1) approximate size/no. of fillings removed ("Total Filling Size Score"), 2) one-second incremental readings by VM 3000: localized Hg vapor levels in µg/m³ vaporizing from amalgam particulate, 3) peak Hg vapor, 4) mass of Hg contained per sample. One dentist provided measurements of Hg vapor that evaporated from 400 mg of room temperature (20 °C) elemental Hg (mass elemental Hg not measured but derived from manufacturer's data sheet on Dispersalloy product) with approximate surface area of 0.07 cm² from Dispersalloy single-spill dental amalgam capsule over 33-minutes to compare with readings from particulate. This size of elemental sample used as readily available from conventional unmixed amalgam capsule. One elemental Hg sample taken: average concentration for first 30min the vapor expressing from elemental Hg: 35 µg/m³. VM 3000 flow rate: approx. 80 l/hour or 0.08 m³/h. Hg evaporated from elemental Hg: 35 µg/m³ × ½ × 0.08 m³/h or 1.4 µg/h. Evaporation rate room temp. elemental Hg (20 °C): approx. 50 µg/cm²/h (range of 40–60 µg/cm²/h) [42]. Theoretical model: Elemental Hg (estimated surface area 0.07 cm² (radius of 0.15 cm), evaporate 0.07 cm² × ½ hour × 50 µg/cm²/h or 1.75 µg/h

Clinic and laboratory setting (n=5)

Gioda
2007²⁶⁷

1. Particulate matter. The sampling instrument was the Particulate Chemical Speciation Air Sampler. Air sampler was placed at the middle of the room or working area- PM10 samples collected over 36-h periods previous to the lab exercise on Teflon filters. Immediately filters were placed in a stainless-steel protective container, sealed, transported to the toxicology lab, weighed using a balance model M-220D, preconditioned in petri slides and kept in a dry keeper and analysed. Filters were weighed each day until three consecutive measurements yield a SD of 0.00002 g. PM10 mass was determined by gravimetry; the concentration was obtained by dividing the mass by air volume. Filters were extracted using concentrated HNO₃ (5 mL) and sulfuric acid 5 M (15 mL), a 5% potassium permanganate solution added to dissolve the sample matrix and a hydroxylamine hydrochloride solution (20%) to reduce excess potassium permanganate. Six filters and six field blanks were collected from the DSL, three filters and three field blanks from the DC. The acidified aqueous samples were then analysed by spectroscopy using atomic absorption-

The statistical software 'GraphPad Prism' version 4.0a was used for statistical analysis. Two-tail paired t-tests assessed differences between the means of PM10 and Hg concentrations (95% CI). Linear regressions analysed the relationship between Hg concentration and n. of amalgams used during the exercise.

2. Hg Vapour. Five students at the DSL were selected-(from each working bench) (SKC mobile # 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5) to wear a passive sampler (SKC), attached to the lab coat as close to the breathing zone as possible. Each student wore the passive sampler 2x four-hour occasions and used between 4-10 amalgam capsules. Total amalgam capsules used during this training ranged from 81-104. At DC, students occupy a numbered (40) dental chair. Eighteen students took the exam in the morning and 17 in the afternoon. Twelve passive samplers were worn by 23 students during the exam and five by the professors. Each sampler was worn by two students (i.e., one in the morning and another during the afternoon); one sampler was worn by only one student (mobile # 15).- An average of 1.5 amalgam capsules was used by each student during the exam period (a total of 51 amalgam capsules). To evaluate the Hg vapor dispersion and extent of distribution throughout the environment, five samplers were also placed throughout the general dental clinic environment (stationary samplers identified as numbers according to the nearest dental chair: 22, 25, 28, 67, 74). A sampler was also placed in an office (stationary sampler # 13) on the same floor (out of the immediate air space of the dental clinic in order to evaluate Hg

distribution throughout the floor). In addition, a reference station sampler was placed outside the building (stationary sampler # 5). The SKC cartridge sorbents were acidified for 40 mins. A total of six passive samplers (five samples plus a blank) were analysed from the DSL and 26 (12 mobile, 7 stationary and 2 blanks) from the DC. All samples were analysed by spectroscopy.

Majstorovic
2024²⁷⁰

The encapsulated materials: dental amalgam Amalcap[®] Plus, alkasite Cention[®] Forte and glass ionomer Equia Forte[®] HT Fil were mixed in a mixer for 10 s at 4500 rpm. The commercial composite Tetric EvoCeram[®], the experimental (lab-prepared) composite, and alkasite Cention[®] Forte were polymerized with the LED polymerization unit Bluephase G2 (Ivoclar Vivadent) at an intensity of 950 mW/cm² for 15 s. The light intensity of the polymerization unit was measured using a calibrated MARC spectrophotometer. Amalgam specimens were ground after a setting period of 24 h, glass ionomer specimens after a setting period of 2.5 min, as prescribed by the manufacturer, while the other materials were ground immediately after light polymerization using a dental drill on a micromotor at 10,000 rpm. The drill was cleaned between samples using manual washing, an ultrasonic cleaner and sterilization in autoclave. Powder samples were weighed and the size of the powder particles was determined by scanning electron microscopy. A portion of the collected powder samples was coated with a 5 nm thick Au/Pd layer (90 % Au/10 % Pd) by sputtering and was etched with argon plasma at 6 kV using the Precision Etching Coating System. FE-SEM images of the prepared samples were acquired using a JSM7000F scanning electron microscope. Particle sizes measured using ImageJ software. Given the irregular shape, ellipsoid shape of the particles was assumed, while equivalent minimal Ferret diameter as the most likely value of the particle size was used for further analysis. The PSD diagrams were constructed using particle size measurements of approximately 200 particles per sample across several SEM images. Depending on the material, a change in mean particle size is visible with different size distribution spread.

Mourouzis
2022²⁷³

Phase 1: Specimen prep - 30 specimens were manufactured using a Teflon[®] matrix from 3 different dental materials: 2 resin composites for direct restorations (n = 10) (Clearfil Majesty Posterior PLT; (ii) a core-build up material (n = 10) (Clearfil Photo Core PLT). The resin composite paste was inserted in a square Teflon mould with dimensions of 14.5 × 14.5 × 2 mm, covering 420 mm³ of volume for each specimen. The mould was positioned on a glass plate and

HPLC analysis - Stock solutions containing 0.1 and 5.0 mg/mL HEMA, TEGDMA, UDMA, BPA, and bis-GMA, respectively, were prepared by dissolving each residual monomer in methanol. Working solutions of standards were prepared by appropriate quantitative dilution of the stock solution (also in methanol). Stock solutions were stored at 4 °C. Intermediate solutions and methanol working standards for the preparation of calibration curves at different concentrations for all monomers were stored refrigerated for up to 1 month. Eluates of the specimens were analyzed by HPLC according to Samanidou et al. (2015) with slight modifications, using an Agilent 1260 Bioinert liquid chromatography system. Chromatographic separation was achieved isocratically in a Kromasil 100-C18 analytical column (250 mm×4.6. mm id, 5 µm) at room temperature, with methanol-acetonitrile-water (80:15:25 %, v/v) as mobile phase at a flow rate of 1.5 mL/min. The sample injection volume was 20 µL. Detection was achieved at a wavelength of 230 nm and a sensitivity setting of 0.002 AUFS.

Hg analysis by CV-AAS - Hg analysis was conducted on amalgam suspensions and three samples collected from the dental chair drainage systems. The determination of Hg was based on the US EPA Method 1631. In a clean glass vial, 5 mL of the sample was mixed with 50 µL HCl and 50 µL BrCl solution to completely oxidize organic and inorganic compounds. The vial was then capped and left overnight to allow oxidation to complete. The next day, the sample was pre-reduced with 20 µL of a 30 % solution (w/v) of NH₂OH×HCl to remove the excess reactive halogens. The Hg concentration in the sample was determined using a CV-AAS; Model Hg-201 Semi-automated Mercury Analyzer. An aliquot of the sample was added to the reduction vessel containing 1 mL of 10 % SnCl₂ solution (w/v) in 10 % HCl (v/v) to convert all oxidized Hg to elemental Hg. Elemental Hg was then removed from the reaction solution by aeration and detected by CV AAS detector. The instrument was calibrated using a working Hg standard solution, prepared by dilution of NIST SRM 3133. LOD of the overall procedure (5 ng/L) was calculated based on the three SDs of the reagent blank (including the pure amalgam leaching solution). The repeatability and reproducibility of the analytical method were up to 0.7 % and 2.2 %, respectively. Since no certified reference material was available for extremely elevated Hg concentrations in water, the effectiveness of Hg reduction from the amalgam leaching solution was tested by the determination of spike recovery. Since the average recovery of spiked Hg was 99.3 %, no recovery factors were applied to calculate the final Hg concentrations. Statistical analysis was performed. The results were expressed as means ± SD, and p ≤ 0.05 was used as for statistical significance for all data. Before determination of median lethal concentration, data were subjected to logarithmic transformation. One-way ANOVA and Tukey's post hoc test were performed to examine the significance of the difference between treatments. When the assumption for normality was violated, the Kruskal-Wallis One-way ANOVA on ranks was performed.

Normality data distribution: Kolmo-gorov-Smirnov test. Homogeneity of variances: Levene test. Comparison mean values of leaching monomers (ng/µL),(normally distributed): ANOVA and Tukeys' HSD post hoc-test or paired samples t-test. For the specimens that did not yield normal distribution, mean values analysed via non-parametric KruskalWallis test, one-way ANOVA with

filled with composite resin in one increment. The resin composite specimens were polymerized using an LED device of 1500 mW/mm² intensity for 40 s covering the whole surface of the specimen. After polymerization, the specimens were transferred to an incubator where they were stored at 37 °C for 24 h and in the dark with 0 % relative humidity to complete the polymerization process.

multiple comparisons using Dunn's test, or independent sample test.-Statistical significance: $p < 0.05$.

Phase 2: an in-vivo experiment. Wastewater produced by water-spray of handpiece used to grind restorations composed from same materials with those in preceding in vitro experiment, collected from dental unit (Planmeca Compact a, Asentajankatu, Helsinki, Finland) disconnected from central drainage. Specimen preparations and placement- The resin composites specimens covered a total surface area of 420 mm². A high-speed handpiece at a speed of 200,000 rpm, using a medium-sized diamond with a grit size of 100 µm, milled the whole samples intraorally. Whole samples milled intraorally, at continuous rate for 1min. Samples milled to simulate clinical operations of polishing resin composite restorations or grinding and removal of failed composite resin restorations. Throughout grinding procedure, water suction used to collect water intraorally, while rubberdam isolation removed. Handpiece water flow constant and volume of collected liquid represented each liquid sample that was approx. 150 mL. Samples manufactured CAD/CAM material in same dimensions as those of composite resin samples and bonded to dental surfaces of patients using single component universal dental adhesive, which does not contain monomers of the restorative materials under investigation. Experimental phase: 1) collection of wastewater on same day as restoration placement 2) performed 1wk later after bonding of specimens to patients' tooth palatal surfaces. After grinding of materials, wastewater collected. To prevent the contamination of samples: before and after each experiment and water specimen, water pipes of dental chair were rinsed through suction of dental unit.

Stone
2008²⁷⁹

Dental chair amalgam samples: samples chairside wastewater from 5 dental chairs fitted with air/water separator. In lab: samples filtered through 0.45-µm pore size mixed cellulose ester membrane filters with positive pressure (argon gas). Filters air dried in fume hood and amalgam containing debris removed from filters and stored in borosilicate glass beaker. Chlorine/chloramine solutions: made daily. Free residual chlorine: made from stock solution of 5% by volume of sodium hypochlorite. Chloramine: reacting sodium hypochlorite with fivefold molar excess aqueous ammonia. Both solutions concentrations of 1 mg/L and 10 mg/L at a pH of 8 at room temperature. Determinations of sample pH completed using a Beckman Φ32 pH meter. Disinfectant exposure simulations: 0.5 g of clinically generated amalgam added to amber-coloured 250 mL bottles. Amalgam samples agitated end-over-end rotation, 30 rpm with 1 mg/L chlorine, 10 mg/L chlorine, 1 mg/L monochloramine, 10mg/L monochloramine, or deionized water for intervals of 0h, 2h, 4h, 8h, and 24h. 16 samples total. Samples obtained at each time interval (in either three or six replicates) and values averaged. Lab. determinations: Immediately after collection of agitated samples, chlorine and monochloramine levels monitored by DPD colorimetric method utilizing Genesys 20 spectrophotometer at wavelength of 515 nm. Sample pH determinations completed with Beckman Φ32 pH meter. Mercury levels determined by USEPA standard method 245.7 (USEPA, 2005) utilizing Millennium Cold Vapor Atomic Fluorescence mercury analyzer. Immediately after collection, all samples filtered through 0.45 µm filter and digested by exposure to solution of KBrO₃/KBr. After oxidation by KBrO₃/KBr

Comparison between chloramine/chlorine levels: t-tests (i.e., 1 mg/L chloramine versus 1 mg/L chlorine; 1 mg/L chloramine versus 10 mg/L chlorine; 10mg/L chloramine versus 1mg/L chlorine; and 10mg/L chloramine versus 10 mg/L chlorine). ANCOVA: determine whether each one of the variables had significant impact on the Hg levels.

solution, sample sequentially pre-reduced with $\text{NH}_2\text{OH}\cdot\text{HCl}$ then ionic Hg reduced with SnCl_2 . Mercury (0) separated from solution by passing sample through gas/liquid separator and purged with high-purity argon gas into cell of PS Analytical CVAFS. Hg concentration determined by AFS at 253.7 nm. Quality assurance/quality control, with blanks, duplicates, and spiked samples, completed by method 245.7 (USEPA, 2005).

Van Landuyt 2014²⁸¹ Measurements were performed during extensive restorative/aesthetic treatments with the nanocomposite Filtek Supreme XTE (3M ESPE), such as veneering and total crown build-up of front teeth. Final contouring and finishing of the composite restorations was standardly performed with a diamond bur (roughness 46–107 μm). For each of the five composites, samples were taken, light cured; then lab. measurement of size and concentration of airborne nanoparticles released from grinding composites; then electron microscopic characterization; then Size measurement of suspended particles; then OH^- generation and non-specific surface activity index measured by electron paramagnetic resonance spectroscopy; then The EPR measurements were done with unfiltered samples ($n = 3$).

Laboratory setting only (n=3)

Paryag 2010²⁷⁵ Part 1- Questionnaire: discussing dental wastewater discharge, disposal of amalgam waste and use of filters and separators in dental chairs + questions on the n. of amalgam fillings (restorations) removed on a monthly basis and the sizes of the fillings.

Part 2- Experimental (waste/mercury concentration calculations): 1) Anatomical replica teeth prepared for and restored with amalgam. 2) Restorations removed after 48 h with a Tungsten Carbide High Speed, bur in a water-cooled Star 430K high-speed handpiece attached to a dental unit with conventional suction system which was interrupted an attached to a surgical particle collection unit. 3) All of the wastewater from each set was collected and trapped particles of amalgam collected from solid separator. Percentage amalgam entering sewer system from removal of dental amalgam from different sizes of fillings+ concentration of Hg in wastewater entering sewer system calculated and used to estimate quantity of dental amalgam/Hg released from dental practices into environment (via correlating experimental data from Part II with questionnaire data regarding amount of amalgam fillings removed over a monthly period by dentists).

Polydorou 2020²⁷⁶ Part 1. BPA concentration in wastewater. A dental unit (disconnected from the waterflow) used to obtain the wastewater samples. Resin composite samples: prepared in a metal mould plate and polymerized by LED light-curing unit. Grinding of samples carried out under standardized conditions, ground for 90 s with diamond bur with a standard grit size of 106 μm at 200,000 rpm with a red contra-angle handpiece. To avoid possible contamination of the water samples with BPA-containing particles from previous experiments, a wash-out phase of the dental unit for 5min took place between each grinding procedure. The water flow was kept stable, so after grinding each sample 750mL of water were collected in a 1 L brown glass bottle. All water samples were concentrated. A five-fold concentration of wastewater samples was necessary to measure BPA concentrations above the quantification limit. This concentration step was performed using SPE with cartridges. 5mL of the dispersed water samples were applied to the preconditioned SPE cartridges and later dried for 30min. At the end of the drying period, the adsorbed BPA was eluted from the SPE

Data are represented as means \pm SD. For the median particle diameter determined by SMPS and nanoparticle tracking analysis and the EPR results, the distributions of the results were checked by Shapiro–Wilk analysis, which indicated that, for some composites, the distribution was unlikely to be normal. Kruskal–Wallis analysis was used for statistically comparing between the different composites. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

The concentration of Hg in each sample (1 surface, 2 surface, 3 surface and 4 surface): 1. Calculations for dilution and digestion of liquid portion: Hg measured through Atomic Absorption Spectrometry using a vapor generating accessory. The detection limit for these measurements was 0.0001 $\mu\text{g/l}$. 2. Calculations for dilution and digestion of the solid portion: approximately 0.1 g of each of the solid portions of the sample was weighed and digested with 5% HNO_3 for about 30 minutes, at 70°C. The resulting mixture was then transferred to a 200 ml volumetric flask and then diluted with deionised water accordingly. See Table 1 in paper for dilution factor calculations.

Part 1. Finished samples analysed by HPLC–FLD. The BPA measurements were carried out on a HPLC unit using a HPLC column. The column and the entire remaining HPLC unit were calibrated once a day according to a fixed procedure. Acetonitrile and formic acid (0.1%) containing water (H_2O and CH_2O_2) were used as eluents during the measurements. A rinse was carried out for calibration of the system immediately before the measurements. Detection of BPA was carried out with an Altus A-30 FLD. For each measurement, 20L of the water sample were injected, at a constant flow rate of 0.75mL/min and a temperature of 35 °C. For the qualitative and quantitative determination of BPA, a dilution (100mg/L) of pure BPA powder and pure EtOH ($\geq 99\%$) was prepared as stock solution. Seven calibration reference standards were determined. The LOD was set at 0.001mg/L and LOQ at 0.005mg/L. Fluorescence diagrams were evaluated. Each measurement result was reintegrated and controlled manually.

matrix with 4mL of methanol and collected by applying a slight vacuum in a brown threaded bottle. The further procedure took place in a test tube holder. The samples were evaporated in their threaded bottles with nitrogen to complete dryness. To recover the dried powder, 1mL of pure EtOH was added. Then the bottles were sealed and shaken for 1min using a vortex mixer followed by retrieving the liquid from the 4ml threaded bottles in 1mL HPLC threaded bottles. Between measurements, the samples were stored in darkness at a constant temperature (4 °C).

Part 2. Filtration method assessment. 3 different materials were used for filtration of BPA-containing water samples: Zeosorb, Katalox Light and Catalytic Carbon. The materials differ in particle size, matrix, kind of reactive surface and separation process. All water samples for filtration tests prepared simultaneously in advance, to keep initial BPA concentration constant for all three filtration materials, so 50 L of ultrapure water used for BPA solution. BPA was first dissolved in 1mL EtOH (≥99%) and then added to the ultrapure water. BPA load of the starting samples corresponded to the worst-case concentration from previous measurements (0.192mg/L). To prevent contamination, only instruments and vessels made of glass, metal or BPA-free plastic used during sample preparation and measurement.

Part 2. The experimental methodology was identical for all tests of the different filter materials. For each material 3 separate replicates with 2 extracted test samples were analysed (n = 6). 500 g of each filter granulate was used per run. The initial BPA concentration was checked by HPLC using the method presented above. Pre-wash procedure required due to possible impurity. The supernatant collected in a glass jar and evaluated for a possible contamination with BPA. Pre-cleaned granules filled into the filter nipples. For the main measurements, 5 L of the water with the initial BPA concentration were added to each filtration material. After completion of the filtering procedure, samples were again taken from the filtered water and analysed by HPLC–FLD. Granules stored after the experiments for 12h each and analysed separately to evaluate if collected BPA might interact with filter material and evidence of new intermediates might be visible in fluorescence examination. For this purpose, superficial granules (50 g each) collected and dissolved in 30mL EtOH in an ultrasonic bath for 20min each. Subsequently, 1mL of the liquid supernatant was collected and pre-filtered with disposable filters before HPLC–FLD analysis.

Statistical tests. BPA measurements: Linear regression model to compare the BPA values for the different material groups. Samples are considered as clusters since several measurements per sample were conducted. Pairwise comparisons between different material groups. Scheffe's method applied to correct for multiple testing problem (adjustment of p-values).

Efficacy of filtration methods: A one-way ANOVA was used. Pairwise comparisons between different material groups. Scheffe's method applied to correct for multiple testing problem (adjustment of p-values). A paired t-test was used to compare the before and after filtration values with each method.

Non-parametric Mann-Whitney tests were performed on the raw data, and parametric ANOVA was performed on the log-transformed mercury concentration data. A University of Alberta statistician performed all of the data analyses

Warwick
2013²⁸³

A newly purchased, manufacturer-calibrated Jerome 431-X mercury vapor analyser was used to record air-borne mercury vapor concentrations during the amalgam removal procedures. Regeneration and zeroing of the Jerome analyser was carried out following the manufacturer's recommendations throughout the data collection process. The minimum LOQ of the Jerome 431-X is 3 µg/m³. Care was taken to ensure that no solid or wet materials were drawn into the analyser during data collection. To mimic the protective equipment worn by a dental student, a disposable ear-loop mask was placed over the intake nozzle of the Jerome analyser. The mask was replaced after every two Hg vapor concentration recordings. The Jerome analyser was regenerated on the morning of each data collection day, at the end of each day, and when the Jerome display indicated that regeneration was. 30 min. after regeneration, the analyser was calibrated and used to collect data. Hg vapor readings taken at an average distance of 38 cm from the dental jaw simulator implanted with the amalgam-filled plastic teeth, with the nozzle of the Jerome analyser pointed directly towards the working area from a superior position, thereby mimicking the position of a dental student's face during amalgam removal. The distance of 38 cm was determined to be the average distance from the face of the drill operator to the operative site. When readings were taken with suction alone, and with suction and water spray, one researcher held the suction tube to the left of the researcher performing the removals, with its source coming from the superior position at a 45-degree angle. The tip of the suction device was placed as close to the contact point of the dental bur on the amalgam as was possible.

Amalgam removals were conducted until a total of 75 mercury vapor readings were performed. Twenty-five measurements were conducted under each of these three conditions: with water spray and high-volume suction, with suction only (no water spray), and with neither water spray nor suction. A University of Alberta statistician determined that 25 measurements under each of the three conditions would be sufficient for satisfactory statistical analysis. The time between each vapor measurement varied depending on a number of factors including recalibration and maintenance requirements of the Jerome analyser, time required to replace amalgam-filled plastic teeth in the dental jaw simulator, and work area clean up.

Crematorium setting (n=2)

Piagno 2020²⁵⁴

N of cremations in BC in 2016: estimated based on the province's age-stratified population and mortality rates and a cremation rate of 82%. For each age category, the number of bodies cremated in 2016 was estimated. A Canada-specific emissions factor for mercury release from crematoriums was derived from oral health data.

See Data collection methods.

Oral health data (mean n of amalgam-filled tooth surfaces per person, by age): collected in cycle 1 of the Canadian Health Measures Survey (Richardson 2014). Mean mass of amalgam per filled surface of 0.26 g: (Adegbembo et al 2004.) Assumed Hg makes up 50% of mass of each amalgam filling. Emissions factor is death-weighted average of the age-specific estimates of the mass of Hg/person. Assumed mass of Hg in body tissues negligible relative to mass in dental fillings and all Hg contained in dental fillings vapourised and released to the atmosphere. Model input data/derivation of Canada-specific emissions factor for Hg release from crematoriums summarized Table 1 in study.

Human health risk assessment: undertaken according to the standard paradigm established by the US NRC (1983): 1)problem formulation: Part A analysis assessed risk to human health associated with chronic inhalation exposure to Hg vapour at the maximum estimated long-term average

24-h period ground-level concentration resulting from crematorium emissions. In part B, we evaluated the maximum estimated short-term average ground-level Hg vapour concentrations against short-term exposure limits. In both cases, risk assessed at the individual receptor level, with receptor positioned at ground level and continuously exposed. 2)hazard identification: Elemental Hg not currently classified as human carcinogen due to inadequate evidence of carcinogenicity, so this assessment exclusively focuses on non-cancer endpoints. 3) dose-response assessment: The US EPA defines a reference concentration (lifetime exposure limit) of 0.3 µg/m³ for inhalation exposure to elemental mercury vapour (IRIS) 1988); in Canada, a more conservative reference concentration of 0.06 µg/m³ has been suggested (Richardson et al. 2009). Both values were considered in the assessment of risks associated with long-term exposure to ground-level mercury vapour from crematoriums. The exposure concentration believed to be immediately dangerous to life or health is 10,000 µg/m³ (National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health 1994). In BC, the short-term (8-h time-weighted average) occupational exposure limit for elemental mercury vapour is 25 µg/m³ (Worksafe BC 2012). This occupational limit is determined for the protection of healthy adult workers in industrial settings that have a shift of 8 h per day for 5 days per week and about 50 weeks per year. To adjust for general population that comprises sensitive subpopulations such as children, pregnant women, and elderly, we separately applied 10 times uncertainty factor and 8-/24-h adjustment factor

respectively to draw a practical value for comparison (i.e., 0.75 mg/m³). 4) exposure assessment: used the EPA's Screening Procedures for Estimating the Air Quality Impact of Stationary Sources (revised 1992) to determine the maximum estimated ground-level mercury vapour concentrations resulting from crematorium emissions. In our model, ambient wind speed and temperature, cremation gas properties, stack specifications, and mercury emission rate were included; however, for simplicity, building downwash and the effects of plume impaction on elevated terrain were excluded. Inputs to screening model included- Ambient wind speed and temp: Hourly wind speed and temperature data collected in 2016 at the Vancouver International Airport were retrieved from the Government of Canada's online repository of historical climate data. Cremation gas properties: based on a review of publicly available cremation facility permits and approvals, the temperature of cremation gas at the point of exit from the stack is typically in the range of 450–600 °C Crematorium stack specifications: the stack height was assigned a value of 7 m; stack internal diameter: 0.6 m m (Montana Air Quality 2013; Department of Natural Resources 2011). Hg emission rate: Canada-specific emissions factor and a conservative cremation duration of 1 h were used to estimate the rate of mercury emission from the crematorium stack for the long-term exposure scenario. For the short-term exposure scenario, a peak emissions factor of 8.32 g per body cremated was used in place of the Canada-specific emissions factor, based on the maximum number of amalgam surfaces counted in any individual in the Canadian Health Measures Survey (Richardson 2014). 5) Risk characterization: For non-cancer endpoints, risk is expressed in terms of the HQ, which relates the exposure concentration to reference concentration. This quantitative estimate of risk is compared with a measure of "acceptable" risk to determine requirements for risk management (if any). For non-cancer endpoints, BC defines acceptable risks as any described by HQ less than 1.0 (Health Canada 2010). In this analysis, the HQ was calculated for both long- and short-term exposure scenarios to evaluate the risks to human health from exposure to Hg vapour associated with crematorium emission

Takaoka
2010²⁸⁰

Continuous Emission Monitor: The Hg concentrations in stack gas were monitored using a speciation mercury continuous emission monitor. This device was developed by Nippon Instruments and the Central Research Institute of the Electric Power Industry in Japan. CEM was developed based on the Ontario Hydro method, which is used to determine the elemental, oxidised, particle-bound and total mercury emissions from coal-fired stationary sources (ASTM D6784-02, 2008); it was compared with the Ontario Hydro method periodically and showed an excellent correlation for mercury concentrations ranging from 0 to 100 µg/Nm³ in a municipal solid waste incinerator. The detection limit of this device is 0.1 µg/Nm³. Some flue gas obtained at Facility No. 7 was simultaneously sampled using an absorption method based on Japanese Industrial Standard K0222. CO, O₂, CO₂, NO_x, SO₂ concentrations were also monitored using continuous emission monitors (CGT-7000 for CO, NOA-7000 for O₂ and NO_x, SOA-7000 for SO₂; Shimadzu Co. Ltd.). In crematory No. 7, the HCl concentration was measured manually based on Japanese Industrial Standard K0107.

Regression equation - CEM = 1.23(JIS)+0.687(R² = 0.93), (1) where CEM = CEM value (µg/Nm³); JIS = JIS value (µg/Nm³)

Abbreviations. ADaM: Aachener Daphnia Medium; AFS: atomic fluorescence spectrometry, Ag: silver, Al: aluminium, ANCOVA: analysis of covariance, ANOVA: analysis of variance; BC: British Columbia, bis-GMA: bisphenol A dimethacrylate, BE: Binding energy, BPA: bisphenol A, BSA: Business Service Authority; BrCl: bromine monochloride CAS: chairside amalgam separators, CEM: continuous emission monitor, CI: Confidence Interval; CO: carbon monoxide, CO₂: Carbon dioxide, CRM: Certified Reference Materials; Cu: copper, CV-AAS: Cold Vapour-Atomic Absorption Spectrometry; CVAFS: cold-vapor atomic fluorescence spectrometer CVC: Calibration Verification Check(s); DC: dental clinic, DEFRA: Department for Agriculture and Rural Affairs, DSL: dental simulation laboratory, DTF: dental treatment facilities, DWW: dental wastewater, EDTA: Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid, EDX: energy dispersive X-ray analysis, EPA: Environmental Protection Agency, EPR: electron paramagnetic resonance, ETOH: ethanol, FE-SEM: Field Emission

Scanning Electron Microscopy; FLD: Fluorescence detector, GC-MS: Gas Chromatography/Mass Spectrometry; GEM: Gaseous Elemental Mercury; GGP: Greenhouse Gas Protocol, HCL: hydrochloric acid, HEMA: 2-hydroxyethyl methacrylate, Hg: mercury; HHV: higher heating value, HIQA: Health Information and Quality Authority; HNO₃: nitric acid; HPLC: High-Performance Liquid Chromatography; HPLC-FLD: high performance liquid chromatography–fluorescence detector, HQ: hazard quotient, HVE: high-volume evacuation, H₂O: water, ICP-MS: inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry, IRIS: Integrated Risk Information System, ISD – Information Services Division; ISO: International Organization of Standardization, KBrO₃: potassium bromate, KBr: potassium bromide, KMnO₄: potassium permanganate; K₂S₂O₈: potassium persulfate; LCA: life cycle assessment, LHV: lower heating value, LOD: Limit of Detection; LOQ: Limit of Quantification; MFC: Mass Flow Controller; Na₂S: sodium sulphide, NASDA: National Association of Specialist Dental Accountants, Na₂S₂O₃: sodium thiosulfate, NH₂OH×HCl: hydroxylammonium chloride, NO_x: nitrogen oxide, , NRC: National Research Council, OH: hydroxide, PDO: private dental office, PSD: Particle Size Distribution; RSD: relative standard deviation, SD : Standard Deviation; SEM: Scanning Electron Microscope, Sn: tin, SnCl₂: tin chloride, SMPS: scanning mobility particle sizer, SO₂: sulphur dioxide, SPE: solid phase extraction, SPME: Solid Phase Microextraction; TEGDMA: triethylene glycol dimethacrylate, TSS: Total suspended solids, TDS: total dissolved solids, UDMA: urethane dimethacrylate, UFC: Unified Facilities Criteria, USEPA – United States Environmental Protection Agency, VS: volatile solids, WBCSD: World Business Council on Sustainable Development, WRI: World Resources Institute, XPS: X – Raphotoelectron spectroscopy.

Appendix F: Quality appraisal

Table 21. Quality appraisal: Health studies

Study	A) SELECTION BIAS			B) STUDY DESIGN				C) CONFOUNDERS			D) BLINDING			E) DATA COLLECTION METHODS			F) WITHDRAWALS AND DROP-OUTS			GLOBAL RATING
	Are individuals selected representative of target population?	What percentage of individuals agreed to participate?	Section rating	Was study described as randomized?	If Yes, was the method of randomization described? (See dictionary)	If Yes, was the method appropriate? (See dictionary)	Section rating	Were there important differences between groups prior to intervention?	If yes, indicate the percentage of relevant confounders that were controlled?	Section rating	Was (were) the outcome assessor(s) aware of the intervention or exposure status of participants?	Were the study participants aware of the research group they were placed in?	Section rating	Were data collection tools shown to be valid?	Were data collection tools shown to be reliable?	Section rating	Were withdrawals and drop-outs reported in terms of numbers and/or reasons per group?	Indicate the percentage of participants completing the study. (If the percentage differs by groups, record the lowest)	Section rating	
Adams 2008 ¹⁹⁴	NL	CT	Weak	N	NA	NA	M	Y	60-79%	M	N	Y	M	Y	N	M	N	CT	Weak	Weak
Ahlgren 2014 ¹⁹⁵	SL	60-79%	M	N	NA	NA	M	Y	CT	Weak	CT	Y	Weak	Y	Y	Strong	Y	<60%	Weak	Weak
Bellinger 2006* ¹⁷⁹ Barregard 2008 ¹⁷⁷ Bellinger 2007 [DA] ¹⁷⁸ Bellinger 2007 [DEA] ¹⁹⁶	VL	80-100%	Strong	Y	Y	Y	Strong	Y	80-100%	Strong	N	Y	M	Y	Y	Strong	Y	80-100%	Strong	Strong

Study	A) SELECTION BIAS			B) STUDY DESIGN			C) CONFOUNDERS			D) BLINDING			E) DATA COLLECTION METHODS			F) WITHDRAWALS AND DROP-OUTS			GLOBAL RATING
	Are individuals selected representative of target population?	What percentage of individuals agreed to participate?	Section rating	Was study described as randomized?	If Yes, was the method of randomization described? (See dictionary)	If Yes, was the method appropriate? (See dictionary)	Section rating	Were there important differences between groups prior to intervention?	If yes, indicate the percentage of relevant confounders that were controlled ?	Section rating	Was (were) the outcome assessor(s) aware of the intervention or exposure status of participants?	Were the study participants aware of the research group they were placed in?	Section rating	Were data collection tools shown to be valid?	Were data collection tools shown to be reliable?	Section rating	Were withdrawals and drop-outs reported in terms of numbers and/or reasons per group?	Indicate the percentage of participants completing the study. (If the percentage differs by groups, record the lowest)	
Bellinger 2008 ¹⁸⁰ Maserejia n 2014 [DSC] ¹⁸⁷ Maserejia n 2014 [DSFC] ²⁵⁸ Maserejia n 2012 [psycho] ²⁰⁹ Maserejia n 2012 [physical] ¹⁸⁸ Shenker 2008 ¹⁹²																			

Study	A) SELECTION BIAS			B) STUDY DESIGN				C) CONFOUNDERS			D) BLINDING			E) DATA COLLECTION METHODS			F) WITHDRAWALS AND DROP-OUTS			GLOBAL RATING
	Are individuals selected representative of target population?	What percentage of individuals agreed to participate?	Section rating	Was study described as randomized?	If Yes, was the method of randomization described? (See dictionary)	If Yes, was the method appropriate? (See dictionary)	Section rating	Were there important differences between groups prior to intervention?	If yes, indicate the percentage of relevant confounders that were controlled?	Section rating	Was (were) the outcome assessor(s) aware of the intervention or exposure status of participants?	Were the study participants aware of the research group they were placed in?	Section rating	Were data collection tools shown to be valid?	Were data collection tools shown to be reliable?	Section rating	Were withdrawals and drop-outs reported in terms of numbers and/or reasons per group?	Indicate the percentage of participants completing the study. (If the percentage differs by groups, record the lowest)	Section rating	
Bjorkman 2018 ¹⁹⁸	VL	Less than 60%?	Weak	N	NA	NA	M	Yes	80-100%	Strong	NA	NA	NA	Y	Y	Strong	No	60-79%	M	M
Bjorkman 2020* ²⁰⁰ Bjorkman 2023 ¹⁹⁹ Sinha 2024 ²¹⁰	SL	CT	M	N	NA	NA	M	Y	80-100%	Strong	CT	CT	Weak	Y	Y	Strong	Y	60-79%	M	M
Sjursen 2011* ²¹¹ Bjorkman 2012 ¹⁹⁷ Bjorkman 2017 ²⁰¹	SL	Less than 60%	Weak	N	NA	NA	M	Y	60-79%	M	Y	Y	Weak	Y	N	M	Y	80-100%	Strong	Weak

Study	A) SELECTION BIAS			B) STUDY DESIGN				C) CONFOUNDERS			D) BLINDING			E) DATA COLLECTION METHODS			F) WITHDRAWALS AND DROP-OUTS			GLOBAL RATING
	Are individuals selected representative of target population?	What percentage of individuals agreed to participate?	Section rating	Was study described as randomized?	If Yes, was the method of randomization described? (See dictionary)	If Yes, was the method appropriate? (See dictionary)	Section rating	Were there important differences between groups prior to intervention?	If yes, indicate the percentage of relevant confounders that were controlled?	Section rating	Was (were) the outcome assessor(s) aware of the intervention or exposure status of participants?	Were the study participants aware of the research group they were placed in?	Section rating	Were data collection tools shown to be valid?	Were data collection tools shown to be reliable?	Section rating	Were withdrawals and drop-outs reported in terms of numbers and/or reasons per group?	Indicate the percentage of participants completing the study. (If the percentage differs by groups, record the lowest)	Section rating	
Cabana-Munoz 2015 ²⁰²	CT	CT	Weak	N	NA	NA	M	CT	CT	Weak	CT	CT	Weak	Y	Y	Strong	NA	NA	NA	Weak
Cabana-Munoz 2019 ²⁰³	CT	CT	Weak	N	NA	NA	M	CT	CT	Weak	CT	CT	Weak	Y	Y	Strong	NA	NA	NA	Weak
Chen 2020 ²⁰⁵	VL	NA	Strong	N	NA	NA	M	N	NA	Strong	NA	NA	NA	Y	Y	Strong	NA	NA	NA	Strong
Chen 2021 ²⁰⁴	VL	NA	Strong	N	NA	NA	M	N	NA	Strong	NA	NA	NA	Y	Y	Strong	NA	NA	NA	Strong
Daniels 2007 ²⁰⁶	VL	85%	Strong	N	NA	NA	M	CT	80-100%	Strong	NA	NA	NA	Y	Y	Strong	N	89%	M	Strong
Dermata 2018 ²⁶³	SL	80-100%	M	Y	Y	Y	Strong	CT	NA	Weak	Y	N	M	Y	Y	Strong	Y	60-79%	M	M
Duame 2021 ²⁰⁷	SL	CT	M	N	NA	NA	Weak	CT	NA	Weak	Y	CT	Weak	Y	Y	Strong	NA	NA	NA	Weak

Study	A) SELECTION BIAS			B) STUDY DESIGN				C) CONFOUNDERS			D) BLINDING			E) DATA COLLECTION METHODS			F) WITHDRAWALS AND DROP-OUTS			GLOBAL RATING
	Are individuals selected representative of target population?	What percentage of individuals agreed to participate?	Section rating	Was study described as randomized?	If Yes, was the method of randomization described? (See dictionary)	If Yes, was the method appropriate? (See dictionary)	Section rating	Were there important differences between groups prior to intervention?	If yes, indicate the percentage of relevant confounders that were controlled ?	Section rating	Was (were) the outcome assessor(s) aware of the intervention or exposure status of participants?	Were the study participants aware of the research group they were placed in?	Section rating	Were data collection tools shown to be valid?	Were data collection tools shown to be reliable?	Section rating	Were withdrawals and drop-outs reported in terms of numbers and/or reasons per group?	Indicate the percentage of participants completing the study. (If the percentage differs by groups, record the lowest)	Section rating	
Duplinsky 2012 ²⁰⁸	SL	<60 %	M	N	NA	NA	M	CT	CT	Weak	NA	NA	NA	Y	Y	Strong	NA	NA	NA	M
Eyeson 2010 ²¹²	SL	NA	M	N	NA	NA	Weak	CT	CT	Weak	NA	NA	NA	Y	Y	Strong	NA	NA	NA	Weak
Forkel 2024 ²¹³	SL	NA	M	N	NA	NA	M	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Y	Y	Strong	NA	NA	NA	Strong
Frisk 2007 ²¹⁵	CT	CT	Weak	N	NA	NA	M	Y	<60%	Weak	CT	Y	Weak	Y	Y	Strong	NA	100%	Strong	Weak
Franzblau 2012 ²¹⁴	SL	NA	M	N	NA	NA	Weak	NA	80-100%	M	NA	NA	NA	Y	Y	Strong	NA	NA	NA	M
Gavic 2019 ²⁵⁵	SL	CT	M	Y	N	NA	Strong	CT	CT	Weak	CT	CT	Weak	Y	N	M	N	100%	Strong	Weak

Study	A) SELECTION BIAS			B) STUDY DESIGN				C) CONFOUNDERS			D) BLINDING			E) DATA COLLECTION METHODS			F) WITHDRAWALS AND DROP-OUTS			GLOBAL RATING
	Are individuals selected representative of target population?	What percentage of individuals agreed to participate?	Section rating	Was study described as randomized?	If Yes, was the method of randomization described? (See dictionary)	If Yes, was the method appropriate? (See dictionary)	Section rating	Were there important differences between groups prior to intervention?	If yes, indicate the percentage of relevant confounders that were controlled ?	Section rating	Was (were) the outcome assessor(s) aware of the intervention or exposure status of participants?	Were the study participants aware of the research group they were placed in?	Section rating	Were data collection tools shown to be valid?	Were data collection tools shown to be reliable?	Section rating	Were withdrawals and drop-outs reported in terms of numbers and/or reasons per group?	Indicate the percentage of participants completing the study. (If the percentage differs by groups, record the lowest)	Section rating	
De Rouen 2002;06* ¹⁸¹ Geier 2011 ¹⁸² Geier 2013 ²¹⁶ Lauterbach 2008 ¹⁸⁴ Martin 2008 ¹⁸⁶ Roberts 2008 ¹⁹¹ Woods 2008 ¹⁹³ Woods 2009 ²⁶²	VL	60-79%	M	Y	Y	Y	Strong	N	NA	Strong	N	Y	M	Y	Y	Strong	Y	60-79%	M	Strong
Halperin-Sternfeld 2016 ¹⁸³	SL	NA	M	N	NA	NA	Weak	Y	60-79%	M	NA	NA	NA	Y	Y	Strong	NA	NA	NA	M

Study	A) SELECTION BIAS			B) STUDY DESIGN				C) CONFOUNDERS			D) BLINDING			E) DATA COLLECTION METHODS			F) WITHDRAWALS AND DROP-OUTS			GLOBAL RATING
	Are individuals selected representative of target population?	What percentage of individuals agreed to participate?	Section rating	Was study described as randomized?	If Yes, was the method of randomization described? (See dictionary)	If Yes, was the method appropriate? (See dictionary)	Section rating	Were there important differences between groups prior to intervention?	If yes, indicate the percentage of relevant confounders that were controlled ?	Section rating	Was (were) the outcome assessor(s) aware of the intervention or exposure status of participants?	Were the study participants aware of the research group they were placed in?	Section rating	Were data collection tools shown to be valid?	Were data collection tools shown to be reliable?	Section rating	Were withdrawals and drop-outs reported in terms of numbers and/or reasons per group?	Indicate the percentage of participants completing the study. (If the percentage differs by groups, record the lowest)	Section rating	
Heggland 2011 ²¹⁷	VL	NA	Strong	N	NA	NA	M	Y	80-100%	Strong	NA	NA	NA	Y	Y	Strong	NA	NA	NA	Strong
Heratizadeh 2018 ²¹⁸	VL	NA	Strong	N	NA	NA	M	CT	NA	Weak	NA	NA	NA	Y	Y	Strong	NA	NA	NA	M
Hilt 2009 ²²⁰	VL	<60 %	Weak	N	NA	NA	M	Y	<60%	Weak	Y	Y	Weak	CT	CT	Weak	NA	NA	NA	Weak
Hilt 2011 ²¹⁹	VL	<60 %	Weak	N	NA	NA	M	Y	60-79%	M	Y	Y	Weak	CT	CT	Weak	NA	NA	NA	Weak
Hsu 2016 ²²¹	VL	NA	Strong	N	NA	NA	M	Y	80-100%	Strong	NA	NA	NA	Y	Y	Strong	NA	NA	NA	Strong
Hu 2021 ²⁵⁶	VL	NA	Strong	N	NA	NA	M	Y	Less than 60%	Weak	NA	NA	NA	Y	Y	Strong	NA	NA	NA	M
Jones 2007 ²²²	SL	<60 %	Weak	N	NA	NA	M	CT	CT	Weak	Y	Y	Weak	Y	Y	Strong	NA	NA	NA	Weak

Study	A) SELECTION BIAS			B) STUDY DESIGN				C) CONFOUNDERS			D) BLINDING			E) DATA COLLECTION METHODS			F) WITHDRAWALS AND DROP-OUTS			GLOBAL RATING
	Are individuals selected representative of target population?	What percentage of individuals agreed to participate?	Section rating	Was study described as randomized?	If Yes, was the method of randomization described? (See dictionary)	If Yes, was the method appropriate? (See dictionary)	Section rating	Were there important differences between groups prior to intervention?	If yes, indicate the percentage of relevant confounders that were controlled ?	Section rating	Was (were) the outcome assessor(s) aware of the intervention or exposure status of participants?	Were the study participants aware of the research group they were placed in?	Section rating	Were data collection tools shown to be valid?	Were data collection tools shown to be reliable?	Section rating	Were withdrawals and drop-outs reported in terms of numbers and/or reasons per group?	Indicate the percentage of participants completing the study. (If the percentage differs by groups, record the lowest)	Section rating	
Lartitegui-Sebastian 2012 ²²³	SL	CT	M	N	NA	NA	M	Y	CT	Weak	NA	NA	NA	Y	CT	M	CT	CT	Weak	Weak
Leybovich 2014 ²⁵⁷	CT	CT	Weak	Y	CT	CT	Strong	CT	CT	Weak	Y	Y	Weak	Y	CT	M	Y	80-100%	Strong	Weak
Lin 2017 ¹⁸⁵	VL	NA	Strong	N	NA	NA	M	N	NA	Strong	NA	NA	NA	Y	Y	Strong	NA	NA	NA	Strong
Lindbohm 2007 ²²⁴	VL	NA	Strong	N	NA	NA	M	CT	80-100%	Strong	N	Y	M	Y	N	M	NA	NA	NA	Strong
Loupou 2020 ²²⁵	SL	<60 %	Weak	N	NA	NA	M	Y	80-100%	Strong	CT	Y	Weak	Y	Y	Strong	Y	80-100%	Strong	Weak
Lygre Gunvor 2013 ²²⁸	SL	CT	Weak	N	NA	NA	M	CT	NA	Weak	Y	Y	Weak	Y	N	M	Y	80-100%	Strong	Weak
Lygre Gunvor	SL	<60 %	Weak	N	NA	NA	M	Y	80-100%	Strong	CT	Y	Weak	Y	N	M	NA	NA	NA	Weak

Study	A) SELECTION BIAS			B) STUDY DESIGN				C) CONFOUNDERS			D) BLINDING			E) DATA COLLECTION METHODS			F) WITHDRAWALS AND DROP-OUTS			GLOBAL RATING
	Are individuals selected representative of target population?	What percentage of individuals agreed to participate?	Section rating	Was study described as randomized?	If Yes, was the method of randomization described? (See dictionary)	If Yes, was the method appropriate? (See dictionary)	Section rating	Were there important differences between groups prior to intervention?	If yes, indicate the percentage of relevant confounders that were controlled ?	Section rating	Was (were) the outcome assessor(s) aware of the intervention or exposure status of participants?	Were the study participants aware of the research group they were placed in?	Section rating	Were data collection tools shown to be valid?	Were data collection tools shown to be reliable?	Section rating	Were withdrawals and drop-outs reported in terms of numbers and/or reasons per group?	Indicate the percentage of participants completing the study. (If the percentage differs by groups, record the lowest)	Section rating	
2016 ²²⁷																				
Lygre Gunvor 2018 ²²⁶	SL	<60 %	Weak	N	NA	NA	M	Y	80-100%	Strong	CT	Y	Weak	Y	N	M	NA	NA	NA	Weak
Lynch 2015 ²²⁹	NL	NA	Weak	N	NA	NA	M	CT	CT	Weak	NA	NA	NA	Y	Y	Strong	Y	80-100%	Strong	Weak
Ma 2021 ²³⁰	VL	NA	Strong	N	NA	NA	M	Y	80-100%	Strong	NA	NA	NA	Y	Y	Strong	NA	NA	NA	Strong
Marell 2014 ²³¹	SL	60-79%	M	N	NA	NA	M	N	NA	Strong	CT	CT	Weak	Y	Y	Strong	NA	80-100%	Strong	M

Study	A) SELECTION BIAS			B) STUDY DESIGN				C) CONFOUNDERS			D) BLINDING			E) DATA COLLECTION METHODS			F) WITHDRAWALS AND DROP-OUTS			GLOBAL RATING
	Are individuals selected representative of target population?	What percentage of individuals agreed to participate?	Section rating	Was study described as randomized?	If Yes, was the method of randomization described? (See dictionary)	If Yes, was the method appropriate? (See dictionary)	Section rating	Were there important differences between groups prior to intervention?	If yes, indicate the percentage of relevant confounders that were controlled ?	Section rating	Was (were) the outcome assessor(s) aware of the intervention or exposure status of participants?	Were the study participants aware of the research group they were placed in?	Section rating	Were data collection tools shown to be valid?	Were data collection tools shown to be reliable?	Section rating	Were withdrawals and drop-outs reported in terms of numbers and/or reasons per group?	Indicate the percentage of participants completing the study. (If the percentage differs by groups, record the lowest)	Section rating	
Melchart 2008* ²³² Weidenhammer 2009 ²⁵¹ Weidenhammer 2010 ²⁵⁰	NL	80-100 %	Weak	Y	Y	Y	Strong	N	NA	Strong	CT	Y	Weak	Y	N	M	Y	80-100%	Strong	Weak
Mikhailichenko 2019 ²³³	VL	NA	Strong	N	NA	NA	M	Y	100%	Strong	NA	NA	NA	Y	Y	Strong	NA	NA	NA	Strong
Montebugnoli 2012 ²³⁴	CT	CT	Weak	N	NA	NA	M	CT	CT	Weak	NA	NA	NA	Y	Y	Strong	NA	80-100%	Strong	Weak
Naimi-Akbar 2012* ²³⁵	VL	NA	Strong	N	NA	NA	M	Y	80-100%	Strong	NA	NA	NA	Y	Y	Strong	NA	NA	NA	Strong

Study	A) SELECTION BIAS			B) STUDY DESIGN				C) CONFOUNDERS			D) BLINDING			E) DATA COLLECTION METHODS			F) WITHDRAWALS AND DROP-OUTS			GLOBAL RATING
	Are individuals selected representative of target population?	What percentage of individuals agreed to participate?	Section rating	Was study described as randomized?	If Yes, was the method of randomization described? (See dictionary)	If Yes, was the method appropriate? (See dictionary)	Section rating	Were there important differences between groups prior to intervention?	If yes, indicate the percentage of relevant confounders that were controlled ?	Section rating	Was (were) the outcome assessor(s) aware of the intervention or exposure status of participants?	Were the study participants aware of the research group they were placed in?	Section rating	Were data collection tools shown to be valid?	Were data collection tools shown to be reliable?	Section rating	Were withdrawals and drop-outs reported in terms of numbers and/or reasons per group?	Indicate the percentage of participants completing the study. (If the percentage differs by groups, record the lowest)	Section rating	
Naimi-Akbar 2014 ²³⁶																				
Naimi-Akbar 2013 ²³⁷	VL	Less than 60%	Weak	N	NA	NA	M	CT	CT	Weak	Y	Y	Weak	Y	Y	Strong	N	CT	Weak	Weak
Perng 2023 ¹⁸⁹	VL	NA	Strong	N	NA	NA	M	CT	Less than 60%	Weak	NA	NA	NA	Y	Y	Strong	NA	NA	NA	M
Pettini 2015 ²⁶⁰	CT	CT	Weak	N	NA	NA	M	CT	CT	Weak	CT	Y	Weak	Y	Y	Strong	NA	NA	NA	Weak
Pezelj-Ribaric 2008 ²³⁸	CT	CT	Weak	N	NA	NA	M	CT	CT	Weak	CT	Y	Weak	Y	Y	Strong	N	80-100%	Strong	Weak
Ptak 2023 ¹⁹⁰	SL	NA	M	N	NA	NA	M	CT	Less than 60%	Weak	NA	NA	NA	Y	Y	Strong	NA	NA	NA	M

Study	A) SELECTION BIAS			B) STUDY DESIGN				C) CONFOUNDERS			D) BLINDING			E) DATA COLLECTION METHODS			F) WITHDRAWALS AND DROP-OUTS			GLOBAL RATING
	Are individuals selected representative of target population?	What percentage of individuals agreed to participate?	Section rating	Was study described as randomized?	If Yes, was the method of randomization described? (See dictionary)	If Yes, was the method appropriate? (See dictionary)	Section rating	Were there important differences between groups prior to intervention?	If yes, indicate the percentage of relevant confounders that were controlled ?	Section rating	Was (were) the outcome assessor(s) aware of the intervention or exposure status of participants?	Were the study participants aware of the research group they were placed in?	Section rating	Were data collection tools shown to be valid?	Were data collection tools shown to be reliable?	Section rating	Were withdrawals and drop-outs reported in terms of numbers and/or reasons per group?	Indicate the percentage of participants completing the study. (If the percentage differs by groups, record the lowest)	Section rating	
Rojas-Alayaga 2012 ²³⁹	SL	CT	M	N	NA	NA	M	CT	CT	Weak	CT	Y	Weak	Y	Y	Strong	N	80-100%	Strong	Weak
Suter 2016 ²⁴²	SL	NA	M	N	NA	NA	M	CT	CT	Weak	NA	NA	NA	Y	Y	Strong	NA	NA	NA	M
Sundstrom 2010 ²⁴¹	VL	CT	M	N	NA	NA	M	Y	Less than 60%	Weak	NA	NA	NA	Y	N	M	NA	NA	NA	M
Sundstrom 2011 ²⁴⁰	VL	CT	M	N	NA	NA	M	Y	Less than 60%	Weak	NA	NA	NA	Y	N	M	NA	NA	NA	M
Tadin 2014 ²⁶¹	CT	CT	Weak	Y	N	CT	Strong	CT	CT	Weak	CT	CT	Weak	Y	Y	Strong	N	N	Weak	Weak
Thygesen 2011 ²⁴³	VL	NA	Strong	N	NA	NA	M	Y	Less than 60%	Weak	NA	NA	NA	Y	Y	Strong	NA	NA	NA	M

Study	A) SELECTION BIAS			B) STUDY DESIGN				C) CONFOUNDERS			D) BLINDING			E) DATA COLLECTION METHODS			F) WITHDRAWALS AND DROP-OUTS			GLOBAL RATING
	Are individuals selected representative of target population?	What percentage of individuals agreed to participate?	Section rating	Was study described as randomized?	If Yes, was the method of randomization described? (See dictionary)	If Yes, was the method appropriate? (See dictionary)	Section rating	Were there important differences between groups prior to intervention?	If yes, indicate the percentage of relevant confounders that were controlled?	Section rating	Was (were) the outcome assessor(s) aware of the intervention or exposure status of participants?	Were the study participants aware of the research group they were placed in?	Section rating	Were data collection tools shown to be valid?	Were data collection tools shown to be reliable?	Section rating	Were withdrawals and drop-outs reported in terms of numbers and/or reasons per group?	Indicate the percentage of participants completing the study. (If the percentage differs by groups, record the lowest)	Section rating	
Tseng 2020a [MS] ²⁴⁵	VL	NA	Strong	N	NA	NA	M	N	80-100%	Strong	NA	NA	NA	Y	Y	Strong	NA	NA	NA	Strong
Tseng 2020b [ET] ²⁴⁴	VL	NA	Strong	N	NA	NA	M	N	80-100%	Strong	NA	NA	NA	Y	Y	Strong	NA	NA	NA	Strong
Watson 2011 ^{*247} Watson 2012 ²⁴⁶ Watson 2013 ²⁴⁸	VL	CT	M	N	NA	NA	M	No	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Y	Y	Strong	N	80-100%	Weak	M
Weber 2012 ²⁴⁹	SL	CT	M	N	NA	NA	M	Y	80-100%	Strong	CT	CT	Weak	Y	Y	Strong	N	CT	Weak	M
Wright 2012 ²⁵²	VL	CT	M	N	NA	NA	M	Y	80-100%	Strong	N	CT	M	Y	Y	Strong	Y	80-100%	Strong	Strong

Study	A) SELECTION BIAS			B) STUDY DESIGN				C) CONFOUNDERS			D) BLINDING			E) DATA COLLECTION METHODS			F) WITHDRAWALS AND DROP-OUTS			GLOBAL RATING
	Are individuals selected representative of target population?	What percentage of individuals agreed to participate?	Section rating	Was study described as randomized?	If Yes, was the method of randomization described? (See dictionary)	If Yes, was the method appropriate? (See dictionary)	Section rating	Were there important differences between groups prior to intervention?	If yes, indicate the percentage of relevant confounders that were controlled ?	Section rating	Was (were) the outcome assessor(s) aware of the intervention or exposure status of participants?	Were the study participants aware of the research group they were placed in?	Section rating	Were data collection tools shown to be valid?	Were data collection tools shown to be reliable?	Section rating	Were withdrawals and drop-outs reported in terms of numbers and/or reasons per group?	Indicate the percentage of participants completing the study. (If the percentage differs by groups, record the lowest)	Section rating	
Zwicker 2014 ²⁵³	VL	NA	Strong	N	NA	NA	M	CT	CT	Weak	NA	NA	NA	Y	N	M	NA	NA	NA	M

CT=Can't Tell, M=Moderate, N=No, NA=Not Applicable, NL=Not Likely, SL=Somewhat Likely, VL=Very likely, Y=Yes

Table 22. Quality appraisal: Environmental studies

Study, year, research design	Criterion 1: Risk of confounding biases	Criterion 2: Risk of post-intervention/exposure selection biases	Criterion 3: Risk of misclassified comparison biases (observational studies only)	Criterion 4: Risk of performance biases (experimental studies only)	Criterion 5: Risk of detection biases	Criterion 6: Risk of outcome reporting biases	Criterion 7: Risk of outcome assessment biases	Overall judgement
Al-Kawas, 2008, Cross-sectional with comparator ²⁶⁴	High	Medium	Low	NA	Low	Low	Medium	High
Binner, 2022, Cross-sectional ²⁶⁵	High	Medium	Low	NA	Low	Low	Medium	High
Duane, 2017, Secondary analysis of dataset ²⁶⁶	High	Medium	Low	NA	Medium	Low	Low	High
Gioda, 2007, Before and after study ²⁶⁷	High	Medium	Low	NA	Medium	Low	Low	High
Kim, 2018, Cross-sectional ²⁶⁸	High	Medium	Low	NA	Low	Medium	Medium	High
Kontogianni, 2008, Cross-sectional survey ²⁶⁹	Low	Medium	Low	NA	Medium	Medium	Medium	Medium
Majstorovic, 2024, Cross-sectional (Part 1: clinic setting) ²⁷⁰	High	Medium	Medium	NA	Low	Low	High	High
Majstorovic, 2024, controlled trial (Part 2: lab-based) ²⁷⁰	Low	Low	NA	Low	Low	Low	Medium	Medium

Study, year, research design	Criterion 1: Risk of confounding biases	Criterion 2: Risk of post-intervention/exposure selection biases	Criterion 3: Risk of misclassified comparison biases (observational studies only)	Criterion 4: Risk of performance biases (experimental studies only)	Criterion 5: Risk of detection biases	Criterion 6: Risk of outcome reporting biases	Criterion 7: Risk of outcome assessment biases	Overall judgement
Mandalidis, 2018, Cross-sectional ²⁷¹	High	Low	Low	NA	Low	Low	Low	High
Marquardt, 2009, Cross-sectional ²⁷²	Low	Low	Low	NA	Low	Low	Medium	Medium
Mourouzis, 2022, Controlled trial (clinic and lab setting) ²⁷³	Medium	Medium	NA	Medium	Low	Medium	Medium	Medium
Olivera, 2020, Prospective longitudinal ²⁷⁴	Low	Low	Low	NA	Low	Low	Medium	Medium
Paryag, 2010, Modelling study ²⁷⁵	Low	Low	Medium	NA	Low	Low	High	High
Piagno, 2020, Modelling study ²⁵⁴	Low	Medium	High	NA	Medium	Medium	High	High
Polydorou, 2023, Controlled trial ²⁷⁶	Low	Low	NA	Low	Low	Low	Medium	Medium
Shraim, 2012, Prospective longitudinal with comparator ²⁷⁷	High	High	Low	NA	Low	Low	Medium	High
Simu, 2014, Cross-sectional ²⁷⁸	Low	Medium	Medium	NA	Low	Low	Medium	Medium
Stone, 2008, Prospective	High	Medium	Low	NA	Low	Low	Medium	High

Study, year, research design	Criterion 1: Risk of confounding biases	Criterion 2: Risk of post-intervention/exposure selection biases	Criterion 3: Risk of misclassified comparison biases (observational studies only)	Criterion 4: Risk of performance biases (experimental studies only)	Criterion 5: Risk of detection biases	Criterion 6: Risk of outcome reporting biases	Criterion 7: Risk of outcome assessment biases	Overall judgement
longitudinal with control ²⁷⁹								
Takaoka, 2010, Modelling study ²⁸⁰	Low	Medium	Low	NA	Low	Low	Medium	Medium
Van Landuyt, 2014, Controlled trial ²⁸¹	Low	Medium	NA	Medium	Low	Low	Medium	Medium
Warwick, 2013, Controlled trial (lab based) ²⁸³	Low	Medium	NA	Low	Low	Low	Medium	Medium
Warwick, 2019, Prospective longitudinal with control ²⁸²	Low	Medium	Low	NA	Low	Low	Medium	Medium

NA=Not Applicable,